

Ecotoxicological impacts of deep-sea mining current scientific knowledge and necessary steps towards the definition of regulatory thresholds

Workshop in Hannover at the
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Katja Schmidt¹, Chris Hauton², Nelia Mestre³, Joana Raimundo⁴, Sophie Paul⁵, Malcolm Clark⁶, Jens Laugesen⁷, Pasqualina Gaetano³, Lisa Egger¹, Matthias Haeckel⁵

¹Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR), Stilleweg 2, 30655 Hannover, Germany

²Ocean and Earth Science, University of Southampton National Oceanography Centre Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom

³Centre for Marine and Environmental Research (CIMA), Universidade do Algarve, Campus Universitario de Gambelas, 8005-139 Faro, Portugal

⁴IPMA Portuguese Institute of Sea and Atmosphere, IP, Division of Oceanography and Marine Environment (DIVOA) Av. Alfredo Magalhães Ramalho, 6, 1495-165 Algés, Portugal

⁵GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Wischhofstrasse 1-3, 24148 Kiel, Germany

⁶National Institute of Water & Atmospheric Research Ltd (NIWA), 301 Evans Bay Parade, Wellington, New Zealand

⁷DNV AS, Veritasveien 1, 1322 Høvik, Norway

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This report consists of three parts:

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PART I

Workshop Objectives and Results

1. Workshop summary

From April 11th to 13th 2023, the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR) and the MiningImpact research project jointly conducted an international scientific workshop on ecotoxicological impacts of deep-sea mining (DSM). The workshop was hosted at BGR in Hannover, Germany, and organized in a fully hybrid format. About 50 participants, including the interested science community as well as some members of the Legal and Technical Commission (LTC) and other stakeholders, came together in person and online, to gather current scientific knowledge on toxic risks and ecotoxicological impacts of deep-sea mining and to discuss possible ways to derive environmental thresholds and to approach regulatory implementation.

The first day afternoon session was held in plenary and consisted of overview talks on the current state of scientific knowledge, existing regulatory frameworks and International Seabed Authority (ISA) regulatory needs. During the second day, discussions in breakout groups on specific topics such as sources and routes of toxic exposure, biological mechanisms of toxicity, ways to derive threshold values and approaches for legislative implementation took place, and the third day morning session was used to summarize the results of day two followed by discussions and possible recommendations. Given the recent developments in the ISA with the preparation of the exploitation regulations and the decision to integrate binding environmental threshold values for specific hazards including toxicity, the workshop was very timely and the outputs in the form of this report ideally can provide useful information in the ongoing ISA process to develop thresholds.

The workshop highlighted the challenges to meaningfully assess the risk of ecotoxic harm in deep-sea mining settings and associated ecosystem consequences. It was concluded that to date we have low confidence in the ability to identify threshold limits for toxic exposure in abyssal fauna. Based on the limited data currently available, threshold values from existing guidelines for coastal marine waters will have limited application for deep-sea ecosystem protection. Key considerations include:

- no site-specific ecotoxicological data available, only default thresholds could be used
- the role of temperature and pressure - adequacy of toxicity tests with shallow-water proxies questioned;
- complex metal mixtures - adequacy of toxicity tests with single metals questioned;
- variety of potential uptake routes, including particulate ingestion, dietary, solution uptake, in water and in sediment;
- unknown key species for ecosystem health or most vulnerable species - what could actually be protected?

The workshop discussion further considered the interaction of ecotoxicity with other impacts, such as plume deposition and increased particle concentration in waters resulting from plume dispersal - smothering, effects on migration, food supply, etc., that may result in cumulative and/or synergistic effects on ecosystem health and biodiversity. Discussions also involved the challenges of discriminating the different thresholds that might be breached during mining. Toxicity is one potential biological consequence of the various impacts of DSM activities. It was questioned how meaningful it is at the moment to consider threshold limits for individual pressures in isolation.

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of current state and ideal situation to develop regulatory threshold values for DSM. While the use of site-specific environmental information (biological effects of toxic trace metals, understanding ecosystem functions, connectivity, food web, cumulative effects, known key species) is the preferred approach and would lead to high confidence in ecosystem protection, the most likely starting point considering missing information is a default approach using existing threshold values based on generic biological effects data for shallow marine water, or the reference site approach using baseline datasets from reference sites, which both would have to be highly conservative and precautionary.

At the moment we can have only very low confidence in ecosystem protection when applying threshold values based on available biological effects data for shallow-marine waters. For greater confidence in ecosystem protection from toxic harm we would need to develop threshold values based on site-specific toxicity data and a good understanding of ecosystem functioning and processes, the food web, species connectivity, traits, biodiversity, and ecological knowledge on key species.

The workshop participants discussed possible methodologies to assess the toxicity of operational and dewatering plumes and meaningful approaches to assign toxic limits for DSM resources, for early and later stages of regulations. Following a precautionary approach, early stage threshold values might be developed from baseline variability of trace metals in seawater, e.g., x-times the standard deviation from mean values. Determination of toxic risk of the bulk resource sediment/ore material plumes (i.e. the combination of metal species in appropriate/relevant chemical states released from freshly exposed mineral surfaces), could be established as part of a contractor's obligation for the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) or the baseline investigations from exploration and exploitation (i.e. PRZs) and implemented as requirements in the Environmental Management and Monitoring Plan (EMMP). Compliance to regulatory thresholds would also be important to document responsible industry behavior in the context of an environmental, social, and governance guidance framework.

Furthermore, key characteristics of bioindicator species and suitable candidates were discussed. Besides the development of threshold values for metal contaminants in water, biota standards could be developed, ideally for key or sensitive species (biological indicators addressing different "problems" such as suspended sediment concentrations, labile metal concentrations, sedimentation, or those that have a key role for communities, biodiversity, functioning of the ecosystem, etc.), considering also bioaccumulation along the food chain.

For a realistic assessment of the ecotoxicological risks associated with metal contaminants mobilized during DSM activities, it would be necessary to use key bioindicator species from the environment and expose them *in situ* to the different metal sources (e.g., operational plumes with different particle concentrations).

2. Workshop rationale

Understanding ecotoxicological risks and impacts caused by DSM activities and transfer into appropriate policy advice is a complex challenge that requires coordination across different fields of expertise. For environmental standards and effective monitoring strategies to be implemented into effective exploitation regulations and management it will be necessary to define suitable indicators of ecotoxicological stress, and potential bioindicator species or particularly vulnerable species as adequate indicators for ecosystem health (e.g., biodiversity indices), as well as threshold values for metal contaminants causing harm. Furthermore, an integration with other deep-sea mining-caused environmental pressures and impacts, such as suspended particle plume dispersal, reduced ecosystem functions, biodiversity, and community composition, is required. This workshop aimed at bringing together scientists from different disciplines (such as biology, microbiology, geochemistry, ecology, environmental science, environmental law) having a broad range of expertise, to discuss relevant aspects of ecotoxicological research related to DSM and the next steps towards an understanding and assessment of toxic threats, as well as approaches to derive regulatory threshold values and to realize legislative implementation.

The initial idea for the workshop was born during the planning of transdisciplinary laboratory experiments by a small group of scientists working in the MiningImpact project on marine trace metal biogeochemistry at ocean interfaces and on deep-sea ecotoxicology, who intended to bring together complementary expertise and foster joint research activities. Aimed at facilitating a more holistic understanding and assessment of toxic risks and ecotoxicological effects of deep-sea mining and sharing knowledge on methodologies for threshold development in regulatory frameworks, the workshop was organized to bring together scientists with different backgrounds and experiences.

The workshop was further motivated by the decision of the Council of the International Seabed Authority (ISA) in March 2023 relating to the development of environmental threshold values as part of the Mining Code and the exploitation regulations (ISBA/27/C/42). Binding threshold values for certain environmental hazards must be part of the environmental standards and guidelines (ESGs) being developed, and toxicity is among the three priority subjects to focus on first. This scientific workshop was hence timely and useful in that outcomes can contribute to the official ISA process on developing binding environmental thresholds that is led by the Legal and Technical Commission (LTC) and started in summer 2023. The workshop report outlines how toxicity threshold values for deep-sea mining operations could be derived and how existing knowledge gaps can be closed.

2.1 ISA exploitation regulations and regulatory needs

Malcolm Clark presented on the status of the draft ISA exploitation regulations, standards and guidelines. This provided an indication of the regulatory context of environmental thresholds and how the outputs of the workshop could inform ISA processes. His talk covered generic aspects of the ISA Mining Code, but focussed on the draft Exploitation Regulations which were prepared by the Legal and Technical Commission (LTC) in 2019, and which are currently being reviewed and revised by the ISA Council. Draft regulation 45 specifically addresses environmental Standards and Guidelines (ESGs), aimed at ensuring mining contractors do not cause serious harm to the marine environment (a requirement under UNCLOS). These ESGs were to cover various environmental quality objectives, indicators and thresholds, including toxicity composition. Standards will be mandatory to support the Exploitation Regulations, and Guidelines (recommendatory) would provide more detailed advice and recommendations in support of achieving the standards. These ESGs form part of

the Mining Code, which is a body of rules and regulations governing exploration and exploitation activities under the auspices of the ISA. Importantly, the draft regulations at the time of the workshop noted that no exploitation activities would be approved unless the environmental standards had been adopted. In 2022 the ISA Council directed the LTC to develop standard/s on environmental thresholds, through a process involving experts as part of an Intersessional Expert Group (IEG). Three pressures were identified as priority: toxicity, turbidity and resettled sediment, and noise/light. Each was to be addressed by a sub-group comprised of scientists, managers and industry members with expertise and data in the particular pressure. Key objectives of the process are to synthesise and review existing information, identify appropriate indicators, define thresholds (including early warning levels as well as uncertainty), and evaluate critical gaps in knowledge. The process proposed by the LTC, the working mode of the IEG, and its potential timeline were described. Anticipated challenges (with the process, data, and expectations) were discussed, and the importance of ultimately defining pressure- and state- thresholds was stressed. The talk concluded with the expectation that the LTC and IEG could learn a lot from this workshop (which has subsequently proven well founded).

3. Workshop objectives and workshop structure

The workshop intended to provide an opportunity for interested scientists to share their expertise and discuss key scientific questions of ecotoxicology related to potential deep-sea mining, summarize current scientific knowledge, identify gaps and approaches to close these, and address related legal and regulatory aspects. The workshop aimed at covering ecotoxicological risks in benthic and pelagic realms across different taxa, life cycles, trophic levels and traits in different biological compartments from microbes to megafauna. The workshop further aimed at fostering joint research activities, such as toxicity experiments. While the focus of the workshop was initially on impacts from polymetallic nodule (PMN) mining, impacts from seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) and ferromanganese crust (CRC) mining were also addressed.

The first day started with a welcome note by the head of the BGR marine geology department, Dr. Christian Müller. Five plenary talks introducing the current state of knowledge and key research questions related to ecotoxicological risks of deep-sea mining, the present state of the Mining Code, and what can be drawn from other national and international regulatory frameworks filled day 1. These set the stage for subsequent discussions in breakout groups on specific topics, which were conducted on the 2nd day. On day 3, the topic moderators presented the results in plenary, followed by a lively and constructive discussion on how the development of threshold values for metal contaminants could be approached, considering the existing knowledge gaps and the conditions associated with the ISA regulatory framework.

List of plenary talks and speakers

Matthias Haeckel (GEOMAR): Overview on the environmental impacts of deep-sea mining

Malcolm Clark (NIWA): Development of ISA exploitation regulations including standards and guidelines and regulatory needs of the ISA

Sophie Paul (GEOMAR): Metal release and mobilization during deep-sea mining and potentially harmful impacts on organisms

Nelia Mestre (University of Algarve): Mechanisms of toxicity in organisms under deep-sea conditions

Jens Laugesen (DNV Oil&Gas): Developing environmental threshold values for metals in deep-sea waters - can existing threshold values for coastal waters be of any help?

List of workshop topics and identified key questions

Sources and routes of toxic exposure

- 1) What are the relevant chemical/physical fractions of metals in the context of DSM-related toxicity, considering the (different) uptake routes in these settings?
- 2) Which metals can we suggest as suitable key indicator variables for threshold definitions?
- 3) What are the limits of current experimental investigations? How can we foster more holistic approaches combining geochemical and biological assessments to determine toxic effects and derive threshold values relevant for DSM?
- 4) How is toxicity integrated with other environmental pressures and impacts (such as sediment plume dispersal and seafloor blanketing, causing smothering, clogging, physical damage, reduced food supply)

Biological mechanisms of toxicity

- 1) What are the key characteristics to define the best indicator species for ecotoxicological assessment of deep-sea nodule mining?

- 2) What are the possible methodologies to assess the toxicity of benthic plumes (and dewatering plumes if near the seafloor)?
- 3) What are the best potential indicators of stress to be measured?

Assigning toxic limits

- 1) Are biological indicator species acceptable to represent vulnerable species?
- 2) How confident are we in applying lab models to the real world?
- 3) How are trigger and threshold values for metal contaminants derived in other directives and guidelines?
- 4) Is it advisable to use default values for metal toxicant thresholds in deep-sea mining settings, as long as no site-specific toxicity data is available?
- 5) Are behavioural responses used in assigning toxicity limits in other scenarios?

Legislative implementation

- 1) How is the threat of toxic harm regulated in other regulatory frameworks? How can we adapt them?

4. Workshop discussions

This section provides summaries from discussions during the workshop. These discussions focused on key questions that had been formulated for the four topics prior to the workshop. The questions were not discussed exhaustively during the workshop due to time constraints, but the main aspects are provided below in bullet or brief text point format. **PART II** and **PART III** of this report attempt to provide more detail to address the scientific and legal background issues.

Topic 1: Sources and routes of toxic exposure

1. What are the relevant chemical/physical fractions of metals in the context of DSM-related toxicity, considering the (different) uptake routes in these settings?

Besides PMN, SMS and CRC need to be addressed. Assessments need to be done for each resource type and cannot be generalized from one resource setting to another.

Metals to focus on are Cu, Zn, Fe, Mn, As, Co, Ni, Pb, Hg and Tl.

Initial baseline data for some metals are available for some PMN contract areas: Mn, Cu, Cd, Ni, As, (Pb, Co) (Zn and Fe measurements are prone to contamination). Several elements including Fe, Zn, (Hg) are available from trace metal clean CTD sampling.

Baseline data are still very limited or absent for some metals (e.g., Hg, Tl)

The relevance of Hg in PMN settings is unclear but probably it is of little relevance. Toxic concentrations of Hg might possibly be relevant for SMS deposits.

First plume data from recent collector tests are available for different physical size fractions.

Assessing the chemical speciation and physical size fractionation of metals is important to assess bioavailability, but often difficult to measure. One approach could be to establish a relationship between total concentration and labile (bioavailable?) fraction (e.g., by using DGTs).

2. Which metals can we suggest as suitable key indicator variables for threshold definitions?

This is difficult to say. There are benefits to monitor fewer elements but toxic impacts will be different for each metal.

3. What are the limits of current experimental investigations? How can we foster more holistic approaches combining geochemical and biological assessments to determine toxic effects and derive threshold values relevant for DSM?

ecotoxicity tests need to be related to physiological responses. This will allow for results to inform the development of ecosystem modelling.

How can we link lethality of or an effect on a certain species (LC_{50} , EC_{50}) to the impact on the ecosystem?

For meaningful threshold value definitions, indicator species need to be defined.

A two-step approach to metal speciation testing might be useful: First, measurement of metal speciation in ecotoxicity tests and second, refinement in a further round of ecotoxicity tests to confirm the metal species and concentration causing an effect

To assess the toxicity mechanisms, ore and sediment tests at various concentrations and additionally single element tests need to be conducted.

4. How is toxicity integrated with other environmental pressures and impacts (such as sediment plume dispersal and seafloor blanketing, causing smothering, clogging, physical damage, reduced food supply)?

Multiple stressor experiments need to be defined. This has partially already been done for physical damage and toxicity.

Combined effects of climate change (other stressors) and DSM need to be considered.

Results of some of the more recent and realistic mining tests are now available: Trace metal mobilisation (Patania II: enhanced labile concentrations only measured within a few 100 m, not more than 1 km away)

Topic 2: Biological mechanisms of toxicity

What are the key characteristics to define the best indicator species for ecotoxicological assessment of deep-sea nodule mining?

- What are the exposure routes of most concern (particulate/solution/dietary)

All phases (particulate, adsorbed, in solution) may have differential toxicity depending on the species considered. For example, particulate phases may be more toxic by ingestion for burrowing species, whilst epifaunal mobile species may not be that impacted by particulate phases, but may be susceptible to metal species in solution (Brown & Hauton, 2018). Sedentary filter-feeding epifauna may be susceptible to exposure both in solution and via captured particles.

In the absence of species or functional group data information (abundance, distribution, diversity, mode of feeding) it is impossible, a priori, to predict which route is of most concern. However, with contractor data on species or functional groups within a location - it may be possible to predict which exposure routes should be considered as a priority for each licence area.

It should be noted that it may be difficult to discriminate between chemical impacts (metal toxicity) and physical impacts of mining (sediment load, smothering fauna, or blocking feeding or respiratory structures), at least during the immediate acute phase of mining. In situ, acute phase mortality or species displacement/migration might result from chemical or physical impacts or a combination of both.

- Characteristics of biomonitoring species

Typically, biomonitoring species should be abundant (either numerically and/or by biomass) in both impact and control/preservation areas, such that any biological response (or impact) can be compared. This potentially renders the choice of monitoring species as location specific.

When identifying potential biomonitoring species, consideration should be given to different functional groups, or different modes of feeding.

In many instances, especially where abundance is low but diversity is high, it may be necessary to establish biomonitoring groups from higher taxonomic levels or from functional groups, rather than specific species.

The ultimate choice of any potential biomonitoring species will be contingent upon contractor data for the EIA. A priori, it is impossible to state that a particular species or group should be used universally.

Consideration was given to the use of meiofauna and macrofauna as biomonitoring species. It was acknowledged that species and groups in these size classes might be useful to integrate organism impacts and identify community level effects. However, the timescales over which community scale effects might manifest remains uncertain.

Key conclusions were:

- Sessile species with a filter feeding mode of life were favoured.
- Larval stages are known to be susceptible and give an indication of generational impacts)Should not rule out mobile species – as behavioural observations can be useful (see below)
- Gaps in knowledge?

From discussion within the group, it was clear that there remain significant gaps in understanding, which preclude more definitive statements being made at this time. The group did express the strong view that early availability for contractor data on species assemblage is required when considering potential biomonitoring species/groups.

What are the possible methodologies to assess the toxicity of benthic plumes (and dewatering plumes if near the seafloor)?

The group considered the relative toxicity of a bulk resource could be established by experiments comparing with known metal pollutants. These experiments might adopt a model organism approach and may be run at atmospheric pressure and a standard temperature. Data from such experiments would establish the relative toxicity of different phases of an ore, without the need to ascertain ore/phase composition, and provide some indication of the potential risk of extracting a particular resource.

Toxicity of dewatering plumes could also be considered in a similar way, again by conducting comparative experiments of dewatering toxicity against known metals in solution using model (shallow-water fauna, or even lab cultures). In this way, the equivalent toxic potential of a dewatering source could be established, without the need to determining the metal composition or concentration in that waste water.

It was noted (again) that it will be difficult to separate the toxicity from metal from other, perhaps physical, impacts. It was suggested that such discrimination might not be necessary in the first instance as, initially, it may be sufficient to identify when a particular resource, mined in a particular way - in toto - produces an unacceptable impact.

It was further noted that, potentially, any impact thresholds established at the seafloor may not be appropriate for application to a dewatering plume, as this is likely to be released at lower pressures and higher temperatures.

List of possible in situ bioassays

Initially, it may only be possible to monitor for lethal effects, or gross behavioural effects/aberrations (e.g., avoidance behaviours/migration). These metrics might provide a definitive 'red light' during the initial stages of mining as considered below.

As understanding develops, and data are collected, from either pilot or commercial scale operations - then it might be possible to refine methodologies to recommend assays of sub-lethal stress.

For example, comparative assays (i.e., control v impacted) of tissue/cellular damage (e.g., lipid peroxidation of the formation of DNA adducts) or tissues recovery (e.g., antioxidant responses) may have potential value in identifying chronic or sub-lethal impact.

The group noted that it would be essential to establish the natural range of variability in any bioassay through baseline survey. Capturing baseline variability in any bioassay should be regarded as beneficial

and essential by any contractor in order to prevent the detection of false positives in impact assessments (i.e. misidentifying chronic 'impact' in the absence of fully establishing the range of variability in a particular bioassay). Any baseline survey should cover a sufficient temporal interval and resolution to capture at least annual variation in a biomarker at sufficient resolution.

Use of shallow-water proxies?

The group concluded that, whilst shallow-water proxies and field or lab model species, might be used to establish a) comparative toxicity of a bulk resource relative to known metals/phases, and b) to establish mechanistic insights of how toxic metals are taken up and how toxic effects are manifested, there are technically difficult challenges to their unambiguous deployment and interpretation for deep sea fauna in situ.

List of possible molecular, cellular biomarkers

The group considered that whilst 'omic approaches (e.g. molecular biomarkers) may be used to better understand the mechanisms and routes of toxicity, and also potential detoxification, their application should be considered in later phases of monitoring. Presently, there is too much uncertainty regarding the interpretation of data to apply them for monitoring at the current time. For example, metabarcoding approaches are taking place in early baseline surveys and in pilot mining experiments but more work is required to fully annotate genomic and transcriptomic pathways in order to avoid excessive 'unknowns', hampering useful interpretation.

Topic 3: Assigning toxic limits

As has been summarised previously (Hauton et al., 2017), the workshop concluded that we presently have low confidence in the ability to identify threshold limits for toxic exposure in abyssal fauna. Existing thresholds of toxicity (notionally LC_{50} , LD_{50} , EC_{50}) are established in shallow water fauna at standard conditions of temperature and pressure. It has been shown that these thresholds do not linearly or predictably transfer to conditions of low temperature and high pressure. Moreover, toxic limits have tended to be established for single metal species in a single oxidation state. Toxic exposure to metals through DSM is expected to occur through metal mixtures and metal complexes of uncertain oxidation status. Further, toxic limits established from laboratory studies are usually derived for rather limited life stages of standard biological model species (e.g. molluscs, crustaceans) that may be physiologically different to the dominant species groups that are impacted by any mining plume.

The workshop concluded that we have low confidence in the *a priori* assignation of toxic limits. Instead, it was proposed that the potential toxic threshold of each mineral resource could be established as part of a contractor's obligation toward the Environmental Impact Assessment or as part of the initial Baseline Investigations in the exploration phase. The toxic risk of the bulk resource (i.e. the combination of metal species in appropriate/relevant ionisation states released from freshly exposed mineral surfaces) could be quantitatively compared for different physical states (dissolved, particulate) against the toxicity of a standard metal(s) in relevant model biological species as a conservative approach to establishing the relative toxic risk of that mineral resource to local faunal physiologies.

The comparative toxic risk of a bulk resource to biological model species at environmentally relevant conditions could be considered in isolation, or could contribute toward the determination of threshold limit through a Weight of Evidence approach (Mestre et al. 2019).

Workshop discussion further considered the challenges of discriminating the different thresholds that might be breached during mining. Conventionally, discussions have considered, toxic thresholds separately to sedimentation/plume thresholds, and separately to thresholds for light or noise pollution. Whilst it may be tractable for disciplinary experts to consider different impacts in isolation, in reality the risk of impacts to species and ecosystems will manifest as a complex combination of different impacts acting simultaneously around a mining event. Organisms may be exposed to elevated metal concentrations at the same time as they are exposed to high levels of fine sediment and increased vibration and light. Ultimately the realised impact of a mining activity will be the function of a complex interaction of pressures. In light of this - does it make sense to consider threshold limits for different impacts in isolation? In real time, the determination of impact will be made by recording species mortality, or species migration away from impacted sites, ultimately resulting in a reduction in the number of live specimens of species recorded in and around mining sites.

In this context, the workshop considered that an initial early threshold could be established that identified **any change** in species or systems (e.g. excess mortality, unexpected migration), beyond natural baseline variability, as an unacceptable breach of threshold (with no reference to the nature of that impact - be it toxic, smothering, vibration, light or something else). This would be a conservative approach to setting thresholds that might be acceptable in the absence of sufficient scientific data. As mining develops, and as scientific understanding improves, then more nuanced threshold definitions could be identified which would reflect amber and green scenarios under any traffic light system.

Are biological indicator species acceptable to represent vulnerable species?

Not necessarily. The group was concerned that we currently have very limited confidence in the identification of vulnerable species at this time. Concern was expressed that we should even consider the assignation of 'vulnerable species', with the argument that there was merit in considering all species 'vulnerable' or having intrinsic value.

How confident are we in applying lab models to the real world?

The group expressed limited confidence in this. Whilst laboratory experiments can identify the metal concentration, or metal mixture concentration, at which shallow organisms are affected, it is not possible to transfer these values to deep-sea fauna directly. By their very design, laboratory experiments are designed to simplify the natural world and the group was conscious of the issues in extrapolating from laboratory observation to real world complexity.

Future shallow water experiments need to be validated by *in situ* studies, but future shallow water experiments could be more meaningful if they focused on more relevant species groups (e.g. sponges, corals). The group recommended that future experiments should focus on more relevant taxonomic or functional groups.

The group noted that the oil/gas industry has established thresholds for deep-sea cold-water corals and that metrics such as these could be considered as a place to start further experiments on thresholds in laboratory modules.

The group expressed the concern that the potential for temperature shock associated with dewatering plume presents a strong confounding factor in establishing toxic impacts but argued that but, in early stages of exploitation perhaps there was no need to have such resolution on the causative agent of any discerned impact, the priority should just be to identify that a process is impactful.

How are trigger and threshold values for metal contaminants derived in other directives and guidelines?

Establishing baseline variability is important to develop a 'traffic light' approach (to discriminate between amber and green scenarios). In initial stages, any impact (e.g. mortality, species changed behaviour or

migration) might be seen as a 'red light' which should require the cessation of all activity until the cause can be identified and rectified.

The challenge of subsequent study would be to identify the transition from green to amber, noting that natural variability in any metric should be included within the range of the 'green light'.

Is it advisable to use default values for metal toxicant thresholds in deep-sea mining settings, as long as no site-specific toxicity data is available?

The group considered that this was not a viable approach at this time. There is insufficient confidence in taking limits from existing legislation, or applying ligand modelling, and extrapolating either or both to the abyssal deep sea.

Are behavioural responses used in assigning toxicity limits in other scenarios?

Behavioural responses have some utility and potentially indicate community level effects.

Topic 4: legislative implementation

How is the threat of toxic harm regulated in other regulatory frameworks? How can we adapt them?

These included OSPAR, EU water framework directive, Norwegian environmental quality standards for classification of water, sediment and biota, Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality, EU marine strategy framework directive, Technical Guidance for Deriving Environmental Quality Standard from the European Commission

This could not be discussed in detail during the workshop.

See **PART III** of this report: Regulatory frameworks for environmental quality in marine waters and environmental management of offshore activities relevant as underpinning for DSM threshold development.

Considering the limited knowledge, does it make sense to define binding threshold values now?

Currently it is difficult to develop threshold values with confidence, hence it is important that they can be adapted easily with advancing scientific knowledge. A possible way forward could be to list threshold values in an annex that the binding parts of the regulation refer to (ISA Council wants to have thresholds in binding instruments (standards), being reviewed every 5 years).

How could an (adaptive) approach to derive DSM-related threshold values for different levels of protection look like?

Composition / concentrations of metals different for the resources (PMN + CRC oxidized, SMS reduced metals)

Possibly useful to define different values for dewatering plume and seafloor?

Which data is required from the beginning and what needs to be developed? – e.g. site-specific baseline data, toxicity data for deep-sea organisms

Baseline variability of metal concentrations and fractions as well as appropriate indicator species for toxicity assessment (holothurians as main C pool, sponge as specific habitat builder and filter feeder, larvae to address connectivity issue and most vulnerable etc) need to be established.

Is a level of protection that is expressed as percent of species protection based on experiments in pure water in any sense realistic?

Difficult/Not appropriate approach. We do not often know what the true biodiversity is at different taxonomic or functional levels, how many species exist, so how can we protect 95% or so? This links with measures that are more state-based thresholds than pressure thresholds.

Should toxicity guidelines be linked with guidelines for other impacts (such as plume spreading)?

Possible approach could be level of mortality, regardless where it comes from; Problem: what variable is measured then? Effect on fauna may take some time (years) to develop

The discussion noted that ecosystem functions (e.g. C remineralization -> O₂ consumption / respiration) are currently not considered in the ISA process on developing binding environmental thresholds.

The discussion further noted that thresholds need to be developed together with spatial footprint (vertical in water column and horizontal extent) and taking into account temporal variability also.

4.1 Upcoming activities and outlook

We here provide an overview on planned and proposed activities in connection with this workshop, to foster an integrated understanding of toxic risks of DSM, to simplify data accessibility and to stimulate future research.

Considering the time-critical regulatory needs of the ISA on one hand and the significant knowledge and data gaps with respect to toxic risks of DSM on the other, two different pathways of action should be followed in parallel over the next years: a pragmatic, likely staged approach in regulatory context of threshold development (also relies on management goals and should involve stakeholders), and a science-based approach to investigate toxic effects of deep-sea mining, find suitable bioindicators and chemical indicator variables, and understand integration of different environmental pressures and effects that determine overall ecosystem consequences in DSM settings. The latter is a cost-intensive process that requires ship-time and modeling approaches that can only be realised in an international collaborative effort.

Immediate actions will involve: (✓ indicates already fulfilled actions)

- ✓ Collate scientific literature on potential toxicity from DSM and DSM-related toxicity data from lab experiments (and in situ)
- ✓ Collate threshold/trigger/guideline values for water quality from existing regulatory frameworks
- ✓ Collate threshold/trigger/guideline values for sediment quality from existing regulatory frameworks
- ✓ Prepare a proposal for the upcoming MiningImpact project third phase - integrating (bio)geochemical, biological and ecological methods
- ✓ Plan in situ field toxicity experiments on future cruises (during upcoming MiningImpact third phase)

- ✓ Contribution to ISA threshold development – e.g. in form of this report.
- ✓ Plan joint ecotoxicological experiments with local conditions (sediment suspension mimicking operational plume, ...) and sessile and mobile fauna, adults and larvae (medium-term)
- Compile seawater baseline trace metal data from different contractor areas in the CCZ (data from contractors available?) and determine variability
- Prepare a database of trace metal baseline data
- Plan joint ecotoxicological experiments with key species
- Establish a DSM ecotoxicology working group consisting of interested scientists having regular meetings to exchange knowledge and plan future joint activities.

Outlook (only possible within well-funded research projects):

- define biological indicator species for different protection (or management) goals such as biodiversity protection, protection of faunal groups, early warnings etc; could be also particularly defined to address different water quality issues and uptake routes (uptake of labile metals, suspended sediments, dwelling in sediment)
- Geochemical speciation modelling / integration with hydrodynamic transport models - for the assessment of metal speciation and transport
- Risk assessment models, food web modelling (considering the integration of toxic effects with other environmental pressures, as well as cumulative and synergistic effects)

5. Workshop recommendations

From the workshop discussions, it clearly emerged that there is currently insufficient scientific knowledge and ecosystem understanding to derive a suite of definite toxicological threshold values that can prevent harm to the deep-sea environment. In light of the limited knowledge it is, therefore, recommended to consider overall a precautionary approach. This can be based on baseline information that contractors are obliged to collect and general information about toxic effects on marine (shallow water) organisms and existing regulatory frameworks (e.g. national water quality standards of New Zealand, Australia, Norway).

In general, following a traffic light system is recommended, where 'green' refers to a safe operational space where observables remain within their natural variability, 'amber' requires a more intense monitoring, including the elevated variable values, and management and mitigation actions need to be executed to return to a 'green' operational space, and finally 'red' requires operations to be stopped immediately and actions for clean-up and ecosystem rehabilitation are executed.

As a conservative approach to setting thresholds that might be acceptable in the current absence of sufficient scientific data, initial thresholds could be established that identified any change in species or systems (such as excess mortality, unexpected migration) beyond natural baseline variability, as an unacceptable breach of threshold (with no reference to the nature of that impact - be it toxic, smothering, vibration, light, etc). As a precautionary measure, those initial thresholds could be based on the most vulnerable identified species (once these are identified). As mining develops, and as scientific understanding improves, more nuanced threshold definitions as well as site-specific considerations could be identified which would reflect amber and green scenarios under a traffic light system.

Further recommendations are:

- A clear definition of terminology for (e.g., trigger, threshold, limit values, Environmental Quality Standards - EQS) is suggested following, e.g. Hitchin et al. (2023).
- Management objectives and levels of protection need to be defined, e.g. what should actually be protected (biodiversity, community composition, faunal groups, ecosystem functions, integrity of food web, etc.) - prerequisite for management thresholds, could be project-specific or generic.
- Targeted studies and experiments are needed to close knowledge gaps, such as key species of the ecosystem, most vulnerable species, biomagnification effects, integration of toxicity with other impacts, use of shallow-water organisms in laboratory experiments and comparison to in situ experiments.
- It may be advantageous to also develop particle concentration thresholds resulting in bulk impacts (lethality), because this may circumvent the need to identify or differentiate individual causes of toxic effects (e.g. particulate or dissolved toxic metal concentrations, physical impacts).
- Contractors should be required to perform comparative bulk toxicity tests (e.g., as part of any pilot mining test). System level changes, individual mortality or species migration would then be part of the real time monitoring, leading to adaptive management scenarios.
- Appropriate monitoring methodologies (e.g. type of toxicity tests, in situ experiments, applicability of indicator variables) need to be developed.

A more in-depth discussion on potentially suitable approaches and challenges for the development of management thresholds for DSM is provided in Part III of this report.

6. Workshop organisation committee

Katja Schmidt (BGR)

Katja is a geologist and geochemist currently working in the Department of Marine Resource Exploration at the German Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR). Her research interest lies on the geochemical behaviour and fate of trace elements at ocean interfaces, with a focus on the role of trace metal speciation. She worked on high-temperature hydrothermal systems at spreading zones and on riverine fluxes of trace elements and radiogenic isotopes from the continents into the oceans, on anthropogenic contamination of emerging pollutants such as gadolinium in rivers, coastal areas, and tap water, as well as on environmental impacts of deep-sea mining.

Chris Hauton (University Southampton)

Chris Hauton is based in the School of Ocean and Earth Science at the University of Southampton. He has broad research interests in understanding the toxic risks of deep-sea mining. His research encompasses all levels of biological organization from molecular studies of gene expression to assays of whole organism physiology and avoidance behaviours. He has previously contributed to the EC MIDAS Project and been a participant of the JPI Oceans 'MiningImpact' suite of projects. He has contributed to UK and international meetings on the impacts of deep-sea mining.

Nélia Mestre (University of Algarve)

Nélia C. Mestre is assistant researcher at the Centre for Marine and Environmental Research of the University of Algarve, Portugal. She obtained her PhD in Ocean and Earth Science in 2009 from the University of Southampton, UK. She is developing work related to marine ecotoxicology, with special emphasis on the environmental threats to fauna by deep-sea mining, and other human activities in the deep sea.

Joana Raimundo (CIIMAR)

Joana Raimundo is currently a Researcher at the Portuguese Institute of Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA) - Division of Environmental Oceanography, affiliated to the Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR) - Contaminant pathways in marine environment. She holds a PhD in Biochemistry (2010). Her work is mainly focused in the relations between exposure, fate and effects of contaminants in marine organisms, searching for responses and effects through biochemical or cellular modifications.

Sophie Paul (GEOMAR)

Sophie Paul is currently a Postdoc at GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel in Germany. She completed her PhD in 2019 at the Jacobs University Bremen, Germany. Her PhD work focused on the biogeochemistry of polymetallic nodule areas in the Pacific with a focus on trace metal cycling and the impact of deep-sea mining on the seafloor. Since then she is especially interested in trace metal speciation, trace metal cycling at the sediment-seawater-interface and the impact of early diagenetic processes on especially rare earth element cycling.

Matthias Haeckel (GEOMAR)

Matthias Haeckel is a senior scientist at GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel, Germany. His research interest is focused on a quantitative understanding of marine biogeochemical processes and how they are altered by anthropogenic activities. He has worked on methane seepage & gas hydrates, sub-seafloor CO₂ storage, impacts from deep-sea mining, and microplastic pollution for 30 years, and has participated in 22 seagoing research expeditions. Since 2015, he is the coordinator of the European JPI Oceans project 'MiningImpact' with 30+ partners.

7. List of workshop participants

Name	Affiliation
Øyvind Fjukmoen	DNV / Norway
Amy Gartman	USGS / USA
Andrea Koschinsky	Constructor University / Germany
Annemiek Vink	BGR / Germany
Becky Hitchin	Commonwealth Secretariat / United Kingdom
Beth Orcutt	Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences / USA
Carmen Sousa	University of Algarve, CIMA / Portugal
Chris Hauton	University of Southampton / United Kingdom
Christian Müller	BGR / Germany
Clara Rodrigues	University of Aveiro / Portugal
Dana Sackett	University of Maryland / USA
Dao Viet Ha	Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology / Vietnam
David Santillo	Greenpeace / United Kingdom
Dominique Anderson	Heriot-Watt University / United Kingdom
Fengjie Liu	Imperial College London / United Kingdom
Ellen Pape	Ghent University / Belgium
Erik van Doorn	Kiel University / Germany
Hiroyuki Yamamoto	JOGMEC / Japan
Isabel Diercks	GEOMAR / Germany
Jeff Drazen	University of Hawaii / USA
Jens Laugesen	DNV / Norway
Jesse van der Grient	SAERI / Falkland
Jessica Volz	AWI / Germany
Joana Raimundo	IPMA/CIIMAR / Portugal
Kamila Mianowicz	IOM / Poland
Katja Schmidt	BGR / Germany
Kerstin Kröger	JNCC / United Kingdom
Leandro Marinho	University of Algarve / Portugal
Malcolm Clark	NIWA / New Zealand
Mark Hartl	Heriot-Watt University / United Kingdom
Marlene Pinheiro	CIIMAR / Portugal
Masanobu Kawachi	National Institute for Environmental Studies / Japan
Massimiliano Molari	MPI Bremen / Germany
Matthias Haeckel	GEOMAR / Germany
Melissa Wang	Greenpeace / United Kingdom
Miguel Caetano	IPMA/CIIMAR / Portugal
Min-Seok Kim	KIOST / South Korea
Nélia Mestre	CIMA, University of Algarve / Portugal
Noemie Wouters	ISA
Patricia Esquete	University of Aveiro / Portugal
Rebecca Zitoun	GEOMAR / Germany
Samantha Smith	Blue Globe Solutions / Canada
Se-Jong Ju	KIOST / South Korea
Sophie Paul	GEOMAR / Germany
Sylvia Sander	GEOMAR / Germany
Tanja Stratmann	NIOZ / the Netherlands
Tasnim Patel	RBINS / Belgium
Tobias Höfig	FZ Jülich / Germany
Yeun Park	KIOST / South Korea

PART II

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1. Environmental impacts of deep-sea mining

Matthias Haeckel

Impacts from mining activities on the marine environment will differ between resource types because polymetallic nodules (PMN) and Co-rich ferromanganese crusts (CFC) are essentially two-dimensional resources of oxide minerals at the surface of the abyssal seafloor and flanks of seamounts, respectively (Hein and Koschinsky 2014), whereas seafloor massive sulfides (SMS) form three-dimensional deposits of sulfide minerals extending tens to hundreds of meters into the subsurface (Hannington et al. 2011). However, three consequences appear to be common for the currently discussed mining technologies, (1) the removal of the uppermost seafloor layer, including its epifauna and infauna, (2) the suspension of mineral debris and/or sediments into the water column, including the release of dissolved substances, that spread with the ocean currents and (3) blanket also some untouched seafloor area in the vicinity of the mined area.

Here, the research outcomes obtained by the European project MiningImpact of the Joint Programming Initiative of Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans (JPIO) are summarized, which so far has focused on the impacts related to the mining of polymetallic nodules. The first project phase (2015-2018) investigated the longer-term (decadal) consequences resulting from small-scale seafloor disturbances introduced by benthic impact experiments (BIEs) in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone (CCZ) and the Peru Basin (DISCOL experimental area) in the 1990s (SO239: Martínez-Arbizu and Haeckel 2015; SO242: Greinert 2015 and Boetius 2015), whereas the second project phase (2018-2024) delivered a comprehensive and independent scientific monitoring of the first industrial trial of a pre-prototype nodule collector vehicle by the Belgian contractor GSR in the CCZ with three expeditions (SO268: Haeckel and Linke 2021; IP21: Vink et al. 2022; SO295: Haeckel et al. 2023).

Figure 1.1: Locations of the MiningImpact study sites (red stars) in the exploration contract areas of BGR, GSR, Ifremer, IOM, UKSRL, and the Areas of Particular Environmental Interest (APEI) 3 & 6 in the CCZ sampled during SO239, JC120, SO268, IP21, and SO295. Map indicates the POC flux at the seafloor in $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ of carbon (Vanreusel et al. 2016).

Figure 1.2: Bathymetric maps of the GSR and BGR areas indicating the locations of the Patania II trial and reference sites. Colored dots indicate locations of baseline sampling during SO268.

1.1 CCZ environmental baseline

During the expeditions a comprehensive dataset of biological, geochemical, geological, and oceanographic information was collected from the contract areas for the exploration of polymetallic nodules BGR, GSR, Ifremer, IOM, and UKSRL in the CCZ as well as the Areas of Particular Environmental Interest 3 and 6 set up by the International Seabed Authority (**Figure 1.1**). The repeated sampling of the pre-impact trial and reference sites in the BGR and GSR contract areas (**Figure 1.2**) in conjunction with the Patania II mining test provides some information with respect to spatial and temporal variability.

1.1.1 BIODIVERSITY

Taxonomic analyses of megafauna from imagery showed a high variability in overall faunal density and community composition on local spatial scales as well as significant differences between the study sites (**Figure 1.3, Figure 1.11**). However, several epifaunal and endofaunal species appear to be widespread across the CCZ (Janssen et al. 2015). Densities of sessile taxa in nodule areas are variable (14-30 individuals per 100 m²; **Figure 1.11**). In nodule areas, anthozoans are the most abundant sessile group within the epifauna larger than 3 cm (>63 %), followed by sponges (Porifera, 6-36 %) (**Figure 1.11, Vanreusel et al. 2016**). Mobile epifauna (>3 cm) was represented by echinoderms (Holothuroidea, Ophiuroidea, Echinoidea, and Asteroidea) in both, nodule-rich and nodule-free areas. Densities varied between 4 and 15 individuals per 100 m² among nodule-rich sites, largely due to the contribution of ophiuroids (Vanreusel et al. 2016). Densities of the mobile epifauna were more than two times lower at nodule-free sites (1-3 ind./100 m²) compared to nodule fields in the same geographical area, with a particularly large decrease (>50 %) in ophiuroids and echinoids (Vanreusel et al. 2016).

Nodule-free seabed also had a distinctly different taxonomic composition (**Figure 1.11**). This is a direct consequence of nodule surfaces being inhabited by sessile metazoan epifauna, on average ~20 animals per nodule. These include Hydrozoa, Anthozoa, and Porifera (Vanreusel et al. 2016), but also smaller organisms, such as nematodes (~78%), copepods (~11%), ostracods, tardigrades, polychaetes, tanaids, and foraminiferan protists inhabiting the crevices of nodules (Gollner et al. 2017).

In soft sediments the macrofaunal community is dominated by polychaetes (42%) and Nematoda (28.9%), followed by Copepoda (10.5%) and Ostracoda (2.7%). DNA barcoding of tissue vouchers showed that the BGR and GSR areas share 21% of polychaete MOTUs (molecular operational taxonomic units), but only 9% of isopod

MOTUs. This difference has been reported previously for the CCZ and has been interpreted as a result of the putative weaker dispersal abilities of isopods (Janssen et al. 2015; Janssen et al. 2019). Metazoan meiofauna abundances in the CCZ is high (on the order of thousands of individuals per 100 cm²) as is their biodiversity, with many rare taxa (Pape et al. 2021; Uhlenkott et al. 2021). Dominant taxa are nematodes (>90%), followed by copepods (<9%). Variability of meiofauna abundance is high (Uhlenkott et al. 2021), and of often similarly high between individual cores of one multicorer deployment as between geographically different study sites.

Figure 1.3: Relative abundances of sessile and mobile epifauna in the reference and trial sites of the GER and BEL areas based on dedicated ROV transects. Overall megafaunal densities in the GER area (25-37 ind./100 m²) were significantly higher than in the BEL area (10-21 ind./100 m²), and lowest for the no-nodule transect (5 ind./100 m²).

Overall habitat heterogeneity is high, and is influenced by factors, such as food availability (e.g., POC flux to the seafloor), seafloor topography (e.g., slope, roughness, seamounts/hills), nodule abundance and size. As a consequence, biodiversity and spatial variability of all variables is high on small (m to km) to large (thousand km) spatial scale. Temporal variability is currently largely not known. Abundance and biomass of all faunal size classes (meio, macro- and megafauna) typically decrease along the productivity gradient from eutrophic to oligotrophic environments (Figure 1.11; Vanreusel et al. 2016). This underlines the importance of benthic-pelagic coupling at the prospective mining sites and its potential negative effect on the benthos when naturally occurring phytoplankton and detritus arriving at the seafloor during times of plume dispersion aggregate and alter the dispersal pattern (Pabortsava et al. 2011; Purser and Thomsen 2012). Evidence of a wide geographic distribution exists for some genotypic clusters (e.g., polychaetes and isopods) that appear to be related not only to life history but also to distance (Janssen et al. 2015). However, assessing population and ecological connectivity across the CCZ remains limited by low sample numbers, a patchy sampling scheme, and the high proportion of undescribed species (Gollner et al. 2017).

1.1.2 BIOGEOCHEMISTRY

Biogeochemical fluxes in the surface sediments follow the general trend of POC fluxes onto the seafloor decreasing from S to N and E to W across the CCZ. A good biogeochemical marker for this is the oxygen penetration depth that is around 2-3 m in the Eastern BGR license area (Mewes et al. 2014; Mogollón et al. 2016), increasing to 4 m and more in the GSR and Ifremer license areas and oxygen not being completely consumed in APEI 3 (Volz et al. 2018, 2020). This directly relates to higher oxygen consumption rates as a key variable for microbial organic matter remineralization and more labile organic carbon (e.g. Chl-a

concentration) being available in the surface sediments of the GER area compared to the BEL area. Also, bioturbation activity as a key ecosystem function shows a slightly deeper mixing depth in the BEL area compared to the GER area. Besides these significant spatial variations on CCZ-scale, the biogeochemical variables also show considerable small-scale variabilities on meter-to-kilometer scale.

1.1.3 HYDROGRAPHY

Time-series measurements of the hydrographic regime in the CCZ show that ocean bottom current velocities are typically 2-4 cm/s and directions are highly variable (**Figure 1.4**). Semi-diurnal (12 h), diurnal (24 h), and near-inertial (48-70 h) frequencies were observed, and on longer time scales clockwise and anti-clockwise rotational flow with a 30-to-90-day frequency dominates (**Figure 1.4**). Regularly, meso-scale eddies detach from the Central American coast towards the CCZ (3-5 per year, particularly pronounced during El-Nino phases). With a lag time of 200-300 days they arrive in the BGR license area, where they can amplify bottom current velocities by a factor of 2-5 (as observed in April/May 2013; Aleynik et al. 2017), which can affect sediment plume dispersion and its deposition area.

Figure 1.4: Three years (April 2013 to May 2016) of current data measured in the German BGR contract area (BGR 2018) by 600-kHz ADCPs at 12-16 m above the seafloor (top: stick plots of current speed and direction; bottom: current velocity, black lines = averaged values).

1.2 Sediment plume dispersal

The monitoring plan of the Patania II trials in the GSR and BGR areas (**Figure 1.2**) involved the deployment of an array of 50 acoustic and optical sensors on 20 platforms to determine the spatial and temporal evolution of the suspended benthic sediment plume and its redeposition at the seafloor (**Figure 1.5**; Gazis et al. 2025). The spatial outline of the sensor array was informed by predictive modelling of the sediment dispersion applying a high-resolution hydrodynamic regional ocean model coupled with a sediment transport module (Purkiani et al. 2021). Model simulations used oceanographic current data from the past ten years and updated parameterizations for sediment particle flocculation that had been derived in lab experiments using on-site

surface sediments (Gillard et al. 2019) to produce probability maps of sediment plume dispersal and deposition for the trial months March to May. All sensors were intercalibrated before and after the expedition to allow for a quantitative comparison of the sensor signals with respect to the mass of particles per volume of water.

Figure 1.5: Bathymetric maps of the GSR trial area showing the Patania-II mining path and the layout of the sensor platforms (green triangles) and AUV survey lines (purple lines) indicating where recorded suspended particle concentrations (in mg/L) were above background values (yellow). See (Gazis et al. 2025) for a detailed analysis

The sediment plume suspended by Patania II formed a gravity current behind the nodule collector that was channeled downslope in local seafloor sections with slopes $>3^\circ$, overall travelling up to ~ 500 m distance. Beyond this distance, the prevailing bottom currents dominated the sediment transport for more than 4-5 km distance, at which the AUV survey still recorded particle concentrations of ~ 0.1 mg/L. The highest suspended particle concentrations of up to ~ 260 mg/L (i.e. four orders of magnitude larger than ambient background values of <30 $\mu\text{g/L}$) were recorded in ~ 100 m distance, but decreased rapidly with increasing time, distance, and altitude, and dropping back to background levels after the plume had passed by. Most of the plume remained close to the seafloor (<5 m above seafloor). However, the plume height increased with distance and time, and elevated suspended particle concentrations were detected up to 50 m height (highest monitoring altitude). Substantial sediment deposition was observed within the first 500 m downslope, but seafloor blanketing was identified on AUV photos up to distances of >3 km. The hydrodynamic model was applied to simulate the recorded suspended sediment concentrations in order to estimate the seafloor area affected by sediment deposition and the spatial and temporal footprint of the sediment plume in the water column. The recorded sensor data could be matched quite well. In addition to detecting and quantifying suspended particle concentrations, diffusive gradient thin film (DGT) passive samplers were mounted on some sensor platforms. They recorded a significant release of some metals (e.g. Cu, Co, Mn) from the suspended sediment plume.

Figure 1.6: Example photos illustrating the impact categories at various distances from the mined site: (top left & centre) thick plume cover (>1 cm deposition estimated), (bottom left & centre) thin plume cover (<1 cm deposition estimated), (top right) collector impact with *Patania II* caterpillar track imprints (removal of 4-8 cm of surface sediments and subsequent deposition of ~3 cm estimated), (bottom right) thick plume cover with a new low-lying suspended sediment plume passing by.

1.3 Effects of mining on the nodule habitat and benthic ecosystem functions

Impact sites of the *Patania II* trials were categorized qualitatively into “collector impact” (the mining area where the collector removed nodules and surface sediment with fauna) and “plume impact” (the area outside the mined area, where a thick sediment cover was deposited). These two sites were sampled for all variables (biology, microbiology, geochemistry) with several replicates. At distances from the mined area of more than a couple of hundred metres considerable less plume material was deposited, but a clear blanketing was observed (termed “plume impact thin cover”, but only studied for some variables, and hence not discussed here). **Figure 1.6** shows example photos of the impact categories.

Figure 1.7: Densities of macrofauna (left, UAveiro, unpublished) and nematode meiofauna (right; after Lefaible et al. 2024) in the GSR area (pre-impact trial, collector impact, and plume impact sites).

Immediately after the Patania II trials a first impact assessment was conducted by sampling the collector and plume impact sites. Abundance of meiofauna and macrofauna was strongly reduced in the collector impact site compared to data of pre-impact samples of the trial sites and reference sites, whereas increased faunal abundances were found in the plume impact site with thick blanketing (**Figure 1.7**). The reason for this observation is not clear at the moment. One possible explanation is that the fauna suspended with the sediment was preferentially deposited in the close vicinity of the mined area, i.e. behaving as rapidly sinking large particles, another explanation is that the fauna in the buried surface sediments is migrating upwards into the deposited sediment layer towards the new sediment surface to avoid suffocation (i.e. to regain the required oxygen supply for respiration). From our data it is currently also not clear, if the fauna (or parts of it) has survived the nodule collection and sediment suspension process.

Figure 1.8: (Left) in situ measured oxygen microprofiles in the GER area in the pre-impact trial site (gray), the reference site (black), the collector impact site (red), and the plume impact site (blue). Solid lines represent the average profile and shaded areas the standard deviation; pre-impact data from SO268 and IP21; impact and reference data from SO295 (Janssen et al. 2024). (Center & right) Total organic carbon (TOC) and Chlorophyll-a content in surface sediments from IP21 (unpublished data BGR and MPI; black = reference, red/yellow = collector impact, blue = plume impact).

Dissolved oxygen concentrations measured immediately and 1.5 years after the trials indicate diffusion of oxygen into the deeper sediment layers in the collector impact sites (**Figure 1.8**), thus indicating strongly reduced or non-existent microbial remineralization of organic carbon in the disturbed sediments. This is corroborated by a reduced peak of nitrite concentrations in the pore water, a metabolite in the nitrate reduction pathway of organic carbon remineralization, as well as lower total organic matter content and more importantly a lower labile fraction (i.e. food quality) than in the pre-impact situation (**Figure 1.8** center & right). Overall, this provides data supporting the previous model predictions of PMN mining impacts on biogeochemical processes in surface sediments (**Figure 1.9**). In contrast, dissolved oxygen consumption is elevated in the plume impact sites with thick deposition (**Figure 1.8**), corroborated by a significantly larger and wider nitrite peak. Unfortunately, this does not yet shed light on the question, if the fauna has survived the nodule collection and sediment suspension process or not – both, labile organic carbon from the deadfall being degraded by the microbes and increased bioturbation as a result of upward migrating fauna could potentially lead to higher oxygen consumption. Further analyses and diagenetic modelling will address this question.

Overall, the caterpillar track imprints of Patania-II added significant small-scale spatial variability to all benthic data, thereby complicating the interpretation.

Figure 1.9: Schematic diagram (Haffert et al. 2020) depicting the biogeochemical processes in the surface sediments: Organic matter deposited on the seabed is mixed into the sediment by burrowing fauna (bioturbation, white dotted arrows), thereby inducing a more effective microbial (orange) remineralization of labile organic matter (green), which in return provides nutrients (blue arrows) for the higher trophic levels of the benthic ecosystem. Polymetallic nodule mining removes this reactive, bioturbated surface layer. Recovery of the biogeochemical processes and fluxes takes thousands of years as it is essentially controlled by the re-establishment of the reactive surface layer through sedimentation (<0.5 cm/kyr) of labile organic matter.

As part of the sensor array, also ocean bottom seismometers were deployed near the collector test sites. The recorded acoustic data (0.1 - 2000 Hz) shows significantly increased noise levels in the frequency range below 10 Hz that is related to the nodule collection activity of Patania-II (**Figure 1.10**). Since this noise level dropped off quickly with distance from the collector, we currently interpret it as seafloor. At higher frequencies the ship noise of the mother vessel is the dominant noise source (**Figure 1.10**).

Figure 1.10: Noise levels (in dB) in the frequency range below 100 Hz recorded with an ocean bottom seismometer over the time of the deployment. Elevated noise levels below 10 Hz correspond to the operating time of Patania II.

Figure 1.11: Comparison of epifauna abundances (sessile and mobile) between (top) normal deep-sea floor in CCZ areas and (bottom) various old disturbance tracks (left to right: 1979 OMCO track, 2015 GSR EBS, 2013 IFREMER EBS, 1995 IOM-BIE) w/o nodules (modified after Vanreusel et al. 2016).

Investigating decade-old benthic impact experiments (BIEs) in the CCZ (e.g., 20-yr old IOM-BIE, 37-yr old OMCO track) and the DISCOL area (26-yr old) can shed some light on the longer-term (decadal) environmental consequences to be expected from deep-sea mining. Prominent marks on the seafloor were clearly visible even several decades after the BIEs were created, irrespective of their size. Our results show that in general epifaunal abundances of sessile fauna attached to the nodules (e.g., sponges, hydrozoa) and mobile fauna associated to the nodule hard substrate (e.g., ophiuroids, isopods) are reduced in the tracks even decades after the impact was created (**Figure 1.11**; Vanreusel et al. 2016). In the DISCOL experimental area also a shift of the epifaunal community structure from dominantly filter feeders (decreasing from 76% to 42%) to

detritivores and predators (increasing from 20% to 49%) was observed (Marcon & Purser, unpublished). Analysis of the species interaction web in the CCZ and DISCOL area identified stalked glass sponges as key structural species supporting a high diversity of associated fauna (**Figure 1.11**; Stratmann et al. 2021). As a consequence, polymetallic nodules are critical for food web integrity and their loss explains the observed decrease in local benthic biodiversity.

In addition, microbial communities and important ecosystem functions did not recover within 26 years after the DISCOL seafloor ploughing experiment, as documented by reduced microbial metabolic activity, reduced oxygen consumption (i.e. organic matter remineralization) due to decreased availability of labile organic matter compounds, reduced microbial cell numbers, and absence of bioturbation activity in the surface sediments (**Figure 1.12**; Vonnahme et al. 2020). Based on these findings numerical modelling predicts that benthic biogeochemical processes and fluxes need thousands of years to recover after the removal of surface sediments during polymetallic nodule mining (König et al. 2001; Haffert et al. 2020; Volz et al. 2020).

Figure 1.12: Summary of investigated disturbance levels in the DISCOL area and observed benthic biogeochemical activity (microbial organic matter degradation, total oxygen uptake (respiration), microbial production). Classification of the observed biogeochemical activities per area of seafloor (from light yellow = high activity to red = low activity). (after Vonnahme et al. 2020).

1.4 Conclusions

Key conclusions from the MiningImpact project (Boetius and Haeckel 2018) are:

- Deep-sea ecosystems associated with polymetallic nodules support a highly diverse fauna of sessile and mobile species; the biodiversity is currently not known for any of the faunal classes.
- Deep-sea faunal communities and environmental variables show a high variability on small to large spatial scales (from hundreds of metres to thousands of kilometres).
- The temporal variability of faunal abundances remains unknown due to the lack of long-term ecological time series.
- Species connectivity over relevant spatial scales for reference zones and for conservation as well as a complete ecosystem understanding remain critical knowledge gaps, currently hampering the assessment of the large-scale (regional) consequences.

Monitoring of the Patania-II collector trials and BIE investigations show that:

- Polymetallic nodule test mining removed the entire bioactive surface layer of the deep seafloor (top 4-8 cm).
- The suspended sediment formed a dense particle plume with concentrations of 10-260 mg L⁻¹ (i.e. 500-10,000 times natural background values of 20-30 µg L⁻¹).

- Initial plume dynamics were driven by turbidity flow behavior, where the plume largely stayed within 10 m above seafloor.
- Plume dispersal was dominated by bottom water currents at a distance of a couple of hundred metres from the test mining area.
- A fine particle plume (3-5 times natural background values) was transported beyond the survey area at 4-5 km distance.
- Suspended plume material resettled at the seafloor inside the mined area and blanketed the benthic habitat more than 1000 m downstream.
- A blanketing thickness of more than 1 cm covered a seafloor area 5-6 times larger than the test mining area.
- Elevated metal concentrations (Mn, Co, Cu) were observed in the dense particle plume.
- Loss of seafloor integrity by nodule and seafloor removal affects all ecosystem compartments and reduces population densities and important ecosystem functions (e.g. nutrient remineralization, microbial growth, bioturbation activity).
- Environmental impacts are long-lasting (on spatial scales of several hundred km² per year and mining operation): benthic biogeochemical processes will take up to several thousand years to recover; the specific nodule habitat in the mined area is lost permanently.
- Sediment plumes will likely blanket the seafloor up to several kilometers outside the mined area; the impacted area is significantly larger than the mined area.

Key recommendations derived from these results include (Boetius and Haeckel 2018):

- Conservation areas need to match habitat characteristics of mined areas to preserve abyssal biodiversity and protect vulnerable ecosystems.
- Minimizing impacts requires careful & adaptive spatial planning of mining operations (e.g. establishing network of representative PRZs) and the development of low-impact mining procedures (e.g. vertical spreading of suspended particle plume should be restricted close to the seafloor, including the injection of the return waste-water plume).
- Technologies for baseline studies and monitoring need to be standardized and regularly revised to reflect state-of-the-art science. Indicator sets for deep-sea ecosystem status and threshold values for harmful effects must be defined.
- Transparent and independent scientific assessment of deep-sea mining operations needs to be secured.

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2. Biological mechanisms of toxicity in organisms under deep-sea conditions

Chris Hauton, Nelia Mestre, Joana Raimundo

This chapter summarises the current state of knowledge on biological mechanisms of toxicity under deep-sea mining conditions, including temperature and pressure effects, the sensitivity of different life stages and potential application of shallow-water proxies.

2.1 Mechanisms of toxicity

Exposure to non-essential heavy metals (e.g. Pb, Hg, Cd, Cr, As) or, indeed, essential metals in excess quantities (e.g. Fe, Cu, Mn, Zn) can produce toxic effects in cells and tissues of all organisms.

By binding or interacting with cellular molecules (e.g. proteins, lipids and carbohydrates) metals are known to affect organelles and other components, including lipid membranes, mitochondria and chloroplasts, nuclei and enzymes involved in both oxidative and anaerobic metabolism (Tchounwou et al. 2012). These interactions might occur through electrostatic interactions between the valent metals and organic molecules, including interactions with cellular components such as DNA or proteins in the nucleus, which might lead to DNA damage or changes in protein conformation leading to aberrations in cell cycle and cell division, to cell death (apoptosis), or carcinogenesis.

Alternately metals ions may have toxic effects by substitution of an essential micronutrient metal co-factor such as the substitution of calcium ions by cadmium in the oxygen evolving centre of Photosystem II, impacting photosynthetic oxygen release (Matysik et al. 1998).

Others exhibit polyvalency (metals that occur in different oxidation states – e.g. ferrous (Fe 2⁺) and ferric iron (Fe 3⁺) or cuprous (Cu⁺) or cupric (Cu 2⁺) copper) that can exert a toxic effect through the creation of reactive free radical ions (species of reactive oxygen and reactive nitrogen) that might adversely affect various important classes of biological molecules such as nucleic acids, lipids, and proteins, thereby altering the normal redox status leading to increased oxidative stress (Phaniendra et al. 2015).

Examples include the formation of the superoxide ion radical (O₂^{•-}) through auto-oxidation, e.g.:

Or alternately, the formation of hydroxyl radicals (HO•) through the Fenton or Haber Weiss reactions:

As metals can also be sequestered within tissues in the form of organometallic complexes (including metallothioneins or phytochelatins) or as insoluble intracellular inclusions (Cosson and Vivier 1997; Cosson 1997) there is potential for metals to bioaccumulate during an organism's lifespan or bioaccumulate through trophic transfer in marine food webs. As such, what might constitute an initial non-toxic concentration in the 'environment' might accumulate to toxic concentrations in long-lived species or be magnified to toxic concentrations, through trophic transfer. Toxic effects may not be immediate and acute, they may be manifest long-term and far field from the initial point of release.

2.2 Detoxification mechanisms and implications

The intracellular regulation of essential and non-essential metals is fundamentally important to cell survival for all organisms. Through evolution, multiple solutions to the problem of regulating metal concentration have evolved and these are variably expressed in all organisms from prokaryote microbes through to large metazoan eukaryotes. However, there are considerable taxonomic differences in the expression and detailed mechanisms of the regulatory processes, even for closely related species (Mestre et al. 2019a). This diversity in mechanisms of detoxification challenge the establishment of 'global' thresholds for toxicity.

Bacterial extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) have been reported which can chelate environmental metals and so reduce their bioavailability for uptake by bacteria and other species at the base of food webs (Nogueira et al. 2009; Yilmaz et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2014). As such, the production of EPS, although variable between different species and strains, appears to provide some protection of bacteria, including cyanobacteria, from the toxic effects of metals in the environment.

Phytochelatins are oligomers of glutathione, produced by the enzyme phytochelatin synthase. They are found in plants, fungi, nematodes and all groups of algae including cyanobacteria, which are key primary producers in low nutrient oceanic environments. Phytochelatins are small, intracellular, metal-binding polypeptides produced when in exposure to increased metal concentration in their environment (Le Faucheur et al. 2005).

In many metazoans, the production of refractile, heat stable metallothioneins (MTs) has been reported. Metallothionein are metal binding proteins which are induced in response to elevated metal exposure and are intracellular protectors while binding toxic metals, such as cadmium, and transporting these between organs by forming inclusion bodies, or being secreted from the cells (Ritterhoff and Zauke 1998) although metallothionein expression does not occur in all species or in all tissues. As an example, Gonzalez-Rey et al. (2007) demonstrated that the differential biochemical responses of MTs in both vent and coastal shrimps are affected not only by the environmental characteristics but also by inter-specific differences.

Diverse antioxidant pathways are reported from both prokaryotes (Pinto et al. 2003; Martínez-Ruiz and Martínez-Jerónimo 2015; Priya et al. 2007) and eukaryotic groups (Lee et al. 2017; Seco et al. 2021). Antioxidant pathways essentially serve to convert reactive oxygen (ROS) and nitrogen species (RNS) to less harmful substrates that can be further metabolised or excreted. Antioxidant pathways include diverse enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and ascorbate peroxidase, and the synthesis of low molecular weight compounds such as carotenoids and glutathione. At high, or acute, levels of metal pollutants, damage to cells occurs because ROS levels exceed the capacity of the cell to respond. At lower, or chronic, levels algae accumulate heavy metals and can pass them on to organisms of higher trophic levels. Recent work has, however, demonstrated that the expression of antioxidant pathways can be considerably different between even closely related species, which makes broad predication of antioxidant capacity based even on close species phylogeny, extremely challenging.

Antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, CAT, and peroxidases (PEROXs) are some examples (e.g. Company et al. 2004; Company et al. 2006; Company et al. 2007; Company et al. 2008; Bebianno et al. 2005; Gonzalez-Rey et al. 2007). MTs can also play a defensive role against ROS. Glutathione can bind to redox-inactive metals and form non-toxic metal complexes. In the deep-sea habitat, the environmental metal concentration varies, with copper for example ranging from 0.17 μM at Menez Gwen to 2 μM at Rainbow vent sites in the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (Kádár et al. 2005). When assessing sub-lethal effects of exposure to copper in hydrothermal-vent shrimp *Rimicaris exoculata* (exposed to 25 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ or 250 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ copper for 72 h, (Auguste et al. 2016) or in the mussel *Bathymodiolus azoricus* (exposed to 300 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ copper for 96h, (Martins et al. 2017) it was observed that Cu had negative effects in the activity of key antioxidant enzymes as well as lipid peroxidation in different

tissues. This highlights that even in hydrothermal vent species that are adapted to metal-rich environment they can be sensitive to exposure to dissolved copper, depending on the concentrations. Different tissues are also differently affected, often due to the route of uptake of the metal over time, such as the case of the gills in *R. exoculata* with a significant induction of metallothioneins after 72h, what was not accompanied by the muscle tissue (Auguste et al. 2016). Nevertheless, all the mechanisms of detoxification consume energy, and this will limit the energy available for other processes such as locomotion, growth or reproduction (Sokolova et al. 2012), what will ultimately compromise the health and survival of the populations potentially affected by deep-sea mining.

Figure 2.1: Simplified synthesis of the routes of metal toxicity and detoxification in animal tissues. Metals in the environment that enter animal tissues can be sequestered by various metal binding proteins, including metallothioneins and other thiol-rich peptides, and either stored or excreted from those tissues. Metallothioneins can also detoxify hydroxyl radicals within cells. Redox active metals can drive the formation of superoxide anion radicals ($O_2^{\cdot-}$) via hydroxyl radicals ($HO\cdot$) that, if unregulated, can lead to lipid peroxidation and damage to cellular membranes. Superoxides can be enzymatically converted to hydrogen peroxide by superoxide dismutase (SOD). Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) is enzymatically converted to water by catalases and peroxidases (CAT and PEROXs, respectively) or by the action of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione disulphide reductase (GR). Synthesis adapted from: Stocker and Keaney (2004), Aitken and Roman (2008), and Martinez-Finley and Aschner (2011). Adapted from Hauton et al. (2017).

2.3 Measurable biological responses

2.3.1 MORTALITY ENDPOINTS

Acute metal toxicity is often measured using model species in carefully controlled laboratory experiments. Normally these experiments identify the concentration of a metal that will kill either 50% or 90% of the population in a fixed exposure time; so-called LC or LD_{50} or LC/LCD₉₀ endpoints, usually at 24, 48, 72 or 96h.

The US EPA maintain a database of acute toxicity data that can be interrogated as a baseline for understanding.

Whilst these data have some use, they are somewhat limited in that they normally only present a single metal exposure, with metal in a single complex/valency and are conducted at standard conditions (notionally a temperature of 20°C and a pressure of 0.1MPa). From recent experiments, reviewed by Hauton et al. (2017), it has been shown that these conditions do not represent those that might be associated with metal exposures from deep-sea mining activity – exposures that will occur at low temperature but potentially high pressure and involving complex metal mixtures and metal complexes. Indeed, experiments conducted at low temperature and high pressure and with metal mixtures (e.g. Cu²⁺ and Cd²⁺, Brown et al. 2017a) have demonstrated that the effects of temperature and pressure on the toxicity of single metals and metal mixtures are not necessarily predictable. This challenges the development of appropriate real-world threshold limits of toxicity based on experimental data (Hauton et al. 2017).

2.3.2 SUB-LETHAL ENDPOINTS

Acute toxicity presents just one aspect of metal exposure in the environment. As discussed, long-term exposure to lower metal concentrations can also exert a debilitating effect on the performance of exposed organisms. Many argue that the nature of these sub-lethal impacts are more insidious than acute outcomes, in that they can take longer to manifest, and can occur in organisms far field from the original source. Moreover, the detection of these effects is more difficult. Nonetheless, some sublethal endpoints might merit consideration in the context of toxicity monitoring.

2.3.2.1 Biochemistry

Quantifying the expression of components of various antioxidant pathways has been advocated as a useful indicator of chronic oxidative stress caused by metal exposure (Seco et al. 2021; Samarakoon et al. 2023; Ou et al. 2023; Han et al. 2024). Whilst this idea has some merit, there are practical challenges in capturing and fixing the antioxidant profile of deep water fauna at the time of collection, essential to ensure that robust data of in situ antioxidant mechanisms or indices of oxidative damage (e.g. lipid peroxidation) are collected. Furthermore, as Mestre et al. (2019a) demonstrate, using biomarkers in shallow-water proxy species, even for closely related species, is not without its challenges.

Moreover, the induction of antioxidant pathways and oxidative damage is part of an organism's normal repertoire of response. Oxidative stress and the production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, can be caused by endogenous sources that might not be associated exclusively to the exposure to toxic insult (including: mitochondria, peroxisomes, endoplasmic reticulum, phagocytic cells). As such, the unequivocal determination of oxidative stress in response to toxic metal exposure can only be made with comparative measurements in 'control' individuals sampled simultaneously from impact-free environments.

The identification of novel biomarkers that could respond more effectively and specifically to deep-sea mining exposure scenarios would be ideal. Although time consuming and expensive, recent technologies such as omics (e.g. transcriptomics, proteomics) may help to achieve this (Sousa et al. 2024).

At the same time, before any biochemical marker of toxic stress can be deployed for evaluating risk or monitoring activities, it would be necessary to verify the baseline variability of that biomarker over multiple seasons/years of that organism's life – as biomarkers exhibit temporal variability as a result of season, life stage, or reproductive condition. All these aspects add complexity to the application of biochemical markers of chronic toxicity, particularly in the case of deep-sea fauna.

2.3.2.2 Physiological, including reproductive metrics

As discussed, chronic exposure to metals can induce detoxification pathways which prevent/delay any toxic impact. However, these pathways require energy expenditure, redirecting energy away from other baseline functions (for example, see the propositions of Sokolova et al. 2012 – particularly their Figure 1).

As a consequence, authors have argued that changes in reproductive output, and other measures of organism gross function might be used as an indicator of chronic metal exposure (Gagneten and Vila 2001; Bielmyer et al. 2006; García-García et al. 2006; Rodgher et al. 2009; Jarvis et al. 2013). As with biochemical indicators of chronic toxicity from metal exposure, physiological and life history metrics of chronic toxicity can only reliably be compared against non-exposed individuals of the same species sampled at the same time, a difficult proposition for deep-water fauna.

2.4 Summary of salient issues

Still there are only a few published studies where the effects of metals were assessed under deep-sea conditions. These involved studies with shallow-water or deep-water organisms, exposed to metals in the lab or in situ, in some also including different temperature and high-pressure regimes (Auguste et al. 2016; Brown et al. 2017a; Brown et al. 2017b; Martins et al. 2018; Martins et al. 2022; Mestre et al. 2019a). Behaviour and biomarkers of oxidative stress are some of the endpoints presented in these studies. The current knowledge can be synthesised as follows:

- Low temperature appears to decrease lethal and sublethal toxicity in shrimps adapted to warmer environments, probably linked to lower metabolism, so is it also likely that there is a delay in toxicity? As the observed delayed mortality in cold-water corals (Martins et al. 2022)?
- Pressure seems to affect differently the lethal and sublethal toxicity of different metals; it potentiates the lethal toxicity of mixtures of metals; being an environmental factor not to be ignored, although there are still limitations in conducting ecotoxicological experiments under hyperbaric conditions (both in situ and in pressurised aquaria);
- Early-life stages are the most sensitive, and crucial for the maintenance of viable populations (Mestre et al. 2019b). The life cycles for most deep-sea species is unknown, so when establishing future thresholds, it is necessary to take this into account.
- Shallow-water proxies are apparently not possible to define for sublethal biomarkers in shrimps. For holothurians there was a broadly similar acute behavioural response, although replication with deep-sea species when conducting in situ experiments is an issue.
- There are thus many questions to answer towards a better understanding of the ecotoxicological effects of deep-sea mining in deep-sea organisms.

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3. Sources and routes of toxic exposure in deep-sea mining settings

Katja Schmidt and Sophie Paul

Deep-sea mining (DSM) activities of polymetallic nodules (PMN) and seafloor massive sulphides (SMS) will release trace metals to the environment that might induce toxic effects in benthic and pelagic organisms, at all levels of biological organization from the molecular level to community and ecosystem level. **Understanding how organisms are exposed to metal contaminants is important for the assessment of the potential toxicity arising from marine mineral mining** and the necessary regulatory decisions to prevent harmful effects from the marine environment (UNCLOS, 1982).

Several trace metals present in the ocean are known to be essential for biological functions in organisms but can become toxic at elevated concentrations, such as Cr, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, Se, Zn, while other trace metals, such as Ag, As, Cd, Hg, Pb, Sb, Sn, Tl, are known to cause toxic effects without any known biological function (**Figure 3.1**).

Figure 3.1: Examples for essential and non-essential metals and metalloids.

Depending on the resource type and setting as well as on the mechanism of ore extraction and dewatering, these metals can become enriched to variable degrees in the environment, compared to natural conditions. **Various abiotic and biotic factors such as metal speciation and lability, uptake routes, organism types, habitat and feeding strategy, life stage and toxicant dose control the toxicity of metals.**

3.1 Metal sources and mobilization processes

Metal sources are the ore material, the associated sediments and/or host rocks that are mined. During mining activity, this material gets mobilized into the environment, is distributed as plumes and re-settles at the seafloor as blanketing layers. Mobilisation of metals generally occurs during the production of the ore from the seabed and the return discharge of material back into the ocean after separating the ore from the production stream on the sea surface operation platform (**Figure 3.2**). Seabed operations and resulting effects will differ considerably for PMN and SMS deposits, while the dewatering processes are likely similar.

Figure 3.2: Mining scenarios for PMN and SMS and release of trace metals to the environment during mining activities. a) polymetallic nodule mining (adapted from Hein et al. 2020), b) massive sulphide mining (adapted from SPC 2013). Not to scale. A: trace metal fluxes from the pore water, B: ore resource, C: riser system.

3.1.1 OPERATIONAL AND DEWATERING PLUMES

For **PMN**, the currently tested mining concept involves the exhaustive removal of the entire top sediment layer containing the nodules (uppermost 5-15 cm, Helmons et al. 2022 and references therein, Peacock 2023) by a hydraulic collector vehicle. The collector activity will lead to the formation of an **operational plume** at the back of the vehicle, resulting from sediment entrained by the nodule collector's seawater jets, the separation from nodules and sediment inside the collector and subsequent sediment expulsion (e.g., Peacock 2023; Gazis et al. 2025). In contrast, mining of **SMS** deposits as a three-dimensional resource will result in a comparatively smaller footprint at the seafloor, and the formation of operational plumes will be limited. Ore extraction will likely be done by devices vertically cutting into the sulphide ore body, but plume formation

Affected areas: PMN mining

Currently, economic calculations consider mining of 2-3 million tons of polymetallic nodules per year for a single mining project. Assuming minimum nodule abundances of 15 kg per square meter, this equates to 200-300 km² of seafloor per year for an economically viable mining project (Weaver et al. 2022). The spatial footprint of the mining activities at the seafloor and in the water column is expected to be larger than the directly affected mine site, mainly because of plume spreading and particle settling.

depends on the exact cutting mechanism and the structure of the deposit. For both, PMN and SMS mining, the ore extracted at the seafloor will be pumped together with water and remaining sediment and fauna to the surface platform via a riser and lifting system (**Figure 3.2**). On board the mining support vessel, the ore material will be dewatered and the excess water and residual fine suspended solids (sediments and crushed ore material) will be pumped back as a slurry (**dewatering plume**). Surface seawater used to clean the nodules aboard the vessel will increase the temperature of the slurry by several degrees Celsius relative to bottom seawater, affecting metal solubilities in the plume. A release of these plumes only a few meters above the seafloor is strongly recommended, in order to minimize the impact on the water column (Thiel and

Forschungsverbund Tiefsee-Umweltschutz 2001). Warmer and hence less dense water becomes, however, more difficult and costlier to return to the seafloor. The discharged water and sediment mass flow rates from seafloor operation and dewatering will depend on the technology used to collect the nodules.

After mobilisation, the inventory, mobility and fate of trace metals in mining-impacted environments is further modified by chemical processes such as mineral dissolution and precipitation, oxidation, desorption and adsorption, integrated with physical processes such as plume dispersal and dilution, flocculation and settling of particles.

Discharge release rates

During the Patania II trials in the CCZ in 2019, the collector discharged 8-12 kg/s of sediment at a discharge flow rate of about 1 m³/s, forming the operational plumes (Muñoz-Royo et al., 2022). Oebius et al. (2001) calculated a discharge flow rate of 0.56 m³/s for commercial PMN mining, with a particle concentration of 8.3 kg/m³.

The composition and grain characteristics (particle sizes and specific mineral surface areas, freshness of mineral surfaces) in plumes depend on resource type and setting and on the plume type (operational plume or dewatering plume), and in turn determine the reactivity and metal transformation between the different physical and chemical states. The operational plumes that will form during PMN mining consist of mineral grains from the soft sediment surface such as biogenic silica, clays, feldspar, quartz and manganese oxides as well as organic detritus, together with crushed nodule material. In the dewatering plumes, particles will probably be dominated by fine-grained crushed ore consisting of poorly crystalline Fe-Mn (oxyhydr)oxide minerals with fresh mineral surfaces, together

with some amount of detrital minerals (Wegorzewski et al. 2015; Kim et al. 2021), in a mixture with a significant amount of sediment (Muñoz-Royo et al. 2021)¹. SMS operational and dewatering plumes will mainly consist of fine sulphide particles, likely together with detrital material from surface sediment or magmatic rocks or silicate debris from SMS cap rocks (depending on setting).

The main stress factors for the environment include enhanced particle loads and turbidity, multiple metals in different chemical and physical forms, and potentially reduced food availability.

Both, operational and dewatering plumes possess an increased toxicity potential that might affect pelagic and benthic fauna including the larval stages of (vent) organisms. Facilitated by an increased chemical reactivity of plume particles due to high reactive surface areas and fresh mineral surfaces that form during ore crushing and processing, the plumes are characterized by enhanced metal concentrations in various states that may become available for biota.

Enhanced trace metal concentrations in the plumes relative to the surrounding seawater are related to:

- the higher particle load, with trace metals bound in the mineral lattice or adsorbed to mineral surfaces of suspended (nano)particles
- a mobilization of trace metals from the suspended material into the dissolved and nanoparticulate phase during remineralization and desorption/dissolution processes
- an adsorptive enrichment of dissolved trace metals from the water column onto plume particles (scavenging).

In oxygenated seawater, extensive mineral dissolution of Fe and Mn oxides, hydroxides, and oxyhydroxides in the dewatering plumes of PMN mining is not expected, but metals will likely be subject to adsorption and

¹ Assuming that no chemicals or substances are added to the production stream to facilitate cleaning of the ore material

desorption processes, related to the large reactive surface area and the high scavenging potential of these types of particles. In contrast, the sulphide minerals dominating in SMS dewatering plumes are likely to be affected by oxidation processes and mineral dissolution (i.e., oxidative dissolution)², releasing metals at different oxidation states into the dissolved phase (seawater) and enhancing the toxicity potential. If the released metals are not immediately re-fixed in oxides or hydroxides or other secondary minerals by oxidation, coprecipitation or adsorption (Hu et al. 2022), local accumulation of dissolved metals in the water column is possible. The dewatering plume generation process results in fine sulphide particles with large and fresh mineral surface areas that are more reactive in seawater than sulphide deposits at the seafloor, where slow oxidation kinetics are estimated to limit the metal release from hydrothermal sulphide (Fuchida et al. 2017; Bilenker et al. 2016). The ore mineral composition, texture and access to fresh particle surfaces are some of the decisive factors determining the bulk lethal toxicity of a deposit (Fallon et al. 2019). Enhanced water temperatures expected in the dewatering plumes would also affect the solubility of minerals and may further facilitate mineral dissolution. Sulphide weathering and mobilization of potentially toxic metals is also discussed in the context of another offshore activity: marine tailings disposal (see **PART III** of this report).

Yet unpublished results of the Patania II nodule collection trials in the CCZ provide first insights into metal mobilization during the formation and dispersal of operational mining plumes. From the measured elements (As, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, REY, V, and Zn), moderate enrichments of Fe, Co, Mn, Ce by factors of 2 to 10 and of Cu by a factor of 1.5 were observed in the dissolved fraction <0.2 µm of the plume compared to natural bottom seawater, at a suspended particle concentration of about 10-15 mg/L (BGR 2024). This moderate enrichment in the dissolved fraction of the plume despite strong particulate enrichments reflects the oxic environment in bottom seawater, stabilising oxide mineral components and favouring scavenging processes.

3.1.2 BLANKETING LAYERS

Particles settling out of the plumes will form blanketing layers that may be up to several cm thick (Vink et al. 2022) and represent additional sources with an enhanced toxicity potential at the seafloor³. Blanketing composition will vary depending on the mineral deposit type (PMN, SMS), the type of plume (operational, discharge), and the distance to the release point. An increased toxicity risk is mainly expected in the blanketing from discharge plumes, due to the dominance of ore material and the presence of fresh, reactive particle surfaces in this plume type. Dissolved metal concentrations in the pore water of the blanketing layer will equilibrate with the respective minerals and metal complexes at mineral surfaces. Dissolved metal contaminants may be released into the overlying water via diffusive pore water fluxes (see also section 3.1.3 below), through sediment resuspension or through bioirrigation, while also the pore waters and the mineral-laden particles themselves also possess an enhanced potential toxicity, especially to deposit-feeding organisms. Metal toxicity may act independently from or in combination with other potential stress factors arising from the deposition of material at the seafloor – physical burial, changed substrate characteristics, and reduced food/energy availability. Biogeochemical activity (e.g., organic matter remineralization) will differ from pre-impact state and will modify the metal budget, distribution, and bioaccessibility of metals over time.

² The toxicity of SMS deposits was investigated in several experimental studies and different processes of metal mobilisation from sulphide minerals such as oxidative dissolution, desorption, and galvanic interaction between mineral couples leading to mineral dissolution were deduced (e.g., Fuchida et al. 2017; Fallon et al. 2019; Fuchida et al. 2018; Simpson and Spadaro 2016, more references in Washburn et al. 2019).

³ Several cm were observed within the mined areas and in close proximity (<50 m) during the Patania II trials (Vink et al. 2022).

Mineral transformation in the deposited material such as oxidation of sulphide mineral phases at aerobic conditions and metal transfer into secondary mineral, dissolved or nanoparticulate forms, or reductive dissolution of oxides in microniches or under anaerobic conditions with metal transfer into pore water will shape the potential toxicity of these deposits.

3.1.3 PORE WATER METAL FLUXES

Diffusive fluxes of dissolved trace metals from the sediment into the bottom seawater may increase in the context of mining activities, leading to transient enrichments in the bottom seawater close to the sediment water interface (SWI). Enhanced metal fluxes due to the removal of surface sediment at the direct mine sites would be mainly expected in environments with shallow oxic-suboxic/anoxic boundaries within the upper 5-20 cm of the sediments. Many potentially toxic metals are strongly enriched in pore water at oxygen-deficient conditions (in the micromolar range), related to the reduction of oxide minerals and metal release into pore water during microbial organic matter remineralization processes, and sediment removal would significantly increase benthic metal fluxes to the SWI (e.g., Fritsche et al. 2001; Paul et al. 2018). Such conditions are, for example, prevailing in the Peru Basin (Haeckel et al. 2001), where increased benthic Mn fluxes at the SWI are evident after a disturbance (Paul et al. 2018). However, such mining-induced metal diffusion into overlying water would be a transient process, as oxygen diffusion into the sediment would re-establish oxygenated conditions in the uppermost centimeters within a few months after disturbance. Dilution in the oxygenated bottom seawater and immediate fixation in oxide minerals further limit the likelihood of long-lasting toxic risks for epibenthic biota related to enhanced metal fluxes. The presence of oxygenated secondary blanketing burying the exposed deeper sediment would also decrease metal fluxes. In the CCZ, the oxic zone in upper surface sediment is usually thicker than 0.5 m (e.g., Volz et al. 2018; Mewes et al. 2014), and consequently dissolved metal concentrations remain generally low. However, several elements (such as Mn, Co, Cu, and V) show characteristic, sharp concentration peaks in the nanomolar range (with 2-100 fold enrichments) in the uppermost 1-3 cm of sediment. This enrichment is likely related to processes such as organic matter degradation (e.g., Cu, V) coupled with a decrease in pH under aerobic conditions (Du et al. 2025), or reductive dissolution of Mn oxides (micronodules) in microenvironments (e.g., Mn, Co) (e.g., Koschinsky et al. 2001; Paul et al. 2018; Paul et al. 2024; Steiner et al. 2023; BGR 2024). These characteristic metal distributions lead to small natural benthic metal fluxes from the sediment into bottom seawater in the eastern CCZ (BGR 2024). Overall, the removal of the top sediment layer during polymetallic nodule mining is not expected to increase metal fluxes at conditions prevailing in the CCZ, but instead, decreasing fluxes related to the removal of labile organic matter and Mn micronodules are likely. However, the deposition of secondary blanketing layers on top of the removed sediment will lead to integrated effects of metal fluxes (see below).

Diffusion of metals from the sediment into bottom seawater might increase in areas with newly deposited sediment/ore material inside and outside the directly mined areas (see **CHAPTER 3.1.2**). In deposits of plume material generated during polymetallic nodule mining, dissolved metal fluxes are not expected to increase drastically. The material will consist, depending on the plume source, of variable amounts of natural sediment and oxidic nodule material derived from nodule fragmentation or crushing. The presence of micronodules is known to increase the concentrations of specific (nodule-associated) metals in surface sediment pore waters (see above) and might lead to enrichments in blanketing pore waters, but this enrichment is expected to be small. In contrast, significantly enhanced fluxes can be expected in areas with extensive sulphide mineral-rich blanketing layers formed during SMS mining, related to dissolution and mineral transformations. This is supported by observations in deposition zones of sulphide-bearing mine tailings in Norwegian fjords and in deep-sea settings in Papua New Guinea, where enhanced metal fluxes have been proven up to decades after cession of mine tailings disposal (Schaanning et al. 2019).

Figure 3.3: Seafloor pictures before (right side) and after (top and bottom left) mining of polymetallic nodules. Plume picture in the upper left (metal transformation in the plumes may occur as a consequence of (bio)geochemical reactions between the dissolved and the particulate phases during plume dispersal).

Risks to the ecosystem

Ore extraction at the seafloor and the discharge of slurry pumped back down to the seafloor represent a major risk to the deep-sea ecosystem. The major environmental stressors include high particle loads and turbidity, enhanced sedimentation, diluted food supply due to reduced particulate organic carbon (POC) concentrations, and enhanced concentration of metals in particulate, colloidal and dissolved states. The expected impacts on the ecosystem such as smothering of benthic organisms, clogging of surfaces and filter organs of filter and suspension feeders, starvation, physical damage, and enhanced metal toxicity. This chapter focusses on metal toxicity of mining plumes and secondary plume material deposits (blanketing), although in reality such impacts will be integrated with other impacts which may lead to joint effects. Our understanding of cause-response relationships between environmental stressors and biological effects in deep-sea ecosystems in the context of deep-sea mining is still very limited and an assessment of effects arising from individual and combined impacts is urgently needed.

3.2 Trace metal speciation

The mobility and fate of trace metals in the environment are governed by their speciation. Trace metals occur in different physical states (physical speciation) and different chemical forms (chemical speciation), see **Figure 3.2**.

Physical speciation describes the phase association and is usually operationally defined by a filtration pore size, with typical sizes classes such as **particulate** ($> 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ or $0.45 \mu\text{m}$), **dissolved** ($< 0.2 \mu\text{m}$), **nanoparticles and colloids** (NPC, $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ to 1kDa), and **truly dissolved** ($< 1 \text{kDa}^4$). Classically, trace metal concentrations in seawater are determined as particulate or dissolved fraction. However, significant proportions of “dissolved”

⁴ Kilodalton (kDa): mass unit used to describe molecular masses.

trace metals passing through a 0.2 μm (or 0.45 μm) filter may in fact be present as NPC aggregates (organic or inorganic colloids and organo-metallic colloids, e.g., Fe (oxyhydr)oxides or Fe-organic matter colloids; see references in Raiswell and Canfield (2012), with distinct physical and geochemical properties compared to truly dissolved species. Owing to their high specific surface area and complexation capacity, colloidal particles may be of great importance in the cycling of particle-reactive elements (Guo and Santschi 1997). Particulate metals comprise both mineralised forms where the metal is bound within the crystal lattice and those where the metal is associated with, or loosely bound to or loosely bound to (oxyhydr)oxide mineral phases, clay, or organic matter with high scavenging potentials.

Chemical speciation includes free hydrated species, metal complexes with inorganic ligands (e.g., Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻, etc.) and with organic ligands (e.g., humic acids, fulvic acids, siderophores, amino acids), and different redox species. Individual species of a metal have different mobility, uptake availability and toxicity.

Chemical speciation and bioavailability modifying toxicity (examples)

Arsenic (As) is more toxic in its trivalent (III) oxidation state compared to its pentavalent (V) oxidation state.

Chromium (Cr) is more toxic in its hexavalent (VI) oxidation state compared to its trivalent (III) oxidation state.

Copper (Cu) is often more bioavailable in its hydrated or inorganically complexed form compared to its organically complexed form.

Trace metal partitioning between the different size pools in ambient seawater is hypothesised to result from a “steady state” of dissolved metal exchange reactions including ligand exchange, sorption/desorption, and aggregation/disaggregation (Fitzsimmons et al. 2015). In mining-associated sediment plumes, similar processes will control the trace metal partitioning between the different pools. **Trace metal release from re-suspended surface sediment into the truly dissolved pool is likely limited in PMN settings. Considerably increased metal concentrations for some elements can be expected, however, in the nanoparticulate/colloidal pool** (e.g., in the form of Fe (oxyhydr)oxides, Mn oxides).

Figure 3.4: modified from Paul et al. (2024), Lead and Wilkinson (2006) – Overview of compound size classes and examples of organic and inorganic compounds within this size schematic. upper part: chemical speciation, lower part: operationally defined physical speciation.

Physical and chemical speciation in the particle plume will evolve as the plume spreads and ages, which in turn modifies the potential toxicity of the plume. Particle plumes will disperse with currents or as turbidity flows, and dilution and size fractionation due to particle flocculation and settling will lead to changes in

suspended particulate matter concentration, size and composition. Particulate, dissolved and colloidal phases will have different dispersal dynamics. Highly reactive NPCs do not readily settle out, and are likely to stay in the water column over long distances and for long times, forming far-field plumes. Their relevance for toxicity needs to be investigated.

3.3 Uptake routes

For deep-sea mining scenarios, various exposure routes of potentially toxic metals need to be considered: (1) the uptake of dissolved, freely available metals across body walls, gills, and digestive tracts of exposed organisms by transmembrane transport (2) the ingestion of (nano)particles such as sediment particles or crushed ore material which become enriched in the guts (Hauton et al. 2017).

3.3.1.1 Transmembrane transport

The biotic uptake of metals through cell membranes is most commonly facilitated by biotic ligands such as membrane proteins or lipid-soluble molecules that bind a metal on one side of the membrane, diffuse across and transfer the metal to the solution on the opposite site. As usually only free metals can bind to the receptor sites, metals need to be available in a truly dissolved state or bound in weak complexes that easily break up in the presence of the biotic ligands (unless they are lipophilic such as methylmercury⁵). The dissociation of metal complexes occurs in the diffusive domain outside of the cell membrane. Metals bound to inorganic ligands (such as CdCl^+) are efficiently taken up, while the uptake of strongly bound metals (such as Cu-DOC complexes) is highly limited. In the presence of partially labile complexes, accumulated metal concentrations increase with increasing thickness of the diffusion domain of the organism, due to a higher contribution of the partially labile complexes. Hence, different types of organisms exhibiting different diffusion domains (that induce different dissociation degrees of metal complexes) may face different available concentrations in a common setting. The uptake of metals bound to colloids is generally limited, related to the slow diffusion rates that increase with size of the compound, independent from its bond strength.

3.3.1.2 Ingestion

The dietary uptake of particulate metals presents a significant route of metal exposure and accumulation to benthic filter-feeding and deposit-feeding organisms (Lee et al. 2000; Simpson et al. 2016 and references therein; Campana et al. 2012; Camusso et al. 2012; Carreiro-Silva et al. 2022), and is controlled by the feeding behavior. The potential toxic impact of metals associated with (nano)particles depends on the mode, rate and selectivity of feeding and on the type of metal binding (i.e., binding with sulphides, organic carbon, or Fe or Mn (oxyhydr)oxide phases) (e.g., Simpson and Batley 2007). Particle-induced toxicity can arise from particle-associated metals or from the physical presence of the particles themselves.

⁵ Lipophilic complexes are lipid-soluble and can hence pass biological membranes

Subsequent effects of particle ingestion can be:

Solubilisation of particles and metal desorption in the gut, release of dissolved metal ions (post-uptake metal toxicity)

Mechanical damage from the particles (with inflammatory responses and oxidative stress), tissue translocation

Starvation due to reduced dietary intake (as particles occupy space in the gut, comparable to microplastics uptake by organisms)

Direct particle toxicity (cytotoxicity)

Metals adsorbed to or crystal lattice-bound in ingested (nano)particles and colloids might be solubilized in the gastrointestinal tract⁶ and enter the cells, where they may exert toxic effects. Metal release depends on the strength of the association to particles, and metals adsorbed to mineral surfaces, e.g. to Fe (oxyhydr)oxides and Mn oxides, are much weaker, and metals are hence released quickly, than metals that are incorporated in the crystal lattice.

A variety of feeding strategies in the different benthic faunal size classes was determined in the CCZ (Stratmann 2023), such as filter and suspension feeders, epistrate feeders, deposit feeders, scavengers, carnivores and omnivores. Deposit feeders can feed in the subsurface or on the sediment surface to various degrees of selectivity on the heterogenous pool of sedimentary detritus (such as

on bacteria, phytodetritus, diatoms, and semi-labile detritus) and can also feed selectively with respect to particle sizes and texture. **Hence, different organisms sharing the same habitat will be differently exposed to potentially toxic metals.**

Metal availability: Bioavailability and bioaccessibility

Numerous definitions for the term “bioavailability” exist and are differently used in different environmental science disciplines (see overview in Semple et al. 2004; Fedotov 2014). We here use it as follows:

Bioavailability is represented by a chemical component, which is freely available to cross an organism’s cellular membrane from the solution the organism inhabits, enter a cell, and become available at a site of biological activity.

Using this definition, particle-bound metals are generally less bioavailable than dissolved forms of metals. In the dissolved form, metals may occur in colloidal or organically complexed forms that will be less bioavailable than truly dissolved hydrated metal ions and metal ions bound to inorganic ligands. Plume formation during mining activities may not only lead to an increase of directly bioavailable metal concentrations, but will particularly increase the amount of “bioaccessible” trace metals in the habitat of the benthic and pelagic organisms, related to the enrichment of suspended (nano)particles in the environment.

Bioaccessible trace metals are *potentially* available for an uptake into the cells of organisms.

The bioaccessible trace metal fraction also includes fractions that are bound in or to particles and nanoparticles and that might be converted into bioavailable forms, either by external processes within the plume or by internal processes after uptake of particles by organisms, liberating the metals from the (nano)particles and making them bioavailable.

⁶ Trace elements associated to particles can permeate across the endoderm of the guts only after their dissolution, via digestive enzymatic or chemical solubilisation (leading for example to reductive dissolution of oxide minerals, see Turner and Olsen 2000. Presence of metal-specific enzymes or ligands for metal dissolution and intake through cell membranes is also an important factor and related to metal essentiality.

Filter and suspension feeders will mainly be affected by dispersing plume particles and may suffer from both physical effects and potential desorption of metals and uptake through the filter organs, while (sub)surface deposit feeders may be affected by the higher (particulate) metal load in sediment blanketing layers formed out of the particle plumes. Feeding strategies partly change through the different life cycle stages of an organism⁷, and experimental investigations unravelling potential toxicities of metals and particle plumes need to consider all relevant life stages.

3.4 Assessment and monitoring

The assessment and monitoring of trace metals in deep-sea mining settings requires indicator variables with established relationships between concentrations/rates and biological effects and also need to address the various biotic uptake routes.

The conventional approach to determine trace metal concentrations of toxic potential in an environment is the filtration of water samples through 0.2 µm or 0.45 µm pore size filters ("dissolved" pool). However, the relation to the actual bioavailable concentration of that metal remains unclear. Established analytical and sampling methods and protocols exist (GEOTRACES Cookbook 2017), but especially for seawater the risk of contamination is high and sampling and analyses are challenging and costly. Chemical speciation of trace metals in the dissolved phase can be assessed by analytical investigations such as voltammetry, which is a labour- and time-intensive method.

Another approach that has received increasing interest is a passive sampling method using the technique of diffusive gradients in thin films, short DGT. It is simple to use, applicable in a range of environments, cost effective and has the potential to trace the bioavailable fractions of a metal in solution. Deployed in situ, small-sized binding membranes accumulate metals over time, usually over days to months for metal concentrations in the deep sea, and time-integrated average concentrations for the period of deployment are calculated. DGT measurements further represent a speciation method, as only the fully labile trace metal fraction of the dissolved pool is measured. DGT-measured labile concentrations include hydrated metal ions and metals bound in weak complexes (usually inorganic ligand molecules, section 1.1.2). **The lability is directly linked to speciation and as the uptake process of trace metals with DGTs generally mimics the diffusion-limited uptake through cell membranes of organisms (Degryse and Smolders 2016), the determination of DGT-labile concentrations might be more conclusive than the measurement of total dissolved concentrations.** Copper, for example, forms quite stable complexes with organic molecules such as DOC in seawater and in turn, its bioavailability in the presence of organic ligands is strongly reduced. This is reflected in significantly reduced DGT-labile concentrations relative to total dissolved Cu concentrations in seawater and highlights the importance to determine speciation data and the potential of DGT measurements for ecotoxicological studies and regulatory aspects (Schmidt et al. 2022). While it is also possible to use **chemical speciation modelling** to determine bioavailable metal fractions (recommended e.g., in Australian/New Zealand guidelines for water quality), the databases are limited especially for saline solutions, and with respect to kinetic reaction rates, and adsorption to particles. Model parameterizations are often poorly validated by data and often rely on theoretical concepts. A more direct way to assess the bioavailable fraction is certainly favourable. In contrast to spot water samples presenting snapshots in space and time, DGT measurements provide average values over prolonged times. **Considering the potential of dynamic bioavailable metal**

⁷ Larvae of filter-feeding organisms can be lecithotrophic, i.e., they feed on energetic reserves and don't filter feed.

concentrations, average DGT-labile concentrations might be more conclusive than total dissolved concentrations to assess the exposure of organisms to toxic metals in mining-affected settings and to monitor toxic metal concentrations in these settings. Nevertheless, the time integration done when calculating DGT-labile concentrations prohibits the monitoring of concentration spikes of metal releases from plumes and prohibits to determine the life span the released metal speciation lasts in the water. A combination with spot sampling to capture short-term concentration spikes in the framework of environmental impact assessments is hence recommended, unless other suitable indicator variables are established.

Application of DGTs in the context of environmental management

DGTs are in use for the chemical assessment of European coastal water bodies (e.g. Rodríguez et al. 2021), for the monitoring of polluted estuarine and coastal marine sites (Gaulier et al. 2021), and to assess the environmental risks of deep-sea disposal of gold mine tailings (Sherwood et al. 2009). DGTs are identified as promising tools to improve quality assessments within the Water Framework Directive WFD (Amouroux et al. 2023), and within the Australian/New Zealand water quality guidelines (ANZG draft for revised copper default guideline).

As part of risk and compliance assessments, DGT-labile test site concentrations can be compared with regulatory thresholds for total dissolved concentrations.

Recently, Amouroux et al. (2021b), Amouroux et al. (2023), and Amouroux et al. (2021a) suggested adapted WFD threshold values for DGT-labile concentrations of a range of metals, which would allow direct comparisons.

Several studies have investigated the potential of DGTs to determine trace metal bioavailability in water, by correlating DGT lability with bioaccumulation of specific metals and toxic effects in different types of organisms (e.g., Degryse and Smolders 2016; Koppel et al. 2019; Strivens et al. 2019). While a general correlation between metal bioavailability and DGT-measured metal concentrations could be demonstrated, generalizations are difficult to make. Here, more research and experiments are required, especially at deep-sea conditions.

Overall, clear dose-response links are still to be established, before DGTs can be used as monitoring tool for DSM activities.

Besides monitoring of bioavailable fractions for transmembrane transport, **indicator variables assessing the risk from (nano)particle ingestion** will need to be defined. These are so far much less developed and a starting point could be the **total suspended particle concentration**, but considerably more research into this is necessary.

3.5 Challenges

The major environmental pressures during deep-sea mining will arise from substrate removal and the dispersal and subsequent deposition of material plumes, and metal toxicity-induced adverse biological effects are one of the concerns when discussing the consequences of these activities to the ecosystem (**Figure 3.5**). **Cumulative risks will arise from the presence of multiple stressors and the potential integration of metal toxicity with other impact mechanisms such as suffocation, clogging of filter and respiratory organs, mechanical damage, particle toxicity, reduced food intake, and biomagnification in the food web. Biological effects could result from either one or several of these impacts, highlighting the need of integrated risk and impact assessments** (see also **PART III**). Indirectly, biota may further be affected by changes in substrate characteristics and changed biogeochemical functions, food/energy availability, and disruption of food webs.

When in the presence of multiple chemical and non-chemical stressors more than one stressor induces a biological response, the joint effect may be additive (summation without interaction of stressors), synergistic (one stressor increases the response to another stressor) or antagonistic (decreased response). Risks and effects from the exposure to (mixtures of) metals in deep-sea mining settings will be difficult to assess in isolation from other stressors. In the context of environmental impacts from DSM, the classic divide between typical ecotoxicological approaches that study harmful effects of exposure to chemical (or physical) agents on ecosystems based on standardized laboratory tests with single species (representative of a trophic level) under controlled conditions, and ecological methods studying effects from exposure to (multiple) non-toxic stressors on communities in real ecosystems to identify links is rendered obsolete and holistic studies with input from different scientific disciplines should be conducted (see also Schäfer et al. 2023).

The overall impact of plume or plume fallout to exposure biota is determined by a range of abiotic and biotic factors (**Figure 3.6**). Integrated effects from plume or plume fallout exposure can be best studied in field surveys of test mining activities or larger-scale disturbance experiments, which however is highly cost-intensive. Direct testing of effects from bulk plume or plume fallout exposure by means of laboratory or mesocosm experiments and observing biological responses at sub-organismal, whole-organismal, population, or community level could assess a so-called bulk plume or plume fallout 'toxicity', referring to the overall risk and considering any effect without knowledge of the exact impact mechanism. However, studying joint effects from exposure in mining settings appropriately by means of laboratory or mesocosm experiments is complicated by the fact that stressors act in different spatiotemporal realms. This means that the interrelation of stressors will vary in space and time and an extrapolation of observations of biological responses along (bulk) stressor gradients derived from simple dilution will bear some uncertainty. Furthermore, the confounding related to the co-occurrence of stressors complicates the derivation of regulatory thresholds for individual stressors based on effects (see **PART III**).

The assessment of (toxic) risk and the definition of suitable monitoring strategies needs suitable indicator variables. For the risk from plume exposure, field studies and bulk toxicity tests should be used to establish relationships between total particle concentrations, total metal concentration, (DGT) labile dissolved metal concentrations, and biological responses for a number of locally-relevant biological proxy organisms (representing different exposure routes and feeding strategies in the pelagic and benthic realm) and relevant life-cycle stages. Results can be used to determine sentinel species (in the absence of knowledge on key species) and to derive sensitive and suitable indicators of joint risk. For the risk from exposure to plume fallout deposits, relationships should be studied between deposition thickness, total metal content, pore water metal concentrations, grain size, organic matter, dissolved nutrients and biological responses in mega-, macro- and meiofaunal communities to derive suitable indicators for pressures, exposure and effects.

Figure 3.5: Sources of enhanced risk, related stressors, potential impacts, biological effects, and ecosystem consequences that can be expected during deep-sea mining. Metal toxicity is one of the potential impacts and can be interrelated with other impacts.

Figure 3.6: Schematic overview of bulk plume toxicity.

3.6 References

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PART III

Legal Background

III

Regulatory frameworks for the protection of the marine environment and the environmental management of offshore activities relevant as underpinning for DSM threshold development

Katja Schmidt and Matthias Haeckel

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1. Introduction

As any other human offshore activity, deep-sea mining (DSM) will cause environmental impacts on the ecosystem, and measures to assess the risks and actual effects will be required as part of the environmental management of these activities. These measures will need to be addressed during different stages of project development (e.g., risk assessment, permission process, compliance monitoring) and the regulations for deep sea mineral exploitation in the Area, currently drafted by the International Seabed Authority (ISA), provide the framework for implementation.

The development of assessment criteria in a regulatory context is a complex process and relies on measurable indicators that are suitable to assess environmental pressures and/or the ecological state. Developed thresholds represent operationally defined boundaries between environmental conditions and are used to assess risks and effects against management objectives of the regulatory framework, ensure compliance, and guide management actions. As management tools, they hence have value in terms of targets and are not simply based on scientific evidence from the environment.

Recently, the Council of the International Seabed Authority (ISA) made a decision relating to the development of binding environmental threshold values as standards accompanying the mining code (ISBA/27/C/42), stating that "...binding environmental threshold values... will be developed to contribute ...of what is required to ensure effective protection of the marine environment ...and to *set measurable requirements with regard to levels of harm* from activities in the Area". The three main pressures to be addressed first are namely toxicity, turbidity and settling of resuspended sediments, and underwater noise and light pollution. The process on developing the binding standards is led by the Legal and Technical Commission (LTC). In the most recent draft regulations on exploitation of Mineral resources in the Area (ISBA/30/C/CRP.1), Regulation 45 specifies that environmental standards for environmental studies, environmental quality objectives and for indicators (with associated quantitative threshold values) are needed and shall be adopted, the latter including, *inter alia*, toxicity, turbidity and settling of resuspended sediments, biodiversity status and ecosystem structures, functions and services.

The environmental pressures of DSM are manifold and risks for pelagic and benthic fauna arise in a complex and dynamic setting with seabed destruction, release of material plumes into the water column and particle settling at the seafloor. Habitat removal, enhanced suspended particle concentrations, enhanced sedimentation, and enhanced metal concentrations are among the major stressors for the environment. The integration of impacts, such as metal toxicity, particle-induced impacts (e.g., clogging of filter organs, reduced food intake, mechanical damage and related particle toxicity, burial), and biomagnification in the food web needs to be considered, in particular when developing appropriate threshold levels for metal contaminants. Metals further occur in complex mixtures and in different physical and chemical states that render their availability along different bio-uptake pathways.

Ideally, the derivation of suitable assessment criteria is based on *site-specific* environmental information and good understanding of ecosystem functions, connectivity, community and food web structures, ensuring appropriate thresholds that provide high confidence in ecosystem protection. If these data are not available, precautionary approaches to derive thresholds without direct ecological evidence will need to be followed.

This chapter provides information on thresholds as part of existing international and national regulatory frameworks for the protection of marine environments, and how thresholds are derived and operationalized in the **environmental management** of offshore activities such as oil and gas, dredging, and submarine mine tailings disposal. This information can be used as basis for the development of thresholds for DSM activities. Besides absolute numbers (often restricted to a few stressors and generic), many frameworks provide detailed

guidance on approaches and concepts how to derive and implement site-specific values and assess risks and effects. The terminology differs between regulatory bodies, which often relates to differences in function and in methodology for derivation. The focus of this chapter is on thresholds for pressure indicators, as most information is available for this type of indicator. Pressure indicators are also typically used for the assessment of risks during offshore activities, while effects on habitats and ecosystems are usually assessed with state indicators. The chapter addresses the **challenges to derive meaningful criteria for DSM** based on current knowledge and existing information and discusses the **potential applicability of certain management thresholds and assessment approaches** provided in the regulatory frameworks or operational in offshore industries. The **appendix** to this report provides a **detailed bibliography** on a) environmental impacts of DSM and other offshore industries including ecotoxicity exposure assessments, b) regulatory frameworks for water and sediment quality and associated guidelines for threshold derivation, environmental management, and monitoring, and c) available baseline data sources for trace metal concentrations in Pacific seawater and sediment. **Appendix 2** provides a compilation of **marine metal contaminant threshold values** from various regulatory sources (such as the Water Framework Directive or the Australian and New Zealand Water Quality Guidelines) for water, sediment, and biota, and in addition lists **operational threshold and guideline values used in the environmental management of offshore industries**.

2. Thresholds: Definition of terms

A regulatory threshold (hereafter simply named 'threshold'), as used in this report, is a quantitative assessment criterion in regulatory frameworks, used as contextual reference point to assess environmental conditions against environmental management goals and objectives and to direct management actions. Regulatory frameworks providing thresholds for indicators of pressure or state use specific terms, such as environmental quality standards (EQS), environmental assessment criteria (EAC), guideline values (GV), threshold values (TV), quality criteria (QC), quality guidelines (QG), Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNECs), or benchmarks, which may or may not be legally binding and have different functions. To establish thresholds as management tools, metrics of environmental condition change must be set in an appropriate framework, consider environmental objectives as well as social and ethical values, and meet legal requirements. Regulatory thresholds are not to be confounded with ecological thresholds, which are defined to represent tipping points, at which small environmental changes cause abrupt changes in ecosystem quality. When provided as a standard, thresholds are legally enforceable.

3. The role of thresholds in environmental management

Thresholds form an integral part of regulatory environmental management frameworks, used to **assess environmental risks, effects, or state** in the regulatory context, **guide management decisions, trigger management actions** to ensure ecosystem protection according to environmental management goals and objectives, and **ensure compliance**. With scientific evidence being transferred into a policy instrument, thresholds have value and provide a judgement of what is acceptable in terms of impacts and harm to the ecosystem. Thresholds are provided in governmental regulations of marine water and sediment quality and play an important role in the regulation of industrial offshore projects and activities, as part of environmental risk assessments and management and monitoring plans.

Regulatory thresholds can be set for measurable indicators of environmental pressures (**'pressure indicators'**, such as contaminants and other physical and chemical stressors) or ecosystem state (**'state indicators'**, at different levels of biological and ecological organization, e.g., for sub-lethal stress, biodiversity, ecosystem functions). The development of thresholds in major regulatory frameworks is an ongoing process, such as in the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (EU-MSFD), the EU Water Framework Directive (EU-WFD), or the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality (ANZG). Thresholds for pressure indicators are most common, and typically operational in the regulation of human activities, such as oil and gas, or dredging and dredging disposal. In contrast, indicators of biological or ecological state often still lack an agreed upon threshold (e.g., ANZG 2023a; Vasilakopoulos et al. 2022), and methodologies to derive them are continuously developed and implemented (European Commission 2024).

Environmental management goals and objectives are qualitative descriptions at overarching levels, such as "achieve or maintain good environmental state to ensure sustaining overall ecological integrity" (MSFD), "avoid significant adverse impacts" (FAO), "prevent and eliminate pollution and protect the marine environment from the adverse effects of human activities, while promoting the sustainable use of its goods and services" (OSPAR), or "biological communities remain in a healthy condition and ecosystem integrity is largely retained" (ANZG). Terms like "good environmental state" or "significant adverse impact" are **value judgements**, and, in the regulatory context, need to be populated by scientific data addressing the quality, spatial and/or temporal extent of effects. Operationalizing the goals and objectives hence necessitates appropriate indicators for assessing the state of an ecosystem, and/or the anthropogenically derived pressure(s) affecting it, accompanied by thresholds marking the boundary between 'acceptable' and 'non-acceptable' conditions for that indicator, in terms of quality to be sustained/achieved, and, in some cases, in terms of maximum spatial extent of acceptable loss or adverse effects (see threshold for MSFD criteria D6C5, and proposed threshold for OSPAR BH3 indicator). Thresholds can also be combined with temporal information such as for the MSFD criteria underwater noise pollution (European Commission 2024). In risk and impact assessments and in environmental management plans of human offshore activities, thresholds are used to operationalize project-specific objectives such as: "no harmful biological effects outside a mixing zone", or "predicted impacts on benthic organisms are sub-lethal, and/or the impacts are recoverable within a period of 5 years following completion of the dredging activities" (EPA-WA 2021). "Avoid serious harm in terms of extent, duration, and magnitude of adverse effects" is a proposed objective for DSM activities (Levin et al., 2016, Leduc et al., 2024). If the goal is to protect ecosystem integrity, objectives should reflect the need to preserve ecosystem structure, biodiversity, functions, connectivity, resilience and ability to provide ecosystem services (Tunnicliffe et al. 2020). Ensuring that ecosystem integrity is preserved can involve accepting some level of disturbance in terms of biodiversity or functions (Hiddink et al. 2023).

Management actions aim to prevent or mitigate adverse environmental effects or to look more specifically whether adverse effects actually occur when a threshold is breached. Therefore, threshold values should be

set in relation to a reference condition, and may include an 'acceptable deviation' from this reference condition. This allows for sustainable uses of the marine environment whereby some level of pressures and their impacts can be accommodated, provided the overall quality of the environment is maintained (European Commission 2017).

Metal contaminant concentrations can be used as sole decision criteria or as one line of evidence (LoE) in **tiered approaches to assess site-specific risks and effects** or ensure compliance, together with other LoE such as bioavailability, toxicity testing, and field biological and ecological assessments. Metal contaminant thresholds represent a measurable concentration below which there is considered to be a low risk for unacceptable effects (in the regulatory context) occurring to an aquatic ecosystem (ANZG 2018b). Especially when only generic, non-locally relevant thresholds are provided, these would form a low tier, and, if the environmental conditions assessed against this threshold indicate high risk, additional data should be obtained and a more detailed assessment is made at the next tier. Furthermore, several regulations provide guidance on how to derive locally-relevant thresholds, either by tailoring generic thresholds or by obtaining data to derive new thresholds. Some regulations for offshore industries provide tailored, activity-related thresholds for environmental management purposes (OSPAR Commission 2014; EPA-WA 2021).

Details on state and pressure indicators and related thresholds that are currently in use can be assessed from the individual regulatory framework websites or guidance material: e.g., HELCOM (<https://indicators.helcom.fi/>), OSPAR (<https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/ospar-common-indicators>), MSFD (Vasilakopoulos et al. 2022; European Commission 2024), WFD (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/surface-water_en; (The European Parliament and the Council 2013, 2008), and Australian & New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh & Marine Water Quality (<https://www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines/resources/key-concepts/indicators>). Thresholds are often provided together with detailed guidance how to assess, manage and monitor the water and sediment quality of aquatic systems or the state of an ecosystem in relation to environmental objectives.

Thresholds generally serve as **boundaries between acceptable** ("good") conditions **and non-acceptable** ("bad") **conditions** of an indicator. In the regulation of human offshore activities, they are often **set in a spatial and/or temporal context** delineating zones/periods of acceptable adverse impact or distinguishing between different categories of impacts or harm. For example, regulatory frameworks allow for designated "**mixing zones**" near effluent point sources, where pollutant concentrations can exceed environmental quality criteria as long as these are met outside the mixing zone. For instance, the EU Directive 2008/105/EC permits member states to establish these zones to manage short-term, localized exceedances. In Australia and New Zealand, mixing zones are regulated at regional levels, allowing for controlled discharges that are deemed manageable within defined spatial boundaries (ANZG 2018h). The mixing zone concept is commonly used in legislation for offshore oil and gas production (OSPAR Commission 2012c), and applied in project-specific environmental risk and impact assessments of offshore activities (Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008; Woodlark Mining Limited 2013; Esso Highlands Limited 2010). Guidelines for dredging proposal environmental impact assessments, published by the Western Australia Environmental Protection Agency (EPA-WA), distinguish **different impact categories** for key species based on strengths of adverse effects and ability of recovery (ZOHI – zone of high impact, ZOMI – zone of moderate impact, ZOI – zone of influence) and provide thresholds derived from biological effects data as boundaries between the individual zones. Thresholds can further be used to **trigger different levels of actions**, with lower and higher threshold values allowing for nuanced regulatory responses. Trigger values can be set as early warning signals that indicate the need for closer monitoring or immediate action to prevent higher threshold values from being exceeded. They serve as a proactive measure to mitigate potential environmental impacts before they become critical. Such a tiered assessment is for example recommended in guidelines for dredging proposals in Western Australia (EPA-WA 2021), with tiered management triggers at the boundary between the zones of Influence and Moderate Impact

for corals, to provide early warning of conditions approaching the management target for that boundary. To assess the suitability for disposal of dredging material in the EU, thresholds for contaminants in sediment and, in some countries, in the water column are provided as action levels (typically two) for a tiered assessment. Concentrations below the first action level allow disposal of the dredged material, while concentrations between the lower and the higher action level trigger further investigation of the material proposed for dumping, which may involve additional chemical evaluation or ecotoxicity tests (OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024). Staged thresholds can also be presented in **traffic light schemes** for environmental management, where a visual structure - commonly green-yellow-red - is used to assess the extent/strength of risk or harmful effects and distinguish between 'acceptable', 'cautionary' and 'non-acceptable' environmental conditions. Between the green/yellow and the yellow/red transitions, further management action is required to mitigate effects and improve conditions. For the environmental management of DSM, Leduc et al. (2024) proposed operationalized definitions of **detectable, significant, and serious harm** in such a traffic light scheme. **Populating the different categories in such traffic-light schemes in terms of effects and setting appropriate thresholds with high confidence in validity and predictive ability, however, requires scientific data on site-specific-environmental states and ecosystem responses (such as biological, biogeochemical, functional) and should involve both state and pressure indicators.**

Examples for thresholds combining a quantity with a temporal component are given in the EPA-WA guideline for environmental impact assessments of marine dredging proposals (EPA-WA 2021). Here, exposure levels such as SPM concentrations are coupled with a specific period of running activity (with a lower threshold value for a longer period of dredging), and thresholds of maximum depth of burial is coupled with at a maximum period of burial, defining the boundaries for the zone of moderate impact (ZOMI) for key species. Thresholds can also be combined, to address effects from more than one pressure, such as effects of suspended sediment concentration (SSC) and sediment deposition as a single deposition event or as pulsed deposition event on corals (EPA-WA 2021). To ensure compliance, none of the thresholds must be triggered.

The permissible spatial or temporal extent of mixing zones or impact categories in the environmental management of offshore activities is often a case-by-case decision of the permitting authorities, and is often based on specifications by the project proponent in the context of risk assessments and EIAs. The OSPAR guideline on a Risk-Based Approach to the Management of Produced Water Discharges from Offshore Installations (OSPAR Commission 2012b) provides a descriptive formulation of acceptable spatial extent and states that "risk should be considered to be adequately controlled if the exposure level (PEC, predicted environmental concentration) does not exceed the PNEC outside a column of water surrounding the installation, the radius of which is defined by a distance from the installation specified by the individual OSPAR member state, or outside the volume of water directly impacted by the discharge that is specified by the individual OSPAR member state. The Dutch implementation considers the risk to be adequately controlled if the PEC at 500 m from the discharge point is not exceeding the PNEC (predicted no-effect concentration). Case-by-case permits of Norwegian dredging proposals by the responsible authority include a temporal aspect such as: "If the turbidity exceeds 10 NTU above the reference level in more than 20 minutes, work must be stopped until the turbidity has fallen below the limit value". In addition, the OSPAR common indicator BH3 'Extent of Physical Damage to Predominant and Special Habitats' introduces a threshold for the spatial extent of damage to a habitat: "The threshold is achieved, when at least x% of the area of a broad habitat type is permanently without anthropogenic physical disturbance (BH3 disturbance category 0) AND the area which is highly disturbed (BH3 disturbance categories 5-9) is less than y% of the total habitat area".

Regulatory thresholds are usually based on scientific evidence, and either set in relation to **biological or ecological effects data** or by applying a **background data or reference site approach**. Related documents

(see overview in Appendix) provide background information on the development of thresholds and often include detailed guidance on approaches how to derive (site-specific) thresholds, especially for pressure indicators (CIS-WFD 2018; Warne et al. 2018). Thresholds operational in risk assessments and permission processes as well as compliance monitoring of industrial offshore activities are usually set for pressure indicators. See **CHAPTER 5** for details on threshold derivation for pressure indicators relevant for DSM, such as metal contaminants in water and sediment and suspended particulate matter, and guidance documents how to tailor generic thresholds or develop site-specific thresholds.

Hiddink et al. (2023) provide a review of approaches that have been used for setting environmental management thresholds for good ecosystem state in regulatory frameworks, including the concepts of 'natural variation', 'detectable change', 'tipping point', the level of change in state that is deemed acceptable using each method, and the strengths and weaknesses of these approaches. While their review focuses on approaches for state indicators, it also provides information on the derivation of pressure indicators. A tipping point approach seems appealing to set thresholds in the context of environmental management of human offshore activities, but biological or ecological responses are often gradual, characterized by progressively increasing magnitude and variance when pressure increases, and true tipping points are rarely statistically detectable, especially for physical disturbance (Hillebrand et al. 2020; Fu et al. 2019). For Hiddink et al. (2023), the most objective method for setting a good-state threshold is based on maintaining the state within the range of natural variation in undisturbed systems.

Thresholds for state indicators may also be derived from a combination of the magnitude of pressure and the sensitivity of the habitat, such as for the complex HELCOM indicator 'Cumulative impact from physical pressures on benthic biotopes' (HELCOM 2023): Different categories of impact are defined, and the threshold between good status achieved and good status failed is set between the low and moderate impact (disturbance) category, above which impacts are interpreted as leading to adverse effects.

Effect-based water quality thresholds for toxicants are often derived from a statistical data evaluation of species sensitivity distributions (SSD) that uses the cumulative distribution of toxicity values for multiple species from different taxonomic groups (e.g., Warne et al. 2018; CIS-WFD 2018). If insufficient toxicity data are available, thresholds can instead be derived from the Assessment Factor (AF) method addressing the uncertainty of limited effects data. Regulatory frameworks often contain more than one threshold for metal contaminants in water, differentiating, for example, between annual average and maximum allowed concentrations based on acute and chronic toxicity data (EU), directly between acute and chronic toxicity (U.S. EPA, basically the same as in the EU), or between five different water and sediment quality classes in Norway. The current Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality (ANZG 2018b) specify three different levels of ecosystem conditions as management targets, for which different thresholds (expressed as percentage level of species protection) are recommended. In the absence of effects-based thresholds, the baseline/reference site approach uses the natural variability of the indicator and derives a threshold based on a high percentile of the background dataset to derive locally-relevant, site-specific values.

Expected **stressors** from DSM activities acting in the water column and at the seafloor (may lead to integrated impacts, list is not exhaustive):

- Elevated concentration of suspended particles in the water
- Elevated concentration of potentially toxic metals in the water
- Elevated sedimentation at the seafloor
- Elevated concentration of potentially toxic metals in resettled material
- Change of substrate
- Habitat removal

- Oxygen and Nutrition depletion

Suitable **indicators** may include:

Chemical indicators (pressure)

- Dissolved metal conc. < 0.2 µm in water
- Total metal concentrations in water
- Particulate metal concentration
- Labile (bioavailable) metal concentration (DGT-labile)
- Oxygen consumption, organic matter degradation rates
- Organic matter quality and amount

Physical indicators (pressure)

- Suspended particulate matter (SPM)
- Turbidity
- Thickness or rate of deposition

Biochemical and biological indicators (state)

- Bio-accumulated metal concentrations
- Biomarkers (of exposure or effects)
- Respiration or metabolic rates
- Lethality/Mortality

Ecological indicators (state)

- Community abundance and biomass
- Community composition
- Species richness
- Species abundance
- Extent of Physical Disturbance to Benthic Habitats
- Extent of habitat loss

4. International and national regulatory frameworks for the protection of the marine environment

Previously deemed as necessary, the recent ISA decision now urges the development of legally-binding, pressure-related environmental thresholds in a timely manner. In the light of the current lack of sufficient locally-relevant effects data and a fragmented ecosystem understanding, at best, this is a highly challenging task. The development and implementation of environmental thresholds as management tools for DSM in the international seabed (the Area) can be informed by existing legal and other authoritative frameworks for the protection and management of the marine environment. Thresholds form an integral part in many of the existing environmental frameworks, and typically include some indicators of pressures that will also occur during DSM and pose risks to the marine environment. For example, several frameworks provide thresholds for concentrations of metals (in water, sediment, and/or biota matrices) that are of concern due to potential mobilization in mining plumes and resettled material caused by DSM. From this a couple of **questions** arise, such as: **Could such existing thresholds for metal contaminants be directly applicable in the regulation of DSM activities?** If not – why not? What additional information relevant for the development of thresholds for DSM can be extracted from existing frameworks?

To explore these questions in depth, we screened different frameworks for marine environmental protection and collated available **pressure-related threshold values for water and sediment quality**, information on how these thresholds were derived, (i.e., the data basis and technical aspects), for technical advice and guidance on suitable **approaches for threshold development**, and on proposed **concepts for risk and effects assessments**. When assessing the potential applicability of existing thresholds as protective measures in the context of future DSM activities in abyssal settings, we need to consider the fundamental differences in ecosystem conditions, community structures and functions, as well as pressure and temperature regimes. Many regulations provide thresholds for shallow-water organisms that are usually generic. Besides being a source of threshold numbers, the greater value of some of the existing thresholds lies in advice on concepts to assess environmental states and quality including the application of thresholds for pressure indicators as part of a tiered assessment of risks and effects, on approaches to develop locally-relevant thresholds or modify existing ones, and how to tackle threshold development in the absence of data.

A range of legal instruments, including binding **international treaties**, such as the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), the London Convention/London Protocol (LC/LP), Regional Sea Conventions, such as the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR), and the United Nations Agreement on Marine Biodiversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ Agreement) governed by international law, **EU directives**, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) or the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), **national regulations, such as the Norwegian water regulations that implement the directives**, and non-binding **guidelines and recommendations, such as** the Australia and New Zealand water quality guidelines, the Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines, or the U.S. EPA recommendation for Water quality Criteria, address aspects relevant for the development of assessment criteria for DSM. In the following we provide a short overview on those frameworks that we used for screening. In **Appendix 1**, Table A8 summarizes the key aspects for each framework, including general aspects on provided thresholds for metals. **Further reading material** include guidance documents on technical aspects of threshold development and implementation, sampling and monitoring as advice for stakeholders and is listed in Table A9. The derived **numerical threshold values for metal contaminants**, extracted for the different matrices, are listed in **Appendix 2** and the attached Excel Table. Tornero et al. (2022) published a background document with compiled available threshold values (TV) for marine chemical

contaminants at EU, regional and beyond EU level in different compartments (water, sediment, biota) that provides a very good overview and is recommended here.

Relevant information extracted from the different frameworks, such as suitable approaches and methodologies for threshold development, are provided in **CHAPTER 5**.

4.1 Water Framework Directive (WFD)

Established as a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, the WFD, adopted in 2000, is setting out rules to halt deterioration in the status of EU water bodies and achieve a good status for Europe's rivers, lakes and groundwater (Water Framework Directive 2000). Good status means, both, good chemical and good ecological status. In coastal areas, the WFD is in force up to one nautical mile from the territorial baseline of a Member State for a Good Ecological Status and up to 12 nautical miles for a Good Chemical Status. It ensures an integrated approach to water management, respecting the integrity of whole ecosystems, including by regulating individual pollutants and setting corresponding regulatory standards. The European Commission and the Member States established a Common Implementation Strategy (CIS) for the Water Framework Directive, to assist in the practical implementation of the Directive with the help of thematic and guidance documents and other supporting technical and scientific documents. More information can be found here: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en.

Metal thresholds: The WFD includes in its Annex X the list of priority substances that Member States must monitor in surface waters, but the standards for them are set in the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (EQSD) and must be met to achieve a good surface water chemical status. The WFD also requires Member States to set and meet Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for substances of national concern, i.e. river basin specific pollutants; the monitoring of which currently contributes to the assessment of the ecological status. The WFD provides thresholds as Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for metal contaminants in different matrices, for the Priority Substances (PS) Cd, Pb (water and sediment), Ni (only in water), and Hg (only in biota).

Guidance: Guidance documents are available on technical aspects, such as for deriving environmental quality standards, or on surface water chemical monitoring. Details on selected guidance documents are provided in Table A9 of the Appendix, and a full list of guidance documents can be found here: [wfd - Bibliothek \(europa.eu\)](#).

4.2 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), adopted in 2008, is a complete assessment framework with comprehensive criteria linked to policy objectives, and is the first EU legislative instrument related to the protection of marine biodiversity. The MSFD aims to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of the EU's marine waters and to protect the resource base upon which marine-related economic and social activities depend. The definition of GES is based on eleven generic descriptors, each of them assessed by several GES Criteria. Descriptor 1 (benthic habitats) and Descriptor 6 (seafloor integrity) are the main descriptors for assessing the state of the seabed, while other descriptors address particular pressures and impacts on the seabed (e.g., D2 – non-indigenous species, D5 – eutrophication, D8 - Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects). The European Commission has also produced a set of detailed criteria and methodological standards to help Member States implement the MSFD. The Directive lists four European marine regions – the Baltic Sea, the North-east Atlantic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. These are located mainly within the geographical boundaries of the existing Regional Sea Convention's

cooperation between the Member States (MS) of one marine region with its neighboring countries that share the same marine waters. At the core of the GES assessment lies the need for threshold values (TVs) that enable a quantitative assessment of environmental status for the indicators and elements used for each GES Criterion. More information can be found here: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/marine-environment/implementation-marine-strategy-framework-directive_en.

Metal thresholds: According to the revised MSFD Commission Decision (European Commission 2017), MS have to consider the Priority Substances (PS) and River Basin Specific Pollutants (RBSP) already identified under the WFD (Water Framework Directive 2000), and establish, through regional or subregional cooperation, a list of additional contaminants that may give rise to pollution effects. For the contaminants already identified under the WFD, the threshold values should be the values set in accordance with that Directive. For contaminants measured in a matrix for which no value is set under the WFD, as well as for additional contaminants, the threshold values for a specified matrix should be established through regional or subregional cooperation. MS are to establish national EQS according to the procedure described in the WFD guidance document no. 27 (CIS-WFD 2018). As alternative to water EQS, MS can also set sediment or biota EQS, as long as they provide at least the same level of protection. Besides the threshold values and assessment criteria agreed at EU or regional level, MS have also indicated some national standards used for the assessment of some contaminants. Tornero et al. (2019) summarize the substances, matrices and threshold values that Member States intend to use for the assessment of the Descriptor 8 (Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects), highlighting the high variability between used thresholds, the prioritized matrix (water, sediment, or biota), and the need for harmonization.

Guidance: The EU and its Member States have jointly developed a common strategy for supporting the implementation of the MSFD. The focus of the strategy is on methodological questions relating to a common understanding of the technical and scientific implications of the MSFD. In particular, one of the objectives of the strategy is the development of non-legally binding and technical guidance in form of technical reports, on various technical issues under the Directive. Available supporting material include guidance documents, status reports and workshop reports on indicator and threshold development for the different MSFD descriptors and environmental monitoring. The most important documents relevant for DSM are listed in Table A9.

4.3 Regional Sea Conventions: Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR)

OSPAR is the Regional Sea Convention responsible for protecting and conserving the North-East Atlantic and its resources and entered into force in 1998. It manages human activities impacting the marine environment and provides regular assessments of the state of the North-East Atlantic with a view to securing its vision of a clean, healthy and biologically diverse sea which is productive, used sustainably and resilient to climate change and ocean acidification. The Convention aims to protect the North-East Atlantic maritime area against the adverse effects of human activities in order to safeguard human health and to conserve marine ecosystems and, when practicable, restore marine areas, which have been adversely affected. It has 16 Contracting Parties: Belgium, Denmark, the EU, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, Luxembourg and Switzerland. The Convention was open for signature at the Ministerial Meeting of the Oslo and Paris Commissions in Paris on 22 September 1992 and entered into force on 25 March 1998. Details are provided here: [Convention | OSPAR Commission](#). OSPAR develops common indicators from which it is possible to infer how much the current situation deviates from

good environmental status (<https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/ospar-common-indicators>).

Metal thresholds: OSPAR provides a list of the naturally occurring substances usually being analyzed to characterize produced water samples along with their established PNECs (OSPAR Commission 2014). The metals of concern are: arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, mercury, lead, nickel and zinc, iron and barium. The method of EQS and PNECs derivation is described in the Appendix of the document. A prerequisite was that the selected PNECs should preferably be based on existing EQS values or PNECs established under the EU-WFD or through European Union risk assessment reports (EU-RAR). The AA-EQS-values for other surface waters are selected as PNECs, over RAR studies and other sources. For metals in sediments, OSPAR uses background-based (BAC) and Effects Range Low (ERL) values for the assessment of contaminants and temporal trends in the environmental status.

Guidance: Reading material is available for different technical aspects and a selection is listed in Table A9. It includes, *inter alia*, background information on PNEC derivation and guidance on monitoring of contaminants in different matrices. Guidelines related to offshore activities involve a Recommendation for a Risk-Based Approach to the Management of Produced Water Discharges from Offshore Installations, Guidelines for the management of dredged material at sea, and Guidelines for monitoring of environmental impacts of industrial offshore activities.

4.4 Regional Sea Conventions: Helsinki Commission (HELCOM)

The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission – also known as the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) – is an intergovernmental organisation (IGO) and a regional sea convention in the Baltic Sea area. As regional platform for environmental policy making, HELCOM was established in 1974 to protect the marine environment of the Baltic Sea from all sources of pollution, and to restore and safeguard its ecological balance.

Metal thresholds: HELCOM core indicators for biodiversity and hazardous substances were developed. Further information is provided here: <https://indicators.helcom.fi/>. Regionally agreed threshold values are derived from a number of sources (such as WFD) to select values that have been scientifically tested and developed with the purpose of assessing environmental status. If several threshold values are available, thresholds based on EQS and the sampling matrix biota are preferred.

Guidance: Reading material is available in form of core indicator status reports for metals in different matrices, and Guidelines for Management of Dredged Material at Sea.

4.5 Norway

The Regulations on the Framework for Water Management (the Water Regulations) implement the EU WFD (the Water Directive) in Norwegian law. The main purpose of the regulation is to provide a framework for setting environmental objectives that ensure the most comprehensive possible protection of the aquatic environment, and sustainable use of water bodies. The protection of ecosystems in coastal waters is addressed by a classification scheme for metals and organic contaminants in seawater, sediment, biota, ranging from “Background” to “Very Bad” in five classes.

Metal thresholds: There is a provision in the WFD which allows a country to develop their own EQS for water, sediment and biota provided that these offer the same level of protection as the EQS set for water. Norway used this approach and developed their own EQS for biota, water and sediments for “river basin specific

pollutants” not otherwise accounted for by the EU directives (NEA 2016, rev. 2020). For the elements Pb, Cd, Ni, the water EQS corresponds to the AA-EQS of the WFD for PS. The EQS represents the upper boundary of the environmental status class “Good”. More limits are defined as boundaries of the other quality classes.

Guidance: Table A9 lists guidance material on details on the classification scheme and methodology for the derivation of class limits. In addition, guidelines for the risk assessment and monitoring of industrial offshore activities were published.

4.6 United States: U.S. EPA recommendation for Water Quality Criteria (WQC)

Under the Clean Water Act section 304(a), U.S. EPA is required to develop and publish water quality criteria that reflect the latest scientific knowledge. National water quality criteria are derived for freshwater or saltwater or both to protect aquatic organisms and their uses from unacceptable effects.

Metal thresholds: National recommended water quality criteria lists a range of metals. Furthermore, US-EPA sediment guidelines are used by public agencies in the US for screening sediments in particular for trace metals and organic contaminants but they are not regulatory criteria. These criteria are based on a large database of Effects Range-Low (ERL) values assembled by Long et al. (1995) for saltwater.

Guidance: Guidance documents (see Table A9) are available for recommended procedures for deriving site-specific water quality criteria, sediment benchmarks, and a framework for risk assessment in aquatic ecosystems. Furthermore, US-EPA provides guidelines how to develop water quality criteria for suspended and bedded sediments in aquatic systems.

4.7 Canada: Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines (CEQG)

Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines (CEQGs), developed by the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME), are nationally endorsed, science-based goals for the quality of atmospheric, aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Marine thresholds have been developed to address the protection of marine water quality, marine sediment quality and tissue quality for the protection of wildlife consumers of aquatic life.

Metal thresholds: Threshold levels are provided for water quality, sediment quality and tissue quality.

Guidance: A technical report provides scientific and technical guidance on the development of site-specific water quality objectives (WQOs).

4.8 Australia and New Zealand: Australia and New Zealand water quality guidelines (ANZG)

The Guidelines are part of the National Water Quality Management Strategy (NWQMS), whose primary objective is to achieve a sustainable use of the nation's water resources by protecting and enhancing their quality while maintaining economic and social development. The NWQMS is designed to improve water quality and reduce pollution through the provision of a range of guiding documents and tools. While the NWQMS is not mandatory nor legally binding in itself, it is used across all levels of government, and by industry and the general public. The Guidelines were developed for aquatic ecosystem protection and provide authoritative

guidance on the management of water quality in Australia and New Zealand (planning, approvals, licensing, compliance, monitoring and assessment). Since its revision in 2018, the Guidelines are available in form of an interactive platform <https://www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines>.

Metal thresholds: The guidelines provide metal Default Guideline Values (DGV) for water and sediment quality, additional water values for different levels of protection. The level of protection depends on the management objective for a water type. Drafts for updated DGVs have been published. The guidelines recommend to use guideline values together with measurements from other lines of evidence in a weight-of-evidence process to determine, if water or sediment quality represents a risk to a particular community value.

Guidance: Comprehensive guidance can be found on the interactive platform itself, on topics such as derivation of guideline values for metal contaminants and other physical and chemical stressors in water, sediment quality assessment, water quality monitoring, weight of evidence approaches for guideline derivation and for the assessment of water/sediment quality, and tiered assessment schemes. Specific guidance is provided for methods to tailor DGVs according to site-specific environmental conditions or to derive new, site-specific GVs, also in the absence of locally-relevant effects data. More information on relevant reading material is provided in Table A9.

4.9 London Convention/London Protocol

One of the first and most important global instruments available to protect the oceans from pollution by controlling sources of waste and developing preventive measures was the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Waste and Other Matter in 1972 (London Convention, LC; IMO 1972). In 1996, the London Convention was updated by the London Protocol, which entered into force in 2006 (LP; IMO 1996). LC/PP does not cover discharges from land-based sources, such as pipes and outfalls. Furthermore, Article III (c) of the London Convention expressly excludes the dumping of wastes arising from deep-sea mining from its scope. Similarly, LP does not apply to waste arising from deep-sea mining either. Instead, the Parties agreed to promote measures to protect the marine environment against pollution caused by inter alia 'wastes or other matter directly arising from, or related to the exploration, exploitation and associated offshore processing of sea-bed mineral resources' within 'the competent specialized agencies and other international bodies'. In other words the issue of wastes arising from deep-sea mining is to be regulated under the auspices of ISA.

EQS thresholds for Priority Substances of the WFD are not themselves legally binding. Member states must either implement them into their national regulations, or they need to develop their own EQS for water, sediment and biota provided that these offer the same level of protection as the EQS set for water. In the United States, the national recommended water quality criteria must be adopted as part of a state's water quality standards to protect the designated uses of their water bodies. These can include site-specific criteria that are different from recommended criteria, as long as the site-specific criteria are protective of the designated use. The ANZG DGVs are as well not mandatory and have no formal legal status. State, territory or local jurisdictions may incorporate the processes and tools, including the DGVs, provided within the Water Quality Guidelines, into their water quality protection policy and regulatory tools. The development of site-specific thresholds is highly recommended.

Recommended approaches used for setting thresholds may differ between regulatory frameworks. As an example, in Europe, the added risk approach (ARA) is used as an option to derive site-adapted EQSs for metals where natural background concentrations exceed the generic EQS. In contrast, in Australia, New Zealand, and

Canada, the preferred approach when natural background concentrations exceed generic thresholds is to derive site-specific thresholds based on a specific percentile of the natural background or reference condition data (van Dam et al., 2019). As other example, in Europe and Canada, field observational studies are noted to be too confounded to be useful in threshold derivations, although the derived data are viewed as important in evaluating and validating the final water quality criteria such as benchmarks. In contrast, in ANZG, field effects data are considered complementary or potentially even preferred over laboratory toxicity testing data for guideline value derivation (van Dam et al. 2019).

5. Threshold development for metals in water and sediment and concepts of quality assessment

This chapter summarizes available information on **approaches for deriving thresholds** for metals in water and in sediments. Substance dossiers and technical guidance documents accompanying legal frameworks for environmental protection (such as WFD, OSPAR, Norwegian Water Regulations, and ANZG), provide **background information on derived thresholds**, assessment methods and quality assurance, as well as detailed advice on **how to develop new thresholds** depending on available data. Many frameworks further provide guidance on **concepts for the implementation and application of thresholds** as instruments to classify environmental conditions, assess hazards or risks and direct management actions according to anticipated objectives. The information provided in this chapter will help to examine whether existing, generic thresholds might be suitable as early stage thresholds for DSM in risk assessment frameworks. The material can further be used to develop a strategy for threshold development and implementation in risk assessment and in management and monitoring frameworks in the context of the ISA draft exploitation regulations.

Worldwide, there is a wealth of guidelines on environmental thresholds and their derivation in the regulatory context (U.S. EPA 1985; rev. 2010; CCME 2007; ANZG 2018b; CIS-WFD 2018). The different approaches to derive thresholds and to account for site-specificity is discussed in **CHAPTERS 5.1** (metals in water), **5.2** (metals in sediment), and **5.3** (suspended particulate matter). Concepts of risk assessment and compliance monitoring are detailed in **CHAPTER 5.6**, and **CHAPTER 5.4** addresses the background concentration approach for threshold development. Further bibliographic reading on threshold development and quality assessment concepts within individual frameworks is provided in the Appendix, table A9.

Chemical assessment criteria for pressure indicators (such as metal concentrations) are usually not used as single evidence to assess a risk or ensure compliance, but form one Line of Evidence (LOE), integrated into an assessment framework using evidence from multiple sources (**CHAPTER 5.6.1**). While the specific LOE differ between legal frameworks, the general concept is the same, considering chemistry to address the pressure (total or bioavailable concentrations), and ecosystem receptors to address both, exposure and effects (toxicity, bioaccumulation, biomarkers, biodiversity at different levels of biological organization). Different LOEs can also be combined in a Weight-of-Evidence (WoE) assessment (**CHAPTER 5.6.2**), which is either at a high tier in a hierarchical decision framework, or a single assessment.

Table 5.1 lists the most commonly used terminology for thresholds used in different frameworks. Throughout this and the following chapter, we tried to refer to the framework-specific term when discussing a specific regulation, and use the term “threshold” or “quality criteria” for more general considerations.

Table 5.1: Terminology of assessment criteria in different regulatory frameworks.

Regulatory framework	Nomenclature
WFD	EQS, QS (Environmental Quality Status, Quality Status)
ECHA	PNEC (Predicted No Effects Concentration)
US EPA	WQC (Water Quality Criteria)
Canada CCME	WQG (Water Quality Guidelines)
Australia + NZ	DGV, GV (default guideline value, guideline value)

Details on how thresholds for individual metals in water and sediment were developed in different frameworks (including data sources, quality assessment) are provided in form of, *inter alia*, EQS dossiers (WFD), EU Risk Assessment Reports (RAR) and Voluntary RAR (VRAR) (ECHA), Australia and New Zealand DGV technical briefs and reports, proposed EQS for Water Framework Directive Annex VIII substances by UK TAG, a background document on Norwegian environmental quality standards (NEA 2014), and a background for Produced Water substances (OSPAR Commission 2014), and the Canadian water and sediment guidelines for the protection of aquatic life (CCME 2007). Threshold derivation typically involves a thorough quality assessment of toxicity data, including reliability and reality checks of derived thresholds (CIS-WFD 2011a; ANZG 2023c). This emphasizes the high effort required to develop management thresholds. Site-specificity of thresholds to address local conditions is mainly addressed in U.S., Canada and Australia (U.S. EPA 1985; rev. 2010; ANZG 2018a; CCME 2003; U.S. EPA 2013). In Europe, possibilities to account for local conditions and adapt thresholds accordingly is limited (CIS-WFD 2019).

5.1 Metals and metalloids: marine water

We here focus on the derivation and implementation of *effects-based thresholds* for metals in (salt)water. Another approach using background concentration datasets is described in **CHAPTER 5.4**. Appendix 2 and the associated Excel table lists available threshold values from major regulatory frameworks used in environmental management.

In the first part of this section, we detail the available assessment methodologies for threshold derivation based on biological effects:

- Species Sensitivity Distribution (SSD) – laboratory tests
- Assessment Factor (AF) – laboratory tests
- Field and mesocosm experiments/observations

The metals for which threshold values are adopted in legal frameworks include Cd, Ni, Pb (commonly derived), Cu, Zn, Hg (occasionally derived), and As, Co, Fe, Mn, Al, Cr, Ag (rarely derived), beside a few more for which only one or two frameworks provide a threshold value (e.g., Tl). van Dam et al. (2018) proposed WQG values for Al, Ga and Mo in marine environments and recently, Markich et al. (2024) proposed water quality guidelines for REE.

The legal frameworks usually provide generic thresholds valid on regional or national levels. To address local conditions, several approaches provide guidance how to tailor existing thresholds or derive new site-specific thresholds, which is discussed in the second part of this section. This step is usually conducted as part of the implementation and application of thresholds for status or compliance assessments.

There is currently no consistency between different legal frameworks regarding whether threshold values refer to total or dissolved concentrations. CCME, ANZG, OSPAR values refer to total concentration of a substance in an unfiltered sample, while threshold values provided in US and WFD and Norway refer to dissolved (<0.45 µm) concentrations.

5.1.1 THRESHOLD DERIVATION: ASSESSMENT FACTOR & SPECIES SENSITIVITY DISTRIBUTION

To convert toxicity data for metals in water into a regulatory threshold, such as a PNEC, GV, EQS, WQC, or else, two different extrapolation methods exist: the species sensitivity distribution method (SSD) and the

assessment factor (AF) method (ECHA 2008c; Warne et al. 2018; CIS-WFD 2018). Using one or the other depends on the availability and quality of toxicity data. Usually, data are based on laboratory toxicity tests, but field and semi-field data may be used complementarily. In rare, activity-specific cases, toxicity data are directly used as limitations in a regulatory context, such as results of whole effluent toxicity tests for offshore oil and gas management (U.S. EPA 2024).

5.1.1.1 Assessment Factor method (AF)

The assessment factor (AF) method has the lowest data requirements and is usually applied when limited toxicity data are available. The method assumes that the entire ecosystem can be protected by protecting the weakest link in the food chain. The deterministic approach takes the lowest toxicity value from a laboratory test and divides it by an appropriate AF (that usually ranges between 10 and 10000) to extrapolate to a regulatory threshold. The sparser the available data, the higher is the assessment factor that is applied. Results of long-term tests (expressed as EC_{10} or NOEC for a sub-lethal endpoint) are preferred over those of short-term tests (EC/LC_{50}), because such results give a more realistic picture on effects on the organisms during their entire life cycle. In the EU (CIS-WFD 2018), the minimum requirement to derive a marine PNEC encompasses at least one short-term $L(E)C_{50}$ from each of three taxonomic groups representing three trophic levels (fish, invertebrates, and algae), resulting in the application of an AF of 1000-10000 to the lowest value. A small AF of 10 can be applied when long-term results (e.g. EC_{10} or NOEC) from at least three freshwater or saltwater species (normally algae and/or crustaceans and/or fish) across three trophic levels + two long-term results from additional marine taxonomic groups (e.g. echinoderms, molluscs) are available. Less conservative AF are applied in the ANZG, which also accept less available data (Warne, 2001). Examples of regulatory thresholds for metals and metalloids obtained with the AF method include marine long-term EQS for As and Cr, developed by the UK Technical Advisory Group (UKTAG) supporting the implementation of the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) (UK TAG 2007a, 2007b), and the DGV for As in ANZG (ANZG 2000).

As it is always the lowest toxicity value (i.e., those from the most sensitive species) that is used to derive AF-based thresholds, these provide protection to all species for which there is toxicity data available. A specific level of protection (see **CHAPTER 5.1.2**), however, cannot be defined.

5.1.1.2 Species Sensitivity distribution (SSD)

Species sensitivity distributions (SSDs) are a key methodology for deriving effects-based numerical water (or sediment) quality criteria for toxic substances. The method is generally preferred over the AF method when the data requirements are met (CIS-WFD 2018; ANZG 2018i; ECHA 2008c), and aims at calculating a concentration, which is expected to protect a certain percentage of the species of an ecosystem against toxic effects. Typically, legal frameworks provide a threshold concentration below which at least 95% of species in a community would be protected (CIS-WFD 2018). An SSD reflects the observation that interspecies differences in sensitivity to a chemical resemble a bell-shaped distribution on a log scale (Posthuma et al. 2019). To construct an SSD, toxicity data from species from different taxonomic groups (typically chronic no-effect or low-effect data - NOEC or EC_{10}) are log-transformed and fitted to a cumulative distribution function. A lower percentile (referred to as HC_p - hazardous concentration for $p\%$ of the species) of this distribution is selected as the basis to derive a protective quality criterion (**Figure 5.1**). The HC_p is equivalent to a protective concentration PC_{100-p} , which describes the percentage of species being protected at that concentration. Typically, the 5th percentile is chosen (i.e., HC_5/PC_{95}). In several frameworks, including those applied in Australia, Canada, and the United States, the HC_5/PC_{95} is used directly as the water quality guideline value or criteria (CCME 2007; Warne et al. 2018), while in Europe, the HC_5/PC_{95} is divided by an additional AF of 1-5 to

derive PNECs/EQs, to adjust for the number of test species and/or data uncertainties (ECHA 2008c; CIS-WFD 2018).

The criteria for SSD data selection for the minimum number of taxa and species needed vary among the policy approaches and jurisdictions. On EU level, the output from an SSD-based quality criterion (EQS, PNEC) is considered reliable if the database contains preferably more than 15, but at least *10 chronic NOECs/EC₁₀ values across at least 8 taxonomic groups* (guidance under REACH is taken as basis for the EU EQS guidelines - (ECHA 2008c; CIS-WFD 2018). The minimum data requirements for using a SSD in the Australia and New Zealand guidelines include toxicity data for *at least five species that belong to at least four taxonomic groups* (Warne et al. 2018; Batley et al. 2018). However, using toxicity data from at least eight species is strongly encouraged, and from more than 15 species is considered optimal. Provided a good visual SSD fit is ensured (especially the lower tails where the HC/PCs are determined), the latter results in a very high reliability of the derived threshold values. In case there are insufficient chronic NOEC/EC₁₀ data, the ANZG guidelines also allow to convert other chronic toxicity data such as chronic LC/IC/EC₅₀ by dividing them by factors of 2-5, to provide estimates of chronic NOEC/EC₁₀ data (Warne et al. 2018). Acute toxicity data can be converted using acute-chronic ratios. The lowest reliability results from converted acute toxicity data and poor fit.

Multiple levels of protection can be derived depending on the selected percentile of the cumulative toxicity value distribution. This is used in the ANZG guidelines to derive different levels of protection in relation to the defined management objectives (ANZG 2018b). The WFD requests to “use an EQS reference that protects at least 95% of the surface waters”, similar to the ANZG management objective for lightly to moderately disturbed waters (criterion is 95% protection level). Examples for SSD-based water metals quality criteria include WFD-Zn (UK TAG 2012d), and ANZG-Ni (ANZG 2024b), both based on saline water only datasets.

While the major field of SSD application is the derivation of water quality criteria, the methodology is generally also applicable for the derivation of criteria for toxic substances in sediment (see **CHAPTER 5.2**), physical stressors such as burial or suspended particulate matter (Smit et al. 2008a), or oxygen consumption, given a sufficient dataset over a stressor gradient.

Figure 5.1: Illustration for deriving a hazardous concentration for 5% of species / protective concentration for 95% of species (HC5/PC95), based on a hypothetical cumulative frequency distribution of log-normal toxicity values of a substance. The different symbols represent different species.

5.1.1.3 Field and mesocosm data:

In Australia and New Zealand, field-based, microcosm and mesocosm data can be used in SSDs, either individually or in combination with laboratory-based data. Details on field and semi-field studies, and how to address field-effects confounding and how to use them to derive GV is described in ANZG (2018c) and Batley et al. (2018). In the EU, field or mesocosm studies may directly be used as the basis of quality standard (QS) derivation or, when an SSD based on laboratory toxicity tests is used, to help select the size of AF applied to the HC5. The general hierarchy to derive thresholds implies that if the conditions to use the SSD-method for the derivation of quality standards are met, it should always be used.

Field and mesocosm data are prone to confounding. To determine which stressor most likely has caused a measured effect (causality), improved ways to isolate the effects of stressors were developed recently, including the use of more sensitive and diagnostic biological indicators (e.g. genomic information, stressor-specific biomarkers, toxicodynamic-toxicokinetic models) (Chariton et al. 2016).

5.1.2 PROTECTION LEVELS

Typically, regulatory frameworks provide more than one threshold for quality assessments. The Australia and New Zealand guidelines use a 95% protection level for DGVs protective for slightly to moderately disturbed waters, but provide additional protection levels (e.g., 99%, 90%, 80%) to account for different management objectives. In the EU, EQS are provided for acute (MAC-EQS) and chronic (AA-EQS) toxicity. Similarly, U.S. EPA uses a Criterion Maximum Concentration (CMC) and a Criterion Continuous Concentration (CCC) based on acute and chronic toxicity, respectively. Canada provides very few national water quality guidelines, usually in form of long-term protection values based on chronic toxicity. Norway applies a water (and sediment) quality classification scheme, where the boundaries between the five classes represent respectively, the upper limit of background concentrations, the PNEC for chronic exposure, the PNEC for acute exposure, and 2-10 times the acute PNEC (NEA 2016, rev. 2020). Where an environmental quality standard (i.e., an EQS) has been proposed in the EU WFD, it is used instead of the PNEC_{chronic}.

5.1.3 ADDRESSING LOCAL CONDITIONS: THRESHOLD MODIFICATION AND DERIVATION OF SITE-SPECIFIC THRESHOLDS

This section discusses approaches how to tailor existing generic thresholds according to local environmental conditions, and how to develop new, site-specific thresholds. A number of abiotic environmental factors can modify the bioaccessibility/bioavailability and toxicity of metals and metalloids to aquatic organisms, including dissolved organic carbon (DOC), pH, salinity, temperature, pressure, alkalinity, or inorganic ligands, and generic thresholds developed for national or international frameworks for water quality are typically based on data from a specific set of solution variables and cannot account for the spatial or temporal variation of these variables. Furthermore, generic thresholds may not be protective for locally important species because they are usually based on a few (often standard) test species. Hence, it is recommended, wherever possible, to tailor generic thresholds or derive new, site-specific thresholds to account for local conditions in the process of local water quality assessments (ANZG 2018a). For a detailed discussion of site-specific thresholds for water quality, the reader is referred to van Dam et al. (2019).

Table 5.2 summarizes the major approaches to derive locally relevant, site-specific thresholds, by either modifying an existing generic threshold, or by deriving new thresholds. **Figure 5.2** highlights the conceptual hierarchy of available approaches. Modification is possible by accounting for locally relevant modifiers of bioavailability, such as DOC, or by recalculating thresholds based on an adapted species selection. Data for

new thresholds can derive from 1) reference-site chemical composition data, 2) laboratory-effects data, and 3) field or semi-field effects data. Also, a WoE approach (see **CHAPTER 5.6.2**) might be appropriate. The approaches vary between the environmental frameworks discussed in this report.

In Canada, Australia and the United States, local thresholds are recommended over national generic WQG/GV/WQC. The *ANZG Water Quality Guidelines* provide guidance on methods for deriving site-specific guideline values for protecting surface water aquatic ecosystems, with *approaches* focusing on the use of biological field-effects data, laboratory-effects data, reference-site data and the use of multiple lines of evidence (ANZG 2018d). Similarly, CCME provides guidance to derive site-specific water quality criteria in Canada (CCME 2003). Also, the *US EPA water quality guidelines* provide guidance to derive site-specific criteria (U.S. EPA 1985; rev. 2010, 2013, 2017; updated 2023). Recommended *approaches* include the Recalculation approach, the Biotic Ligand Model (BLM) for freshwater Cu to address bioavailability-modifying factors, the Water-Effect Ratio (WER) for metals other than Cu, and the background concentrations approach. In the EU, existing guidance on threshold implementation suggests to consider locally relevant bioavailability and background concentrations for water quality classification and compliance assessments (CIS-WFD 2019). The derivation of new, site-specific thresholds is not addressed in the EU guidelines.

Table 5.2: Approaches to adapt thresholds to local environmental conditions (blue) at the site of interest or to derive site-specific, new thresholds (green), as basis for compliance monitoring/risk assessment. The compilation is mainly based on the guidelines for threshold development in Canada (CCME 2003), United States (U.S. EPA 2013, 2016a, 2017; updated 2023, 1985; rev. 2010), Australia and New Zealand (ANZG 2018a), the EU (CIS-WFD 2018, 2019), and van Dam et al. (2019). Focus is on toxicants in water, but the approaches are generally also applicable to derive thresholds for physical stressors (SPM) or ecosystem receptors (biomarkers, bioaccumulation, bioassays, biodiversity). LOE: Line of Evidence, as described in CHAPTER 5.6.1. TV: threshold value

Approach	Description	Site-adapted TV	New, site-specific TV	LOE	EU WFD	ANZG	CCME	U.S. EPA
Adjustment based on modifiers of bioavailability and toxicity	<p>Modifiers such as DOC, pH, T, alkalinity, hardness and inorganic ligands change the toxicity and bioavailability of metals and metalloids to aquatic organisms</p> <p>Adjust TV according to local conditions, relates receiving water physicochemistry to the bioavailability and toxicity of metals to aquatic organisms</p> <p>e.g., BLM, chemical speciation modelling, empirical regressions</p> <p>The BLM can be used to normalize the toxicity database to site-specific chemical conditions, considering the effects of water quality parameters on bioavailability</p> <p>Note, that for marine environment currently one draft BLM for Cu is available</p> <p>Multiple linear regression models available for Cu-DOC</p>	x		Ch	<p>X</p> <p>(need to be considered during compliance monitoring, BLM currently only available for freshwater Ni; draft freshwater Cu, Zn, Mn)</p> <p>DOC correction method currently only available for DOC-normalized Cu PNEC</p>	<p>X</p> <p>The Cu draft DGVs can be adjusted for different DOC concentrations to produce DOC-modified DGV, based on US-EPA draft marine BLM</p>	<p>X</p> <p>(MLR used to derive thresholds for freshwater Zn and Cu)</p>	<p>X</p> <p>(draft marine BLM for Cu available)</p>
Account for Background concentration – Added Risk Approach (ARA)	<p>Adjust toxicity data to derive a maximum permissible addition (MPA) concentration or “added EQS”</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Subtract background concentrations in test media for toxicity tests (might be relevant for tests using natural water as a diluent) from the effects data 2. Add (ideally background-corrected) MPA to local background to derive an adapted threshold <p>Requires that spatial and temporal variability of local background concentrations are well characterized</p> <p>the ARA implies that the MPA is derived from toxicity data that are based on the added metal concentration in toxicity tests</p> <p>Limitation: implies that only the anthropogenic additions of a substance (i.e. the amount added to the natural background concentration) are considered to be relevant for the effect assessment of that substance, but relationship between toxicity and natural background</p>	x		Ch	<p>X</p> <p>(as option to calculate site-specific EQS when generic EQS is exceeded)</p> <p>Zn EQS comes as EQS_{add} (used tests are mixture of natural seawater with background, and artificial seawater, cb subtracted where possible, but majority of the studies did not mention background concentrations and results were based on</p>	<p>-</p> <p>(when background conc. higher than DGV, derive new, site-specific GV based on reference condition approach)</p>	<p>-</p> <p>(when background conc. higher than WQG, derive new, site-specific QC</p>	<p>-</p>

Approach	Description	Site-adapted TV	New, site-specific TV	LOE	EU WFD	ANZG	CCME	U.S. EPA
	concentrations is unknown and some populations might in fact live close to their upper tolerance limit				nominal concentrations) UKTAG2012, Zn-RAR EQS Cd dossier: ARA suggested for setting QS for Cd (i.e., MPA+bg), but in EU Directive implemented as total risk EQS			
SSD Recalculation	removal of data from existing SSD for species not local or relevant to the site of interest, adjust SSD dataset so that it better reflects the taxonomy and, therefore, the sensitivity of species that reside at the site of interest while not explicitly mentioned, this can also involve addition of relevant new data (e.g., cold-water species, deep-sea species)	X (the key site-adapted toxicity consideration for deep sea waters is the exclusion of algae and photosynthetic plants)		bio	-	-	x	x
Water-Effect ratio (WER)	Takes into account relevant differences between the toxicities of a metal in laboratory dilution water and in the site water conduct parallel toxicity tests using 2 different test diluents, a standard laboratory water and water collected from the site of interest The WER is calculated by dividing the toxicity estimate for a particular percent effect observed in the site water test, by the estimate generated from the standard laboratory water test. The generic WQB is then modified by multiplying it by the WER				-	-	x	X (BLM for Cu was preferable over WER approach)
Account for background concentration – BG approach	Calculate an upper limit or a multiplier of local background dataset or reference site dataset, to derive a threshold	-	x		-	X preferred approach in case there are no effects-based DGV	x	x

Approach	Description	Site-adapted TV	New, site-specific TV	LOE	EU WFD	ANZG	CCME	U.S. EPA
	define a measurable level of change from a natural reference condition that, although the ecological consequences are unknown, is considered unlikely to result in adverse effects Not effects-based, highly conservative					available, or when the natural background concentration exceeds the DGV		
Laboratory toxicity testing	Conduct single substance tests using locally-relevant species and local water (instead of synthetic water), apply SSD or AF approach depending on available data If not enough data – use to validate generic TV, or add into database of existing SSD (see recalculation approach)	x	x	bio	-	x	x	x
Direct toxicity assessment	multiple contaminants may warrant a whole effluent or ambient water toxicity testing approach instead of deriving a local TV for a single or several contaminants				-	x		
Field or semi-field data	TV derivation for physical and chemical stressors and toxicant stressors based on direct assessment of level of response and change in an ecosystem exposure or effects indicator to the stressor(s) of interest can include in situ testing with caged species, microcosms, mesocosms, or observations from ecosystems across an existing (manipulated) gradient of stressor concentrations also useful approach for stressors such as deposited sediment, or bioaccumulating toxicants suitable field effects data would result from studies in which confounding is low (or can be resolved), a causal or strong inferential relationship is established between biological and ecological response data and corresponding stressor concentrations along a sufficient exposure gradient, and communities of potentially sensitive organisms were assessed obtained information more representative than that obtained from traditional laboratory-based, single-species toxicity tests Limitations: often, more than one pressure or stressor will be influencing the status of the local ecosystem. This makes it difficult to determine which pressure or stressor was the primary cause of the observed ecosystem responses, especially when pressures or stressors are expected to interact or produce similar responses	x	x	eco	Accepted method for developing generic environmental quality standards, but in practice, field or model ecosystem studies used to validate generic PNECs/EQS and/or adjust AF applied to an HC5 from an SSD or to the AF method. In EQS derivation, field and mesocosm data have an important role as lines of evidence in helping define the standard (through helping reduce uncertainty) but are not recommended to replace laboratory-based ecotoxicity data	field effects data are considered complementary or potentially even preferred over laboratory toxicity testing data for WQB derivation Field-based, microcosm and mesocosm data can be used to constrain SSD, either by themselves or in combination with laboratory-based data		

Approach	Description	Site-adapted TV	New, site-specific TV	LOE	EU WFD	ANZG	CCME	U.S. EPA
Multiple LOE	Using a combination of multiple independent lines of evidence on the effects of a stressor, including laboratory and field studies		x	all	X Use field or semi-field data to validate and/or adjust PNEC/EQS	X Recommended, but not yet applied For details see https://www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines/guideline-values/derive/mLOE		USEPA (2016), Chapter 8

Bioavailability models that capture key toxicity modifying variables are used to derive *adaptable thresholds* for selected metals, and include **biotic ligand models (BLMs), multiple linear regressions (MLR), or metal toxicity-DOC correlations**. Bioavailability-based thresholds for selected metals (mainly Cu, Ni, Zn) are available in regulatory frameworks in the United States, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, and the EU. U.S. EPA's 2007 aquatic life *freshwater* quality criteria for Cu toxicity (U.S. EPA 2007) was the first incorporating a **BLM** approach. The BLM is a computational approach that couples chemical speciation calculations with toxicological information to predict the biological availability and toxicity of aquatic metals (Paquin et al. 2002; Smith et al. 2015) and can account for variations in metal toxicity using local water chemistry information. The key concept of a BLM is that organisms possess a key binding site (biotic ligand) that interacts with the toxic metal and other cationic components of the water, and that the degree of accumulation of the toxic metal at the binding site is directly related to the observed toxicity (ANZG 2018a). The approach incorporates the competition of cations for binding to abiotic ligands and to biotic receptors, the site of toxic action on the organism. BLM calculations can be used to adjust toxicity values to a 'normalised' set of water quality conditions prior to deriving water quality guideline values, so that the sensitivity of all species is expressed under the same water chemistry condition, or to make site-specific adjustments to DGVs based on site-specific water quality conditions (ANZG 2018a). Default thresholds are typically provided for a reference condition and change accordingly in response to changes in site-specific water quality variables. Input data for the BLM can include variables such as temperature, pH, DOC, major cations (e.g., Ca, Mg, Na, K), major anions (e.g., SO₄, Cl), alkalinity, or sulfide. The European WFD guidelines strongly recommend to incorporate bioavailability in the derivation of QSs for metals, whenever possible (CIS-WFD 2018). A full BLM was adopted to derive bioavailability-based EQS for freshwater Ni (European Chemicals Bureau 2008; CIS-WFD 2011b), and further BLM-based EQS are available for freshwater Cu (ECHA 2008a; UK TAG 2012a), freshwater Mn (UK TAG 2012c), and freshwater Zn (UK TAG 2013). In Europe, the BLM bioavailability correction according to site-specific conditions is applied to the test site/monitoring dataset, not to the threshold itself, i.e., BLMs are used as part of a consideration of metal bioavailability under local water composition. The reference conditions used to derive the bioavailability-based threshold represent worst-case bioavailability conditions in order to make the EQS_{bioavailable} adequately protective of all EU waterbodies when applied as a screening step within a tiered compliance assessment process (CIS-WFD 2019). In a tiered approach, test site concentration is first compared to EQS_{bioavailable}. If that fails, the bioavailable fraction of test site concentrations is calculated (using simplified BLM tools, or, alternatively, chemical speciation modelling or DGT lability). The Canadian Federal Water Quality Guideline (FWQG) for freshwater Cu adopted a BLM allowing to normalize the Cu toxicity database to site-specific chemical conditions and derive an adjusted threshold, similar to the EPA BLM. For a discussion of differences between Cu BLMs developed in the different regulatory frameworks in the United States EPA, the EU, and Canada see ECCC (2021) and ANZG (2018a).

The only *marine BLM* approach to derive bioavailability-based water quality criteria protective of aquatic life in estuarine/marine environments was developed for Cu by United States EPA (U.S. EPA 2016a). This BLM allows to determine acute and chronic criteria values based on the site-specific water quality variables temperature, pH, DOC, and salinity, but still (at the time of writing) only exists as a draft document. No marine BLM-based thresholds are available in the EU. No bioavailability normalization is recommended for the marine Ni DGV, as the effects of DOC on Ni toxicity in marine water were shown to be minor (ANZG 2024b). For Zn, it is recommended to assess bioavailable Zn at the test site (ANZG 2021).

An **MLR** approach has been suggested as a simpler method compared to BLMs for deriving guideline values (Brix et al. 2017; DeForest et al. 2018) and was used by Environment Canada in developing a Zn guideline value for freshwater (CCME 2018). Similarly, the ANZG Ni and Zn GVs for freshwater are MLR-based (ANZG 2024a, 2024c) and can be adjusted depending on the water's chemical conditions.

Besides temperature (and potentially pressure), DOC is the most influential bioavailability/toxicity modifier in the marine environment, its relevance is particularly known for Cu. Increasing DOC has been shown to significantly reduce the ecotoxicity of Cu in freshwater and marine water. In the EU, a **correction for the effect of DOC** on the Cu toxicity in saltwater is derived and applied (ECHA 2008a; UK TAG 2012b). A reference species sensitivity distribution is constructed at 1 mg/l DOC, which allows for adjusting the threshold (PNEC) value to suit site-specific DOC conditions where concentrations exceed 1 mg l⁻¹. A DOC correction is further available for freshwater Pb in the EU (CIS-WFD 2011a). In the Australia and New Zealand guidelines, the USEPA-BLM for Cu was used as basis to develop a DOC-adjustable Cu marine DGV (currently available as draft (ANZG 2023c). Also for freshwater Cu, a DGV adjustment based on DOC concentration has been developed (ANZG 2023b).

As alternative to the application of full BLMs or using linear regression models for one or more toxicity modifiers such as DOC to develop adaptable thresholds, DGT-labile concentrations may provide another way to adapt total metal thresholds. Within a large European research project, adapted EQS_{DGT} were developed for Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn, Cd, Pb, Ni (Amouroux et al. 2021b; Amouroux et al. 2021a; Amouroux et al. 2023). The EQS_{DGT} are based on the slope of the regression of total metal concentrations and DGT-labile metal concentrations and are supposed to serve as reference for DGT-labile (as approximation of bioaccessible) monitoring/test site metal concentrations.

Local **natural background concentrations** are differently accounted for in different regions. In Europe, thresholds are either directly provided as an 'added' concentration limit, i.e., as concentration that adds to natural background, such as Norway EQSs (NEA 2016, rev. 2020), UK Zn PNEC (UK TAG 2012d), or the OSPAR PNECs (OSPAR Commission 2014). Background concentrations can also be considered as part of tiered compliance assessments, as outlined in the WFD EQS implementation guidelines (CIS-WFD 2019). If bioavailability models exist, and the bioavailable test site concentrations breach a generic, bioavailable-based EQS (that typically integrates natural background concentrations), the background concentrations are considered next. If the total dissolved concentrations at a test site are close to background (i.e., <90th percentile of background dataset), then the risk is low. If no bioavailability model exists and the EQS refers to the total dissolved concentration, the background concentrations should be directly considered when the EQS is breached, comparing test site concentrations with a threshold expressed as maximum permissible concentration MPC (**added risk approach - ARA**). The ARA accounts for ambient background concentrations, and the threshold applies only to the additional contribution above the ambient background level. First, the toxicity data of the generic PNEC should be re-evaluated. For each toxicity study that is used to derive the PNEC, the metal background level measured in the culture or test media is subtracted from the effect value in order to derive an "added EQS" – EQS_{add}. In a second step, the background concentration is subtracted from the test site data before comparing the net test site concentration with the EQS_{add}. The use of the ARA implies that only the anthropogenic additions of a substance are considered to be relevant for the effect assessment of that substance. However, due to missing information on background metal concentrations in toxicity tests, this is in reality rarely the case. The draft Zn EQS_{bioavailable}, that is provided as PNEC_{add} (UK TAG 2012d, 2013) is a good example: while the background Zn concentrations in the toxicity tests used to construct an SSD were subtracted where possible, the majority of the studies did not mention background concentrations and results were based on nominal concentrations. OSPAR provides PNECs for As, Pb, Cd, Ni, Zn, and Hg in form of MPC+cb (OSPAR Commission 2014), requesting to account for local background concentrations. However, toxicity data in the source documents (such as EQS dossiers, EU-RAR, UKTAG proposed EQS) were usually not corrected for background concentrations, except for some Zn data. The EU EQS dossiers for Cd and Hg that were used to derive EQS thresholds for the WFD (CIS-WFD 2005a, 2005b) suggest the use of the ARA for setting the quality standards (i.e.; QS=MPC+cb). However, the European Commission decided to refer to the **total risk approach TRA** for these two elements in the WFD (i.e., integrating natural background concentrations), and proposed

quality standards that already account for and comprise the natural background concentration. Outside Europe, the ARA is uncommon and the development of new, site-specific thresholds is recommended in case that background/reference site concentrations exceed generic (bioavailability-based) threshold values.

Figure 5.2: Conceptual hierarchy of available approaches for deriving water quality criteria (van Dam et al. 2019).

The ability to derive protective thresholds for **deep-sea environments** by adjusting existing thresholds, based on bioavailability corrections, background considerations, or an adaption of species selection, is limited as it includes many unknowns. Considering the influence of **high hydrostatic pressure and low temperature** on organism responses to acute and chronic toxicity (Mestre et al. 2014; Mevenkamp et al. 2017a; Koppel et al. 2018; Brown et al. 2017; Chapman 2016), how relevant are toxicity tests with surrogate, shallow-water species extrapolated to predict impacts on deep-sea benthic biota? All existing regulatory thresholds are based on standard temperature and pressure conditions (20°C, 1 bar), while studies with cold-water species in Antarctica and the Arctic have shown a delayed toxicity response to metals due to their slower uptake kinetics, slower growth and development, and lower metabolic rates (Koppel et al. 2018; Chapman 2016), but high sensitivity (Chris Hickey, pers. communication), while elevated hydrostatic pressure can enhance the toxicity of selected metals and the synergism of multiple metals (Mevenkamp et al. 2017a; Brown et al. 2017). Similar critical considerations were made regarding the protective ability of shallow-water-based thresholds for deep-sea tailings disposal (DSTD) environments (Stauber et al. 2022; Simpson and Spadaro 2016). To account for these large uncertainties, additional AF for deep-sea thresholds could help to increase conservatism of derived thresholds and support the precautionary approach. The protective ability of modified thresholds in deep-sea environments would further need to be validated before they can be adopted in regulatory frameworks, which may become a challenge by itself (laboratory tests with site-specific deep-sea organisms not possible, *in situ* tests require realistic exposure scenarios and are expensive).

As long as the influence of toxicity-modifying variables such as pressure and temperature in saline matrices is not fully understood and predictable, and chemical speciation and biotic ligand modelling cannot fully depict this influence the development of new, locally-relevant thresholds for deep-sea environments is probably more meaningful. **Considering the currently very fragmented state of knowledge on toxicity**

mechanisms for deep-sea organisms, the most likely way forward will here be the reference condition approach (see CHAPTER 5.4).

5.1.4 STRESSOR MIXTURES

The presence of mixtures of toxicants can result in additive toxicity (sum of the toxicity of the individual components), greater than additive toxicity ('synergism'), or less than additive toxicity ('antagonism'). Cedergreen (2014) and (Liu et al. 2017) concluded that assuming additive toxicity is a reasonable first assessment approach. Synergistic effects were observed from the presence of Cu and Cd (Brown et al. 2017). Guidance how to mathematically deal with mixture toxicity is provided in (ANZG 2018a) and (Zwart and Posthuma 2005), including the concentration addition model (used for chemicals with similar modes of action, all relevant stressor concentrations are added and the total value is compared to the sum of threshold values) and the response addition model (in case of different modes of action). However, obtaining reliable, less conservative information on mixture toxicity or joint effects in the presence of other stressors may warrant either direct toxicity assessments (DTA) using single-species toxicity testing (see WET/DTA box), or mesocosm or field studies for the specific toxicant/stressor mixtures of concern, preferentially along pressure gradients.

DTA, together with the measurement of water chemical and physical properties, can be used to derive a proxy for a variety of stressors present that all may contribute to adverse effects. As an example, electrical conductivity has been demonstrated to summate the stressor-receptor response relationship adequately for water quality objective setting (e.g. U.S. EPA 2016b). In case of whole effluent toxicity testing with material discharged from single point source, a 'safe' dilution could be calculated and used as assessment criteria during risk assessments (see CHAPTER 6.1.3, 6.2.3, 6.3.3, and 6.4).

5.2 Metals: marine sediments

Potential contaminant exposure routes for benthic organisms living in or on surface sediments are manifold and include 1) **uptake from pore water** (for benthic organisms that burrow in the sediment), 2) **uptake from overlying water** (for epibenthic organisms and for benthic organisms that burrow in the sediment and create burrows that are flushed with the overlying water) or 3) **direct or unintended ingestion of sediment** (sediment-feeding organisms) (Hauton et al. 2017; Simpson and Batley 2016; ECHA 2023). Contaminants released from sediment to the water column, both by diffusive flux of dissolved chemicals and through physical disturbance such as sediment resuspension and biological actions, are a risk for benthic and pelagic organisms, while **resuspended particles** themselves are a source of particulate contaminants especially to suspension-feeding organisms (Simpson and Batley 2016) (besides other particle-induced effects such as mechanical damage or reduced food uptake). Dietary uptake of particle-bound contaminants is a significant exposure route for deposit and detritus feeders (Camusso et al. 2012), but has not yet been explicitly accounted for in the development of concentration-response models for the prediction of sediment metal toxicity. It has to be speculated that the most sensitive organisms are those that respond to the pore water concentrations of contaminants only, despite the greater 'available' pool of particle-associated contaminants (Simpson et al. 2013b). The exposure route is strongly influenced by species-specific feeding mechanisms, life-stage, gut retention time and the behaviour of the organisms in or on the sediment, and more than one exposure route may be of relevance for an individual. The dominant exposure route may also change in different life stages or due to different activities in a life stage (ECHA 2023).

Numerical sediment quality guideline values (SQGVs) were developed in numerous legal regimes (see Excel table for overview on available data). The **derivation of SQGVs** is either based **on empirical approaches** that

make use of co-occurring metal (and other toxicant) concentrations and observed biological effects in contaminated sediments, on the **equilibrium partitioning approach** combined with water quality guidelines, or **toxicity testing** using spiked sediments. The preferred approaches for quality criteria derivation differ between different countries, and all have advantages and disadvantages (Simpson et al. 2013b). **Table 5.3** summarizes the approaches used to derive SQGVs in different legal frameworks, including both predictive and retrospective assessments. Recent reviews on various approaches for the derivation of SQGVs in national and international regulations for sediment quality assessment are provided by , e.g., Leppanen et al. (2024), Birch (2018) and Simpson et al. (2013b).

The process to derive protective assessment criteria for metal contaminants in sediment is challenging, related to the co-occurrence of potential pollutants, different contaminant exposure pathways, and the high variability of sediment properties that strongly impact metal availability and toxicity. Mixtures of toxicants or other stressors can result in either additive toxicity, greater-than-additive toxicity (synergism) or less-than-additive toxicity (antagonism), all of which have been reported (García-Barrera et al. 2012; Brown et al. 2017; Mahmoudi et al. 2007). While SQGVs derived from co-occurrence of chemicals and biological effects suffer from non-causality, single substance SQGVs do not account for effects from toxicant mixtures, dietary exposure, and trophic transfer (biomagnification), and both approaches lead to high uncertainties. **Hence, SQGVs should not be used for strict pass-fail judgement during risk assessments, but only as one LOE (see CHAPTER 5.6) together with further evidences such as toxicity testing. Field validation is an essential element of SQGVs development process because it provides a basis for assessing their reliability in sediment quality assessments** (Ingersoll et al. 1997).

5.2.1 EMPIRICAL APPROACHES

The empirical approaches use data from biological responses to contaminated sediment, typically derived from field surveys or laboratory toxicity tests (direct toxicity tests) with sediments or extracted pore water. The biological responses range from community or population responses measured in the field, to a multitude of endpoints (e.g., survival, growth, reproduction) measured using bioassays in the laboratory (or, in case of *in situ* testing, in the field).

5.2.1.1 Large biological effects databases

A large biological effects **database for contaminated and uncontaminated sites from coastal marine and estuarine environments throughout the United States**, compiled by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has been used to derive sediment quality benchmarks that are widely used worldwide for risk assessments. By relating sediment toxicity data to measured sediment contaminant concentrations, the original intention was to evaluate three approaches for the establishment of effects-based assessment criteria and validate their results: the EqP approach (see **CHAPTER 5.2.3**), the spiked-sediment toxicity test approach (see **CHAPTER 5.2.2**), and various methods for evaluating synoptically collected biological and chemical data in field surveys (Long and Morgan 1991). In a next step, sediment quality benchmark concentrations were derived from a ranking of co-occurring chemical concentrations in the sediments and observed toxicity and other effects data in increasing order and applying statistical analyses. Because contaminants typically co-occur (e.g. different metals and organics), toxicity or other effects were equally attributed to all contaminants within the mixture. Biological effects data predominantly include benthic community analyses (endpoints such as abundance and indices of species richness) and bioassays of field-collected samples with mixtures of substances (variety of toxicological endpoints, most common mortality), but also included limited bioassays of reference sediments spiked with specific chemicals and predictions

based on equilibrium partitioning of contaminants between sediment and pore water (EqP models) (Long et al. 1998).

Two large sets of saltwater SQGVs were derived from this dataset: **ERLs/ERMs** (Long et al. 1995) and **TELS/PELS** (Macdonald et al. 1996). The difference between ERL/ERM and TEL/PEL statistics is that ERL/ERM only used chemical concentrations associated with adverse biological effects, whereas TEL and PEL incorporated concentrations are associated with both, effects and no-effects. Two levels of empirically derived assessment criteria are derived from the compiled effects database: a concentration below which adverse effects are rarely observed, and a second concentration above which adverse effects will likely occur. The effects range-low (ERL) is set as the lower 10th percentile of the effects data set for each chemical. The median or 50th percentile, of the effects data was identified and referred to as the effects range-median (ERM). The TEL was defined as the geometric mean of the 15th percentile of the effects data and the 50th percentile of the no-effects data, and a probable-effects level (PEL) was defined as the geometric mean of the 50th percentile of effects data and 85th percentile of no-effects data (Macdonald et al. 1996). Both sets of SQGVs were intended to be used as informal, i.e., not regulatory, tool to assist in the interpretation of chemical data for sediments. Unlike the water quality guidelines, which are based on effects data for individual contaminants, the majority of the effects data used to derive SQGs suffer from **co-occurrence of contaminants**, where observed biological effects were ascribed equally to each toxicant. This prevents the observed effects being confidently assigned to any one contaminant and is the source of significant uncertainty in empirically derived SQGs. Jones-Lee and Lee (2005) criticized that the approach presumes that the "effect" reported for each sediment was caused independently by each of the measured chemical contaminants in that sediment, and that no other chemical or condition not included in the database has any influence on the manifestation of the "effect" that co-occurs with the particular chemical of focus.

Such limitations mean the empirically-derived SQGVs are only useful as a screening tool to initially identify locations and chemicals of most concern. The value of these SQGVs is greatest when applied to sediments with broad mixtures of contaminants (Simpson et al. 2011; Long 2006), but they should not be considered thresholds for any of the individual contaminants in isolation. Toxicity and bioaccumulation tests, toxicity identification evaluations, and benthic community assessments provide complimentary information for assessing sediment quality. **Empirical SQGVs are no regulatory criteria.** In the United States, ERL/ERM values are in use in the risk assessment of contaminated sediments at Superfund Sites. In Canada, TEL and PEL values were adopted into the national SQGs (CCME 1999, 2002), while Australia and New Zealand derived their assessment criteria (SQGV/SQGV_{high}) from the ERL/ERM dataset (ANZG 2018i; Simpson et al. 2013b). OSPAR uses ERLs as interim Environmental Assessment Criteria (EAC) (OSPAR Commission 2008a).

The same statistical approach as described above can be applied to larger field datasets regions. As example, see Menchaca et al. (2012) for an empirical approach to derive threshold values for freshwater sediments in Northern Spain.

5.2.1.2 Benthic community responses: field-species sensitivity distribution (f-SSD) and field-community sensitivity distribution (f-CSD)

This approach uses biological community responses to mixtures of contaminants in sediments to derive site-specific guidelines for a range of metals. Field data of benthic communities and contaminant loadings in marine sediments measured in parallel were used, applying a field-based species sensitivity distribution (f-SSD) (Leung et al. 2005; Kwok et al. 2008; Hewitt et al. 2009). Such an approach avoids the laboratory-to-field extrapolation and the single chemical-to-chemical mixtures extrapolation (i.e., it also addresses cumulative effects). The endpoint in these studies is effects on communities, such as a decrease in abundance of individual species along a chemical gradient. Only sensitive species are considered during the SQGV derivation,

excluding information on how tolerant or rare species respond to chemical exposure (Lui et al. 2014). Unless there is a distinct concentration gradient of a specific contaminant, relating the observed effects to individual contaminants remains confounded by co-occurring contaminants, factors that influence contaminant bioavailability, as well as other physical and chemical parameters. According to Simpson et al. (2013b) such studies are better included as part of an ecology LOE (see section 5.4). The approach appears useful for the validation of existing assessment criteria and for the derivation of multiple-stressor site-specific thresholds that better account for the interactions of chemical stressors and other (natural) stressors, e.g. variations in temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, and food availability.

In another approach, field-based sediment quality guidelines were derived from the relationship between species density of benthic infauna and contaminant level applying a nonparametric empirical Bayesian approach, using the Norwegian Oil Industrial Association database and extracting concurrently obtained data on species density and contaminant levels in sediment samples (Lui et al. 2014). All available species data, including sensitive, rare, and insensitive ones were utilized. Méndez-Fernández et al. (2019) constructed a SSD model for the abundance of sensitive macroinvertebrate taxa based on sediment Hg EC₅₀ values.

5.2.2 LABORATORY TOXICITY TESTS (SPIKED SEDIMENT)

Toxicity testing of spiked sediments is used to derive thresholds for individual substances, a detailed discussion and information and guidance on standardized tests for sediment-dwelling species can be found in ECHA (2023), CIS-WFD (2018), Simpson et al. (2013b), Simpson and Batley (2016), and Leppanen et al. (2024) and references therein. Most toxicity data are based on the use of spiked sediments in which clean sediment has been contaminated deliberately in the laboratory and test organisms introduced to this spiked sediment. Toxicity tests are usually performed according to OECD, ASTM or USEPA guidelines for a range of benthic invertebrates. Numerous standardized toxicity test methods for sediments are available (see overview given (ECHA 2023; ANZG 2023a). Most of the standard sediment toxicity tests referred to or requested in regulations rely on scoring relatively simple endpoints (i.e., mortality and reproduction). To protect populations, communities, and ecosystems, rather than individuals, more subtle endpoints would be needed when deriving quality criteria or evaluating the risks of chemicals (Leppanen et al. 2024).

The approach is applied in Europe (ECHA 2023; CIS-WFD 2018) to derive sediment SQGs. Because the bioaccessibility, bioavailability and toxicity of sediment contaminants such as metals is strongly influenced by sediment properties (see box on bioavailability), modifying factors such as grain size or organic carbon should be acknowledged, whenever possible, during threshold derivation. This will allow the derivation of adaptable thresholds. Typically, toxicity test-based SQGVs are derived with the AF approach (see **CHAPTER 5.1.1.1**). The size of the AF depends on the availability and variety of toxicity data, and the lowest AF (10) is applied when three data from long term tests with species representing different living and feeding conditions are available. In principle, also the SSD modelling approach can be applied to sediment toxicity data, however, the minimum data requirements for an SSD are rarely met. So far, SSD-based HC5 values were derived for Cu-, Pb-, and Ni-spiked sediments applying SSDs to whole sediment toxicity data (Simpson et al. 2011; Vangheluwe et al. 2013; CIS-WFD 2011a).

5.2.3 MECHANISTIC APPROACHES: EQUILIBRIUM PARTITIONING, SEM-AVS AND PORE WATER CONCENTRATIONS

An approach to derive SQGVs for sediment-dwelling organisms in the absence of ecotoxicological data is based on the **equilibrium partitioning theory**, using water quality criteria (WQC) for aquatic organisms and suspended matter/water or sediment/water partitioning coefficients (K_d). The EqP approach considers the

dissolved forms of metals in pore water as the primary route by which benthic organisms are exposed to contaminants (Di Toro 2013; Burgess et al. 2013; Birch 2018). The approach assumes that the partitioning of the chemical between sediment solid phases and pore water is at equilibrium, and equal sensitivity of pelagic and benthic organisms. Assuming that the dissolved concentrations of contaminants in pore water are a surrogate for bioavailable contaminant concentrations in the sediment to sediment-dwelling organisms, the SQG is defined by the concentration of the contaminant in the sediment that is in equilibrium with the **water quality criteria** concentration in the pore water ($SQG = K_d \times WQC$). If the SQG is exceeded, the metal concentrations in the pore water are expected to be higher than the water quality threshold and hence could be potentially toxic. This approach, however, only works if the partitioning behavior between dissolved and particulate phases is well understood and constrained (CIS-WFD 2018). However, as the distribution coefficients integrate the binding of metals with multiple solid phases, K_d s can vary by several orders of magnitude between different sediment types (ECHA 2014).

In the EU, the EqP approach is used as one option to derive SQGVs (PNECs or EQSs), although effects-based thresholds for benthic organisms are preferred when toxicity data are available (CIS-WFD 2018; ECHA 2008c). One example is the PNEC for Cu in marine sediments, derived from the pelagic marine PNEC based on the EqP approach (ECHA 2008a). Norway uses EqP-derived PNECs for Cd, As, and Cr in their sediment classification scheme (NEA 2014). In Australia and New Zealand, the EqP is described as one possible approach to derive numerical sediment quality criteria for organic substances (ANZG 2018i).

The bioaccessibility and bioavailability of metals in sediment is strongly influenced by factors modifying the partitioning of metals into the dissolved phase (see box), namely acid-volatile sulfides (AVS) (only present in anoxic sediment), concentrations of solid and dissolved OC, redox conditions, iron and manganese oxyhydroxide phases and sediment particle size (Simpson et al. 2013b). Gao et al. (2015) proposed a refinement of the SQGV derivation via EqP approach, by considering AVS-bound (MAVS) and residual mineral-bound (MR) metal fractions ($SQGV = K_d \times WQC + MR + MAVS$). Jiwaringrueangkul et al. (2024) present an even more advanced SQGV calculation, additionally considering grain size and TOC as modifying factors. They derived site-specific K_d s based on metal concentrations of pristine sediments by dividing the labile-bound metal fraction in the sediment by the pore water metal fraction. Developed site-specific SQGs are adapted to local (estuarine) conditions.

The technical possibilities to measure metal concentrations in the pore water strongly advanced over the past decade, making it easier to assess the dissolved concentrations directly. This allows to directly assess compliance of dissolved pore water concentrations in sediments with water quality thresholds, without relying on assumptions for equilibrium distributions (but still relying on the assumption of equal sensitivity of pelagic and benthic organisms).

The US EPA presents two complementary approaches for deriving mechanistic equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmarks (ESBs) for metal mixtures (Cd, Cu, Pb, Ni, Zn, Ag) in sediment, which are protective for benthic organisms. In the first approach, the EBS assumes equilibrium between the solid phase and interstitial water phase of sediments and considers the difference between acid-volatile sulfides (AVS) and simultaneously extracted metals (SEM). This approach assumes that metals bound to AVS in the solid phase (extracted by cold extraction with 1 M HCl) do not partition into the dissolved phase and hence are not available to cause toxicity. When the difference of SEM (extracted together with AVS) minus AVS of the mixture is less than 0, these metals should not cause direct toxicity to benthic organisms (the so-called solid-phase AVS benchmark). The second approach considers dissolved pore water concentrations in relation to the WQC of the individual metals. Sediments containing these metals should not cause direct toxicity to benthic organisms if summing up the measured pore water concentrations of the metals divided by their respective WQC_{chronic} is less than 1.0 (the so-called interstitial water benchmark). Adverse effects may occur, when one of the criteria

is not met (U.S. EPA 2005; Burgess et al. 2013). The approach is used for exclusion of toxicity in risk assessments of contaminated sites (Superfund). EBS for metal mixtures based on the EqP assumes (1) that the partitioning of the metal between sediment AVS (or any other binding factors controlling bioavailability) and interstitial water approximates equilibrium; (2) organisms receive equivalent exposure from interstitial water-only exposure or from exposure to any other equilibrated sediment phase; (3) for the cationic metals cadmium, copper, lead, nickel, zinc, and silver, partitioning of metal between the solid phase and interstitial water can be predicted based on the relative concentrations of AVS and SEM; (4) the WQC concentration is an appropriate effects concentration for freely-dissolved metal in interstitial water (i.e., similar sensitivity of benthic and pelagic fauna); and (5) the toxicity of metals in interstitial water is no more than additive (U.S. EPA 2005). U.S. EPA (2005) proposes a further refinement and considers both AVS and organic carbon (OC) solid phases controlling the partitioning of metals into the dissolved phase and hence the bioavailability of metals: $(SEM - AVS)/f_{OC}$, where f_{OC} is the fraction of sediment that is organic carbon. The metal mixture ESBs do not consider the antagonistic, additive or synergistic effects of other sediment contaminants (except for those in the mixture) or the potential for bioaccumulation and trophic transfer of metal mixtures to aquatic life.

In the ANZG sediment quality guidelines, The SEM - AVS approach is used as bioavailability qualifier (Simpson et al. 2013b). Simpson et al. (2013b) provide a detailed discussion of the approaches based on equilibrium partitioning, including a discussion on the limitations of the AVS-ESB approach for oxic sediments, and the necessity to define upper limits for metals at high AVS concentrations. The SEM-AVS concept has been employed in the EU risk assessments for cadmium, zinc, and nickel, and in the voluntary industry risk assessments for copper and lead (CIS-WFD 2018), and is included as one LOE to assess bioavailable fractions in sediments during compliance monitoring in the guidelines for EQS derivation for WFD (CIS-WFD 2018). **Since not only AVS (and OC) influence metal availability (see box), the SEM-AVS approach should only be used as one LOE to assess the bioaccessible (i.e., dissolved) fraction.** The approach is further applied throughout the literature to assess toxic risks in sediments (Rodrigues et al. 2023).

5.2.4 LABORATORY TOXICITY TESTS (WATER-ONLY)

A WQG for sediment pore waters can be derived based on dissolved contaminant toxicity for benthic organisms (Simpson et al. 2011; ANZG 2018f; U.S. EPA 2005), that could be related by EqP to a sediment quality guideline value. The approach is thought to be protective for exposure to benthic biota via sediment-associated waters. However, stress to organisms due to non-natural conditions may occur.

5.2.5 BACKGROUND CONCENTRATION APPROACH

Because of the uncertainties of extrapolating data from the laboratory to the field, the impossibility of accounting for the sensitivities of all sediment dwelling organisms, and large variability of physical sediment characteristics over small geographical areas affecting the bioavailability of chemicals, the ecological realism of empirically and theoretically (EqP) derived SQGVs has been questioned (Bjorgesæter and Gray 2008). The background concentration approach (for a more detailed description see **CHAPTER 5.4**) provides a pathway to derive numerical assessment criteria either in the absence of relevant effects-based thresholds, or when there is a large uncertainty associated with available (often generic) thresholds. The approach does not take into account or imply biological effects or toxicity. There are two general options: to use an upper limit of a background or reference dataset based on statistical analyses, where concentrations below that value are considered “near background” and safe. The other option involves a multiplier to derive a threshold.

Bjorgesæter and Gray (2008) proposed a protective background-based SQGV that is 3.6-times the background value, based on field survey data. However, this is not a general rule as shown by Menchaca et al. (2012), who

demonstrated that effects on biota can, in some cases, already occur at concentrations of only two times background. This demonstrates the importance to base background-based thresholds on site-relevant datasets (i.e., similar grain size distribution and chemical composition) and to choose a conservative statistical measure.

Fisher et al. (2019) argued that setting thresholds based on a less conservative percentile or a multiplier of a background dataset is not recommended because corals growing in environments with naturally elevated exposure to stressors may be closer to their physiological limits and would not tolerate further increase. On the contrary, for corals growing under extremely clear conditions, adjustments based on either percentiles or multipliers may prove overly conservative.

5.2.6 LEVELS OF RISK AND LEVEL OF PROTECTION

Numerical sediment assessment criteria in regulatory frameworks are often staged, defining different sediment quality classes/levels of risk. The empirically derived benchmarks ERL and ERM (originally not thought to be used as regulatory thresholds) represent two levels of risk: a concentration below which adverse effects are rarely observed, and a second concentration above which adverse effects will likely occur. ANZG identifies an upper and a lower limit for sediments (DGV and GV-high) based on the USEPA ERL/ERM classification, and Norway defines 5 classes of sediment quality. Sediment quality assessments for the purpose of defining the environmental status of a marine region (Burgeot et al. 2022) or the suitability of a dredged sediment to be disposed in the ocean (OSPAR Commission 2009c) are often based on a lower, 'close-to-background' criterion and an upper, often effects-based criterion (see details in **CHAPTER 5.6** and **CHAPTER 6.2.3**).

Multiple levels of protection can be derived from any single substance or field SSD approach (Kwok et al. 2008). The level of protection can also be adjusted if sediment quality guideline values are based on reference site data (see **CHAPTER 5.2.5** and **5.4**), e.g. by using a more conservative (80th) or a less conservative (99th) percentile of the dataset as threshold.

5.2.7 SITE-SPECIFIC THRESHOLDS

Site-specific guideline values can be derived using species, endpoints and conditions more reflective of a specific site or region. Generally, the approaches to derive site-specific thresholds for metals in sediment are similar to those already outlined for water quality guidelines (see **CHAPTER 5.1.3**), including the use of reference-site data, field-effects data, or multiple LOE based on two or more of laboratory, field-effects and/or reference-site data, and consideration of bioavailability/toxicity modifiers. As an example, see Méndez-Fernández et al. (2019) on Hg sediment standards for Northern Spain.

Table 5.3: Approaches to derive sediment quality assessment criteria in different regulatory frameworks. Numerical values are provided in Appendix 2 and the Excel table provided with this report.

Sediment Quality Guideline frameworks	Description	Remarks
EU WFD (CIS-WFD 2018)	<p>derivation process is based on that used for effects assessment under REACH, but with an additional consideration of field or mesocosm data</p> <p>use of different lines of evidence to generate the final standard</p> <p>the following are suitable for deriving the sediment quality standards: (i) spiked sediment toxicity tests with benthic organisms, (ii) water column ecotoxicity data used with equilibrium partitioning (EqP), (iii) empirical field or mesocosm data</p> <p>Quality standard based on sediment toxicity data preferred over EqP-derived quality standards: apply AF or SSD when chronic data available, when only acute data than apply AF and conduct EqP calculation, choose lowest value;</p> <p>Reliable data arising from field/mesocosm studies can be used to influence the derivation of the QS_{sediment}, to derive an EQS: validate or refine QS (e.g., reduce or increase AF, or choose EqP over toxicity testing).</p> <p>Field or mesocosm data may refer to TEL/PEL, ERL/ERM and other empirical derivations, or f-SSD; when field threshold is lower than EqP, then apply AF of 5 or field threshold to obtain new QS</p> <p>Field and mesocosm data have an important role as lines of evidence in helping to define the standard (through helping reduce uncertainty) but would not be regarded as 'higher tier' data that would replace laboratory-based ecotoxicity data</p> <p>EQS sediment for Pb and Cd (only freshwater) available, derived from chronic toxicity tests and SSD</p>	Multiple LOE
ANZG (Simpson et al. 2013b)	<p>because only a limited number of sediment toxicity tests were available, ANZG uses the empirical field ecological and laboratory ecotoxicity-effects database from North America, with the DGV representing the 10th percentile value of the data distribution(=ERL) and using the median value as an additional upper guideline value (=ERM), except for Cu-low and Hg-high (based on empirical effects data from Hong Kong, see McCreedy et al., 2006)</p> <p>In case of absence of toxicant values for sediments: the suggested approach is to use the reference site approach. It is important to compare derived guideline values with concentrations for sediments of similar grain sizes and OC contents; or use WQG as surrogates, and compare pore water concentrations to these WQGs</p> <p>With the availability of more sediment toxicity tests, the use of SSDs to derive guideline values has been demonstrated for Cu (Simpson et al. 2011).</p> <p>Alternative approaches discussed in Simpson et al. (2013)</p>	<p>the role of grain size and organic carbon (OC) as major variables controlling contaminant bioavailability was illustrated as a precursor to future guideline value derivations that might more explicitly take these into account</p> <p>Attempt to develop Sediment Property-Specific Guideline Values for Metals (Simpson derived Cu SQGs normalized to OC in <63 µm fraction, provide matrix how to modify GV depending on varying properties)</p>
U.S. EPA (U.S. EPA 2017; updated 2023, 2005)	<p>The EPA has dealt directly with the toxicity of chemicals in sediments in fresh and marine waters through equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmarks (ESBs)</p> <p>USEPA published mechanistic SQGs, called equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmarks (ESBs)</p> <p>in some cases, whole-sediment toxicity testing was performed to "validate" the ESB values for selected contaminants</p> <p>empirical and mechanistic SQGs are not used in regulations but have been used at Superfund sites as part of ecological risk assessments</p>	

Sediment Quality Guideline frameworks	Description	Remarks															
	ESBs are the USEPA's recommendation of the concentration of a substance in sediment that will not unacceptably affect benthic organisms or their associated designated uses. USEPA chose the equilibrium partitioning approach because it accounts for the varying biological availability of chemicals in different sediments and allows for the incorporation of the appropriate biological effects concentration.																
NEA (Bakke et al. 2010; NEA 2014)	<p>5 sediment classes of contamination</p> <p>Their 1997 guidelines were based not on biological effects, but on intervals of excesses of concentrations over background concentrations. The update in 2007 largely followed the approaches being developed by the EU Water Framework Directive (EU WFD, 2010, but retaining the five classes</p> <p>Upper class boundaries based on OSPAR-background concentrations (Class I), PNEC_{chronic+bc} (Class II), PNEC_{acute+bc} (Class III) and ratio class limit IV and III in water phase (Class IV)</p> <p>PNEC chronic and acute either derived via EqP approach (e.g., Ni, As, Cr) and AF application, or, if data available, from toxicity testing (e.g., Pb, which has been derived via SSD+AF, or Ni, which has been derived from EqP approach + AF), often only freshwater toxicity used (e.g., Cd)</p> <p>Where a sediment quality standard (EQS) has been proposed in the European Union Water Framework Directive, it was used instead of the PNEC_{chronic}</p> <p>For Pb, a WFD interim QS_{sed} based on marine and freshwater sediment toxicity (SSD+AF) available (EU lead dossier), final class II boundary defined as QS+bc (as proposed in EU lead dossier – defined the QS_{sed} as MPA, using the added risk approach)</p> <p>For Cd, a WFD interim QS_{sed} based on freshwater sediment toxicity (AF) available (EU cadmium EQS datasheet), final class II boundary defined as EQS+bc (as proposed in EU cadmium dossier – defined the QS_{sed} as MPA, using the added risk approach) – note, that M-241 reports a wrong AF applied to the toxicity endpoint to derive PNEC_{chronic} (4 instead of 50 as used in the EQS dossier)</p> <p>For Ni class II boundary, a PNEC_{sed} based on the EqP approach using a PNEC freshwater is used, but not properly cited (data source unclear, neither derived from Ni RAR, nor nickel EQS dossier)</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="1525 416 2089 608"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="1525 416 1641 469">I Background information</th> <th data-bbox="1648 416 1749 469">II Good</th> <th data-bbox="1756 416 1872 469">III Moderate</th> <th data-bbox="1879 416 1989 469">IV Poor</th> <th data-bbox="1995 416 2089 469">V Very poor</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="1525 474 1641 544">Background level</td> <td data-bbox="1648 474 1749 544">No toxic effects</td> <td data-bbox="1756 474 1872 544">Chronic effects of long-term exposure</td> <td data-bbox="1879 474 1989 544">Acute toxic effects at short-term time exposure</td> <td data-bbox="1995 474 2089 544">Extensive toxic effects</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1525 549 1641 608">Upper limit: background</td> <td data-bbox="1648 549 1749 608">Upper limit: AA-QS, PNEC</td> <td data-bbox="1756 549 1872 608">Upper limit: MAC-QS, PNEC_{cut}</td> <td data-bbox="1879 549 1989 608">Upper limit: PNEC_{cut} * AF¹⁾</td> <td data-bbox="1995 549 2089 608"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p data-bbox="1525 612 2089 632">Figure: Classification system for water and sediment. 1) AF: safety factor</p>	I Background information	II Good	III Moderate	IV Poor	V Very poor	Background level	No toxic effects	Chronic effects of long-term exposure	Acute toxic effects at short-term time exposure	Extensive toxic effects	Upper limit: background	Upper limit: AA-QS, PNEC	Upper limit: MAC-QS, PNEC _{cut}	Upper limit: PNEC _{cut} * AF ¹⁾	
I Background information	II Good	III Moderate	IV Poor	V Very poor													
Background level	No toxic effects	Chronic effects of long-term exposure	Acute toxic effects at short-term time exposure	Extensive toxic effects													
Upper limit: background	Upper limit: AA-QS, PNEC	Upper limit: MAC-QS, PNEC _{cut}	Upper limit: PNEC _{cut} * AF ¹⁾														
HELCOM	EQS for metals in sediment provided for Pb (secondary origin, see EU lead dossier), Cd (secondary origin, see EU cadmium dossier), and Cu (new, based on SSD+AF)																
OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2021b, 2008a)	<p>OSPAR defined Environmental Assessment Criteria (EAC)</p> <p>EACs represent the contaminant concentration in the environment below which no chronic effects are expected to occur in marine species, including the most sensitive species. For metals, no EAC values yet available, and Effects Range Low (ERL) are used instead. A second criterion is based on the background concentrations (BAC)</p>																
CCME (CCME 2002)	Uses empirical North America dataset (PEL/TEL) as lower and upper quality criteria																
EU Technical Guidance Document (TGD)	Effects assessment for the marine sediment compartment (predictive, for marketing substances)– derive PNEC _{sed}																

Sediment Quality Guideline frameworks	Description	Remarks
(European Chemicals Bureau 2003)	<p>use EqP to derive a PNECsed based on PNECsaltwater, in case of absence of toxicity data for benthic organisms, use this as PNECsed in case of concern (based on modelled PEC), conduct sediment toxicity tests (spiked sediment)</p> <p>Four situations are distinguished to derive a sediment PNEC, depending on availability of toxicity test data: only acute freshwater PNEC, fresh water and marine acute toxicity, chronic freshwater toxicity, or chronic toxicity data for benthic freshwater and a minimum of two marine organisms – in the latter case a PNECmarine sediment is calculated using a lower assessment factor of 10 that is associated with data obtained from long-term tests. A PNECmarine sediment obtained from such data is preferred for risk assessment.</p>	
<p>ECHA (ECHA 2008c)</p> <p>Building TGD, 2003</p>	<p>Effects assessment for the marine sediment compartment (predictive, for marketing substances) – derive PNECsed</p> <p>The effect assessment is based on the estimation of the Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNECsed). In the absence of ecotoxicological data for sediment-dwelling organisms, the PNECsed may be provisionally calculated using the equilibrium partitioning method (EqP). This method uses the PNECwater for aquatic organisms and the suspended matter/water partitioning coefficient as inputs.</p> <p>If ecotoxicity data on sediment dwelling organisms is available, the PNEC is calculated using the lowest value and an Assessment Factor (AF) related to the amount of information. The default AFs range between 10 000 and 10 for the marine environment.</p> <p>When no results from long-term tests with sediment organisms are available and the PEC/PNEC ratio derived from the results of short-term sediment tests or via the equilibrium partitioning method is a cause for concern then the need for long-term testing with sediment organisms should be considered</p>	

5.3 Suspended particulate matter

Suspended particulate matter (SPM) in the water column is a major stressor that can cause adverse biological effects related to the particle load itself (causing, e.g., clogging of filter organs, reduced food supply, particle toxicity), or due to metals bound in the mineral lattice or at particle surfaces that can cause toxic actions after metal mobilization in a suspension or particle internalization or particle ingestion. In the context of DSM, most severe effects are expected for sessile-filter-feeding benthic organisms exposed to the suspended particle plumes, but also pelagic organisms can be affected (also depending on the release depth of discharge material). Relevant thresholds can be defined for total suspended particle concentrations and for particulate metal concentrations. The total particle load, mineralogy, chemistry and metal bonding type, particle shape, and grain size are important variables that control the negative impacts of SPM on biota, contributing to the complexity of deriving thresholds protective for organisms exposed to particle plumes.

5.3.1 TOTAL PARTICLE CONCENTRATIONS

Total SPM concentrations are rarely addressed in national or international regulatory frameworks for water quality. In the ANZG hierarchy of guideline values for physical stressors such as turbidity or SPM, site-specific GV are preferred over default GVs available for Australian and New Zealand ecoregions (ANZG 2018e) (for IMCRA mesoscale bioregions, turbidity DGVs were derived from satellite datasets, using the 80th percentile, (ANZG 2018g). To derive site-specific GVs for physical stressors that cause problems at high values or concentrations (e.g. nutrients, SPM, oxygen demand), ANZG recommends to use the 80th percentile of a dataset from an appropriate reference site. Regulated at state level, the Queensland state derived turbidity and SPM DGVs for different regions and sub-regions, such as for the Queensland wet tropical offshore region with a limit of 0.7 mg/kg SPM (State of Queensland 2009). As a side note, in the Solwara I EIA, the older value of 1.2 mg/kg for the Queensland wet tropical offshore region has been used as SPM threshold and outside boundary of the plume mixing zone. While the default approach for developing guideline values for physical and chemical (PC) stressors uses reference data, it is also valid to develop guideline values for PC stressors using field effects or laboratory effects data to develop dose-response relationships.

US EPA provides a framework addressing the physical properties and numerical threshold criteria of suspended and bedded sediments (SABS), defined as particulate organic and inorganic matter that suspends in or is carried by the water and/or accumulates in a loose, unconsolidated form on the bottom of natural waterbodies (U.S. EPA 2006b). SABS in excessive amounts are recognized as a major ecosystem stressor, and the document describes a process that states, tribes, and territories can apply to develop SABS criteria to support water quality standards and protect designated uses, including appropriate indicator selection and the development of conceptual response models. As it does not address the effects of co-occurring toxic contaminants, the SABS guidelines do not provide concepts for an integrated assessment. U.S. EPA has dealt directly with the toxicity of chemicals in sediments elsewhere (U.S. EPA 2005). Regulated at state level, numerical SABS criteria applied for turbidity and suspended solids are provided in the form of exceedances over background (e.g., "not more than 10 % above background" or "no more than 10 NTUs above background") or absolute values (e.g., "not greater than 100 NTU"). Several states provide criteria for an averaging period (e.g., 30 days) as well as an allowed daily maximum concentration (U.S. EPA 2006b).

There are no assigned marine EQS values for SPM concentrations in the EU.

Information on adverse biological or ecological effects from suspended particles and sedimentation are often derived in the context of major offshore activities such as dredging, oil and gas activities, submarine mine

tailings disposal, or bottom trawling (see **CHAPTER 6**), but findings and implications can also be relevant to other sediment disturbances as sources of elevated turbidity or sedimentation (bottom-trawling, DSM). Numerous scientific studies reported effects of enhanced particles loads in the marine water column on benthic or pelagic organisms (Erftemeijer et al. 2012; Johnson 2018; Fähse et al. 2023; Tuttle and Donahue 2022; Bilan et al. 2023; Tjensvoll et al. 2013; Wurz et al. 2021; Cummings et al. 2020; Mobilia et al. 2021; Pineda et al. 2017c; Yang et al. 2017; Fisher et al. 2019; Negri et al. 2019; Baussant et al. 2018; Alam et al. 2022; Larsson et al. 2013; Järnegren et al. 2020; Scanes et al. 2018; Liefmann et al. 2018; Carreiro-Silva et al. 2022). Derived limits of adverse (sub-lethal) effects typically range between 3-20 mg/kg, depending on environmental settings and studied organisms. A value of 10 mg/l has repeatedly been reported as protective for sponges (Pineda et al. 2017a; Wahab et al. 2019), corals (Fisher et al. 2019; Baussant et al. 2018), and fin fish (Harvey et al. 2017), see also literature review for benthic sponges and corals in Offshore Norge (2024), and is often used as operational threshold limit for risk assessments and compliance monitoring of offshore activities (see Excel table for examples of operational thresholds for offshore activities). In the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park, lower values of 0.7-2 mg/l are used for the open coastal and offshore waters as threshold values for coral protection (Australian Government 2010). This value, however, is not effects-based, but derived from the 80th percentile of a reference dataset, according to the ANZG guidelines that were applied by the Queensland regional government (State of Queensland 2009). (Smit et al. 2006a) derived effects-based PNEC threshold values of 0.2 mg/l and 0.8 mg/l for barite particles (a weighting agent) and water-based drilling mud, respectively, simulating offshore oil exploration drill cuttings. More literature on effects of enhanced particle loads can be found in the Appendix tables and in **CHAPTER 6**.

The high variability of derived effects sizes of SPM concentrations reflects the significant differences in experimental conditions, such as physical and chemical properties of suspended and settled material, frequency and duration of exposure, studied organisms, ambient background conditions that tested organisms are adapted to, exposure routes, measured endpoints, and life stage. The effect of pressure on adverse effects from enhanced particle loads is presently unknown, as there are almost no data on effects of enhanced particle loads on deep-sea organisms from depths >300 m.

In abyssal plains such as in the CCZ, not only high hydrostatic pressure exists but also the ambient suspended particle concentrations are extremely low (0.01-0.03 mg/kg, (Gardner et al. 2018; Haalboom et al. 2022; Gazis et al. 2025)). For DSM-relevant thresholds for SPM or turbidity, this means that site-specific thresholds for suspended particulate matter (or turbidity) need to be developed based either on effects studies that consider local ambient conditions and realistic exposure scenarios, or by applying the (conservative) background concentration approach. Alternatively, van der Grient and Drazen (2022) used an extrapolation approach to derive thresholds for deep-sea organisms in the CCZ. They found that responses and sensitivities of shallow-water fauna to increased SSC are similar across different habitats, hypothesizing that results are transferable to deep-sea environments. They found that effects start to occur at concentrations of more than 4 times the background, which results in extrapolated thresholds for CCZ bottom water of 0.04-0.08 mg/kg SPM. This finding, however, needs to be validated for DSM settings, where especially SMS suspended particle plumes will be enriched in potentially toxic metals (and also PMN dewatering plumes). Exposure to this type of particles leads to biological responses likely caused by combined and potentially synergistic mechanical and metal toxicological impacts from the plume material, as shown by Carreiro-Silva et al. (2022) and Wurz et al. (2024) for deep-water corals and sponges. These studies demonstrate that effects from suspended particles and from metal toxicity cannot be studied in isolation and whole plume toxicity assessments with mining-relevant plume sediment/ore material are required, aiming to evaluate the combined toxicity from all potential stressors that are present, and to identify suitable proxy pressure indicators.

5.3.2 METAL CONCENTRATIONS IN SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER (SPM)

Thresholds for suspended particulate metal concentrations can either be set equivalent to metal concentration thresholds in bedded sediment or derived from thresholds in water, via the EqP approach. Sediment quality standards are derived from toxicity testing with sediment-dwelling organisms (**CHAPTER 5.2.2**), empirical field studies (**CHAPTER 5.2.1**), or via extrapolating a quality standard applicable to the concentration in sediment (i.e., protective for benthic life) from the quality standard derived for the protection of life in water (EqP approach, **CHAPTER 5.2.3**). The complexity and challenges in setting metal thresholds in sediments is discussed in **CHAPTER 5.2**, acknowledging the importance of abiotic factors (such as grain size or mineralogy) and biological factors (such as life stage, feeding behavior) that determine the bioaccessibility, bioavailability, and toxicity of sediment-associated metals in organisms.

The suitability of applying sediment thresholds to metal contents in SPM seems is limited, but this depends on the mode of sediment threshold derivation. For example, sediment threshold values that are considered to be protective for organisms taking up metals from pore water (EqP, pore water and spiked sediment tests) may be relevant when addressing metal mobilization from suspended particles into the dissolved water phase. Particulate metal uptake in filter-feeding organisms should be more closely related to the fine, resuspendable fraction of the substrate, rather than to total sediment chemistry on which SQGs are often based. Accordingly, attempts to relate tissue burden of filter-feeding animals to total bottom sediment chemistry have failed (Spooner et al. 2003), but also the chemistry of the smaller sediment size fractions cannot always be correlated. Recent work has further revealed that, at least for some localities, there is no direct relationship between suspended solids metal concentrations and uptake by filter-feeding organisms (Lee et al. 2016), underlying the importance of factors such as uptake routes (dissolved, particulate) and selective feeding, besides abiotic factors determining the bioaccessibility of metals to these organisms.

An approach using partitioning coefficients to translate a metal EQS for dissolved water into an equivalent EQS for suspended particulate matter is applied in the EU to derive quality standards for the assessment of water quality in accordance with the WFD (CIS-WFD 2018). K_d s are defined as the concentration ratio between the particulate phase and the dissolved phase under the assumptions of equilibrium, reversibility and trace conditions. The main aim of the WFD is the achievement of good chemical status for all water bodies, but Member States can decide on the matrix for certain substances (i.e., water, sediment, suspended solids, biota). For example, the cadmium quality standard (QS) for water in the EU WFD EQS dossier is, related to its particle-reactivity, provided as concentration in SPM in addition to a value for dissolved concentrations. The Cd K_d for water-SPM (European Chemicals Bureau 2007) is based on monitoring data on the distribution of Cd in the dissolved and in the particulate matter phase in different European waterbodies (130,000 l/kg), and represents the European average. Note, that the K_d value in the Cd EQS dossier differs from the K_d value provided in EU guidance (CIS-WFD 2009) that provides partitioning coefficients (K_d) for water-SPM and water-sediment for the elements Cd, Ni, Pb, and Hg. As K_d s are a function of environmental factors such as DOC, POC, particle size, pH, salinity, particle mineralogy etc., and can strongly vary for one metal. Hence they should be derived from water bodies of local relevance. Harmesa et al. (2024) provide an overview on K_d values for a selection of different marine waters.

Concluding remarks for SPM:

Considering the multiple potential stressors that may induce adverse effects in fauna exposed to enhanced particle loads (mixture of dissolved and particulate metals, enhanced particle load) that may act independently or synergistically (or antagonistically), the derivation of protective thresholds for SPM should involve an integrated assessment of the effects. Furthermore, physical and chemical properties of suspended solids as well as biotic factors such as feeding behavior or life stage (e.g., Lee et al., 2016) strongly influence biological responses to enhanced particle loads, impeding simple causal (metal or particle concentration) dose-response

relationships. This complexity results in a range of possible responses (at equal nominal concentrations) and further limits the applicability of generic thresholds. To determine the actual risk of realistic particle suspensions for site-specific taxa, it is most appropriate to conduct locally-relevant testing with particle suspensions over the expected range of concentrations and key taxa (i.e., direct toxicity testing, in the laboratory or field) and apply a conceptual response model to investigate responses as a function of level of exposure, and derive effects-based thresholds that ensure protection of site-specific organisms or communities. Proxy indicators that are either related to the exposure or the effects can be derived, accepting that the exact mechanisms leading to observed adverse effects in the presence of multiple stressors may remain unknown. In case of effects sizes derived from laboratory experiments, additional assessment factors could acknowledge the unknown effect of pressure.

An integrated assessment of adverse effects from suspended particles is for example used for the regulation of dredging material disposal (U.S. EPA 1991), see also **CHAPTER 6.2**). The tiered assessment of dredged material involves toxicity testing of the combined dissolved and suspended particles phase, which should not exceed a limiting permissible concentration (LPC), i.e., a concentration that will not cause unreasonable toxicity or bioaccumulation. For the risk assessment, a median lethal concentration (LC_{50}) is calculated from a serial dilution experiment with the dredged material. If the predicted concentration in the combined dissolved and suspended solid material beyond the boundaries of the disposal site within the first 4 h after dumping, or at any point in the marine environment after the first 4 h (the phase of initial mixing) is less than 0.01 of the LC_{50} , the LPC for a water-column impact is met.

Considering the current state of knowledge (i.e., almost absent effects-based data) and the precautionary approach, early-stage, site-specific SPM thresholds for DSM should be based on background concentration levels.

5.4 Reference condition / Background concentration approach

The background concentration/reference condition approach is a good starting point for setting and applying site-specific environmental thresholds in the absence of locally-relevant thresholds or effects data, or when early warning thresholds need to be established in a hierarchical assessment framework. The derived thresholds are used to differentiate between environmental conditions near background/local reference and conditions that statistically deviate. As such, this is a precautionary and highly conservative approach that takes any statistically significant deviation from the natural background as potential risk, without having any knowledge on the biological or ecological or toxic effects, if the threshold is exceeded. Such thresholds need to be based on an adequate number of samples to ensure statistical robustness. The approach is recommended in several legal environmental frameworks (CCME 2003; ANZG 2018e; U.S. EPA 2006b) that often also provide guidance on its application. Typically, an upper limit of a background or reference site dataset for a measurable variable is used to establish the threshold. The most widely used statistical approaches are: median + MAD (**median absolute deviation**), mean + 2-times SD (**standard deviation**), an 80th, 90th, 95th, or 98th **percentile**, or a **multiplier**. They result in more or less conservative values relative to the mean background concentration (Reimann and Caritat 2017) for a review on statistical approaches to establish geochemical background variations and thresholds in soils). A suitable example are the background-based sediment quality standards for Hg for Northern Spain that were derived by Méndez-Fernández et al. (2019) using some of the above-mentioned calculations.

In Australia and New Zealand, the derivation of site-specific guideline values (GV) for physical or chemical stressors (other than toxicants) based on reference data is, in the absence of local effects data, generally preferred over a default GV (DGV) (ANZG 2018e). For toxicants, it is the preferred approach in case there are

no effects-based DGV available, or when the natural background concentration exceeds the DGV. In both cases the recommended approach is to calculate the 80th percentile (or, in the case of physicochemical variables such as temperature and pH that can cause adverse effects at low concentrations, the 20th percentile) of a reference site dataset to derive site-specific GVs for “slightly-to-moderately disturbed” systems. When the median (i.e., the 50th percentile) of a dataset from the test site is higher, the threshold would be breached (also called the P50-P80 approach), indicating a ‘measurable perturbation’ at the test site. Depending on the agreed ecosystem condition and associated level of protection, the reference site percentile can be adjusted down or up to achieve higher or lower protection, respectively. Taking the mean value of the test site dataset for comparison with this threshold is contrasting the more conservative assessment preferred if guideline values are based on effects data instead of background reference data and where exceedance of the value indicates the potential for ecological harm. Here, it is recommended that a toxicant DGV is deemed to be exceeded if the 95th percentile of the test distribution is higher (ANZG 2018j). The background dataset approach is also discussed in guidelines related to dredging activities in Western Australia (EPA-WA 2021; Fisher et al. 2019). Comparing the mean of a background turbidity dataset to effects-based turbidity threshold derived for corals revealed a conversion factor of 1.5 to 2.2, while the 80th percentile of the background dataset would result in much too conservative thresholds. However, setting thresholds based on a background approach is not recommended for all environments because corals growing in marginal environments (i.e. turbid reef zones) may be closer to their physiological limits while for corals growing under extremely clear conditions, adjustments based on either percentiles or multipliers may prove overly conservative (Fisher et al. 2019).

The Canadian water quality guidelines also provide guidance to derive site-specific water quality guidelines based on a background or reference dataset (CCME 2003), referring to mean, median, mean + 2-times SD, and the 90th (or 10th) percentile as statistical measure applied to represent the background or reference site conditions of a variable in water. In the US EPA Framework for Developing Suspended and Bedded Sediments (SABS) Water Quality Criteria, total suspended solids values above the 75th percentile of a background dataset are considered as impaired (U.S. EPA 2006b).

The OSPAR Commission defined background assessment concentrations (BAC) - a concentration value that is close to background and that can be used to test whether observed mean concentrations at a test site are close to the background value (OSPAR Commission 2008a). When the upper confidence limit (usually 95%) of the mean concentration is at a test site is below the BAC, the mean concentrations are at background levels. Setting a BAC is based on the typical precision achieved during a monitoring programme. Currently used BACs for metals in different matrices are based on precisions of 10-20%, which resulted in BACs = ~1.5-2 times background concentrations (OSPAR Commission 2008a). BACs are used to assess the status and trend of a range of pressure and state indicators (such as metals in sediment or biota, biomarkers) in the OSPAR marine regions (OSPAR Commission 2023a). This is typically employed together with a second set of assessment criteria that are based on biological effects (environmental assessment criteria EAC, or ERL) in a colour-coded approach (blue≤BAC: conditions for indicator close to background; BAC<green>ERL: conditions deviate from background, likely no biological effects; ERL<orange: effects possible). For the integrated assessment of biological effects and chemical contaminants within OPSAR, BACs were also developed for a range of biomarkers of exposure and effects and for bioassays, besides metal contaminants in sediment and biota (Davies and Vethaak 2012; Vethaak et al. 2017; Burgeot et al. 2022). For the definition of the Italian thresholds for biomarkers, the ICES-OSPAR method (Davies and Vethaak 2012) was adopted, taking either the 90th (for MN and EROD) or the 10th percentile (for AChE, LMS-Cyt) of data from the reference sites.

Table 5.4 provides an example on the derivation of background-based threshold values using the ANZG and OSPAR approaches based on the statistics of a fictive monitoring dataset for dissolved Cd.

In hierarchical risk assessments of offshore activities, chemical assessment criteria that are based on background datasets are often applied in early tiers. One example are tiered assessments whether a dredged material is suitable for disposal at sea (OSPAR Commission 2009c; Australian Government 2009; Birch 2018). van Dam et al. (2014) describe the derivation and application of a site-specific GV for Mn in a freshwater stream to assess the risk of pollution from a uranium mine waste discharge. Using descriptive statistics, the authors derived site-specific trigger values for different levels of action that correspond to the 80th, 95th and 99.7th percentiles, respectively, of the reference site dataset. Finally, derived background dataset-based thresholds can also be combined with an allowed duration of exceedance (McArthur et al. 2002).

Hiddink et al. (2023) concluded that there are two approaches that allow to define an ecologically meaningful good ecosystem state and estimate thresholds quantitatively from data, namely “staying within natural variation” and “maintaining ecosystem functioning”. However, thresholds for the latter are difficult to derive, and the authors argue that the most objective method for setting a good-state threshold is based on maintaining the state within the range of natural variation in undisturbed systems, with the threshold set as fifth percentile of the natural variation. Setting such thresholds do not preclude human use (e.g., bottom trawling), as example, threshold of marine seabed community biomass is suggested to be located between 54 and 79% of the undisturbed state, which covers observed decreases of biomass related to bottom trawling.

Table 5.4: Example on the derivation of a threshold value using the ANZG and OSPAR approaches based on the statistics of a fictive monitoring dataset for dissolved Cd. From a fictive baseline dataset (reference site), the ANZG-derived threshold using the 80th percentile (P80) is 5.6 ng/L. For a fictive impact site, ANZG compares its median value (6.2 ng/L) with the P80 threshold value. i.e., the threshold is breached at the impact site. The OSPAR-derived threshold is calculated as 1.5x the mean of the baseline (reference site) concentration (6.99 ng/L). OSPAR then compares the mean upper 95% confidence interval (6.98 ng/L) of an impact site dataset with this threshold, i.e., the threshold is not breached at the impact site. P80, P95, P98: 80th, 95th, and 98th percentile of a dataset. BC: Background concentrations. CI: confidence interval. SD: standard deviation. BAC: background assessment concentrations.

	Reference Site	Impact Site (ANZG method)	Impact Site (OSPAR method)
	Cd (ng/L)		
Mean	4.86		
Median (P50)	4.65	6.2	
P80	5.6		
P95	5.73		
P98	5.77		
Mean + 2-times SD	6.2		
1.5xBC mean	6.99		
Mean-lower CI (95%)	4.37		
Mean-upper CI (95%)	4.99		6.98

5.5 Direct Toxicity Assessment / Whole-effluent Toxicity (DTA/WET)

Direct toxicity assessments (DTA) - or Whole Effluent Toxicity (WET) assessments, often used synonymously - provide a direct measure of the toxicity of mixtures including combined effects of multiple substances of known or unknown identity, and accounts for interaction between substances including potential synergistic effects from multiple (metal) stressors (e.g., van Dam and Chapman 2001; Vlaming et al. 2000; de Vries et al.

2022; ANZG 2023a; OSPAR Commission 2007). The types of mixtures that are typically assessed include urban runoff water, sewage discharge, wastewater from industries such as mining or oil production, dredge spill, agricultural runoff water, seawater desalination and power generation, other industrial effluent or any combination of compounds that occurs in or is likely to enter the environment and for which the toxicity is unknown. Furthermore, direct toxicity testing can also be conducted with sediments (whole sediments, pore water or aqueous elutriates). Direct toxicity tests measure the cumulative effects of all stressors and can be conducted in the laboratory or *in situ* (e.g., in mesocosms, or using caged organisms at discharge sites). In laboratory experiments, test organisms are exposed to the mixture (i.e., a waste discharge, or contaminated sediment) and effects are studied. Ideally, testing should include different taxonomic groups having different sensitivities to different toxicants at different life cycle stages, and differing exposure pathways (feeding strategies and behaviours), and different test endpoints (for example, survival, development, growth, reproduction) should be studied (ECHA 2023; Simpson and Batley 2016). DTA/WET is primarily used in prospective (hazard) and retrospective (risk) water and sediment quality assessments (see also **CHAPTER 6**). Is a waste effluent suitable for discharge? May a contaminated sediment cause toxic effects and needs further management action and remediation? Effects sizes can be used to derive thresholds, e.g., in form of site-specific 'safe' dilutions, to assess compliance (e.g., in tiered risk assessments, see **CHAPTER 5.6**), and to validate the applicability of generic thresholds. It may further be used to derive suitable proxy indicators (SPM conc., metal conc. in water or sediment) that could be used for monitoring purposes.

DTA/WET testing is an established method in the regulation of waste discharges in aqueous environments. For example, it is recommended by the US EPA as an important component of permits regulating industrial and municipal effluent discharges in the United States through the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) program to protect water quality, together with requirements based on chemical-specific water quality criteria. WET has been acknowledged by OSPAR as having an added value compared to the single-substance approach (OSPAR Commission 2007), and has been implemented in the OSPAR Recommendation 2012/5 for a risk-based approach (RBA) to the management of produced water discharges from offshore installations (OSPAR Commission 2012b; Karman and Smit 2019). Guidelines for the assessment of dredged material involve DTA with the dissolved + suspended phase of dredged material in different dilutions and with the solid phase of the dredged material (both phases are operationally defined) to determine the toxicity and ensure compliance with assessment criteria (Australian Government 2009; U.S. EPA 1991). Furthermore, DTA has been implemented in the Australia and New Zealand water and sediment guidelines for fresh and marine water as part of the decision framework to ensure environmental protection (van Dam and Chapman 2001; Simpson et al. 2013b; ANZG 2023a, 2018a). Toxicity testing allows the determination of site-specific limits, such as 'safe' wastewater dilution, derived from a dilution series. DTA can also be applied to assess the bioavailability and toxicity of one or more toxicants under site-specific conditions (i.e. local species, local dilution water) to derive a site-specific guideline value (ANZG 2023a; van Dam et al. 2019). Site-specific DTA can further involve approaches of *in situ* toxicity testing with caged organisms, useful for assessing environmental impacts, determining confidence in predicting impacts from laboratory studies, or to assess compliance with regulatory thresholds.

DTA per se does not identify the toxic components of a mixture. Translation of toxicity results into values for individual chemical components can either be done by the equivalency method (Gruiz et al. 2016), which enables toxicity originating from unknown mixtures to be converted into the concentration of an equivalently toxic reference substance (e.g., dissolved Cu), chosen for comparison. The other approach is the toxicity identification evaluation (TIE), a technique used to identify the source of toxicity in a complex environmental sample or mixture. It involves the sequential iteration of physico-chemical fractionation combined with toxicity testing to separate and identify toxic components from non-toxic components (Jop et al. 1991; ANZG 2023a).

With respect to DSM, DTA is a promising approach to integratively assess risks of suspended plume (whole plume toxicity) or settled blanketing (whole blanketing toxicity) material and derive suitable proxy indicators. The testing can be conducted along a pressure gradient, i.e., either using different dilutions (in the case of plume material), or different mixtures of blanketing and background sediment (using sediment sampled along a deposition gradient).

5.6 Concepts of quality assessment

5.6.1 LINES OF EVIDENCE AND CONCEPTS FOR QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Historically, environmental quality assessment moved from single-stage “pass-fail” relying on a single assessment parameter (usually chemical composition) to more nuanced assessments using several lines of evidence (LOE) from the fields of chemistry, biology and ecology. This is based on the fact that exceedance of a (generic) pressure threshold value does not necessarily mean that adverse biological or ecological effects will occur, but instead that further investigations should be undertaken to investigate whether exceedance indeed leads to effects.

For the **environmental assessment of water and sediment quality** in the context of i) **monitoring programs to assess ecological status and trends**, ii) **baseline studies** for upcoming activities, or iii) **risk assessment** of contaminated sediments (e.g. remediation of contaminated sediments), **hazard assessment** of a material proposed for discharge/disposal (e.g., disposal of dredged material; discharge of effluents), and **compliance monitoring**, it is recommended and common procedure to use a set of different LOEs in order to direct management actions and derive conclusions. For example, the ANZG Water Quality Guidelines recommend measuring indicators from multiple LOEs across the pressure–stressor–ecosystem receptor causal pathway during water quality monitoring programs, as it gives higher confidence and less uncertainty in the evidence of the assessment and subsequent management decisions to meet the water/sediment quality objective rather than basing evaluation on a single LOE (ANZG 2018k).

Table 5.5 summarizes different LOEs that use indicators of pressure and indicators of exposure and effects at different levels of biological organization, grouped into **Chemistry LOE**, **Biology LOE**, and **Ecology LOE**. Further details on common LOEs applicable in water and sediment quality assessments are provided in Simpson and Batley (2016).

Table 5.5: Examples for different lines of evidence and examples of suitable assessment criteria.

LOE Group	LOE examples	Examples of assessment criteria
Chemistry	Assessment of chemical composition: total concentrations, bioavailable fractions	Threshold values for water and sediment quality
Biology	Assessment of exposure and/or effects: toxicity testing (laboratory or field studies, for example, of multiple species, varying exposure pathways, and acute and chronic endpoints such as mortality, growth, reproduction or avoidance), DTA	<u>Toxicity</u> : %effect vs reference; % dilution required to be non-toxic <u>Bioaccumulation</u> : significantly different from reference <u>Biomarkers</u> : statistically significant differences compared to reference

	biomarkers to assess sub-lethal alterations, bioaccumulation	
Ecology	Assessment of effects on communities: benthic community structure	Community indices significant changes in measurements of diversity and richness (Extent of difference in comparison with reference locations)

Table 5.6 summarizes typical **concepts** used to assess water or sediment quality for decision-making, derived from legal frameworks and the literature. Many frameworks use a tiered, decision-tree assessment, while in other frameworks, several LOE are carried out simultaneously.

Tiered assessments are designed to specify an appropriate level of information required for decision-making, while keeping the process time and cost effective. Such frameworks start with screening for potential risks and add case specificity (i.e., additional LOEs) as the need for more detailed information increases (Simpson and Batley 2016). Thresholds for metal contaminants are typically used in early tiers. If quality guideline values are exceeded, more complex investigation will follow to confirm or reject the possibility of biological effects and/or decide, whether compliance with management objectives is ensured, whether a dredged material can be disposed, or a contaminated sediment requires remediation. In a typical procedure, the chemical composition is first compared to guideline values, followed by determining the bioavailable fraction of metals in case of exceedance, followed by **toxicity testing and ecological testing** in case also the bioavailable fraction exceeds the guideline value (Simpson et al. 2013b). **Hierarchical or simultaneously conducted LOE** are partly combined to develop a **Weight-of-Evidence (WoE)** conclusion for decision-making (see **CHAPTER 5.6.2**).

The Australian and New Zealand guidelines for water and sediment quality (ANZG 2018b) provide stepwise guidance for applying the Water Quality Management Framework (WQMF) to human activities that relate to water/sediment quality decisions and actions, such as the assessment of e.g., waste discharges, conduct a remediation study, conduct a baseline study, apply for a development approval, or implement a broad-scale monitoring programme (<https://www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines/framework>). The management framework involves the definition of management goals and relevant indicators, the determination of guideline values for these indicators, the definition of quality objectives, the assessment if quality objectives are met, and the implementation of a management strategy. The guidelines further provide examples how the WQMF can be applied to typical anthropogenic uses.

5.6.1.1 Sediment quality assessment

Sediment quality is assessed as part of prospective assessment frameworks to predict the likelihood of future effects for marketing chemicals (e.g., under REACH), or as part of retrospective site-specific assessments of historically contaminated sediments to evaluate the risk to the environment and the need for remediation (e.g., Leppanen et al. 2024). Another frequent application includes the prospective evaluation of the risks of ocean disposal of dredged sediment. Furthermore, large monitoring programs for marine waters in Europe (e.g., within WFD, MSFD, OSPAR, HELCOM) assess sediment quality as part of the evaluation of environmental status and trends. The complexity of assessing contaminated sediments warrants several LOEs such as chemistry and toxicity to assess the ecological implications of the contaminants of concern. Tiered decision-tree approaches and the inclusion of multiple LOEs in a WOE framework have become powerful tools in assessing sediment quality (Birch 2018); and SQGVs are often used in lower tiers of such risk assessment

frameworks (e.g., Delvalls et al. 2004; Chapman et al. 1999; MMO 2015; Australian Government 2009; Simpson et al. 2013b). The assessment of sediment quality is part of ecological risk assessments (ERAs) for sediments that follow established ERA frameworks (den Besten et al. 2003; U.S. EPA 1998; European Chemicals Bureau 2003; ECHA 2008b). In Europe, sediment quality assessment is part of the surface water protection under WFD and used to assess overall ecological and chemical status. The EU Commission recommends a tiered assessment framework for sediments (CIS-WFD 2018, 2010b); guidance documents No. 25 and 27 are the most relevant guidelines for the sediment compartment. OSPAR and HELCOM provide guidelines for the assessment of dredged material for sea disposal. Examples for assessments regulated under national law include the assessment of contaminated sediment in Norway (NEA 2018b) or the assessment of dredged material for sea disposal in the UK (MMO, 2015). An overview of decision-making frameworks for the ecotoxicological assessment of contaminated sediments and of dredged material in selected European countries is provided in den Besten et al. (2003), SedNet (2018) and Olsen et al. (2019). Sediment quality is also assessed along with biological effects as part of monitoring programs for offshore oil and gas activities (Marappan et al. 2022).

For Australia and New Zealand, sediment quality guidelines were developed as part of the Australia and New Zealand guidelines for the quality of fresh and marine water - ANZG (Simpson et al. 2013b). For the management of dredged material, national guidelines were developed and include a tiered hazard assessment framework (Australian Government 2009) that is used in the application process for a sea dumping permit. In the United States, no national sediment quality guidelines were developed, but the EqP approach is endorsed for the assessment of contaminated sediments (Superfund sites). Specific guidelines were developed for the evaluation of dredged material proposed for ocean disposal, and also include a tiered assessment framework (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016). In Canada, sediment quality guidelines were developed for the protection of aquatic life by CCME (CCME 2002).

Background values have partly been incorporated into SQGs as a separate level of enquiry in a tiered framework on a site-specific basis (e.g., USA, Canada, England, Wales and Australia) (Piva et al. 2011; Benedetti et al. 2012).

Many guidelines and handbooks provide guidance on sediment quality and risk assessments (Simpson and Batley 2016; Simpson et al. 2013b; NEA 2018b; CIS-WFD 2018; ECHA 2014, 2008c; ANZG 2018i, 2018b; CCME 2002). Reviews on this topic are further available from the scientific literature (e.g., Lehoux et al. 2020; Leppanen et al. 2024; Birch 2018; Kwok et al. 2014; Bruce et al. 2021). Methods for sediment sampling and analysis, toxicity testing, and ecological studies are described, *inter alia*, in Simpson et al. (2013b), Simpson and Batley (2016), NEA (2018b), and ECHA (2023). As different benthic species have different sensitivities to different toxicants at different life cycle stages, it is recommended to use a range of organisms having differing exposure pathways (feeding strategies and behaviours) and different test endpoints (for example, survival, development, growth, reproduction) for ecotoxicological assessments of contaminated sediments (ECHA, 2023; Simpson and Bratley, 2016).

5.6.1.2 Assessment of dredged material

The quality of dredged material and its suitability for ocean disposal is typically assessed in tiered decision frameworks, using chemical and biological LoEs and proceeding through the tiers only until information is sufficient to determine compliance or noncompliance with assessment criteria (**Table. 5.6** and **CHAPTER 1**). European guidelines for the assessment of dredged material (often called 'Action Levels') typically comprise lower and upper values similar to SQGVs. The lower AL is often based on background values, while upper values are related to SQGs for bulk sediment. Management action is triggered when AL1 is exceeded, inducing biological assessments including bioassays and bioaccumulation. As grain size distribution has a strong

influence on total metal content and metal bioaccessibility, Spanish and German jurisdictions provide Action Levels based on size-normalised data (<63 µm and <20 µm, respectively) (DEA 2012). Australia uses one SQG value as Screening Level, while regulations in the United States for the disposal of dredged material do not require nor endorse use of sediment quality guidelines for decision making purposes (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016). A review by DEA (2012) addresses action levels and guideline values in different countries used for making decisions on the suitability of dredged material for open water disposal, and summarizes approaches to derive SQGVs and limitations in their application.

While the concepts to assess the hazard of dredged material in the EU (e.g., OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024) only address impacts after deposition on the sea floor (comparison of solid phase with sediment AL, toxicity testing with benthic organisms), the US and Australia/NZ guidelines (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016; Australian Government 2009) also address the potential impacts in the water column during ocean disposal and transport through the water column. Elutriate testing determines whether contaminants present in the dredged material are mobile and will transfer to the water once dredged or dumped. If the elutriate test results exceed water quality criteria after initial dilution (that occurs within four hours after dumping), then further steps including bioavailability assessments and acute toxicity testing are required. In the US, the elutriate test is conducted at a lower tier, prior proceeding with toxicity assessments of combined liquid plus suspended particles phases and the solid phase. In Australia, the elutriate test is conducted at a higher tier, when non-compliance of dredged material with SQGVs and exceedance of background concentrations is proven at low tier. The regulation for dredging and placement of dredged material at the Historic Area Remediation Site (HARS) in the Atlantic Ocean (USACE and USEPA 2016) uses a parallel assessment of chemical and biological LoEs instead of a tiered approach, investigating the liquid, the suspended particle, and the solid phase of the dredged material.

5.6.1.3 Water quality assessment

In Australia and New Zealand, compliance with chemical guideline values is considered as one of a number of LOEs that may be used when assessing water quality in a WoE or decision scheme process. Other LOEs could include monitoring or assessment of ecosystem receptors. Where initial measurements (i.e. steps early in the hierarchy) are near or above DGVs, the consideration of bioavailable fractions and background concentrations is recommended. To assess bioavailable fractions, it is recommended to first filter the water sample through 0.45 µm, then assess metal speciation by using DGT or voltammetry, or conduct BLM. Background concentrations should be determined, and, if the background level exceeds the DGV, it is recommended to use the referential approach to derive a new site-specific guideline value (see **CHAPTER 5.4**). Where monitoring site concentrations exceed both generic assessment criteria and site-specific assessment criteria based on reference water quality, it is considered prudent to further investigate the potential for ecological impacts, through site-specific direct toxicity testing and/or field monitoring/assessment of biological communities. Further evidence can be obtained from measurements of bioaccumulation. The guidelines provide examples for typical water quality management frameworks, such as the assessment of waste discharge, conducting a baseline study, implementing a broad scale monitoring program, or application for a project development approval.

The technical guidance for monitoring of environmental water quality for protecting the marine ecosystem in the heavily used Cockburn Sound in Perth's coastal waters lays out a management framework addressing the effects of toxicants and other stressors (EPA-WA 2017). The tiered assessment framework includes two sets of quality criteria, with lower tier environmental guidelines for pressure indicators as early-warning indicators and higher tier environmental standards for effects indicators (for more details, see **CHAPTER 6.4.3**).

In Europe, coastal water quality is assessed as part of large monitoring programs to investigate the ecological and chemical status (e.g., within WFD, MSFD, Norway), and includes the chemical status in water, sediment, and biota (Burgeot et al. 2022).

Marine water quality is further assessed during offshore oil and gas activities in the European Regional Seas (such as North Sea, Mediterranean Sea), and in the North Atlantic. OSPAR developed a risk-based approach (RBA) framework to assess the environmental risk posed by produced water (PW) discharges (OSPAR Commission 2012c), following the general concept of Environmental Risk Assessment (ECHA 2008b; U.S. EPA 1998). The risk is considered to be acceptable when the Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) is lower than the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC) (European Chemicals Bureau 2003). The OSPAR RBA guidelines in support of the RBA recommendation (OSPAR Commission 2012c) suggest using either whole effluent toxicity (WET) tests or a substance-based assessment to derive PNECs for PW discharges (see **CHAPTER 6.1.3.1**). OSPAR further provides a list of the naturally occurring substances usually being analyzed to characterize PW samples along with their established PNECs (OSPAR Commission 2014). Furthermore, the assessment of water quality is also part of monitoring programs for offshore oil and gas activities (NEA 2015, rev. in 2021; OSPAR Commission 2017b).

Potential impacts of dredging and disposal of dredged material in the water column is addressed in the US and Australia/NZ (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016; Australian Government 2009), where water quality criteria and elutriate toxicity testing with pelagic organisms is used to investigate whether contaminants present in the dredged material are mobile and will transfer to the water phase once dredged or dumped (see **CHAPTER 6.2.3**).

Table 5.6: Examples for (tiered) approaches to assess water or sediment quality (for hazard and risk assessments and monitoring plans).

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs		Application and Remarks
Netherlands Dredging (RWS-Waterdienst 2008; SedNet 2007)	Single LOE	Assessment of dredged material to consider the site of relocation (at sea, in freshwater, on land or in closed storage facilities): chemical sediment quality criteria for individual substances direct into pass or fail (one out, all out)		
Sediment quality triad (Chapman et al. 1987; Chapman 2007)	Triad WoE assessment (as part of tiered assessment) Three LOE	Sediment quality assessment In case contaminant concentrations exceed SQGV and background/reference site concentrations (Tier 1), proceed with WoE used to determine whether toxic contaminants are impairing a sediment community, by combining data from three LOE (chemical analysis of sediment, ecotoxicological bioassays, and in situ benthic community structure) and elaboration through a WOE procedure in use in The Netherlands and Belgium for sediment quality assessments		WoE: Rule-based assessment
WFD; (CIS-WFD 2018, 2010b)	Tiered assessment, different LOE	Assessment of sediment quality, chemical compliance checking against EQS (good status) <u>Tier 1:</u> compare concentration of chemicals to sediment EQS <u>Tier 2:</u> conduct site-specific studies (bioavailable fractions, bioassays, benthic community assessments)		Good ecological and chemical status of all waters Use of passive samplers as complementary method to assess lability of metals
Norway (NEA 2018b)	Tiered assessment, different LOE	Risk assessment of contaminated sediments for sediment management and remediation, also applicable for assessing quality of dredged material <u>Tier 1:</u> assesses potential contaminants of concern and conduct toxicity tests with pore water extracts and several species <u>Tier 2:</u> in case contaminant threshold levels (boundary between sediment class II and III) are exceeded, and/or the toxic effects on growth and mortality exceed set levels for three species: conduct whole sediment toxicity tests on mortality and behaviour on one out of two species, and modelling of contaminant transport to assess risk of		

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs		Application and Remarks
		spreading hazardous substances and risk of impacts on the ecosystem (Threshold values have yet to be established for the acceptable/unacceptable spread of hazardous substances from sediments)		
ANZG (Simpson et al. 2013b)	Tiered assessment in decision tree, different LOE WoE at highest tier	<p>Quality assessment for contaminated sediments</p> <p><u>Tier 1:</u> total metals, compare to SQGV (if available)</p> <p><u>Tier 2:</u> in case of non-compliance, compare to background concentration</p> <p><u>Tier 3:</u> in case of non-compliance, determine dilute acid-extractable metals, compare to SQGV (bioavailability)</p> <p><u>Tier 4:</u> in case of non-compliance, consider other factors controlling bioavailability (AVS, pore water concentration, speciation)</p> <p><u>Tier 5:</u> in case of values above guidelines, toxicity testing (e.g. multiple species, varying exposure pathways, acute and chronic endpoints such as mortality, reproduction, development, growth, avoidance) – if toxic, site is at high risk</p> <p><u>Tier 6:</u> in case on non-toxic, evaluate other LOE (bioaccumulation/biomagnification, benthic community structure), apply WoE ranking</p> <p>In specific cases, full WoE might be favourable to tiered assessment, e.g., for remediation of contaminated sediments, or the presence of unknown mixtures of contaminants at a site</p>	<pre> graph TD T1[Tier 1 assessment] -- PASS --> R[] T1 -- FAIL --> T2[Tier 2 assessment] T2 -- PASS --> R T2 -- FAIL --> T3[Tier 3 assessment] T3 -- PASS --> R T3 -- FAIL --> T4[Tier 4 assessment] T4 -- PASS --> R T4 -- FAIL --> T5[Tier 5 assessment] T5 -- PASS --> R T5 -- FAIL --> T6[Tier 6 (WoE) assessment] T6 -- PASS --> R T6 -- FAIL --> HR[] R --> LR[LOW RISK] HR --> HR_RISK[HIGH RISK] </pre>	WoE: scoring The toxicant concentrations measured from the <2 mm sediment fraction of a sediment sample should be compared with the sediment DGVs. Provide methods to determine sediment property-specific guideline values (such as Cu related to grain size and OC)
OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2009c) very similar to HELCOM	Tiered assessment, different LOE	<p>Dredged material suitable for disposal at sea?</p> <p><u>Tier 1:</u> Physical properties (grain size etc)</p> <p><u>Tier 2:</u> chemical composition, compare to Actions Levels (AL) – above AL2 not suitable for disposal, when concentrations between AL1 and AL2, conduct further investigations, below AL1: suitable for disposal</p> <p><u>Tier 3:</u> If the potential impacts of the dredged material cannot be adequately assessed on the basis of the chemical and physical characterisation (such as contaminant concentrations between AL1 and AL2), ecotoxicological and/or biological testing may be conducted, continue with toxic bioassays, biomarkers, micro- and mesocosm experiments</p>		Fraction <2 mm should be analysed less than 63 µm or 20 µm, additional to full grain size data, to anticipate the effects of contaminants adsorbed on sediment particles on deposit or filter feeders Tier 3 only infrequently used by contracting parties for decision-making

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs	Application and Remarks
UK (MMO 2015)	Tiered assessment, different LOE	<p>Assessment of dredged material</p> <p><u>Tier 1</u>: compare sediment chemical composition to Action Levels (AL)</p> <p><u>Tier 2</u>: if concentrations between AL1 and AL2, compare to local background</p> <p><u>Tier 3</u>: if concentrations between AL1 and AL2 and above background, or if slightly above AL2, conduct further LOE (ecological survey, bioassay, bioaccumulation)</p>	
United States (U.S. EPA 1991)	Tiered assessment, different LOE	<p>Assessment of dredged material – suitable for ocean disposal?</p> <p>The prediction of concentrations of dispersing dredged material in the water column in a spatial and temporal realm is conducted with numerical modelling – used to predict concentrations during and after initial mixing (4 hours after dumping)</p> <p><u>Tier 1</u>: information sufficient to make decision (may include physical, chemical, and biological data)? If yes, does material meet criteria for exclusion from further testing? (is material predominantly sand and similar to disposal site? Bioassays on the suspended particulate and solid phases show that limiting permissible concentrations not exceeded and liquid phase composition not exceeding WQC?)</p> <p><u>Tier 2</u>: if information not sufficient or indicates need for further assessments, proceed with evaluation of potential water column impact - determine chemical composition of elutriate (prepared as filtered elutriate of tested sediment with sediment-to-water ratio 1:4, stir 30 min, leave 1h) and check compliance of dissolved concentrations with WQC (concentrations do not exceed WQC beyond the boundaries of the disposal site at any time nor exceed the WQC anywhere in the marine environment 4 h after dumping), evaluation of benthic impacts (compare to SQG, if available)</p> <p><u>Tier 3</u>: acute toxicity testing (lethality) with elutriate containing the dissolved+ suspended particulate phase (WET testing), compliance threshold is defined as 0.01 of acute toxicity (usually, LC₅₀), to be met at the boundaries of the disposal site and after allowance for initial mixing (i.e., after 4h); chronic solid phase toxicity testing (toxicity threshold: mean mortality of any one species exposed to proposed dredged sediment does not exceed the mean mortality observed with reference sediments more than 10% (> 20% for amphipods); bioaccumulation</p> <p><u>Tier 4</u>: chronic toxicity tests for water column and/or benthos, case-specific evaluation criteria</p>	<p>Disposal of dredged materials</p> <p>Addresses both, impacts in the water column and impacts on benthic communities</p> <p>No SQGV used</p>

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs	Application and Remarks																																	
<p>Guidance for Performing Tests on Dredged Material Proposed for Ocean Disposal (USACE and USEPA 2016)</p>	<p>Simultaneous assessment of different LOE, decision matrix</p>	<p>Assessment of dredged material</p> <p>USACE: for permit from the New York District (NYD) of the United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) for dredging and placement of dredged material at the Historic Area Remediation Site (HARS) in the Atlantic Ocean</p> <p>When dredged material proposed for ocean placement does not meet the exclusionary criteria for further testing (such as predominantly sand, or composition very similar to proposed disposal site), further testing of the liquid, suspended particulate, and solid phases is required in a parallel assessment (assessment criteria must be met at the boundaries of the disposal site during initial mixing and anywhere after initial mixing):</p> <p>Liquid phase (prepared as elutriate of tested sediment with sediment-to-water ratio 1:4, stir 30 min, leave 1h, filter), determine chemical composition, conduct acute toxicity testing in case criteria are not available or synergistic effects are expected—see toxicity testing for suspended particulate phase; after allowance for initial mixing (i.e., after 4 hours), the limiting permissible concentrations should not exceed WQG or 0.01 of acute LC₅₀ (toxicity threshold)</p> <p>Suspended particulate phase (prepared as unfiltered elutriate of tested sediment with sediment-to-water ratio 1:4, see above): conduct acute toxicity testing of combined liquid+suspended solid phase; after allowance for initial mixing (i.e., after 4 hours), the limiting permissible concentrations should not exceed 0.01 of acute LC₅₀ toxicity (i.e., no significant undesirable effects will occur due to chronic toxicity)</p> <p>Solid phase: conduct chronic toxicity testing, bioaccumulation (no significant undesirable effects will occur due either to chronic toxicity or to bioaccumulation - mean mortality of any one species exposed to proposed dredged sediment does not exceed the mean mortality observed with reference sediments > 10% (> 20% for amphipods))</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="1216 308 1368 339">Liquid assessment (WQG, or tox. Testing)</th> <th data-bbox="1368 308 1543 339">Suspended particulates assessment (tox. Testing)</th> <th data-bbox="1543 308 1704 339">Solids assessment (tox. Testing, bioaccum.)</th> <th data-bbox="1704 308 1776 339">Decision</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 339 1368 371">v</td> <td data-bbox="1368 339 1543 371">v</td> <td data-bbox="1543 339 1704 371">v</td> <td data-bbox="1704 339 1776 371">v</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 371 1368 403">x</td> <td data-bbox="1368 371 1543 403">v</td> <td data-bbox="1543 371 1704 403">v</td> <td data-bbox="1704 371 1776 403">x</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 403 1368 435">x</td> <td data-bbox="1368 403 1543 435">x</td> <td data-bbox="1543 403 1704 435">v</td> <td data-bbox="1704 403 1776 435">x</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 435 1368 467">x</td> <td data-bbox="1368 435 1543 467">x</td> <td data-bbox="1543 435 1704 467">x</td> <td data-bbox="1704 435 1776 467">x</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 467 1368 499">v</td> <td data-bbox="1368 467 1543 499">x</td> <td data-bbox="1543 467 1704 499">x</td> <td data-bbox="1704 467 1776 499">x</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 499 1368 531">v</td> <td data-bbox="1368 499 1543 531">v</td> <td data-bbox="1543 499 1704 531">x</td> <td data-bbox="1704 499 1776 531">x</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1216 531 1368 563">x</td> <td data-bbox="1368 531 1543 563">v</td> <td data-bbox="1543 531 1704 563">x</td> <td data-bbox="1704 531 1776 563">x</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Liquid assessment (WQG, or tox. Testing)	Suspended particulates assessment (tox. Testing)	Solids assessment (tox. Testing, bioaccum.)	Decision	v	v	v	v	x	v	v	x	x	x	v	x	x	x	x	x	v	x	x	x	v	v	x	x	x	v	x	x	<p>Addresses both, impacts in the water column and impacts on benthic communities</p> <p>no SQGVs used</p>
Liquid assessment (WQG, or tox. Testing)	Suspended particulates assessment (tox. Testing)	Solids assessment (tox. Testing, bioaccum.)	Decision																																	
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<p>Australia (Australian Government 2009)</p>	<p>Tiered assessment, different LOE</p> <p>WoE as highest tier</p>	<p>Dredged material suitable for disposal at sea? Assessment of sediment quality</p> <p>criteria need to be met after allowance for initial mixing (i.e., after 4h), predicted dilution can be based on numerical modelling, calculations or on a dilution factor of 100</p> <p>Tier 1: review available information (exemptions from assessment, chemical and toxicity data), sufficient for decision? If not, proceed with Tier 2</p> <p>Tier 2a: compare chemical composition of dredge spoil (solid phase) with national sediment screening levels of likely contaminants (=SQG)</p> <p>Tier 2b: in case of non-compliance, or for contaminants without screening levels, compare data to background levels (80th percentile of dataset)</p>	<p>Risk assessment and approval of open-sea disposal of dredged sediments</p> <p>Addresses both, impacts in the water column and impacts on benthic communities</p>																																	

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs	Application and Remarks
		<p><u>Tier 3a</u>: in case values are higher than background, compare elutriate data to WQG (usually 95% protection, in case other LEP are valid this value would be higher or lower, respectively) after initial dilution (dilution 4h after dumping, either modelled, calculated, or 100 times)</p> <p><u>Tier 3b</u>: if below, proceed with bioavailability investigation (SEM-AVS, speciation, dilute acid extraction, pore water); if above WQC, but impacts could be mitigated (i.e., higher pre-dilution before disposal), proceed with bioavailability investigation as well</p> <p><u>Tier 4</u>: conduct sediment toxicity testing (whole sediment and/or pore water) in case contaminants of concern have been found to be bioavailable – compliance met when toxicity tests show less than a 20 per cent effect in the endpoint (use organisms with different exposure routes); bioaccumulation test if bioaccumulating substances are present above SQG-high values; if toxic, spoil not suitable for disposal</p> <p><u>Tier 5</u>: WoE, in selected cases</p> <p>In case sediment is suitable for disposal, the assessment of potential on the environment needs to be assessed</p>	
ANZG (ANZG 2018b)	Different LOE, tiered assessment with WoE at higher tier, or WoE directly, depending on application management Framework	<p>general framework for assessment of water quality to meet environmental objectives</p> <p>recommends measuring indicators from multiple lines of evidence across the pressure–stressor–ecosystem receptor (PSER) causal pathway. This will give greater weight (or certainty) to assessment conclusions and subsequent management decisions to meet the water/sediment quality objective</p> <p>Make early decisions about which lines of evidence to measure, to ensure adequate baseline data are available to properly detect and assess possible future effects</p> <p>Examples for application of WoE provided, inter alia, for assessing waste discharge, conducting a baseline study, implementing a broadscale monitoring program, or applying for a project development approval</p>	
ANZG (ANZG 2018k)	Tiered assessment, different LOE WoE at highest tier	<p>Assess compliance with waste discharge license</p> <p><u>Tier 1</u>: determine dissolved contaminant concentrations, in case of WQG exceedance outside the mixing zone, assess bioavailable fractions, compare again to WQC</p> <p><u>Tier 2</u>: in case of non-compliance, determine toxicity (e.g., DTA) and ecosystem health (biodiversity) to assess consequence of WQG exceedance</p> <p>To obtain more information, biomarkers and bioaccumulation could be determined</p>	WoE conclusion based on best expert judgement

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs	Application and Remarks
		Comply WoE	
Cockburn Sound (EPA-WA 2017)	Tiered assessment (narrative decision scheme)	<p>Environmental monitoring plan (water quality)</p> <p>According to ANZG environmental quality management framework (EQMF) Establishment of staged quality criteria: environmental quality guideline EQG (ANZG DGVs for metals and metalloids; additive toxicity of toxicant mixture), and different environmental quality standards EQS (such as for bioavailability, toxicity, bioaccumulation); criteria vary depending on anticipated level of protection Example of one possible decision path (others are possible, e.g. when bioaccumulation/bioaccumulation and toxicant mixtures are considered):</p> <p><u>Tier 1</u>: measure chemical composition and test against EQG <u>Tier 2</u>: if exceeded, compare to natural background – if exceeded, establish new background <u>Tier 3</u>: if Tier 1 EQG or background-based new EQG exceeded, determine bioavailability and check against EQS (95th percentile of bioavailable contaminant conc. in the test samples should not exceed WQG) <u>Tier 4a</u>: if exceeded, conduct DTA, test against DTA EQS (should not result in a statistically significant effect on lethal acute endpoints or of greater than 50% on sublethal chronic endpoints, for any species, compared to the reference/control water) <u>Tier 4b</u>: in case of an effluent discharge: if only 3 species (from 3 taxonomic groups) are tested, the dilution of effluent (as % effluent) at the boundary of a moderate protection zone should be greater than that represented by the lowest chronic EC₁₀ (i.e. the EC₁₀ for the most sensitive species) divided by a safety factor of 2 <u>Tier 5</u>: if exceeded, conduct direct biological and ecological measures and compare to EQS (The median of the distribution of measurements for any biological or ecological indicator should be within the 10th and 90th percentile of the natural range measured at suitable reference sites) If tier 5 EQS is exceeded, the overall EQS is triggered and management actions need to be implemented</p> <p>At several points in the scheme, low risk can be assigned Implementing management actions can also be triggered earlier in the decision scheme</p>	
Cockburn Sound (EPA-WA 2017)	Tiered assessment	<p>Environmental monitoring plan (sediment quality)</p> <p>According to ANZG environmental quality management framework (EQMF)</p>	

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs		Application and Remarks
	<p>(narrative decision scheme)</p>	<p>Establishment of staged quality criteria: environmental quality guideline EQG (ANZG ISQG for metals and metalloids), and different environmental quality standards EQS (such as for bioavailability, toxicity, bioaccumulation)</p> <p>Example of one possible decision path (others are possible, e.g. when bioaccumulation/bioaccumulation-prone elements are present):</p> <p><u>Tier 1</u>: test against EQG</p> <p><u>Tier 2</u>: if exceeded, check whether natural background is >EQG, if yes, determine new site-specific EQG based in background</p> <p><u>Tier 3</u>: if Tier 1 EQG or background-based new EQG exceeded, conduct bioavailable measures and compare to bioavailability EQS (bioavail. concentrations should not exceed EQG)</p> <p><u>Tier 4</u>: if bioavailable EQS exceeded, test pore water concentrations against pore water EQS (95th percentile of bioavailable contaminant conc. In pore water should not exceed WQG)</p> <p><u>Tier 5</u>: of pore water EQS exceeded, conduct toxicity testing and compare to toxicity EQS (should not result in a statistically significant effect on lethal acute endpoints or of greater than 50% on sublethal chronic endpoints for any species, compared to a matched reference sediment)</p> <p><u>Tier 6</u>: if toxicity EQS exceeded, conduct direct biological and ecological measures and compare to EQS (The median of the distribution of measurements for any biological or ecological indicator should be within the 10th and 90th percentile of the natural range measured at suitable reference sites)</p> <p>If tier 6 EQS is exceeded, the overall EQS is triggered and management actions need to be implemented</p> <p>At several points in the scheme, low risk can be assigned Implementing management actions can also be triggered earlier in the decision scheme</p>		
<p>(Piccardo et al. 2024)</p>	<p>multiple LOE, full WoE</p>	<p>Integrated ecological risk assessment of marine protected sites (soft-bottom habitats in the Northern Adriatic Sea)</p> <p>Simultaneous LOE assessment, weighted integration into synthetic WoE assessment quantitative WOE model SediquaSoft® used</p> <p>LOE: chemical characterization, ecotoxicological properties, and benthic community status, separate hazard quotient was derived for each LOE</p> <p>Classification of an overall risk</p>	<p>Levels of risk for adverse effects to the ecosystem, integrating outcomes of LOE-1-LOE-5</p>	

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs		Application and Remarks
<p>(d'Errico et al. 2021)</p>	<p>multiple LOE, full WoE</p>	<p>Monitoring the ecological risk of dredging activities</p> <p>integration of five LOE (chemicals in abiotic matrices, their bioavailability, biomarkers, bioassays, and benthic communities) through the quantitative WOE model Sediqualsoft®, validated in a case study for environmental risk assessment related to dredging activities of polluted sediments</p> <p>monitoring of the risks during the different stages of dredging and disposal activities in different parts of the investigated harbour, provides guidance for decision-making</p> <p>calculates hazard quotients for each LOE</p>	<p>See Piccardo et al., 2024</p>	
<p>OSPAR (Vethaak et al. 2017; Burgeot et al. 2022)</p>	<p>multiple LOE, integrated assessment</p>	<p>Assessment of environmental status in each of five compartments (Sediment, water, mussel, fish, and gastropods)</p> <p>integrating data on contaminants and biological effects (biomarkers, bioassays) from a test site (assessed against background assessment concentrations (BACs) and against environmental assessment concentrations (EACs) (or 3x BAC in case no EAC-like is available) and their analogous criteria for biological responses),</p> <p>for each analyzed parameter a specific colour is given: if below BAC (blue), between BAC and EAC (green), or above EAC (red)</p> <p>No weighing of evidence</p> <p>can be used for the purposes of an overall assessment, and it is proposed that a simple threshold figure (e.g. 95% < EAC) is used to determine whether or not overall "Good Environmental Status" for MSFD Descriptor 8 is met in this assessment</p>	<p>Integrated assessment at one site (integrating data on contaminants and biological effects from several compartments, y-axis: percentage)</p>	<p>shows the proportion of analyses that were at background (blue, <BAC) or elevated above background at either acceptable (green, >BAC) or unacceptable (red, >EAC) levels</p>
<p>Discharge permits for oil and gas activities gulf of Mexico (U.S. EPA 2024)</p>	<p>Mixing zone, toxicity testing</p>	<p>Assessment of risks from oil and gas activities to obtain a discharge permit</p> <p>Application of mixing zone, thresholds must be met at 100 m distance as thresholds, limiting permissible concentrations (or effluent limitations) defined, that must be met at the edge of the mixing zone: (1) the chronic NOEC for PW (derived from toxicity testing with a series of different PW dilutions, NOEC expressed as fraction of 100%) must be equal or higher that the predicted effluent concentration (PEC, referred to as critical dilution); (2) the acute LC₅₀ for drilling fluids must be equal or >3% (LC₅₀ derived from toxicity testing with a series of different dilutions of unfiltered drilling mud supernatant)</p>		
<p>UK Oil and gas RBA (BEIS 2020)</p>	<p>Mixing zone, tiered assessment, toxicity testing</p>	<p>RBA to the management of produced water discharges</p> <p>Considers a mixing zone</p> <p>predicted PW concentration (PEC, expressed as fraction of 100%) at 500 m distance must be equal or smaller compared to the PNEC of the PW (determined from whole effluent toxicity testing, expressed as fraction of 100%) - PEC/PNEC<1</p>		

Legal framework, guidance documents	Approach	Objective/Description/LOEs		Application and Remarks
		<p>If breached, the affected water volume must be calculated and an EIF is derived (see Norway RBA EIF), if EIF<10: low risk, if EIF>10: further management actions required (review of BAT, BEP)</p>		
<p>Norway (Offshore Norge 2022)</p>	<p>Mixing zone, WQC and toxicity testing</p>	<p>Used for risk assessment and monitoring purposes Environmental Impact Factor (EIF) is a risk-based management tool Uses the combined PNEC of individual substances, or the PNEC of the whole effluent together with numerical modelling of plume dispersal to calculate EIF An EIF of 1 represents a water volume of 100 m x 100 m x 10 m, where PNECs are not met; the larger the EIF, the larger is the affected water mass Used for risk assessment of PW and drilling mud discharges</p>		
<p>PNG Draft DSTD guidelines (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010)</p>	<p>Mixing zone</p>	<p>Concentrations of individual dissolved substances must meet WGC at the edge and outside the mixing zone</p>		
<p>Western Australia Guidelines for dredging and dredging disposal (EPA-WA 2021)</p>	<p>Benthic impact zones</p>	<p>Impact prediction and compliance monitoring of dredging and dredging disposal</p> <p>Benthic impact zones represent spatial zones at the seafloor that are affected by an anthropogenic activity (dredging or disposal of dredged material) that differ in the severity of impact on sensitive benthic habitats and the potential for recovery Typically, three zones are distinguished: high impact, moderate impact and influence Application of thresholds to define boundaries between zones of different impact strengths – these are based on a combination of different stressors (SPM, light, sedimentation) that were integrated with duration and frequency of the activities (for example, the outer boundary of ZOH (zone of high impact) for activities no longer than 10 d is defined as not more than 20 mg cm⁻² d⁻¹ and not more than 70 mg/L total suspended matter and not less than <0.1 daily light integral DLI) In addition, guideline values considering coral recovery provided, expressed as percentage mortality, recruitment reduction over a period of time For each boundary, tiered triggers could be defined to allow for early warning signals initiating management actions before the most stringent limit is reached</p>		

5.6.2 WEIGHT-OF-EVIDENCE

The Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach is an inferential process of collecting evidence, and evaluating and integrating them to reach a conclusion in an assessment of a particular problem (ECHA 2017; U.S. EPA 2016c). It is accepted that stronger inferences can be drawn on issues if multiple LOEs are available. The approach integrates data of multiple LOEs (such as chemical, biological, and ecological information), and can be applied in two different ways: to reach qualitative conclusions in an environmental assessment, or to establish a quantity, such as a benchmark or guideline value (U.S. EPA 2016c; ANZG 2018d; ECHA 2023). WoE methods for deriving quantities by weighing evidence are proposed in various legal instruments in Australia, the U.S., and Europe and fall into two basic approaches: (1) combine the quantitative evidence (such as arithmetic mean, geometric mean or a percentile of the dataset), or (2) choose the best quantitative evidence based on expert judgement. In both cases, the individual evidences could be weighed to indicate how influential they should be. A proposed application could be to derive site-specific guideline values where there is a need to ensure greater confidence in the final value (ANZG 2018k). Although not explicitly named as such, the EU guidance (CIS-WFD 2018) uses an integrated approach weighing evidence from different sources (EqP, toxicity testing, and field or mesocosm data) to derive an EQS.

In environmental assessments, WoE approaches are commonly applied to determine causes of observed effects, hazards posed by chemicals or other agents, the completeness of remediation, the risk from dredged sediments, and other environmental qualities (Suter et al. 2017; Linkov et al. 2009). U.S. EPA (2016c) has developed and adopted comprehensive WoE guidelines for ecological assessments. The underlying principle of WoE in the assessment of environmental quality is that none of the considered LOEs is *per se* conclusive to answer a management question (e.g., pose contaminated sediments a risk for adverse biological or ecological effects; (Chapman 2007). The first WOE approach used in environmental risk assessment was the **sediment quality triad**, using three different LOEs to compile evidence for hazard and exposure (sediment chemistry, toxicity testing and benthic community structure), for the assessment of pollution-induced sediment degradation (Chapman et al. 1987; Chapman 1990). Since then, WoE approaches were widely applied in environmental assessments and incorporated in legal frameworks addressing water and sediment quality (e.g., ANZG 2018b). In ANZG, WoE is the central platform for water/sediment quality assessments in the Water Quality Guidelines. Numerous analytical techniques exist for combining LOEs to reach conclusions concerning environmental qualities (methods described in detail in Suter et al. 2017, Linkov et al. 2009, U.S. EPA 2016c), ranging from qualitative (how do the evidence of different LOE support final assessment, involves best expert judgement) to semi-quantitative (scoring, rule-based), to fully quantitative. **Numerical scoring** is based on defined measurement responses for each LOE (such as exceedance of guideline values for sediment chemistry, elevated toxicity compared to controls, significant differences compared to controls for bioaccumulation, or reduced benthic diversity or abundance relative to controls for benthic community structures) and widely adopted in sediment quality assessment to reach a conclusion (Simpson et al. 2013b). The scores indicate a WoE assessment of the level of risk or impairment for each LOE, ranging from 'not significant' to 'adverse', and are brought together for the final overall assessment, which allows to rank the sediments according to the overall risk for adverse effects from sediment contamination. Fully **quantitative WOE** methods statistically derive risk probabilities from several LOEs. The use of formal decision-analytical tools (Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) and Bayesian methods to WoE were proposed (Linkov et al. 2009; Linkov et al. 2015). Another quantitative WoE approach was developed by Piva et al. (2011), allowing to derive an overall cumulative WOE level of risk (see below). The application of a WoE can be either part of a tiered assessment as last step in the hierarchy, or be conducted as single, comprehensive assessment. Further details and reviews on WoE approaches and frameworks for environmental quality assessments can be found in U.S. EPA (2016c), Suter et al. (2017), Weed (2005), ANZG (2018k), Linkov et al. (2009), and Regoli et al. (2019).

Examples for WoE applications incorporated in environmental assessments (tiered or not) are provided in **Table 5.6**; further examples are outlined in ANZG (addressing, for example, quality assessment of waste discharges, sediments requiring remediation, or baseline studies in the preparation of human activities).

Colour-coding the data presentation of a WoE assessment provides an easy visual indication of the **level of hazard or risk (Figure 5.3)**, and has recently been applied in various environmental quality and risk assessments using the quantitative WoE model Sediqualsoft®. Such hazard or risk meters provide stakeholders simple interpretation of complex data. Examples include the quality and risk assessment of dredging activities and offshore oil and gas production (d'Errico et al. 2021; Regoli et al. 2019; Manfra et al. 2021), the assessment of environmental hazards from natural hydrocarbons seepage (Benedetti et al. 2014) and of marine mine tailings deposit sites (Mestre et al. 2017), the assessment of chemical contamination in coastal waters (Lehtonen et al. 2019), and the assessment of environmental quality in marine protected areas and harbor areas (Piccardo et al. 2024; Bebianno et al. 2015). The quantitative WOE model integrates data for sediment chemistry, bioavailability, biomarkers, bioassays, and benthic communities and calculates, based on weighted quantitative evidence of the individual LOE, an overall cumulative WOE level of risk (Piva et al. 2011). Computed as probability of impairment by assigning the risk level to one of five classes of risk, the risk classification can be linked to possible management options. This is exemplified in the Italian law regulating the technical procedures, monitoring and assessments of all activities related to the movement, dislodgement, discharge, use and treatment of marine sediments (Ministerial Decree DM173/2016). In contrast to other national and international regulations and guidelines for the disposal of dredged materials that typically request a hierarchical assessment, Italy adopted a WoE approach for risk assessment. The approach is to be used to determine the quality class of dredged material and to direct associated management options, based on chemical analysis and ecotoxicological bioassay evidence.

Figure 5.3: Risk meter for levels of ecological risk, divided in 5 classes ranging from 'Absent' to 'Severe' that are associated with different management options, integrating chemical hazard, ecotoxicological effects, and the status of benthic assemblages. 'Severe' means that dredging material needs to be removed from the marine environment. Adapted from: Piccardo et al. (2024).

6. Thresholds and concepts for assessing risks and impacts of offshore industries

The development and implementation of thresholds as management tools for DSM activities can be informed by the respective knowledge on environmental impacts and on thresholds operational for risk assessments and monitoring of existing offshore industries, such as oil and gas production, dredging and disposal of dredging material, submarine mine tailings disposal (STD), and bottom trawling, utilizing. These offshore activities share similar sources of risk for adverse environmental impacts with proposed DSM activities. This includes the discharge of drilling muds and produced water during oil and gas exploration and production, habitat removal, formation of operational sediment plumes, enhanced sedimentation, and habitat change from dredging, dredging disposal, and bottom-trawling, and discharge of particle-rich mine tailings and hyper-sedimentation during STD. These offshore activities have been partly ongoing for decades, and related environmental studies involving laboratory testing, field monitoring, and numerical modeling formed a substantial knowledge base about the associated environmental risks and impacts. While results are usually not directly transferable to DSM settings because of very different prevailing environmental conditions in abyssal environments and different spatial and/or temporal footprints of activities, scientific evidence on ecosystem responses to similar pressures can still provide useful information for the development of thresholds for DSM activities.

Offshore activities within the EEZs must comply with numerous international and regional conventions such as UNCLOS, London Convention / London Protocol (LC/LP), OSPAR and legislation on the EU and national levels. UNCLOS confers extensive rights on coastal states to utilize living marine resources and other resources on the continental shelf under their jurisdiction, and combines these with a duty to protect and conserve the marine environment. While there are no dedicated specific international or national regulations in place for specific offshore activities, several legal instruments provide frameworks, recommendations and guidelines that address the environmental management thereof. The **disposal of dredged material** is primarily regulated by the London Convention of 1972 and its 1996 Protocol, which set guidelines for managing and chemically characterizing dredged material (IMO 1972, 1996). Countries usually implement their obligations under the London Protocol through national regulations, a relevant example is the Commonwealth Environment Protection (Sea Dumping) Act 1981 in Australia (Australian Government 2009). In addition, international treaties, like HELCOM and OSPAR, provide guidelines on dredging and dumping at sea (HELCOM 2020; OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024), and several countries established national assessment guidelines for dredging and disposal of dredged material as decision-making frameworks (Australian Government 2009; U.S. EPA 1991). These guidelines often use a tiered (hierarchical) assessment in a decision-making framework (see **CHAPTER 5.6.1**). Information collected in the initial tiers may be sufficient for making decisions, or more extensive evaluation at higher tiers may be needed when information is unclear. While the national dredging-related guidelines in the US and in Australia address both, the risks for adverse impacts of disposal at the seabed and in the water column, European guidelines typically only address the risks for adverse impacts at the seabed. International regulations or guidelines specifically applying to the **marine disposal of mine tailings** are not in place. Discharges of contaminants from pipelines and other land-based sources into the ocean fall outside of the regulatory scope of LC/LP, and hence, the LC/LP do not apply to submarine mine tailings disposal. Draft national guidelines for deep-sea tailings disposal (DSTD) exist in Papua New Guinea (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010). An example on how scientific evidence is used as basis for recommendations for regulatory thresholds and guidelines for the development of best available techniques for STD is provided in (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019), published as outcome of a research project by the Research Council of Norway and the mineral industry in Norway (KPN NYKOS). **Offshore oil and gas**

exploration and production within areas of national jurisdiction is governed by a range of principal legislations (as an example, the relevant regulations and guidelines for UK are provided here: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/oil-and-gas-offshore-environmental-legislation>). OSPAR developed a Recommendation for a Risk-Based Approach (RBA) to the management of produced water discharges from offshore installations, and guidelines in support of this recommendation (OSPAR Commission 2012b, 2012c), as policy instrument to assess the environmental risk posed by produced water discharges, resulting in the identification, prioritization and adoption of risk reducing measures.

Several countries have adopted/propose to adopt legislation permitting **deep-sea mining activities** in their EEZs, see also the listing available here: <https://www.isa.org.jm/national-legislation-database/>. In 2022, the Cook Islands granted a number of permits for deep-sea mining exploration activities within its EEZ. However, the country has not issued any extraction permits to date. In January 2024, the Norwegian Parliament approved deep-sea mining exploration in a designated part of its EEZ and allowed mining companies to apply for an exploitation permit, which will be approved by the Norwegian Parliament on a case-by-case basis. No exploitation permits have so far been issued and the decision is on hold since October 2024. Portugal is the only EU Member State in which specific legislation on deep-sea mining in areas under national jurisdiction has been adopted, albeit not at national level. A specific legal regime applying to deep-sea mining was adopted in the autonomous region of the Azores in 2012 in the form of Regional Legislative Decree (21/2012/A of 9 May 2012) which provides for the economic regulation of the geological resources in the adjacent seabed to the archipelago of the Azores. In 1980 the United States established the "Deep Seabed Hard Mineral Resources Act" (Chapter 26, Sections 1401-1473 of Title 30 "Mineral Lands and Mining" of the US Code, the general and permanent laws of the U.S.) as an interim legal regime until the international treaty (i.e. UNCLOS and subsequently the ISA Mining Code) would be adopted. Among others the Act does recognize the seabed mineral resources as common heritage of mankind, the freedom of the High Seas, the protection of the environment from damage caused by resource exploration or exploitation activities, and the establishment of an international revenue-sharing fund. As responsible authority the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) developed the respective regulations for exploration (Part 970 "Deep Seabed mining regulations for exploration licenses" of Title 15 of the Code of Federal Regulations) and exploitation (Part 971 "Deep seabed mining regulations for commercial recovery permits" of Title 15 of the Code of Federal Regulations).

Common to **all offshore activities** is the **presence of multiple stressors**, and it is not always possible to unequivocally identify cause-effect relationships. Individual stressors can act individually (the joint effect is an additive effect), or one stressor modifies the response of an organisms to another stressor (effect interaction), if the joint effect is larger than predicted, this is called synergism, if the joint effect is lower, it is called antagonism. In the dominance model, the joint effect equals that of the stressor/chemical with the highest individual effect. Additivity and antagonism are the most frequent interaction types in the presence of multiple stressors (Tekin et al. 2020) (see also **CHAPTER 5.1**). Approaches to assess impacts from known and unknown stressors from an effluent or contaminated sediment include whole material toxicity testing, such as direct toxicity assessments of effluents or sediment (see **CHAPTER 5.5**). This allows to assess effects of multiple stressors of known or unknown identity, and to account for cumulative effects. In the oil and gas industry, Environmental Impact Factors (EIF) were developed as a risk-based management tool to evaluate the environmental risks connected to discharges of produced water and drilling discharges and to evaluate the effects of alternative mitigation measures, and presently required by Norwegian authorities in reporting and planning of environmental management (Singsaas et al. 2008; Smit et al. 2006c). The EIF combines the risks from individual stressors in a single measure, and the methodology to calculate the EIF (Smit et al. 2011) follows the generic concept for environmental risk assessment as described by the US Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA 1998) and the European Commission (European Chemicals Bureau 2003). The EIF

represents a volume of recipient water containing concentrations of one or more substances to a level exceeding a threshold for ecotoxicological effects. Multiple stressors can also be addressed by combined thresholds for individual stressors to define a boundary between acceptable and unacceptable conditions, where none of the individual thresholds must be breached in order to ensure compliance. This is applied, for example, in the Guidelines for environmental impact assessments for dredging proposals in Western Australia (EPA-WA 2021). Another approach is the use of quality indices such as the WQIs that address several water quality parameters (review in (Uddin et al. 2021), applied to assess seawater quality around wind farms (Wei et al. 2024), though this approach is currently not very common as management tool for offshore activities.

Here, we provide an overview on major environmental risks and impacts arising from the different offshore activities, address some regulatory aspects and highlight management concepts of risk assessment and compliance monitoring that include the application of operational thresholds. In the Appendix, we compiled references for more detailed information on environmental impacts, both in form of peer-reviewed scientific publications (Table A6) and technical reports (Table A7). Examples for thresholds operational in the environmental management of offshore industries are provided in the Excel table accompanying the Appendix, including a comparison of different offshore activities.

6.1 Offshore Oil and Gas exploration and production

6.1.1 PRESSURES

Offshore oil and gas operations can be divided into three phases: exploration (includes seismic surveys and the drilling of exploratory and appraisal wells), production (includes drilling of production and injection wells, and the construction, placement and operation of infrastructure to produce oil and gas), and decommissioning (involves activities such as the plugging of wells and removal of infrastructure). Environmental impacts may occur throughout any of the three operational phases as well as after the abandonment, from *discharge of produced water, oil/gas, chemicals, drilling muds and cuttings*, physical impacts from the placement of installations and pipelines, noise and light, and atmospheric emissions, and from historical cuttings piles (Marappan et al. 2022).

6.1.1.1 Produced water

Produced water (PW) as a by-product of oil and/or gas production operations includes formation water extracted during oil and gas recovery, condensation water and re-produced injection water (seawater injected along with dissolved inorganic salts, dissolved and dispersed hydrocarbons, trace metals, naturally occurring radioactive substances, and production chemicals). As a major source of contaminants from oil and gas extraction activity, produced water separated from the oil and gas on the platform is typically treated in accordance with strict regulations before being discharged (e.g., OSPAR Commission 2021a). Over 75% of the PW generated offshore is discharged to sea following treatment to meet regulatory requirements (Azizov et al. 2021; Beyer et al. 2020).

6.1.1.2 Drilling waste discharge and cuttings piles

Drilling of both hydrocarbon and injection wells generates drill cuttings, which are fragments of crushed rock; the chemical and mineral composition of drill cuttings reflects that of the rock layers being penetrated by the bore hole. The drilling process includes use of drilling fluids (or muds), which carry the drill cuttings to the surface, serve to lubricate and cool the drill bit, and to control well pressures as part of safe drilling operations

(Marappan et al. 2022). Cuttings piles can arise from drilling operations where the drilled cuttings and associated drilling fluids are discharged at the location of the well and accumulate depending on the water current in the region. The major components of drill muds are a base fluid (typically fresh or salt water, as oil-based and synthetic muds were gradually phased out from mid-1990s for environmental reasons), a weighting material (typically barite, bentonite or ilmenite), and chemical additives to improve the performance of the fluid (Bakke et al. 2013). Clays or organic polymers are incorporated to create a homogenous fluid. The chemicals used as additives today are mostly classified as PLONOR (Pose Little or No Risk to the Environment) by OSPAR Commission (2012a). The dispersion of drilling waste (muds and cuttings) represent a risk for adverse effects, both in the water column (enhanced particle load=suspension) and at the seafloor (due to sedimentation), and is influenced by various factors, including particle size distribution and density, vertical and horizontal turbulence, current flows, and water depth. In deep water, the range of cuttings particle size results in a significant variation in settling velocity, and a consequent gradient in the size distribution of settled cuttings, with coarser material close to the discharge location and finer material very widely dispersed away from the location (Marappan et al. 2022). Historic cuttings piles represent an additional potential anthropogenic source of pollutants. Extensive discharges of oil-based cuttings were common in the past and led to the formation of large waste deposits of polluted drill cuttings beneath and around the oil and gas platforms (Tornero and Hanke 2016). There is a risk of leakage of contaminants from old cuttings piles (e.g. hydrocarbons and heavy metals) resulting from physical disturbance during platform activities, storms, or trawling as well as of generation of potentially toxic compounds resulting from biodegradation and other diagenetic processes over the years (Tornero and Hanke 2016; Breuer et al. 2004; Bakke et al. 2013).

6.1.2 IMPACTS

Drilling waste and produced water are considered as the major sources of stress on the environment during regular operations (Bakke et al., 2013). Especially within the OSPAR region, there is a wealth of information on offshore oil and gas activities-related environmental impacts, based on laboratory and mesocosm experiments and on field monitoring surveys of the oil and gas industry, (see reviews in Neff 2005; Neff et al. 2011; Bakke et al. 2013; Cordes et al. 2016; OSPAR Commission 2009a; OSPAR Commission 2019; Beyer et al. 2019; Beyer et al. 2020; Marappan et al. 2022; Nielsen et al. 2023; International Association of Oil & Gas Producers 2016; Offshore Norge 2024). An overview on the relevant literature and environmental reports is provided in Appendix tables A6 and A7. Discharges of drilling muds and PW can extend over several km, while the ecological impacts at the population and community levels on the seafloor are most commonly on the order of 200–300 m from the source (Cordes et al. 2016; Bakke et al. 2013). Overall, the magnitude of the impact is closely linked to the quantity and time of waste discharges.

6.1.2.1 Produced water

Toxic actions in the water column from PW constituents such as dispersed crude oil, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, alkylphenols, heavy metals, and other constituents are the major concern for adverse impacts from PW discharges (Beyer et al. 2020). Several of the metals found in PW have a high toxicity to aquatic organisms and some have a potential for bioaccumulation. Information on PW ecotoxicity is mainly based on field monitoring surveys (typically with caged organisms such as blue mussels or wild fish) and laboratory experiments (e.g., Nielsen et al. 2023; Beyer et al. 2020).

Toxicity testing with PW samples from different installations showed that the majority of EC₅₀ values are smaller than 20% of PW (and as low as 0.02%) and typically range between 1 and 20% (see reviews in Nielsen et al. 2023; Karman and Smit 2019; Parkerton et al. 2018). The results of the whole effluent toxicity (WET) testing are expressed in terms of produced water dilution that corresponds to a given degree of effect (de

Vries et al. 2022). This testing approach considers the toxicity of PW as a whole and does not distinguish between individual substances. While monitoring surveys find detectable exposures in caged mussel and fish up to several km downstream from PW outfalls, most laboratory and field studies of PW impact assessments on the Norwegian Continental Shelf show limited *acute* toxic effects on pelagic organisms at PW dilution of <1000-times (e.g., Beyer et al. 2020; Marappan et al. 2022; Brooks et al. 2011), corresponding roughly to a distance of less than 1000 m from the discharge point (Neff 2002). Significant acute effects on water column organisms seem to be limited to the first 100 m of the diluting PW plume (Beyer et al., 2020). Effects at dilutions >1000 are observed, however, after weeks of exposure (Marappan et al. 2022), showing that the exposure time plays an important role. Results from regular monitoring programs within the water column of the Norwegian sector of the North Sea concluded that biological effects from exposure to PW in the North Sea ecosystem is mainly related to organic constituents in the PW (Brooks et al. 2023) and not from the metals present.

6.1.2.2 Drilling waste discharges

Discharged drilling waste may affect pelagic, demersal and benthic fauna both during dispersal in the water column (elevated suspended particulate matter and turbidity) and after sedimentation (burial, sediment grain-size changes, organic matter enrichment causing oxygen depletion and changes in nutrient fluxes, toxicity) (Bakke et al. 2013). Sessile fauna, for example corals and sponges, and early life stages are especially sensitive to exposure. A comprehensive review on potential environmental impacts of drill cuttings discharge and from disturbance of historic cuttings piles provided in OSPAR Commission 2019). For coral communities, Offshore Norge (2024) summarizes main sources identified as a possible threat during drilling operations, its potential effects, potential influence areas and applicable methods for documenting the impact/influence.

Suspended drilling waste discharge could affect water column organisms, sponges, corals and other sessile, filter-feeding fauna exposed to the discharging plume in the water column and close to the seafloor. Damage of feeding and respiratory organs can cause metabolic and oxidative stress, and DNA damage, and affect growth, reproduction and survival rates (e.g., Bechmann et al. 2006; Bakke et al. 2013). While studies indicate that the main effect mechanism is physical and metal bioavailability is low, chemical toxicity cannot be ruled out (Neff 2005; Bakke et al. 2013). No standardized tests are available to study the effects of suspended particles in the laboratory or in mesocosm experiments. Differences in experimental set-ups, undocumented physical properties of the tested material (such as WBM, barite, drill cuttings), the type of exposed taxa and of observed endpoints and variations in how toxicity data are reported (e.g., as EC₅₀, LC₅₀ or as LOEC; effect size is often only poorly constrained) makes it difficult to compare numerical effects concentrations between different studies. A comprehensive study on sublethal and lethal effects of drilling mud discharges containing barite on adult pelagic organisms (fish) and filter feeding bivalves reported lowest effects concentrations (LOEC) of 0.5 mg L⁻¹ and significant responses in taxa above 2 mg/L (Bechmann et al. 2006). Such concentration levels are typically restricted to a radius of less than 1-2 km in the water masses (Neff 2005). Based on published EC₅₀ values of several taxonomic groups computed as species sensitivity distribution (SSD, see **CHAPTER 5.1.1.2**), Smit et al. (2006a) determined hazardous concentrations for 5% of species (HC5) for barite of 20 mg/L and for WBM of 80 mg/L (not to be mistaken with the PNECs of 0.2 mg/l and 0.8 mg/l for these substances, respectively, that were derived by applying an additional assessment factor of 100 to the HC5). The lowest reported LOEC values were 0.5 mg/L and 10 mg/L, respectively (for scallops, Cranford et al. 1999). Lower effects concentrations of barite compared to WBM material (which usually also contains barite) indicate that there may be other effects factors than just physical stress from the particles controlling the effects. Metal impurities in barite that might lead to toxic effects, grain size and shape may be effects-modifying factors. Offshore Norge (2024) summarized results on effects from WBM suspensions in sponges, corals, fish, larvae and eggs and concluded, based on these findings, that there is overall a risk for long-term effects above ~10-20 mg/L. The early life stages of corals and many other taxa may be very sensitive to natural and

anthropogenic suspended sediments (Jones et al. 2015), which can clog feeding and swimming structures and hence impact reproduction rates and connectivity (Järnegren et al. 2020). Studies with mussel larvae and embryos by Bechmann et al. (2006) suggest that exposure to suspended drilling mud at concentrations of 4 mg/L can have important ecological consequences. Järnegren et al. (2020) studied the effects of a range of bentonite, barite and drill cuttings concentrations on coral larvae and determined effects concentrations and lethal concentrations as well as recovery. The sensitivity of the larvae varied with age, with younger larvae significantly more susceptible to lower concentrations of drill cuttings than older larvae. Effects are most severe in the experiments with bentonite clay, related to the coagulation tendency of this material. Effects were observed at concentrations >18 mg/L bentonite and >55 mg/L barite in suspension, and corresponding EC₅₀ values derived in this study are 10 and 20 mg/L, respectively. The corresponding EC₁₀ value for barite is 3 mg/L.

Edge et al. (2016) reported sub lethal effects of WBM on sponges and concluded that observed cellular toxicity may have been caused by an increase in exposure to the clearly bioavailable metal contaminants as well as the physiological stress associated with the barite particles.

The *deposition of drilling waste discharges* at the seafloor has been shown to cause changes in species richness, abundance, biomass, and diversity of benthic macro- and megafauna communities (e.g. Neff 2005; Jones et al. 2012; Schaanning et al. 2008; Hess et al. 2013; Trannum et al. 2010; Trannum et al. 2011; see reviews in Bakke et al. 2013; IOGP 2021; Offshore Norge 2024). Water-based muds (WBM) are generally regarded to be less toxic than oil-based fluids, with metal toxicity of WBM associated with cuttings discharge having generally been deemed to be negligible (Neff 2005; International Association of Oil & Gas Producers 2016). Toxic effects after sedimentation, when it occurs, is probably rather caused by sulfide and ammonia byproducts of organic enrichment. WBM cuttings deposits were found to affect the benthos at burial depths above 3 mm (Trannum et al. 2010, Trannum et al. 2011; Schaanning et al. 2008; Bakke et al. 1989; see also references in Offshore Norge 2024), which is generally typical for conditions within 250 m from a drilling waste discharge point. Conditions simulated by Barlow and Kingston (2001), with repeated sedimentation on filter feeding bivalves showed effects at burial depths as low as 1 mm, a layer thickness corresponding to an exposure up to 500 m from a drilling site. Trannum (2017) showed reduced sediment reworking activity of brittle stars and bivalves when a layer of 2.5 mm drill cuttings was added, compared to a similar thickness of added natural sediment. Reduced bioturbation may result from a toxic response reducing the capacity of the organism to mix the upper sediment. Using a Species Sensitivity Distribution (SSD) based on published studies with soft-bottom organisms, Smit et al. (2008b) derived a HC5 value of 6.5 mm for burial (i.e., max. 5% of species affected). There are, however, indications that this burial depth is not protective for cold-water corals (Larsson and Purser 2011). As grain size distribution and organic matter content of the sediment strongly influence the resulting damage to coral from burial, the authors suggested to include these modifying factors when determining thresholds for WBM burial. Field observations on disturbance and recovery patterns show significant adverse effects caused by physical smothering and burial on benthic communities, especially of sessile organisms, within 40 to 100 m of drilling sites (Jones et al. 2012; International Association of Oil & Gas Producers 2016; see references in Offshore Norge 2024), which is generally corresponding to deposition thicknesses above 10 mm. Benthic foraminiferal responses to WBM and natural sediment burial demonstrate that a sediment layer of about 2.4 cm thickness severely limits the migration of benthic foraminifera and represent a physical barrier for these organisms independent of the type of burial material (Hess et al. 2013), with negative effects on the benthic foraminiferal abundance and species richness. The foraminiferal assemblage composition responded differently to the two materials added. For the macrofauna community from the same experiment that only responded to WBM and not to natural sediment of the same thickness (Trannum et al. 2010), the drill cuttings clearly represent an additional stress factor to physical smothering. The significant reduction in abundance and diversity of the macrofauna with increasing thickness of the WB layer was likely related to particle

properties like sharpness and stickiness, starvation due to low nutrient content, or toxicity amplifying the physical impacts from burial itself.

6.1.3 OPERATIONAL THRESHOLDS, CONCEPTS OF RISK ASSESSMENTS AND MONITORING

A detailed review of the environmental management of offshore oil and gas activities and national regulations applying to offshore discharges is beyond the scope of this report. We here focus on some relevant aspects regarding operational thresholds and other management tools used in risk-based assessments and monitoring and provide examples of national or regional regulatory management strategies for offshore oil and gas activities.

Different types of thresholds are operational for the environmental management of offshore oil and gas activities. This includes generic thresholds for individual dissolved substances, as they are typically provided in regulatory frameworks for environmental water quality. In addition, generic thresholds specifically addressing pressures from oil and gas waste discharge and deposition (PW, drilling waste) have been developed, and also site-specific thresholds for whole effluents are in use (see also summary in **CHAPTER 6.4**) that require direct toxicity assessments.

Management thresholds *for risk assessment and compliance monitoring* were developed for example for suspended matter concentrations in drilling discharge, burial, oxygen depletion, and contaminant concentrations (Smit et al. 2006b; Smit et al. 2008a; Smit et al. 2006a); Offshore Norge 2024; OSPAR Commission 2014). Smit et al. (2006a; 2008a) derived chronic PNECs for suspended barite (0.2 mg/L) and WBM (0.8 mg/L) based on SSD-derived HC5 values and an assessment factor of 100. Another threshold has been developed for natural sediment burial (Smit et al. 2008a), with the PNEC value set equivalent to the SSD-derived HC5 value (6.3 mm). These thresholds are used by oil companies on the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NCS) in the risk assessment of drilling discharges. Based on studies for both benthic corals and sponges expected on the NCS, Offshore Norge (2024) proposed operational 'thresholds' for deposited material (such as 3 mm as threshold for minor effects) and suspended solids (such as 10 mg/L) in a spatial and temporal context. However, these "thresholds" represent the tolerance thresholds of exposure studies or monitoring surveys with often poorly constrained effects sizes, while the derivation of regulatory thresholds such as Predicted No Effects Concentrations (PNECs) typically requires to account for uncertainties from type and quality of data, lab to field extrapolation etc. (see **CHAPTER 5** on approaches, ECHA 2008b; Warne et al. 2018), often though the application of assessment factors. For PW, the OSPAR Agreement 2014-05 provides a list of the naturally occurring substances including metals usually being analyzed in PW, along with established PNECs (OSPAR Commission 2014).

Australia and Europe have adopted risk-based approaches (RBAs) to manage and regulate PW discharge typically through a range of operational control measures, including inline monitoring, chemical characterization, whole effluent toxicity (WET), dispersion modeling, and periodic water quality, sediment, and benthic habitat surveys of the marine environment (Binet et al. 2024). PNECs of PW are compared with predicted environmental concentrations (PECs) of PW to determine the environmental risk of the PW discharge.

6.1.3.1 OSPAR maritime region – a risk-based approach for the management of oil and gas discharges

In 2012, OSPAR adopted a **risk-based approach (RBA)** to the management of produced water (PW) discharges in the OSPAR Maritime Area in the North Atlantic (OSPAR Commission 2012c), which is applied by oil and gas

operators as part of their risk management systems. The Recommendation includes requirements to perform risk assessments on discharge of PW, and that best available measures shall be selected in order to reduce risk, and is supported by guidelines providing general guidance for Contracting Parties (OSPAR Commission 2012b). Following the concept of environmental risk assessment (ECHA 2008b), the environmental risk of discharges of PW should be evaluated by comparing the results from an exposure assessment (which assesses the predicted exposure concentration (PEC) in the receiving environment) to the results from a hazard assessment (which assesses the predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC). If the risk is not considered to be acceptable, appropriate measures will be required to be implemented by industry to avoid or minimize the risk. The key rationale for using RBA in PW management is to focus mitigation actions on discharges and substances that represent the greatest risk to the environment.

The hazard assessment estimating **PW ecotoxicity** can be conducted **on whole effluent or an individual substance level**, using either data from whole-effluent toxicity (WET) tests, or using the composition derived from produced water chemical characterization. The Member states can decide which approach to implement in national regulations. The **WET approach** involves toxicity testing on different trophic levels (e.g., bacteria, algae, crustaceans) carried out at different levels of dilution of the PW, and the lowest effective concentration (usually EC₅₀) value is divided by an assessment factor (AF, see **CHAPTER 5.1.1.1**) to calculate the PNEC. In this regard, the PNEC value is given as a fraction of the discharged PW. The AF typically accounts for uncertainties in the data, such as extrapolating from acute to chronic exposure and from laboratory to field conditions. Where test results (EC₅₀) for three test species from three trophic levels are available (bacteria, algae, crustacea), an assessment factor of 1,000 should be applied (OSPAR Commission 2012b; BEIS 2020). Alternatively, an SSD approach (see **CHAPTER 5.1.1.2**) is recommended to derive toxicity thresholds, when effects data (NOEC or EC₁₀) for at least 5 species from at least 4 taxonomic groups are available (IOGP 2020). The **substance-based approach** involves using the concentration of PW constituents and comparing these concentrations to established toxicity thresholds (such as those provided by (OSPAR Commission 2014). To derive a single risk indicator that represents the overall risk of the PW based on individual substance PEC/PNECs, several methods are available, ranging from straightforward summation of the PEC/PNEC ratios (assumes additivity of the individual aquatic ecotoxicity of each chemical compound found in the PW sample) to more comprehensive methods (BEIS 2020). Comparison of the WET and substance-based approaches for several PW sources is provided in de Vries et al. (2022), Parkerton et al. (2018), and Nielsen et al. (2023), pointing to advantages and disadvantages of the two approaches (see also Smit et al. 2024). The substance-based approach suffers from the potential presence of unknown components in the PW while for the WET approach, it was pointed out that when limited acute toxicity testing was used it would not capture chronic effects over longer time scales.

OSPAR Member states are required to implement the RBA Recommendation into national regulations, which has been completed e.g. by Norway (implemented in Section 60 of the Activities Regulations; Norwegian Ocean Industry Authority 2023), by the Netherlands (de Vries and Tamis 2014), and UK (BEIS 2020). In 2020, the International Association of Oil & Gas Producers published an industry-driven guidance document for RBA of produced water discharges (IOGP 2020; Smit et al. 2024) aiming for a broader understanding and consistent application of produced water RBAs globally. This new guidance includes a tiered assessment framework to address the risk of PW discharge, allowing to scale the assessment efforts to a specific scenario aiming for a broader understanding and consistent application of PW of produced water RBA techniques globally (Smit et al. 2024). If lower tiers indicate high risk, additional data is obtained and a more detailed assessment is made at the next tier. The proposed framework allows to refine higher tier assessments through the application of species sensitivity distributions and the inclusion of exposure time to avoid conservative assessment factors. This enables assessments to better approximate observations from field verification, included as a final tier to determine the level of discernible effects (Smit et al. 2024).

During the past decades, a number of numerical models have been developed to evaluate the potential fates and effects of discharged PW and drilling waste on the water column and at the seafloor. A comparison of different numerical risk assessment tools for produced water with different complexity is provided in de Vries and Karman (2009). Computer-modelling tools such as DREAM (Dose-related Risk and Effect Assessment Model) (Reed and Rye, 2011) implement PNECs for example for PW substances, whole PW effluents or for drilling waste discharge-related sedimentation to derive PEC/PNEC ratios to assess the potential risk of exposure to the discharges in the water column and at the seafloor. The **Environmental Impact Factor (EIF)** methodology (Johnsen et al. 2000; Reed and Rye 2011) as an indicator for environmental risk was developed along with DREAM by the oil and gas companies active on the Norwegian shelf (Smit et al. 2003). It combines the PEC/PNEC ratios for individual substances in a single unit of measure for the total risk of the produced water and accounts for the volume of discharge. A simple additive function is typically applied for this calculation and potential synergism and antagonism caused by the mixture is not taken into account. The EIF is the volume of recipient water containing concentrations of one or more substances to a level exceeding a generic threshold for ecotoxicological effects (i.e., $PEC/PNEC > 1$), divided by a unit volume of recipient water ($100 \times 100 \times 10 \text{ m}^3$; Offshore Norge 2022; Johnsen et al. 2000). EIF calculations have been used to identify discharges with the highest risk to prioritize where mitigation efforts are most needed (Rye et al. 2004; Singsaas et al. 2008). Components that contribute the most to the EIF can then be targeted for reduction or substitution, thus reducing the overall environmental risk of the PW discharge (Smit et al. 2011). While the EIF methodology provides an indication of the risk or probability of impact to occur in the marine environment, no direct links exist between the value of the EIF and the actual level of harm to the environment. Since 2002, DREAM/EIF is being used by all operators on the Norwegian Continental Shelf for produced water discharges. The EIF concept has also been developed for drilling discharges (EIF-DD), considering both stressors in the water column and in the sediment (Smit et al. 2006c; Smit et al. 2008b). The EIF-DD for the water column contains toxic component concentrations and suspended particle concentrations as stressors, while the sediment contains toxic components concentrations, oxygen depletion, changes in grain size distribution and coverage by sedimentation as stressors. PNECs have been derived for the non-toxic stressors (Smit et al. 2008b; Durgut et al. 2015). Similar to the EIF for PW, 1 EIF equates to $100 \times 100 \times 10 \text{ m}^3$ in the water column and to $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ on the seafloor (i.e. $100 \text{ EIF} = 1 \text{ km}^2$).

The definition of the **acceptable spatial extent** of the zone where the risk does not need to be adequately controlled generally follows the concept of mixing zones (see **CHAPTER 6.4.1**). The mixing zone for offshore oil and gas installation discharges can be expressed either as a fixed **distance**, a site-specific distance or as a **volume of water** beyond that a threshold should not be exceeded. The OSPAR RBA Recommendation states that "risk should be considered to be adequately controlled if the exposure level (PEC) does not exceed the PNEC outside a column of water surrounding the installation, the radius of which is defined by a distance from the installation specified by the individual OSPAR member state, or outside the volume of water directly impacted by the discharge that is specified by the individual OSPAR member state" (OSPAR Commission 2012c). The volume of water directly impacted by the discharge can be determined by hydrographic modelling of dispersion of the discharge. In case the risks are not adequately (i.e., the exposure level exceeds the PNEC), management actions including the application of BAT and BEP and implementation of site-specific actions should be initiated to reduce the risks (OSPAR guidelines 2012). Dutch and UK authorities consider the risk to be adequately controlled when the PEC beyond 500 m from the discharge point is not exceeding the PNEC derived from WET testing (BEIS 2020; de Vries and Tamis 2014). More specifically, the UK RBA approach recommends to calculate a WET PEC/PNEC at 500 m using either a generic or an average dilution factor. Only if this fails (i.e., $PEC/PNEC > 1$), more complex approaches to assess the risk follow, using dispersion modelling and substance-level PEC/PNEC ratios (BEIS 2020). In Norway, risk assessments should first be conducted at substance level. All operators discharging produced water have to perform and report substance-based risk assessments, resulting in calculated field specific EIFs (OSPAR Commission 2023b). It is important to note, that

EIFs are usually not used as operational thresholds, but mainly for ranking purposes, as it indicates the size of the affected water volume and discriminates between the various substances contributing to the risk. In Norway, the responsibility to define the acceptable spatial extent in the water column or at the seafloor where the risk does not need to be adequately controlled remains with the contractor. While an earlier OSPAR report on the assessment of the discharges, spills and emissions from offshore installations on the Norwegian Continental Shelf in 2009-2013 (OSPAR Commission 2015) states that installations with an EIF exceeding 10 are to perform whole effluent testing (WET) of the produced water from 2018 onwards, this requirement disappeared in the report for the period of 2016-2020 (OSPAR Commission 2023b). It remains unclear, below which EIF value the risk would be assessed as adequately controlled. In the UK RBA implementation, a WET-based $EIF \leq 10$ is considered low risk (BEIS 2020). If the WET-EIF is higher, a substance-based risk assessment that helps gaining insight into the most important contributors to the risk is required to inform decisions on risk mitigation measures. Similarly, in Denmark the risk is adequately controlled where the EIF is below 10 (OSPAR Commission 2024).

Karman and Smit (2019) developed an early risk screening method that can be used to ensure that efforts are directed toward installations with a high likelihood that risk be not adequately controlled. If the discharge volume is less than a specific amount, the likelihood that the risk is adequately controlled (using the risk criterion that WET PEC/PNEC should not exceed 1 beyond 500 m distance) is >99%.

6.1.3.2 Australia

In Australia oil and gas operators are required to demonstrate that environmental impacts of their activity are managed to levels that are as low as reasonably practicable, for example, through risk assessments comparing predicted no-effect concentrations (PNECs) with predicted environmental concentrations (PECs) of PW (Binet et al. 2024). PNECs in PW can either relate to individual substances, in which case the ANZG water quality criteria (DGVs) can be used as generic thresholds, or they can be determined for the whole effluent through direct toxicity testing in different PW dilutions (WET, **CHAPTER 5.5**). The methods used to derive a PNEC from PW WET testing data in form of a non-toxic (safe) dilution varies considerably and has also been a function of the number of species used in the WET testing program (Binet et al. 2024). PNECs for PW are typically derived using the assessment factor (AF) approach, whereby an AF between 10 and 1000 is applied to the lowest NOEC or EC_{50} (see **CHAPTER 5.1.1.1**). If, however, the minimum requirements based on the number of species, types of species, and number of representative taxonomic groups have been met, species sensitivity distributions (SSDs) may be used to derive PW PNECs in form of minimum dilutions of PW required to protect a nominated percentage of species (e.g., 95%, 99%) in the receiving environment (Belanger et al. 2017; Binet et al. 2024). The SSD approach to WET toxicity testing is increasingly used by Australian oil and gas operators to derive PNECs for PW discharge risk assessments (e.g., ENI Australia 2017; Woodside 2018).

Oil and gas operators in Australia apply the concept of mixing zones for the environmental management of produced water. In Australia, wastewater discharges into waterways, and any associated mixing zones are regulated through inter alia, environment protection approvals (EPAs) and licenses (EPLs) issued under the Waste Management and Pollution Control Act. Australian states have developed guidelines for industries proposing a mixing zone as part of a project undergoing environmental impact assessments or seeking to apply for an EPA or EPL (e.g., NT EPA 2013), with reference to the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality 2000 (ANZECC 2000). Acute water quality criteria should be achieved at the edge of the area where initial mixing occurs (near-field mixing zone), and chronic effects criteria must be met at the boundary and outside of the far-field mixing zone.

The current best practice approach for managing PW discharge in Australia is using SSD-derived PCx values to set targets for required dilution of PW within proposed mixing zone boundaries. The boundary sizes vary

between platforms and are determined based on dispersion modeling and PW discharge rates. WET testing using sublethal endpoints was undertaken with PW of the Blacktip Project, Northern Territory, Australia and the results were used to derive SSD-based PNEC values and associated dilution factors required within a PW mixing zone. To achieve the chronic 99% level of species protection in accordance with the ANZECC/ARMCANZ (2000) marine water quality guidelines, minimum safe dilution factors of up to 263 are required. Direct toxicity assessments are preferred over applying DGVs for individual substances to derive the relevant concentrations for a particular level of species protection (ANZECC). Hence, even though higher dilutions are calculated from ANZECC toxicant trigger values for individual substances and pH, the WET-derived dilution is adopted as the most reliable minimum requirement at the mixing zone edge to meet the 99% level of species protection value. The Blacktip operator Eni proposed a circular mixing zone for the PW discharge with a horizontal distance of 50 m from the diffusers as part of its EPL, in accordance with the NT EPA Guidelines on Mixing Zones and based on PW sampling and analysis undertaken since commencement of production and dispersion modelling. The Blacktip annual monitoring report from 2022 shows compliance with this 50 m mixing zone and that the ANZECC water quality guideline values for 99% species protection are being met at the mixing zone boundary ($PEC/PNEC \leq 1$).

Applying the SSD methodology on the results of direct toxicity assessment with PW from the Goodwyn Alpha petroleum project using sublethal chronic endpoints, the dilution required to protect 99% of species is calculated and used to model the maximum distance of 1200 m (i.e., the boundary of the mixing zone) at which the 99% PNEC is achieved (Woodside 2018). For the Ichthys Gas Field in Western Australia, the lowest NOEC of acute WET toxicity testing was used as minimum dilution of produced water condensate to not be acutely toxic (158), which corresponds to a near-field mixing zone boundary in about 60 m distance from discharge (Asia-Pacific Applied Science Associates 2009).

Thresholds are also used in Monitoring and Management Frameworks for oil and gas projects. As described for example in Woodside (2018), monitoring changes in water quality and sediment quality as well as investigating potential toxicity via WET testing and implementing management to maintain acceptable levels of changes is standard industry practice in Australian waters. A number of trigger values for each indicator have been defined and are monitored during operations to detect changes.

6.1.3.3 United States

In the United States, point source discharges are regulated by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) through discharge permits, under Section 402(a) of the Clean Water Act (CWA). The permit system includes limits based on substance concentrations, but also considers toxicity, bioaccumulation, dilution and discharge rate. For PW discharges in the US Gulf of Mexico, the Final NPDES General Permit for Oil and Gas Extraction in the Gulf of Mexico (U.S. EPA 2024) defines environmental limitations for PW and drilling waste discharge. Produced water discharges must meet limiting permissible concentrations (LPC) at the edge of a 100-meter mixing zone. The LPC is defined as the No Observed Effect Concentration (NOEC) of the PW (expressed as percentage of 100% PW, which corresponds to dilution factor) and is based on 7-day chronic toxicity tests of sensitive species exposed to PW in different dilutions. In other words, the predicted site-specific PW concentration at 100 m distance must be less than the PW NOEC. Such whole effluent-LPCs are less conservative compared to the EU whole effluent-PNECs, where, depending on the effects size derived from toxicity testing (e.g., EC_{50} , EC_{10} or NOEC), an additional assessment factor between 10 and 1000 applies to the derived toxicity value. For example, if NOEC values are available the AF is 10, i.e., the PNEC is 10x more conservative compared to the US LPC. However, meeting the threshold of $PEC/PNEC < 1$ in Europe is required at a distance beyond 500 m (e.g., UK), in contrast to meeting the threshold at 100 m distance in the Gulf of Mexico. Other effluent limitations to be met at 100 m distance include thresholds for mercury and cadmium in barite added to drilling fluids (1.0 mg/kg and 3.0 mg/kg, respectively). Drilling fluids and cuttings are

supposed to meet both a daily minimum and a monthly average minimum effluent toxicity limitation of 3.0 percent by volume, which means that the acute LC₅₀ of a drilling mud, expressed as fraction of 100%, must be 3% or larger for a permitted discharge. The 96-hour LC₅₀ is derived from toxicity testing of the supernatant of the drilling mud, conducted according to the drilling fluid toxicity test guidelines (Appendix 2 to subpart A of 40 CFR Part 435) using serial dilutions of a suspended drilling mud sample (decant of a 1:10 mixture of mud and seawater after 1h). Drilling fluids sediment toxicity (i.e., the toxicity of the drilling mud material settled after 1h) is to be determined according to the EPA 'Standard Guide for conducting 10-day Static Sediment Toxicity Tests with Marine and Estuarine Amphipods'.

6.1.3.4 Monitoring – the Norwegian case

In addition to risk assessment, thresholds are also applied in monitoring plans. Monitoring may include chemical analysis of seawater and chemical and biological effect monitoring (e.g., biomarkers, bioaccumulation) in biota collected from the vicinity of offshore installations. OSPAR and national guidelines for the monitoring of offshore oil and gas activities provide advice for field monitoring surveys of the water column and at the seafloor (e.g., OSPAR Commission 2017b; NEA 2015, rev. in 2021). As Norway did not develop a dedicated licensing regime for maritime activities, the responsibility of licensing is on the relevant authorities in each sector. Permits for any activities that may cause pollution are issued according to the pollution control act. For oil and gas exploration and production on the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NCS) the discharge permits are issued by the Norwegian Environmental Agency (NEA). Companies operating on the Norwegian continental shelf are obliged to carry out environmental monitoring in order to obtain information on the actual and potential environmental impacts of their activities and to provide authorities with a better basis for regulating discharges and emissions. The specific requirements relating to environmental monitoring of the water column and the benthic habitat in connection with offshore oil and gas activities are set out in the Activities Regulations relating to conducting petroleum activities. Guidelines for environmental monitoring of petroleum activities on the Norwegian continental shelf (NEA 2015, rev. in 2021) provide more detailed requirements that supplement the more general regulatory requirements, and there is also the Handbook on Species and Habitat of Environmental Concern (Offshore Norge 2024) that was prepared in support of these guidelines. Water column monitoring surveys are to be conducted every 3 years, investigating the potential biological effects of offshore oil and gas activity on the biota living within the water column of the Norwegian sector of the North Sea. Monitoring is typically based on investigating caged mussels at increasing distances (500, 1000 and 2000 metres) from the installations and on wild fish caught around the discharge sites (e.g., Brooks et al. 2011; Brooks et al. 2023). The programme is designed to identify possible effects in the immediate vicinity of a discharge as well as regional impacts.

6.2 Dredging and disposal of dredged material

Dredging is carried out for a variety of purposes, such as development and maintenance of marine infrastructure (e.g., navigation channels, ports, LNG terminals), offshore mining (e.g., aggregates, placer deposits) and ecosystem enhancement (such as removal of contaminated sediment). Capital dredging projects involve the excavation of sediments to create ports, harbours and navigable waterways, whereas maintenance dredging ensures sufficient water depth is maintained for safe navigation by the periodic removal of sediment. Much of the material removed during these activities requires disposal at sea. Stress on the environment from dredging activities and the disposal of dredged material at sea occur both in the water column and at the seafloor and leads to enhanced risks for adverse biological and ecological effects. A bibliography on

environmental impacts and existing regulations and guidelines is provided in the Appendix tables A6, A7, and A9.

6.2.1 PRESSURES

Both dredging and the dumping of dredged sediments may cause harm to the marine environment. During dredging, sediment is removed from the seafloor and, depending on the purpose and the applied dredging technique, the dredged material is either relocated directly at the dredging site (e.g., during water injection dredging) or dumped at a spatially distant disposal site. The relocation or disposal leads to particle clouds in the water column and to areas at the seafloor covered with re-deposited sediment. A detailed review on the pressures related to dredging activities and dredged sediment disposal is provided in OSPAR Commission (2008b). Different types of dredging techniques (see brief descriptions OSPAR Commission 2009b) are associated with different pressure extents and environmental risks.

Dredging and spoil disposal introduces sediment to the water column to varying degrees from three main sources: mechanical interaction of the dredging equipment with the seabed substrates, overflow associated with loading of dredged material and land reclamation, and disposal of dredge spoil at sea. The main dredging and sediment disposal-related pressures on the environment include substrate removal and alteration of substrate characteristics, alteration of the bottom topography and hydrography, noise pollution, hydraulic entrainment, suspended particles in the water column, reduced light penetration, mobilization of potentially toxic compounds, release of organic matter and nutrients, and sedimentation. These pressures may impact seafloor integrity (i.e., structure and functions) and adversely affect benthic and pelagic communities. Dredging activities and the disposal of dredged sediment often result in the spread of fine sediments over a wider area, as resuspended fine particles have low settling velocities and can remain suspended in the water column for many hours, thus expanding the impacted area in the water column and at the seafloor. Contaminant mobilization associated with dredging can occur in particulate, colloidal, or dissolved fractions, each characterized by a different transport and/or exposure pathway (Thibodeaux 2005; see also **PART II-CHAPTER 3**). The release of contaminants into the dissolved phase can result from expelled sediment pore water during sediment removal and from desorption of contaminants from suspended sediment particles (elements hence becoming more bioaccessible). While the exposures and resulting risks associated with contaminant release would be expected to be shorter than those associated with bedded sediments, the magnitude and temporal extent of these risks will depend on the duration of the dredging operation, composition of the sediment being dredged (e.g., grain size distribution, mineralogy), contaminants associated with the sediment, and current velocities (Bridges et al. 2008). Sediment in the vicinity of anthropogenic areas can contain elevated levels of metals, and the disposal of such contaminated sediment may induce adverse effects.

6.2.2 IMPACTS

Multiple potential stressors associated with dredging activities can act in the environment and cause adverse impacts on marine species, habitats and ecosystem processes (OSPAR Commission 2009a). The effects are species-dependent, but sessile benthic organisms and larvae are generally most vulnerable (see e.g., Erftemeijer et al. 2012; Todd et al. 2015). Rather short-term impacts are related to increased particle loads during dredging and sediment disposal, while substrate removal and habitat degradation can have long-lasting impacts on the ecosystem.

Generally, impacts are related to the intensity, duration and frequency of dredging and hence exposure to increased turbidity and sedimentation, as well as to environmental site conditions (such as sediment

properties, contamination of sediments, currents) (see Erftemeijer et al. 2012). Besides the total loss of organisms, benthic impacts may include smothering, physical damage, chemical toxicity, or reduced food availability, causing a range of adverse behavioural and physiological responses as well as lethal responses. Physical removal of substrate, burial and changes in the substrate characteristics due to sedimentation (grain size, porosity, composition, physical properties) lead to habitat loss and degradation and can result in a reduction of biodiversity and abundance of benthic species and change community structures as well as the disruption of ecological functions and connectivity. Mobilized toxic contaminants in different physical forms increase the risk for ecotoxicological effects in biota. Depending on metal speciation and feeding behavior (i.e., exposure routes), uptake may occur via particle ingestion in sediment- and filter-feeding organisms, or through cell membranes. Toxic effects on (sub)organism level can have consequences at higher levels in the biological organization, also due to the potential biomagnification of toxins (e.g., Hg) in the marine food chain. Turbidity due to **enhanced particle load** affects photosynthetic organisms because of reduced light penetration in the water column and can reduce primary production and carbon flow to the seafloor. Enhanced particle loads may further impact behavior and physiology of marine organisms at various stages of their life cycles and mortality (e.g., Alam et al. 2022; Stenvers et al. 2023; Pineda et al. 2017a; Fisher et al. 2019). Clogging of filtration mechanisms in pelagic and benthic filter-feeding fauna will reduce food uptake and respiration rates. The impacts of suspended particles and sedimentation (natural sediment) on different species were investigated in a range of laboratory and mesocosm studies. Not always in a dredging context, this includes, *inter alia*, studies on corals (Fähse et al. 2023; Tuttle and Donahue 2022; Erftemeijer et al. 2012; Bilan et al. 2023), sponges (Tjensvoll et al. 2013; Wurz et al. 2021; Cummings et al. 2020; Mobilia et al. 2021; Pineda et al. 2017a, Pineda et al. 2017b), fish (Wenger et al. 2017; Johnson 2018; (Harvey et al. 2017), bivalves (Yang et al. 2017), deep-sea jelly fish (Stenvers et al. 2023), juvenile fish (Lowe et al. 2015), and shrimp eggs and larvae (Alam et al. 2022). A detailed overview on available scientific studies on impacts from enhanced sediment loads is provided in Offshore Norge (2024), and more review is found in e.g., OSPAR Commission (2008b).

In-depth information on responses of key benthic marine organisms to dredging pressures in a spatial and temporal context is available from the WAMSI Dredging Science Node project, an industry- and science-driven research initiative that accompanied large-scale dredging programs in Western Australia. Based on environmental monitoring data collected from four dredging projects related to LNG infrastructure development and maintenance and to port upgrades (Pluto, Cape Lambert, Gorgon and Wheatstone) and on laboratory experiments, tolerance thresholds for the different studied taxa (corals, sponges, seagrass) to different pressures including suspended particles, sedimentation and light deprivation have been derived (see WAMSI 2019; Pineda et al. 2017a; Fisher et al. 2019; Negri et al. 2019). The project outcomes also include a literature review on impacts on finfish (Harvey et al. 2017). It has been shown that the impacts typically result from a combination of smothering and turbidity-related effects in the near field close to dredging and disposal areas (10s to 100s of meters), and from turbidity-related effects in the far field that may extend over much larger distances (kilometers) down-current from the suspended sediment generating activities (EPA-WA 2021). Biota may be affected directly or through effects on key ecological processes they rely on for survival at the community level, such as reproduction.

How different types of dredging and disposal of dredged material may affect seafloor integrity is discussed in CEDA (2023). Studies reviewing reported benthic communities' potential for recovery following dredging and dredged material disposal conclude that impacts are difficult to predict but range from months to decades (see CEDA 2023). Resilience and recovery strongly depend on habitat characteristics (type of substrate, community structures) and other environmental site conditions, the frequency and duration of dredging, and the spatial extent of the impact.

6.2.3 OPERATIONAL THRESHOLDS AND CONCEPTS OF RISK ASSESSMENT

Assessment criteria operational in risk assessments of dredging projects involve numerical and narrative thresholds for pressure and biological effects indicators. The thresholds are typically implemented to assess risks for adverse impacts for the purpose of permit application, and (less often), as monitoring criteria. A detailed description of the regulatory regimes applicable for dredging activities and disposal of dredged material nationally is beyond the scope of this report; here we focus on selected key concepts to assess the quality of dredged material and its suitability for ocean disposal in Europe, the United States and Australia at national or regional level. A synthesis on the discussed concepts can be found in **Table 5.6 (CHAPTER 5.6)**.

The disposal of dredged material is primarily regulated by the International Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (the London Convention, LC; IMO 1972) and its later Protocol to the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Protocol 1996, LP; IMO 1996) which set guidelines for managing and chemically characterizing dredged material. Under the 1996 protocol dumping of dredged material is allowed, provided permits are obtained. Under this umbrella, dredging is regulated by regional and/or national legislation. The management of dredged material, especially the disposal of dredged material, is typically regulated by national waste dumping regulations, and permits are issued by the responsible national authority.

In accordance with LC/LP, regional or national guidelines have defined criteria under which dredged material may be exempted from the testing for the purpose of issuing a dumping permit. These criteria are similar throughout the different legislations and include that dredged material is either composed predominantly of sand, gravel or rock; or is not contaminated and taken far away from the sources of pollution (e.g., capital dredging at pristine sites in remote offshore areas), or the quantity of dredged material from single dredging operations does not exceed a specific size per year (see e.g., OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024; Australian Government 2009; U.S. EPA 1991). Applicants for dumping permits are in this case often still required to consider issues such as turbidity, nutrients and environmental impacts despite being exempt from testing (see NAGD, 2009).

The concepts for risk and impact assessments of dredging activities are risk-based and involve at least chemical LoE to assess sediment quality. Some regulations only address potential impacts to benthic communities, while others also address impacts in the water column. For decision-making, ranking of sediment quality based on chemical criteria is used exclusively or, depending on the specific national or regional regulation, more often form the first part of a tiered assessment of dredged material quality and toxicity. A special case are the U.S. regulations, where assessing chemical sediment quality is not mandatory (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016). Tiered assessments typically involve the assessment of pressures at lower tiers (i.e., chemical LoEs), and more complex assessments of possible biological effects (i.e., toxicity and bioaccumulation LoEs) at higher tiers in case of an indicated risk or residual uncertainty after low-tier assessments. A simultaneous assessment of chemical *and* ecotoxicological LoEs to address suitability of dredged material for ocean disposal is required in Italy (Decree 173/16) and on a regional level in the United States (USACE and USEPA 2016). A spatial impact zonation scheme for the protection of benthic communities and habitats in the context of dredging activities (both loading and disposal) is in use in Western Australia, with effects-based tolerance thresholds for pressure-indicators defining the boundaries between zones for impact prediction, and hierarchical triggers of successive management actions at these boundaries during operational phases (EPA-WA 2021).

Besides specific guidelines for dredging disposal, national guidelines for sediment quality assessment can be relevant for risk evaluation and decision-making such as dredging and disposal of dredged material. Examples are the Norwegian Guidelines for risk assessment of contaminated sediments (NEA 2018a) and the sediment quality guidelines for Australia and New Zealand (Simpson et al. 2013a). These guidelines generally follow

existing international frameworks for environmental risk assessment. The latter typically comprise the stages of data collection, hazard assessment, exposure assessment, and risk characterization, as, for example, outlined in the US Guidelines for Ecological Risk Assessment (U.S. EPA 1998), the EU technical guidance document on environmental risk assessment (European Chemicals Bureau 2003), and Guidance for Chemical Safety Assessment for single substances for four environmental compartments including water and sediment published by the European Chemical Agency ECHA (<https://echa.europa.eu/guidance-documents/guidance-on-information-requirements-and-chemical-safety-assessment>).

6.2.3.1 Disposal of dredged material in the European Union

While there is no specific legislation at EU level addressing dredging activities, several EU Directives may be relevant for the management of dredged material and decisions relating to dredging projects including the disposal in the ocean. This includes the Environmental Impact Assessment Directive 2011/92/EU, The Birds Directive 2009/147/EC and the Habitats Directive 92/43/EC, the Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC. Typically, compliance with the relevant EU framework is to be assessed during the licensing process for a project. Under the umbrella of the global LP/LC legislation, several European Regional Sea Conventions (RSC) set guidelines for the management of dredged material at sea, aiming at reducing the adverse effects of dredging and dumping operations on the marine ecosystem. The OSPAR Guidelines for the Management of Dredged Material in the North Sea (OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024; OSPAR Commission 2017a) and the HELCOM Guidelines for the Disposal of Dredged Material at the Baltic Sea (HELCOM 2020) specifically address the disposal of dredged material by dumping (including from hydrodynamic dredging adjacent to the dredging activity) and are designed to assist Contracting Parties in the management of dredged material in these maritime regions. Contracting Parties are also encouraged to exercise control over dredging operations in order to minimize the quantity of the material to be dredged and the impact of the dredging activities as well as to apply Best Environmental Practices (BEPs). Contracting Parties should take these guidelines into consideration in the authorization or regulation procedures for dredged material (OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024). For a comparison of the LP/LC, OSPAR and HELCOM conventions concerning dredging see Pazikowska-Sapota (2011).

The OSPAR and HELCOM guidelines include a tiered assessment scheme for dredged material to approve disposal, with physical and chemical assessments required at the base level and, in case potential impacts cannot adequately be addressed, the optional assessment of biological effects at a higher tier. The implementation and the setting of assessment criteria for the material to be disposed at sea is within the custody of each signatory state and hence, there are differences among these criteria. **Action Levels (AL)** should be developed for individual substances (at least for contaminants of most concern, i.e., those on the primary list in the guidelines) and can be set on the basis of concentration limits, biological responses, environmental quality standards or other reference values (OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024). They should ideally be derived from studies of sediments that have similar geochemical properties to those dredged and/or to those of the receiving system. OSPAR signatory states have developed national ALs of contaminants for the assessment of sediment quality as screening mechanisms for specific substances (for an overview on applied ALs and the methodology for their derivation see OSPAR Commission 2008b). An older review on the application of ALs in European Countries can be found in Alvarez-Guerra et al. (2007). Generally, an AL is a decision rule based on the findings of one or more characteristics in comparison to the respective benchmarks (MMO 2015) and ALs are used to avoid acute and chronic toxic effects in relation to decisions about disposal at sea. Practically and in a stricter sense, **ALs** applied in OSPAR and HELCOM maritime regions are **chemical criteria used** to classify dredged material, and for higher confidence, chemical and toxicological outcomes of an assessment should be combined to classify sediments regarding predicted sediment toxicity.

Lower ALs are used as limit below which dredged material is generally considered non-contaminated and hence of little environmental concern for disposal at sea. The **upper ALs** are used as the limit above which dredged material is considered unsuitable for normal disposal at sea but may be suitable for other management options. Along with the upper action levels, mechanisms for managing sediment that breaches upper action levels vary from country to country, for example, from prohibiting dumping at sea to use of environment management options such as confined aquatic disposal (OSPAR Commission 2017a; Cronin et al. 2023). Material **below the upper ALs but exceeding the lower ALs** requires more detailed assessment before suitability for disposal at sea can be determined (additional chemistry, ecotoxicity tests, additional consideration or evidence such as physical size distribution or other considerations to apply a WoE). In those countries that use these two hierarchical ALs, the lower AL is typically based on a background dataset (e.g., 80th percentile, BAC), while the upper AL is either an effects-based sediment quality criteria (such as empirically derived SQGVs) or a multiplier of AL1. At the optional **'biology' tier**, OSPAR recommends to evaluate the effects of the dredged material with bioassays, testing the whole sediment, including its pore water, or an elutriate of it. The primary purpose of toxicity bioassays is to provide direct measures of the effects of all sediment constituents acting together, taking into account their bioavailability. The use of a suite of tests (including both acute and chronic endpoints, and at least one whole-sediment test) with different organisms having different feeding requirements, sensitivities and covering the range of exposure routes (i.e. water; water plus sediment uptake; and sediment ingestion) and being broadly relevant for the test site is suggested. However, many Contracting Parties predominantly use contaminant ALs for assessing the risks and relocation solutions for dredged material, while the use of toxicity testing is limited (Häkkinen et al. 2020).

The current national regulations for the assessment of sediment quality in the context of dredged material disposal in several European countries is compiled in SedNet (2018) including details on assessment principles and the legal status of the regulations. In *The Netherlands* (signatory to the OSPAR Convention), only chemical analyses are used to consider the site of relocation (at sea, in freshwater, on land or in closed storage facilities), regulated in the Soil Quality Decree since 2008. For dredged material management options in the marine environment, the Netherlands use only one set of action levels derived from background concentrations of which some provide guidance (guidance levels) while others are strict (threshold values). They direct towards pass or fail (SedNet 2018). In *Norway* (signatory to the OSPAR Convention), the regulation of dredging and dredged material disposal falls under Regulation No. 931 on Pollution Control (Pollution Control Regulation). Decision rules for disposal are primarily based on sediment classification of dredged material using the Norwegian sediment classification scheme that is linked to sediment risk assessment guidelines (NEA 2018a). In the tiered decision scheme of the risk assessment guidelines, chemical characterization as well as toxicity testing of pore water and whole sediment is included. Generally, exceedance of sediment class II triggers higher tier risk assessments which consider the risk of spreading (plume modelling) and risks of impact on the (local) ecosystem including the water column (for more details, see NEA, 2018). Maintenance dredging operations in Norway are regulated by the local counties (SedNet 2011). In this case, sediments of class I and II can be disposed of in the marine environment, disposal of sediments in class III requires further evaluation of potential risk to the environment, while handling of sediments in class IV and V require site-specific remediation plans and extensive monitoring during operations. For large-scale dredging operations site specific risk assessment is required. This will form the basis for remediation plans and possible disposal options (SedNet 2011, 2018). The *UK* (signatory to the OSPAR Convention) is considering implementation of a tiered approach. A review by MMO (2015) on the currently used UK approach to assess the suitability of dredged material for disposal concluded that, while the current UK approach fulfils the legal obligations under OSPAR, UK's AL used in the licensing of the disposal of dredged material to sea are not fit for purpose, i.e., in terms of the ability to avoid disposal of toxic sediments at sea and refusal of non-toxic sediment disposal (see also Mason et al. 2022). The proposed tiered framework for UK includes further chemical and ecotoxicological assessments of the sediment for the AL1>dredged material<AL2 case, similar to those applied in the US and

Australia. Decision rules for toxicity data are discussed. In *Italy* (signatory to the Barcelona Convention), the Decree of the Italian Ministry of the Environment no. 173/2016 regulates the technical procedures, monitoring and assessments of all activities related to the movement, dislodgement, discharge, use and treatment of marine sediments. The decree lays out methodological procedures and criteria for dredged sediment characterization, sediment classification and identification of appropriate management options and monitoring. The assessment of sediment quality integrates ecotoxicological bioassay and chemical analysis into a WoE model of hazard assessment. The chemical classification is based on the comparison of measured concentrations with predefined reference values L1 and L2, while the ecotoxicological characterization is based on a battery of bioassays. A dedicated software (SediQualSoft 109.0®; Benedetti et al. 2012) can be used for the integrated classification and to assign the sediments to one of five quality classes that correspond to different management options. d'Errico et al. (2021) applied an integrated WoE model in accordance with the decree as tool for monitoring the risk of dredging activities, supporting a “site-oriented” decision making process, by applying hazardous quotients as thresholds in different LoE for chemistry, bioassays, biomarkers, and bioaccumulation.

A more sophisticated assessment of dredged material for the purpose of dispersal permits is conducted in the United States and Australia (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016; Australian Government 2009), where biological assessments are the rule and also potential impacts in the water column during and after disposal are addressed.

6.2.3.2 Disposal of dredged material in the United States

EPA is responsible for designating and managing ocean dumping sites for the disposal of dredged material under the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act (MPRSA). Only dredged material that is permitted or authorized for disposal under the MPRSA may be disposed at such a site. EPA's ocean dumping criteria (40 CFR Parts 227 & 228) provide the requirements for evaluating the potential for adverse effects of ocean discharge of dredged material on marine organisms and human uses of the ocean. Exemptions can be made if the proposed dredged material is composed predominantly of sand, gravel, rock, or any other naturally occurring bottom material with a particle size larger than silt, or when the material is substantially the same as the substrate at the proposed disposal site prior to any dumping activities and the proposed dredging site is far removed from known existing and historical sources of pollution. For the assessment of dredged material for ocean disposal in U.S. marine waters, two documents are relevant: the testing manual for dredged material proposed for ocean disposal (U.S. EPA 1991), and the guidance for performing tests on dredged material proposed for ocean disposal at the Historic Area Remediation Site (HARS) in the Atlantic Ocean (USACE and USEPA 2016).

Specific assessment criteria for water quality and for water column and sediment toxicity are provided in form of limiting permissible concentrations (LPC) that must be met at any point in the marine environment after initial mixing (that dispersion of liquid, suspended particulate, and solid phases of dredged material that occurs within 4 h after dumping), and at the boundaries of the disposal site during initial mixing. Hence, there is a spatial and a temporal dimension of a mixing zone, where water quality and toxicity may not meet quality standards or other requirements otherwise applicable. The prediction of concentrations of dispersing dredged material in the water column in space and time is conducted by numerical modelling. The LPCs mean that dissolved concentration do not exceed WQC after initial mixing and that contaminant concentrations in the liquid, suspended solid or solid sediment phase that will not cause unreasonable acute or chronic toxicity or other sublethal adverse effects to pelagic and benthic fauna based on bioassay results using appropriate sensitive marine organisms.

The testing manual for dredged material (U.S. EPA 1991) uses a **tiered-testing procedure** for evaluating compliance with limiting permissible concentrations (LPC). The procedure comprises four levels of increasing complexity that generate information to assist in making ocean-disposal decisions, moving from pressure-related criteria to effects-related criteria to decide whether dredged material meet criteria for ocean disposal (see also **Table. 5.6** in **CHAPTER 5.6**). In a first tier, elutriates prepared as filtered supernatants of dredge spoil-water mixtures are chemically analysed to approximate the proportion of contaminants that might be released from sediments and become bioavailable during disposal of dredged material. The mean concentration of any dredged-material constituent dissolved into the liquid phase of dredged material, after initial mixing, should not exceed applicable marine water quality criteria. If all compounds of concern fall below the WQC after initial dilution, effects on organisms in the water column would not be expected during disposal. If **any contaminants are present at levels above their relevant guideline values, or** if there are no WQC for all contaminants of concern, or synergistic effects are suspected among the contaminants (such as for metals), a potential water-column impact must be evaluated in a second tier. Acute toxicity testing with the liquid plus suspended phase of the dredge spoil is then conducted in different dilutions (the unfiltered supernatant of the dredge spoil-water mixture is used). The LPC is defined as 1% of the effects size of the most sensitive organism (LC_{50} or EC_{50}), expressed as fraction of the undiluted liquid plus suspended phase of the dredge spoil. The predicted concentration of the dredged material remaining in suspension after initial dilution should not exceed the LPC. If this criteria (in form of a safe dilution) is not met, chronic toxicity testing is to be conducted. At tier 2, also the toxicity of the solid phase is assessed with chronic bioassays, which needs to be expanded at tier 3 in case of exceedance.

In a second guidance for performing tests on dredged material proposed for ocean disposal for permit from the New York District of the United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) for dredging and placement of dredged material at the Historic Area Remediation Site (HARS) in the Atlantic Ocean (USACE and USEPA 2016), the assessment of the liquid, suspended particulate, and solid phases is required in a **parallel assessment using chemical and toxicological LoE** concurrent with U.S. EPA (1991) methodology and criteria.

6.2.3.3 Disposal of dredged material in Australia

In Australia, several overarching pieces of legislation govern dredging. The Sea Dumping Act implements Australia's obligations under the 1996 London Protocol concerning ocean disposal of dredged material, while the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act as Australian Government's central piece of environmental legislation provides the legal framework for the environmental assessment and approvals process for actions that are likely to have a significant impact on matters of national environmental significance. In addition, dredging associated with offshore petroleum and greenhouse gas storage activities in Commonwealth waters require assessment and authorisation under the Offshore Petroleum and Greenhouse Gas Storage (OPGGS) Act and associated regulations, including the OPGGS (Environment) Regulations 2009. For proposed dredging activities that occur within three nautical miles from the Territorial sea baseline, State and Northern Territory Governments are primarily responsible for regulating loading and dumping activities (State of Queensland 2009). The **National Assessment Guidelines for Dredging (NAGD)** (Australian Government 2009) sets out the framework for assessing and permitting offshore disposal of dredged material under the requirements of the Sea Dumping Act. The NAGD contains provision for the granting of permits for dredging based on the assessment of the applicant's capacity to meet their obligations under the Sea Dumping Act and any permit granted, the Establishment of a Technical Advisory and Consultative Committee for long-term management, and the development and the implementation of an Environment Management Plan for the loading and disposal activities. The Sea Dumping Act applies in all Australian waters, except areas determined to be within the 'limits of a State or of the Northern Territory'. An

example for regulation of dredging and dredged material disposal at state or Northern Territory level are the NT EPA guidelines (NT EPA 2013) that closely follow Australian Government (2009).

The Australian National Assessment Guidelines for Dredging (Australian Government 2009) consists of four parts, namely looking for disposal alternatives, assessing of sediment quality, assessing of potential impacts on the environment, and management and monitoring. The **tiered sediment quality assessment**, as outlined in **Table. 5.6** of **CHAPTER 5.6**, is roughly following the U.S. approach (U.S. EPA 1991) and includes a comparison of the chemical sediment composition with sediment screening levels at a lower tier, proceeding with consideration of sediment background concentrations, chemical sediment elutriate composition and metal bioavailability in the sediments. If risk is still preceding, toxicity testing with whole sediment or pore water and bioaccumulation assessments need to be conducted to confirm or deny the risk for adverse effects. The different LoE may or may not be combined in a WoE assessment. The assessment criteria need to be met at the dredge site after allowance for initial mixing (i.e., after 4h). To predict concentrations of dredged material after initial mixing, either a dilution factor of 100 is applied, or the comparison is based on numerical modelling or other calculations. The guidelines further outline methods for sediment sampling and analysis, sediment quality assessment and biological testing for the purpose of discharge permits.

Comparing guidelines from United States and Australia, the assessment of the chemical composition of the whole sediment against sediment quality criteria and of substance bioavailability is only addressed in Australia (before toxicity testing of the sediment) and not in the US, while the two US guidelines (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016) also address water column toxicity applying toxicity testing, which is not considered in Australia. In Australia, impacts in the water column are only addressed with the chemical LoE, and in case of non-compliance, disposal is unacceptable.

6.2.3.4 Disposal of dredged material in Canada

The disposal of dredged material is regulated via the Disposal at Sea Regulations (SOR/2001-275). Two AL were defined for screening waste or other matter: a lower level, which is passed if the concentrations of specific substances are below chemical assessment criteria (such as ISQG). If one or more substances fail this criterion, biological testing for sediment assessment needs to be conducted (acute and chronic), and, depending on the outcomes of these tests against agreed criteria (e.g., survival rate in acute test >20% lower compared to reference sediment), sediment can be considered to be above the upper AL, below the upper AL but above the lower AL, or below the lower AL. Apitz and Agius (2013; 2017) proposed improvements to these regulations, such as an extended list of metals with proposed ALs to be screened for, the potential for chemical upper ALs to avoid unnecessary toxicity testing of sediments with very high contaminant levels (as done in Europe), using more advanced approaches for chemical interpretation (such as mean hazard quotients for the sum of the contaminants), and including an early-warning bioassay already at tier 1.

6.2.3.5 Benthic impact zones

The consideration of dredging impacts to sensitive benthic habitats in a spatial and temporal realm is addressed specifically in Western Australia and imposed in a regulatory framework. In Western Australia, scale and number of dredging projects has been large by world standards and projects often occur in sensitive environments. The Western Australia EPA expects proponents to present their assessment of dredging impacts in accordance with the Technical Guidance for the **Environmental Impact Assessment of Marine Dredging Proposals (EPA-WA 2021)**. This document describes an impact prediction and assessment framework, intended to assist proponents in the EIA and management of dredging-related activities in WA, and addresses impacts to benthic communities and habitats caused by direct removal, burial or suspended sediments introduced to the water column by dredging or dredge spoil disposal. The guidance does not

address approval under the Sea Dumping Act. Adverse effects of contaminant release from sediments and dispersion on marine environmental quality in Western Australia's Marine Environment are addressed separately though the Western Australia environmental quality management framework (EPA-WA 2016).

The EIA guidance establishes an approach for generating and presenting predicted impacts on benthic habitats and communities and the uncertainty associated with these predicted impacts as part of the EIA, and provides a framework for the development of monitoring and management plans for dredging proposals. The guideline sets out an **impact zonation scheme** to describe and present the extent, severity and duration of predicted impacts of dredging for EIA. The definition of these zones relates to the amount of acceptable damage (e.g. total mortality in the zone of high impact) to key communities such as corals, sponges, and seagrass (EPA-WA 2021). The **Zone of High Impact (ZoHI)** is the area where serious damage to benthic communities is predicted or where impacts are considered to be irreversible, and the **Zone of Moderate Impact (ZoMI)** is the area within which predicted impacts on benthic organisms are sub-lethal, and/or the impacts are recoverable within a period of 5 years following completion of the dredging activities (**Figure 6.1**). The spatially most distant zone is the **Zone of Influence (ZoI)**, an area within which changes in environmental quality associated with dredging plumes are predicted and anticipated during the dredging operations, but where these changes would not result in a detectible impact on benthic biota (EPA-WA 2021). **A set of tolerance thresholds for benthic communities that integrate duration and frequency of exposure are proposed as management thresholds defining the outer boundaries of the zones.** The guidance incorporates findings of the WAMSI Dredging Science Node relating to biological responses and tolerance thresholds of key benthic marine organisms such as corals, sponges, and seagrass to dredging pressures in the tropical waters of Western Australia. Thresholds are typically comprised of a numerical value for a pressure unit and a pressure-associated averaging period (i.e., a temporal component). The prediction of spatial and temporal pressure fields for an operation should be done through numerical plume (hydrodynamic and sediment transport and fate) modelling. The output for individual pressures can then be interrogated against the biological effects-based criteria for the species present at the location to determine the likelihood of measurable impacts, and boundaries can be drawn accordingly. Boundaries between the different zones of impact may be defined by a combined threshold that addresses several stressors such as DLI and suspended particles. Typically, the ZoHI will extend <1 km from the dredge site whereas the ZoI could extend 10's of kilometres.

Figure 6.1: Benthic impact zonation scheme.

Thresholds are not only required to predict zones of impact during the pre-dredging and **dredge spoil disposal** environmental impact assessment phases, but also during the operational phase as triggers for management actions and for compliance monitoring. The use of tiered trigger values as part of a management system designed to provide early warning of conditions approaching the management target for the zone boundaries and within the management zones is described in Fisher et al. (2019) and EPA-WA (2021). Successive management actions are triggered in case of exceedance, following a traffic light approach (for further details, see **CHAPTER 6.4.3**). **When monitoring data for biological responses and recovery become available, the tolerance thresholds could be refined as part of adapted management, considering the requirements to be ZOMI and boundaries adjusted accordingly.**

6.2.3.6 Windows of environmental sensitivity

Temporal or seasonal restrictions for dredging and disposal activities (“dredging windows”) related to environmental sensitivity are used as a management tool to minimize potential adverse impacts and are imposed e.g., in Europe, the U.S. and Australia (OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024; EPA-WA 2021). Such temporal management on dredging and disposal operations acknowledges sensitive and critical timings e.g. of organism’s reproduction cycles of sessile and transient biota (fish) and usually needs to be addressed in environmental impact assessments. In Australia, dredging is prohibited during shallow-water coral spawning periods to protect these larval cohorts from elevated suspended sediment (EPA-WA 2021; Järnegren et al. 2020). In the U.S., the Water Quality Certificate that must be obtained for all operations occurring in state waters regulates that states may impose an environmental window to protect an individual species of concern, or an assemblage of fishes, such as migratory species.

6.3 Submarine tailings disposal of mine waste

The disposal of mining waste into the marine environment is an offshore activity with a long history and causes significant impacts to the ecosystem. During mineral processing, the valuable target commodity is extracted from an ore or industrial resource material in a processing plant. The material waste stream that is left over from this process is called tailings and typically consists of a mixture of grinded ore/rock and water added to the process, with the liquid phase called ‘liquor’. The tailings further contain, depending on the extraction process and the target commodity, variable amounts of residual process chemicals such as flotation agents, flocculants, surfactants, sodium cyanide or other acids used to optimize mineral recovery, and dissolved metals (e.g., Vare et al. 2018). The disposal of such tailings into the marine environment has been identified as one possible tailing management approach. Such marine tailings disposal involves the transport of mine waste tailings from the mine processing plant on land to the shore, where they are discharged through a pipeline into the marine environment at different water depths. The discharges are intended to be placed below the mixing zone, such that impacts to the biologically productive zone are avoided (GESAMP 2016). Worldwide, less than 1% of the extracted waste from mineral processing is deposited in the sea (Vogt 2003), despite the fact that mining waste is one of the largest waste streams.

Both ‘submarine (or sea) tailings disposal’ (STD) and ‘deep-sea tailings disposal’ (DSTD) are used as terms to describe the disposal and deposition of mine tailings into the marine environment, with STD generally referring to deposition depths in water depths shallower than 1000 m, while DSTD is used for operations with final deposition depths between 1000 and 4000 m. Using the definition of Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2015), the BAT Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries (European Commission 2018), refers to STD if disposal occurs at <100 m in the euphotic zone, and to DSTD tailings for discharge at a depth of 100 m

or more, with subsequent formation of a gravity flow that deposits the majority of the material downslope at depths >1000 m. In this report, we use the term marine mine tailings as general description.

Marine mine tailings disposal has been phased out in many countries, and is currently only practiced in a few countries, namely in Norway, where mine tailings are deposited in fjords (6 mines); in Turkey, where DSTD into the anoxic Black Sea is conducted (Çayeli Bakir mine); and in PNG (Ramu, Simberi and Lihir mines), and Indonesia (Batu Hijau mine) with DSTD into open ocean settings. Two more projects exist in PNG with approved environmental permits but have not yet started (Woodlark and Wafi-Golpu projects, see below), two more projects are planned in Norway (Engebø Rutile and Garnet, former Nordic Rutile; Nussir ASA) that hold a valid environmental permit, and a third has not yet been approved. In Norway, pipe outflows are located 20-130 m below the sea surface, with final deposition depths between 30 and 500 m (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022). In PNG, Indonesia, and Turkey, discharge depths range from 100 to 250 m, and deposition depths from 1000 m to 4000 m. Discharge is usually running continuously for several decades, with discharge sizes ranging from 0.037 Mt/yr to 4 Mt/yr in Norway (ESA 2024), 4.3 Mt/yr for Cayeli Bakir, 2.9 Mt/yr for Lihir, 3.2 Mt/yr for Simberi, 5 Mt/yr for Ramu Nickel, and 58 Mt/yr at Batu Hijau, the world's largest operation (see Kwong et al. 2019). The planned Wafi Golpu project in PNG anticipates 16.5 Mt/yr of discharge, and the Woodlark project 2.4 Mt/yr. The planned Nordic Rutile mine in Norway will discharge 4 Mt/yr.

The tailings originate from the production of industrial minerals/raw material (quartz, calcite, feldspar, microcline/nepheline, ilmenite, rutile, garnet) and of valuable metals such as Fe, Ni, Co, Cu, Pb, Zn, Ag and Au from oxide, sulfide and silicate minerals. These target commodities are associated with a variety of different rock types ranging from mafic to alkaline intrusive rocks, high-grade metamorphic rocks, highly weathered lateritic rocks (Ramu Nickel), to quartzite and marble. Gold mineralizations are often associated with copper porphyries in complex magmatic-hydrothermal settings and either found disseminated in the altered intrusive rock or more concentrated in epithermal alteration zones (metasediments, metavolcanics) around the intrusions (e.g., Bat Hilau, Wafi-Golpu, Lihir). The majority of the gold is hosted in sulphides, but it also occurs as free Au or in oxides (e.g., Simbeli). The particle composition of the tailings discharges reflects the (partly) complex deposit geology and the target commodity.

Because of significant environmental concerns, several operations have decided to phase out or limit their disposal of extractive waste into the sea (European Commission 2018). In Norway, the only western European country that still practices STD, the marine discharge has been publicly and legally debated for decades, including several court cases (ESA 2017, 2021, 2024; see **CHAPTER 6.3.3.1**). The main dispute relates to whether or not permitting STD undermines certain articles in the WFD. The Norwegian government recently won a court case against environmental organizations, confirming the legality of approval of an environmental permit granted by the Norwegian authorities to the company Nordic Rutile (now Engebø Rutile and Garnet). At the time of writing, the case is still pending in the Court of Appeal (Bogarting Lagmannsrett 2024), a decision is expected in 2025.

6.3.1 PRESSURES AND RISKS

The continuous discharge of mine tailings into the marine environment introduces multiple stressors that do or have the potential to adversely impact pelagic and benthic habitats. The milling procedure during mineral processing typically produces particles ranging from silt- to clay-size, although coarser tailings are known as well. Depending on the discharge setting and design, tailings form density currents at the discharge point that follow the morphology, and/or the material (or part of it) is dispersed in the water column and settles according to particle gravity. Observations of DSTP operations in PNG and in Indonesia have shown that dilute tailings subsurface plumes shear off an descending density current and form neutrally buoyant horizontal plumes in the water column, especially at density discontinuities (Shimmield et al. 2010 and references therein;

Hughes et al. 2015; Stauber et al. 2022; Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018c). Multiple of these plumes may form during gravity flow descent, comprised of the finer tailings solids and dilute liquor including dissolved metals and process chemicals (Hughes et al. 2015; Stauber et al. 2022). The horizontal plumes are thought to represent 10 to 30% of the total tailings discharge volume (Shimmield et al. 2010). Density currents are also known to form in Norwegian fjords (Bøe et al. 2018).

Up to several million tonnes of tailings are discharged per year, and the deposited material can be dozens of metres thick in the main deposition zone close to the discharge point and cover several square kilometers of the seafloor (Olsgard and Hasle 1993). The Misima tailings (deposition ceased) for example cover an area of about 20 km² and the thickness in the main deposition zone ranges between 1.5 and 75m (Shimmield et al. 2010). At Lihir, the depositional and ecological footprint extends across a broad plain up to 20 km east of the outfall and to depths of at least 2000m (Shimmield et al. 2010; Hughes et al. 2015), covering a total area of about 60 km². Up to several meter thick deposits are also known from tailings in Norwegian fjords (Bøe et al. 2018), with the accumulated material typically decreasing rapidly with distance. Sedimentation rates from several metres yr⁻¹ close to discharge, to 4–5 cm yr⁻¹ within 1 km from the outfall site, and in the order of 1 mm yr⁻¹ at distances >2–3 km from the outfall have been reported (Olsgard and Hasle 1993). Tailings material deposited at the seafloor and tailings plumes in the water column represent the major stressors to the environment. The deposition of tailings material from downslope gravity flows and/or dispersing particle plumes causes direct smothering of benthic fauna, with epifauna and sessile biota predicted to be most at risk (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022). Changes of submarine topography at the main deposition site and substrate alteration are further factors that may cause stress in the environment. The newly deposited substrate differs from original natural sediment, with often finer-grained and sharper particles, changed porosity, other mineralogical and chemical composition (potentially toxic metals or chemicals can be enriched), and lower organic carbon content that may impact biological communities and ecosystem functioning besides the direct physical impact of burial, and further determine recolonization patterns. Further sources of risk include upwelling and sediment resuspension (Stauber et al. 2022). While tailings characteristics such as the mineralogy, chemistry, and physical properties determine the hazard of the disposed material, the actual exposure in relation to natural conditions depends on a range of site-specific physical, oceanographic, sedimentological, and (biogeo)chemical conditions and processes during and after deposition and shape the site-specific risk to the environment. Biotic factors (such as species, life stage, feeding behavior) ultimately determine the specific impacts to organisms and communities.

The dispersal of tailings in the water column with enhanced concentrations of suspended particles can cause adverse effects on the phytoplankton and zooplankton communities in the water column through increased turbidity, toxicity of chemicals and/or damage from particles (Reinardy et al. 2019; Farkas et al. 2017). The pelagic macro- and megafauna, including fish, can also be affected and migration routes or spawning areas can be altered (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019). Also, benthic filter-feeding biota may be impacted by suspended particle loads. Composition and particle characteristics of the tailings have shown to influence the intensity of the effects. The grinding step during mineral processing often produces fine-grained but sharp-edged particles and highly reactive mineral surface areas as compared to natural mineral grains, increasing the chemical reactivity of the particles and potentially facilitating the mobilization of toxic metals. The grain size determines the dispersal and settling behavior in the water column and shape the availability of particles along different bio-uptake routes in the water column and at the seafloor (water filtration, feeding selectivity). Fine-grained particles may interfere with the respiratory and/or feeding organs of marine organisms (Shimmield et al. 2010; Brooks et al. 2019), causing physical damage that may be intensified if the particles are sharp-edged (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022; Schaanning et al. 2008) and potentially reducing food intake. Feeding activity in the water column may be also be compromised when the suspended material contains low organic carbon content (e.g., Ellis et al. 2002). Further risks include flocculation of fine particulate material entrapping

phytoplankton and invertebrate larvae (Stauber et al. 2022), and direct particle toxicity (Michel et al., 2014). A comprehensive summary of observed biological responses to enhanced suspended particles in marine pelagic organisms is provided in Alam et al. (2022).

Tailings often contain process chemical and/or metals and metalloids that are associated with the tailings solids or liquid and pose a toxic risk to the environment during transport and after sedimentation. Mobilisation of metals and metalloids into the dissolved phase can occur during mineral processing on land, in the dispersing plume after the disposal or following tailings deposition at the seafloor. Depending on feeding behavior and life stage, different exposure pathways can be relevant, such as dissolved metals uptake through cell membranes, and particulate metals uptake via the dietary exposure route. The latter risk is particularly high for actively or passively suspension-feeding and non-selective detritus-feeding organisms. Furthermore, dissolved and particulate metals may bioaccumulate in the tissues of smaller organisms, with some metals such as Hg being prone to biomagnify up in the food chain, reaching higher and potentially toxic concentrations in predators. Tailings from gold and copper-gold mining are of specific concern as gold, one of the major target commodities of mining companies disposing tailings into the oceans is often associated with sulfide minerals (pyrite, arsenopyrite, or Cu sulphides) that contain increased amounts of potentially toxic metals such as As, Cd, Cu, or Hg and pose a risk to the environment. Depending on the type of mineral processing, gold mining tailings contain smaller or larger amounts of primary sulphides and/or secondary processing products such as oxides and oxyhydroxides in a bulk rock mineral assemblage (silicate, quartz). In pressure oxidation circuits such as in use for the Lihir gold mineral processing, the vast majority (>98%) of the sulphide gets oxidized (Shimmiel et al. 2010) and metals such as As become bound in oxide minerals (ferric arsenate) or scavenged to Fe oxyhydroxide minerals (Edinger 2012). In this case, only very small fractions of the primary sulphides pass through into the tailings. However, secondary Fe oxyhydroxides form due to excess quantities of Fe added to neutralize/detoxify any leftover, highly toxic cyanide used as process chemical that may be present in the tailings after the precious metal has been extracted (Shimmiel et al. 2010). Possible fates of tailings-derived ferric arsenate in the marine environment are unclear. At reducing conditions after deposition, As bound in secondary oxides and oxyhydroxides may become mobilized into the pore water and the overlying bottom water (Edinger 2012). Arsenic concentrations in pore water at Lihir tailings deposition impact stations is strongly elevated and has been related to redox mobilization of As from oxides, without however, a substantial net flux into bottom seawater (likely due to re-oxidation at the sediment-water interface, Shimmiel et al. 2010). In contrast, historically impacted stations from the abandoned Misima mine do not show similar As enrichments in the solid phase or pore water.

Sulphide-bearing mine tailings are also known from Norwegian fjords (e.g., Ulveryggen, abandoned; Titania ASA). Simpson and Spadaro (2016) tested the bioavailability and acute and chronic toxicity of metal sulfide minerals to benthic marine invertebrates using whole sediment toxicity tests and showed that metal bioavailability and toxicity of a sediment is generally low in the presence of sulfide minerals (see **CHAPTER 5.2**). Uncertainty remains with respect to the stability of sulphide minerals following tailings deposition, and potential longer-term transformation into more soluble forms due to oxidation that would increase metal bioavailability and the risk of toxic effects (Simpson and Spadaro 2016). The risks for enhanced dissolved metal concentrations in pore water and bottom seawater posed by sulphide mineral oxidation are generally predicted to be low in deep-sea environments (GESAMP 2016). Natural weathering processes of sulphide ore deposits on the seafloor occur in cold waters of near neutral and buffered pH, and oxidation reactions result in direct formation of secondary oxide and oxyhydroxide minerals thereby reducing net mineral dissolution (see Fallon et al. 2017; Bilenker et al. 2016). Galvanic processes that could directly lead to sulphide dissolution (Fallon et al. 2017; Mun et al. 2020) are unlikely, as this requires direct sulphide mineral contacts not provided in tailings deposits. However, at reducing conditions within/below the tailings deposits secondary oxide and hydroxide minerals can dissolve, releasing metals into the pore water and overlying water column.

Furthermore, continuously enhanced metal fluxes from sulphide-bearing ore tailings into overlying seawater were observed in abandoned disposal sites in Norwegian fjords, and do indicate enhanced and ongoing metal leaching from tailings material, either related to direct mineral dissolution or mobilization from secondary reaction products (Schaanning et al. 2019; Hoff et al. 2024; Mun et al. 2020).

Over the past 25 years, a wealth of scientific studies addressed environmental risks and impacts of marine mine tailings disposal, significantly advancing knowledge on hazards and exposure, ecosystem consequences and long-term recovery and on issues related to the environmental management. In 2010, the final report of an independent evaluation of Deep-Sea Mine Tailings Placement (DSTP) in PNG has been published. The study has been conducted with financial support provided by the Government of Papua New Guinea via the 8th European Development Funding Initiative (Shimmield et al. 2010) and the attachment of this report presents the draft guidelines for the regulation of DSTD in PNG (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010). In 2015, the international concern regarding environmental impacts of the marine disposal of mine tailings led to an international workshop held in June 2015 in Peru, organized as joint IMO and GESAMP activity and with support from the Office for the LC/LP and Ocean Affairs, the INDEEP network, the Norwegian Research Council and DOSI. The final report of this workshop has been published by the GESAMP and the LC/LP Secretariat in 2016 (GESAMP 2016). In Norway, a joint project of national governmental institutions and industry partners (NYKOS) aimed at increasing the knowledge base for submarine tailings disposal in Norway and developing guidelines and best available techniques for submarine tailings disposal in Norwegian fjords. Results are published peer-reviewed and in a guideline document (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019). The European Surveillance Agency (ESA) published a review of technical and scientific data concerning the discharge of mining waste into Norwegian waters and associated impacts on the ecological and chemical status of the affected water bodies (ESA 2024). Furthermore, the EIS of planned projects in PNG are a valuable source of information on risks and concepts of impact assessment and threshold application. An overview on relevant literature and project reports is provided in Tables A6 and A7 in the Appendix.

Biological effects on pelagic and benthic organisms and communities were addressed in case studies at different levels of the biological and ecological organization (e.g., Trannum et al. 2019; Brooks et al. 2019; Schaanning et al. 2019; Reinardy et al. 2019; Mevenkamp et al. 2017b). Long-term impacts and recovery were for example studied by Josefson et al. (2008), Hughes et al. (2015), Trannum et al. (2023), Haywood et al. (2016), Hoff et al. (2024). Comprehensive reviews and syntheses of ecological impacts of deep-sea tailings disposal are published, *inter alia*, by Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2015; 2022), Stauber et al. (2022), Hughes et al. (2015), Morello et al. (2016), Dold (2014), Reichelt-Brushett (2012), and Edinger (2012), focusing on Norwegian fjord settings and DSTD in PNG. Environmental management of marine mine tailing disposal from a scientific point of view is addressed in Vare et al. (2018), while current state of regulations are addressed in Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2022) and Stauber et al. (2022). The complexity of the behavior and fate of suspended particles during plume dispersal has been described by Davies and Nepstad (2017), highlighting the challenges for realistically predicting plume dispersal and settling. Stauber et al. (2022) provide a comprehensive overview on driving stressors and major impacts and developed a generic ERA framework applicable to DSTP. The history and recent status of marine mine tailings disposal is also reviewed in Kwong et al. (2019).

6.3.2 BIOLOGICAL AND ECOLOGICAL RESPONSES

Enhanced sedimentation rates, elevated suspended particle concentrations and particle properties, changed habitat characteristics and toxic compounds in the environment are among the major concerns of inducing biological and ecological responses in marine tailings disposal areas. On (sub)organism level, physiological, behavioral, lethal, biochemical, and cellular responses as well as inflammation and starvation may be induced. Potential longer-term consequences for the ecosystem include loss of biomass and biodiversity, changed

community structures and functions, and connectivity disruption. To assess site-specific exposures and adverse impacts, a range of studies have been conducted. Laboratory and mesocosm exposure experiments are used to assess effects from suspended particles, enhanced sedimentation, and chemical toxicity. Field sampling and field monitoring is used to study impacts on benthic communities and recovery at active and abandoned sites, and recolonization experiments are conducted to determine initial recovery. Spatial and temporal extents of exposure are typically predicted with numerical modelling tools.

While benthic impacts have been studied in detail and are relatively well understood, significant challenges remain regarding the assessment of the fate and impacts of sub-surface tailings plumes at all water depths, and evidence on actual biological effects in the water is still poorly constrained (Stauber et al. 2022).

6.3.2.1 Effects from combination of multiple stressors

The presence of multiple stressors both in the water column and at the seafloor due to marine tailings disposal often precludes attributing observed effects to a single stressor. Identifying clear cause-response relationships for individual stressors is difficult to reveal and often integrated impacts from a combination of multiple stressors are likely to have caused the observed effects in the pelagic or benthic fauna. Multi-stressor biological responses have been discussed in ecotoxicological laboratory (e.g., Brooks et al. 2019), mesocosm (e.g., Trannum et al. 2018), and field studies (Josefson et al. 2008; see also Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022 and Stauber et al. 2022).

Experiments with *repeated sedimentation* of different tailings have shown that hyper-sedimentation can be only one of several stressors causing responses of different intensity, and further impact mechanisms may be active (Trannum et al. 2018). This could include starvation due to low nutrient content in the tailings, mechanical damage due to particle angularity, chemical toxicity due to the presence of process chemicals and suffocation and clogging of feeding and respiratory organs related to the fine grain size that may have caused the observed adverse effects to benthic fauna. *Whole sediment toxicity tests* conducted with tailings impacted sediments from the Lihir deposition site (PNG) to observe effects on different benthic species (amphipods, bivalves) identified dissolved and particulate metals (exposure via overlying water, pore water and dietary uptake), clogging of gills, and reduced food availability as most likely stressors contributing to the observed ecotoxic effects (Stauber et al. 2022 and references therein). Impact mechanisms in *field studies* are especially difficult to identify. Metal impacts on benthic biota in the field are difficult to separate from the effects of other stressors (Stauber et al. 2022). Impacts on benthic communities observed 15 years after closure may have been caused due to either of, or a combination of high sedimentation rates, which buried sessile biota and caused smothering by clogging feeding organs; changed substrate characteristics impacting recolonization; reduced food availability and metal toxicity via pore water and dietary uptake (Josefson et al. 2008), with strong evidence that toxic impacts are at least partly responsible for deterioration. It has also been suggested that epithelial injury may increase the risk of uptake and toxic effects of metals or chemicals (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022).

The integration of impacts and potential synergisms will depend on biotic factors such as feeding behavior of affected fauna. In the following, an overview on the results of different study approaches to determine impacts from marine tailings disposal is provided.

6.3.2.2 Toxicity studies

Trace metal exposure routes for pelagic and benthic organisms include the uptake of metals dissolved in seawater and pore water, and the ingestion of particle-associated metals. To assess the direct toxicity of mine tailings, exposure tests with tailings material are conducted. This can involve ecotoxicity tests in the laboratory

and *in situ* field studies with caged or wild organisms. It has been shown that observed biological effects can relate to both particulate and/or chemical exposure. Brooks et al. (2019) used a range of different experimental setups (exposure to tailings liquor; exposure to filtered supernatants of tailings-seawater mixtures at different ratios, whole sediment toxicity tests) to discriminate between chemical (dissolved) and particle-induced toxicity of different mine tailings to benthic organisms. Toxic responses were observed to variable degrees in all test set-ups. While toxic responses in the filtered solutions can only be caused by chemical toxicity of process chemicals or dissolved metals, significant whole sediment toxicity of a tailings material with only minor toxicity of the dissolved fraction has been attributed to physical interference of very fine-grained, round particles to test species (benthic amphipods), with clay-sized particles possibly inducing cytotoxicity to gill epithelial cells. The potential impacts from particulate metals in the whole sediment exposure is not discussed. Caged mussels, deployed in the water column at different distances to a tailings discharge showed sublethal biological effects in the test species correlating with distance. Observed effects are most likely caused by exposure to flotation chemicals and/or metals in the tailings (Brooks et al. 2018), although interaction with fine-grained particles could not be excluded (Brooks et al. 2019).

The effects of the disposal of deep-sea tailings on pelagic communities and the potential for bioaccumulation and biomagnification of mine-derived trace metals through the food web have been studied by Brewer et al. (2012) at the operating Lihir disposal site. The authors compared the relative abundance, diversity and trace metal concentrations in zooplankton, micronekton and pelagic fish in tailings-impacted and reference zones and calculated the biomagnification from lower to higher trophic levels. They observed little adverse effects on the faunal abundance and biodiversity in the local food web. Tailings discharge results in elevated concentrations of trace metals in the less mobile zooplankton at the disposal site, but there is little evidence for widespread biomagnification from lower trophic levels to large fish except for mercury. While elements such as Cd or Cu biomagnify in micronekton and bait fish, and mercury biomagnifies in the coastal pelagic fish, the biomagnification factors are not significantly different between the disposal site and the reference site and hence, the enhanced metal content in zooplankton at the disposal sites is not passed through the food web at increased levels.

Mining companies applying for an environmental permit for DSTD in PNG typically assess the toxic risk of tailings material for pelagic fauna and benthic fauna as part of an EIA. Direct toxicity tests of tailings liquors are used to study impacts on pelagic fauna, aiming to determine the minimum dilution required for the tailings liquor to be non-toxic ('safe' dilution) in the water column. For the proposed Wafi-Golpu tailings, a dilution of at least 1800 times has been determined as being protective for pelagic fauna (e.g., see Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018c, see **CHAPTER 6.4.4.2**). In another study ammonia, used as process chemical to recover Ni and Co, was identified as primary toxicant for the toxicity observed from nickel ore mine tailings liquors (see Stauber et al. 2022). The toxicity of settled tailings material to benthic fauna is studied as well. One such study with sulphide-bearing tailings material from the proposed gold mine Wafi-Golpu revealed continuous release of Cu into the overlying water for at least 17 weeks in a mesocosm setup, which has been attributed to the oxidation of sulphide minerals (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018c). At a ratio of 20% tailings to 80% sediment, this Cu mobilization did not translate into toxicity to or bioaccumulation in amphipods and bivalves known to be sensitive to copper. Higher tailings concentrations were not tested. An enhanced mobilization of Cu into pore water was observed for 100% tailings material, potentially causing toxic responses. An publically inaccessible study cited in Stauber et al. (2022) conducted whole tailing-containing sediment toxicity tests from the Lihir mine DSTD deposition area and observed toxic responses, most likely related to dissolved metals, while starvation could not be ruled out. Other studies with Lihir mine tailing sediments identified dissolved and particulate metals (exposure via overlying water, pore water and dietary uptake), clogging of gills, and reduced food availability as most likely stressors contributing to the observed ecotoxic effects (Stauber et al. 2022).

6.3.2.3 Suspended tailings particles exposure experiments

It is long known that pelagic filter feeders can ingest mineral particles upon exposure. Farkas et al. (2017) revealed ingestion of fine-grained mine tailings from marble processing and surface attachment to the filtering apparatus in a pelagic filter-feeding copepod, which may lead to chronic effects, e.g. due to reduced energy intake. Acute toxicity was not observed at the tested concentrations of up to 5 g/L, and feeding rates were not impeded. Generally, the ability to select food will have a strong influence on the impact of suspended particles to filter-feeding, pelagic organisms (Arendt et al. 2011). Mine tailings have further been shown to impact early life stages of Atlantic cod and haddock (Reinardy et al. 2019, Farkas et al. 2021). Mineral particles from marble processing adhere to haddock and cod eggs, affecting egg buoyancy, survival and larval development at tailings concentrations of 1-10 mg/L (Farkas et al. 2021). At concentrations of 3.2 mg/L, copper mine tailings that contain high metal concentrations and silica nanoparticles (ESA 2021) adhere to cod egg surfaces but did not induce adverse effects (Reinardy et al. 2019). An increase in cod larvae mortality was attributed to combined effects of life stage, particle exposure, and differences in mine tailings particle sizes and shape characteristics compared with suspended sediment exposures particle exposure, while the observed increase in DGT-labile dissolved Cu concentrations was likely not the reason for enhanced mortality (there was no significant elevation of metallothionein gene transcription in hatched larvae, a sensitive marker for induction of metal detoxification mechanisms). Observed sublethal detoxification responses may have been induced by exposure to the inorganic particles that may have lead to reduced food uptake due to unselective feeding.

6.3.2.4 Sedimentation exposure experiments

Mesocosm experiments to study the impact of settled tailings material showed varying responses on benthic communities and functions, depending on a range of abiotic (tailings characteristics such as grain size, mineralogy, particle forms; burial thickness) and biotic (feedings behavior, size class) factors.

Trannum et al. (2018) studied macrofaunal responses to repeated sedimentation in different faunal feeding groups including surface deposit feeders and suspension feeders (including number of individual and species, biomass, species richness, diversity indices), together with biogeochemical processes. The observed responses are tailing type-specific and feeding group-specific and strongly correlate with tailings thickness, with some very fine-grained material already causing responses in surface deposit feeders at deposition thicknesses as low as 3 mm. Significant effects were also observed in suspension feeders during the exposure to suspended particles for the time of tailings addition. Suffocation and clogging of feeding and respiratory organs by this very fine-grained material have been identified as most likely impact mechanism, which could also intensify effects from chemical toxicity such as from flotation chemicals. Results show that besides impacts related to physical burial and changed substrate characteristics (porosity, oxygenation, grain size, organic matter content), the settled particles themselves can have detrimental effects on biota, due to their small size and angularity. Overall, a layer thickness of 2 cm represents a threshold level above which all tailings types had adverse effects, both on nutrient fluxes and faunal parameters.

Meiofauna was typically thought to be generally more tolerant to burial compared to macrofauna, but in a mesocosm experiment studying impacts on benthic communities from the deposition of 1 to 30 mm of coarse-grained iron ore mine tailings, effects in macrofauna were less pronounced compared to meiofauna responses. A reduction of functional processes have been observed already at 1-mm tailings added (Mevenkamp et al. 2017b), while community structures (in terms of biomass and composition) remained largely unaffected at this addition. Structural changes of meiofauna with reduced biomass and shifts in vertical distribution became apparent at 0.5 cm burial with tailings added and more pronounced at 3 cm, likely caused by reduced food availability. No effects were observed for the macrofaunal composition or mortality even at

3-cm burial. The study clearly shows that even small levels (1 mm) of instantaneous burial by mine tailings may significantly reduce benthic ecosystem functioning immediately. The particular characteristics of settled material strongly influences the biogeochemistry inside the sediments and the way the ecosystem responds to substrate burial.

Tailings metal content can have an additional adverse effect on macrofaunal communities. Trannum and Schaanning (2017) have shown that an addition of 2 cm of sulfide-bearing tailings results in a significant reduction in density and number of individuals of soft bottom macrofauna, likely attributed to metal toxicity. In addition, reduced food availability and particle angularity leading to physical effects could play a role.

The results show that responses are sensitive to tailings characteristics and taxa, and an effects threshold should be carefully determined with site-specific investigations.

6.3.2.5 Long-term impacts on benthic ecosystems

Field studies at active and abandoned disposal sites and recolonization experiments are used to investigate impacts of large-scale marine tailings disposal on benthic ecosystems in the (deep) sea, focusing on benthic macrofaunal, meiofaunal and foraminiferal community responses, and partly additionally addressing biogeochemical processes. An overview on studies conducted at disposal sites in Norway is provided in Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2022). Further information on long-term impacts of mine tailings disposal to benthic ecosystems can be found in NEA (2019b), ESA (2024), Vogt (2003), Stauber et al. (2022) and Baza-Varas et al. (2022). Responses of benthic communities to tailings sedimentation (i.e., to burial, changed substrate characteristics, enhanced metal content, low organic carbon content etc.), as well as subsequent recovery are taxon-specific and depend on tailings characteristics, impact strength (i.e., tailings thickness), spatial footprint, and environmental conditions such as sedimentation rates. Observed responses typically include reduced species richness and/or abundances and the presence of more tolerant, opportunistic species (e.g., Hughes et al. 2015). In areas close to the disposal site, communities may have disappeared completely. It has been shown, that initial recolonization of tailings can occur within 1-2 years (e.g., Olsgard and Hasle 1993; Trannum et al. 2023), but not necessarily with the same species composition and diversity as originally present, and that benthic communities may remain impacted for up to several decades after disposal has stopped (e.g., Hughes et al. 2015; Josefson et al. 2008; Dauvin 2010; Shimmield et al. 2010; Trannum et al. 2019, 2023; Elberling et al. 2003; Hoff et al. 2024; Schaanning et al. 2019; Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022).

The benthic ecological footprint of marine gold and copper mine tailings in PNG have been studied in detail. The ongoing discharge of mine tailings from the Lihir gold mine (continuously operating since 1996) is associated with substantially reduced infaunal (macro and meio, forams) abundances and changes in higher-taxon community structures in the tailings deposition zone up to 20 km to the east of the discharge point (sampling in 2007, Hughes et al. 2015). The sampling locations are characterized by a 3–7 cm thick layer of fine-grained orange tailings material on top of consolidated mud, and show significantly enriched trace metal concentrations. The scale of impact on metazoan meiofauna and calcareous forams declines with water depth (800–2020m) and thus, with distance from the tailings outfall, but is still significant down to 1700m. Macrofauna and organic-walled forams are severely impacted to at least 2000m (Hughes et al. 2015; Shimmield et al. 2010). Haywood et al. (2016) observed a decreased species richness and a predominance of less complex growth forms in coral communities around the Lihir disposal site. At the Misima tailings deposition site, where DSTD took place for 15 years at rates from 2 cm/yr up to 10 cm/yr until 2004 (Stauber et al. 2022) that completely eliminated sessile benthic fauna, effects on community structure of macrofauna and benthic forams persisted 3.5 years after its conclusion. Reduced macrofaunal densities and changed community structure is here potentially attributable to chemical toxicity and/or physical disturbances. Geochemical tailings signals (enhanced metal content) in distal settlements are not expressed in a deteriorated

community composition (Hughes et al. 2015). Meiofauna recolonization experiments with Batu Hilau mine tailings in Indonesia revealed no significant difference in meiofaunal communities, numbers of species or numbers of taxa after 97 days compared to natural sediment control (Gwyther et al. 2009).

Ongoing disposal of very fine-grained tailings from a marble mine into a Norwegian fjord have shown to impact benthic infauna and epifauna communities, with changed species composition and decreased species richness and species diversity, as well as changed functional community composition and diversity (Trannum et al. 2019). Functional responses include an increase in mobile carnivores/omnivores and species utilizing symbionts, while deposit and suspension feeders of sessile and tube-living taxa decrease, probably due to smothering in combination with tailings-associated changes of the substrate. Higher sensitivity of epifauna compared to infauna has been related to living modes. Mine tailings in Norwegian fjords continue to have local impacts on biogeochemical processes and seafloor macrofauna and foraminiferal communities in the impacted areas decades after deposition (Trannum et al. 2023; Schaanning et al. 2019; Hoff et al. 2024). At an abandoned deposition site of sulfide-bearing tailings from an ilmenite mine, trace metal fluxes at the sediment-water interface have been shown to be significantly enhanced decades after cessation (especially Cu and Ni), likely driven by ongoing sulfide leaching. Prevailing disturbance effects observed in benthic macrofaunal community status is most likely driven by the tailings-induced Cu gradient (Schaanning et al. 2019), although other factors may play a role. The observations are in line with mesocosm experiments with the same tailings material from the ilmenite mine by Trannum and Schaanning (2017), where considerable faunal mortality has been observed. Earlier field studies by Olsgard and Hasle (1993) at the same deposition site showed that sedimentation of 4–5 cm of tailings per year resulted in changes of fauna composition, while at rate of 1 mm per year no impact was observed on the fauna. Metal leaching is generally favored in areas where natural sedimentation rates are low and bioturbation is high, promoting both downwards transport of O₂ and upwards transport of tailings over decades (Schaanning et al. 2019). At another 40-year old deposition site of sulfide-bearing tailings from a Cu mine, a Cu concentration gradient in the sampled sediments was found to be significantly correlated to the faunal structure, and enhanced metal fluxes at the sediment-water interface indicate prevailing metal leaching in the tailings material (Trannum et al. 2023; Hoff et al. 2024). Species patterns with opportunistic and tolerant species likely reflect prevailing toxic effects and the limited circulation in the deposit area (Trannum et al. 2023). Foraminiferal community structures in the same depositional setting have been shown to remain changed decades after impacts, being dominated by more stress tolerant and opportunistic species (e.g., Hoff et al. 2024). Experimental short-term recolonization with freshly produced tailings of similar composition revealed to be possible, but is characterized by lower species richness, abundance and biomass than the controls (Trannum et al. 2023).

Persisting impacts on benthic communities were also observed at a tailings deposition site of a lead and zinc mine in Western Greenland, 15 years after the disposal of tailings had stopped (Josefson et al. 2008), with slow recolonization and communities dominated by opportunistic species. Ongoing exposure to high trace metal concentrations in the sulfide-bearing deposits have been identified as major impact mechanism, being at least partly responsible for the long-lasting deterioration, although other factors may also contribute (e.g. changed sediment texture, which may preclude establishment of the original fauna; burial; or reduced food availability for deposit feeders). Elberling et al. (2003) found foraminiferal communities to recolonize quickly (<1 year) at this site, but also remaining at low diversity and characterised by a few opportunistic taxa for up to 10 years.

Recovery may take longer in the deep sea compared to shallower water settings used for STD, due to the slow growth rates and metabolism in the deep-sea, long-lived species, which often have variable larval and juvenile survival and delayed maturity and reproductive output (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019).

Capping sulphide-bearing tailings with natural clays may represent a useful management strategy to mitigate potential toxic exposures (Schaanning et al. 2019; Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022), facilitating recolonization by

accelerating the burial of tailings below the active bioturbation zone where sediment oxygenation is otherwise maintained for decades (e.g., Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022; Trannum et al. 2023). Capping has also been considered as mitigation tool for a planned DSTD operation in PNG (EIA, Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018c), where copper mobility in sulfide-bearing mine tailings have shown to be significantly reduced at capping depths of more than 20 mm. However, capping does not always seem favorable to avoid metal leaching (Pedersen et al. 2022), and its success will depend on tailings composition.

6.3.3 ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

UNCLOS calls upon states to adopt laws and regulations to prevent, reduce and control pollution of the marine environment from land-based sources in its Article 207, including pollution that reaches the marine environment by means of rivers, estuaries, pipelines, and outfall structures, “taking into account” internationally agreed rules, standards and recommended practices and procedures.

International regulations or guidelines specifically applying to the marine disposal of mine tailings are not in place, but have been deemed as necessary (GESAMP 2016; Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022). As pipeline discharges and other land-based sources of marine pollution do not fall under the definition of dumping and hence fall beyond the regulatory scope of the LC/LP, this global legislation for the protection of marine environments is not applicable (GESAMP 2016; IMO 2022), except for the overall objective of protecting the marine environment from all sources of pollution. Both LC/LP and GESAMP noted a governance gap on global STD regulation (GESAMP 2016), and also OSPAR is considering the need for guidance on deep-sea disposal of mine tailings (OSPAR Commission 2017a). The LC/LP Secretariat commissioned a report on the issue (Vogt 2003). An international workshop on the impacts of mine tailings in the marine environment organized as joint IMO and GESAMP activity was held in Lima (Peru) in June 2015, with support from the Office for the LC/LP and Ocean Affairs, the INDEEP network, the Norwegian Research Council and DOSI (GESAMP 2016). The workshop aimed at providing a synthesis of the scientific understanding of DSTD impacts and identifying gaps, thus providing the basis for a development of international guidelines including best management practices. More recently, a joint project of national Norwegian governmental institutions and industry partners (NYKOS) aimed at increasing the knowledge base for submarine tailings disposal in Norway and developing guidelines and best available techniques for submarine tailings disposal in Norwegian fjords.

National guidelines specifically for DSTD have so far only been developed in Papua New Guinea (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010). As outcome of the Norwegian NYKOS Project, a document on guideline recommendations and best available techniques for submarine tailings in Norwegian fjords have been published (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019). Specific DSTD guidelines are supposed to include specific information for baseline studies, environmental impact assessments, monitoring during operations, closing plans and post closure monitoring (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010; Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019). The guidelines should be developed in collaboration with the scientific community and industry, to ensure that they are based on robust scientific knowledge and the latest analytical tools and methods available. Lastly, the guidelines should follow an adaptive management system, allowing for adjustment as new knowledge and new techniques become available (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022).

In 2016, a (non-binding) resolution from the International Union for Conservation of Nature called for stopping ongoing sea disposal of mine tailings and ban marine disposal from new mines. It was signed by 51 out of the 53 participants, and was only opposed by Norway and Turkey (IUCN 2016; ESA 2024). The resolution further asked for a regulation of submarine tailings disposal from land-based activities in the same manner as from disposal in the open sea, applying the general principles of the IMO, and the London Convention and Protocol.

Links between Submarine Tailings Disposal and Deep-Sea Mining

DSM activities have several pressures and impacts in common with the disposal of land mine tailings in the marine environment. Long-term disposal of fine-grained particles and their dispersal in the water column, enhanced sediment deposition and substrate alteration, often in deep-sea settings >1000 m, and the mobilization of toxic compounds from tailings are pressures to the environments that also result from DSM activities at the seafloor and the discharge of waste slurries back into the ocean after ore dewatering (Vare et al. 2018). Gravity flows are typical for DSTD and may also form during DSM depending on bathymetry (Gazis et al. 2025). Although the mineral resources of interest at the seafloor differ from the land-based resources (massive sulfides, polymetallic nodules, and cobalt crusts), characteristics of the discharged material may be similar to some extent (especially when comparing sulfide-containing tailings disposal and SMS mining plumes). Information on environmental risks and (long-term) impacts of marine tailings disposal and recovery and an evaluation of current practices and issues of its environmental management including regulatory aspects can (and should) thus be utilized as source of information in the process of developing environmental management regimes for future DSM. The GESAMP workshop in 2015 noted that both activities also face similar knowledge gaps and uncertainties related to limited knowledge on biota, plume impacts, ecotoxicology at high pressures, and ecosystem recovery. In 2017, a new GESAMP working group has been established (WG42, sponsored by IMO and UNEP), with the aim to provide independent advice on the impacts of wastes and other matter in the marine environment from mining operations, including land-based and marine minerals mining. A Working Group report on "Impacts of mine tailings waste matter in the marine environment from mining operations" was supposed to be finalized at the end of 2023 (GESAMP 50th annual session). At the time of writing, this report has not been published yet. Originally intended to also contain impacts of deep-sea mining, this part is now supposed to become a separate report. The decision to split the report and revise the part on DSM and revise ToR of WG42 followed discussions among the Lead Agencies, and in particular takes into account comments by the ISA). The GESAMP DSM report is now supposed to be undertaken by a new working group anticipated to be sponsored by ISA and UNEP members with expertise on the deep-sea environment and DSM, who will be recruited based on the revised terms of reference. The current status is unknown.

6.3.3.1 Norway

There are several EU-directives that affect the evaluation of mine waste management in Norway. The most important directives are the Directive on the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries (Directive 2006/21/EC) and the Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) implemented in Norwegian legislation by the Norwegian Waste Regulations, and the Water Regulations (Vannforskriften), respectively. The Mining Waste Directive distinguishes between disposal at sea and on land, and comprises both types of disposal (see also NEA (2019b) and Walder (2014) for an overview on relevant legislation in Norway).

The discharge of mine tailings into the sea is a common practice in Norway where large quantities are deposited into coastal fjords (Brooks et al. 2018). Six operations are currently active, with two more having approved permits to dispose mine tailings into Norwegian fjords in near future. Five of these are primarily industrial minerals/raw materials operations (Skaland Graphite AS: graphite; Sibelco: microcline/nepheline; Titania AS: ilmenite; Hustadmamor AS: calcite; Quartz Corp: quartz); and one is an iron ore mine (Rana Gruber ASA: magnetite, hematite). A valid discharge permit without current operation is hold by Sydvaranger Drift AS (iron ore). The two planned operations include one for industrial minerals (Engebø Rutile and Garnet AS: rutile and garnet) and one for copper (Nussir ASA). Furthermore, historic tailings deposition occurred in several fjords, from sulphide ore (Cu, Pb, Zn and Ni) and ilmenite mining. Details about the deposition sites of companies authorized to deposit mine tailings in water bodies and permit requirements can be found in ESA (2024).

A technical guidance document for the evaluation/characterization of tailings intended for sub-sea deposition (Walder 2014) has been issued by the Norwegian Mineral Industry, and was reviewed by SAMS. The guideline considers a range of potential approaches and tools for the characterization of a prospective receiving sub-sea environment; e.g. bottom flora, fauna, fish, water current, and water conditions; in addition to, methods for characterization of waste that will potentially be placed in a sub-sea tailings facility. More recently, general guidelines and best available techniques recommended for submarine tailings in Norwegian fjords have been developed as synthesis report of the NYKOS Project (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019). The report presents a summary of the comprehensive results of the project (addressing spreading of tailings particles in the water column, the behavior and toxicity of process chemicals, trace metal mobilization, ecotoxicological effects, long-term effects on benthic fauna and recolonization potential) as well as the outcomes of a synthesis and best available techniques workshop. The report also outlines relevant national legislation for the regulation of the submarine disposal of mine tailings in Norway, and provides summaries on the status of sea disposal of mine tailings in Norway, the U.S., Canada, Indonesia, Papua New Guinea, and the Philippines (and related environmental issues), and how disposal permits are governed in these countries. Recently, the EFTA Surveillance Authority (ESA) published a critical review of impacts of mine tailings disposal in Norwegian waters and the permitting process/permit obligations (ESA 2024). The report includes an overview on current STD practices in Norway, on hazards and extents of exposure, and known environmental effects (including chemical and ecological water body status based on WFD reporting and site-specific studies including monitoring and toxicity testing), on permitting requirements for assessment and management of risks (e.g., environmental monitoring) and addresses the issue of required exemptions to the WFD (see below). It further contains a bibliography with links to all existing STD permits in Norway.

The discharge of mining waste to fjords is controlled by case-by-case permitting that stipulates limits for quantities, frequencies and concentrations and contains requirements for monitoring (ESA 2024). Permits are issued by the Norwegian Environment Agency under the Norwegian Pollution Control Act and also contain a requirement to comply with the Water Framework Directive (for further details on core elements in discharge permits see ESA (2024). According to the WFD, that has been implemented by Norway, water bodies must meet the environmental objective of prevention of water body deterioration and of good ecological and chemical status by 2027 (Article 4(1)), unless an exemption has been applied: Member States will not be in breach of the Directive, if "failure to achieve good groundwater status, good ecological status or, where relevant, good ecological potential or to prevent deterioration in the status of a body of surface water or groundwater is *the result of new modifications to the physical characteristics of a surface water body...*" and, inter alia, the following condition applies: "*the reasons for new modifications are of overriding public interest and/or the benefits to the environment and to society of achieving the WFD objectives are outweighed by the benefits of the new modifications or alterations to human health, to the maintenance of human safety or to sustainable development*" (WFD Article 4(7)(c); see CIS-WFD 2017). Similar exceptions to achieving good status in its coastal and marine waters are included in the MSFD (article 14). Exemptions according to Article 4(7) can only be made when the deterioration of the water body is expected solely as a result of hydro-morphological changes and as a consequence of the disposal of mining tailings. Article 4(7) does not provide an exemption if deterioration caused by inputs of pollutants from point or diffuse sources drives the water body to a status below good (CIS-document 36). For the planned mine tailings disposal in the Førdefjord (see also box), it has been stated that particle dispersion would not have a negative impact outside the disposal site and also that the status of the water bodies would not deteriorate as a result of leaching from tailings (ESA 2017). The Norwegian WFD implementation has a somehow broader wording (Section 12(2)(b)) than the WFD: "The benefits for society of the new intervention or activities shall be greater than the loss of environmental quality", but is thought to reflect both alternative criteria, i.e. the reasons of overriding public interest and benefits to human health, the maintenance of human safety or to sustainable development (Bogard request to EFTA Court 2024). Concerns have been raised by NGOs and members of the public on the fact that mining companies are discharging

waste into water bodies and that this is threatening the chemical status of the water bodies and also the non-deterioration principle as expressed under the WFD.

The case Engebø Rutile and Garnet AS – a legal dispute

The application and validity of the WFD exemptions to STD highly debated in Norway. In a recent case of dispute, the legality of a disposal permit for a planned rutile and garnet mining project is questioned.

Norway approved a permit to the company Nordic Rutile (now Engebø Rutile and Garnet AS) for the disposal of mine tailings from a rutile mine in marine waters of Førdefjord in 2015. The permit conditions include concentration limits for particles that apply at the border of the deposit area and shall ensure that spreading outside the deposit area is minimized so that negative effects of the tailings deposition are kept to a minimum. The concentration of particles shall not exceed 2 mg/l 40 metres above the point of discharge and 3 mg/l at the edge of the planned disposal area. Deposition of particles is limited to 3 mm per year at the edge of the disposal area. To provide information on the effects of deposition, the permit also includes a requirement to monitor before, during, and after tailings deposition (GESAMP 2016; NEA 2019; ESA 2024).

The submarine tailings disposal will lead to a deterioration of the water status in the Førdefjorden-ytre surface water body contrary to Article 4(1)(a)(i) of the WFD. In its original pollution permit, the Norwegian Government sets out the reasons for applying the “overriding public interest” exception to the WFD environmental objectives (WFD Article 4(1)) for granting the permit. The permit decision is based on a weighting of environmental damage and negative impacts of the project against the benefits to society, and the responsible authority/ministry identified the future income from mining operations as the main benefit to Norwegian society. Several complaints concerning the permitting decisions by the Norwegian authorities were received by the ESA. The first complaint was closed in 2017 (ESA 2017), another one in 2021 (ESA 2021). Finally, two Norwegian environmental NGOs took legal action against the Norwegian State for granting the permit to Nordic Rutile before the Oslo district court. In January 2024, the Oslo District Court dismissed the application in full. Subsequently, both NGOs have appealed the judgment to the Borgarting Court of Appeal, now limited to the question of whether the requirement of “reasons [...] of overriding public interest” in Article 4(7)(c) of the WFD is fulfilled. The case concerns whether the derogation granted by the Norwegian authorities can be justified due to “reasons of overriding public interest”, in accordance with Article 4(7)(c) of the WFD (EFTA Court 2024). The Borgarting Court of Appeal requested an Advisory Opinion of the EFTA Court (established by the EFTA States as Court of justice) regarding the interpretation of Article 4(7) of the WFD (Bogarting Lagmannsrett 2024). One opinion to the EFTA court was provided by the ESA (ESA, 16.7.2024), and three more written statements were submitted to the EFTA court to this case by the European Commission, the Norwegian Government, and Friends of the Earth Norway and Young Friends of the Earth Norway). The EFTA court sent its final report back to the Borgarting Court <https://eftacourt.int/download/13-24-report-for-the-hearing/?wpdmdl=9970> (EFTA Court 2024), where the case is still pending at the time of writing. There is a judicial disagreement of whether or not article 4.7(c) calls for a *balancing of interests* between the advantages of a project causing a deterioration in the status of a water body and its negative impact on the water body, and whether there is an overriding public interest.

The maximum acceptable size of spatial footprints from tailings discharge both in the water column and at the seafloor is not generally regulated in Norway but decided case-by-case. While the dispersion of particles discharged into the water is regulated in the disposal permits through threshold values for particle concentrations at the boundary of disposal sites, there are no permit threshold values for metals in a spatial realm. A disposal site is an area that is selected for the disposal of tailings, delimited in extent and depth.

Together with the border area (an area outside the disposal site border that receives particles dispersed with the water current), a zone of influence can be defined, outside which the impact of particle dispersal is supposed to be below the limit for a negative ecological impact (NEA 2019a). The environmental permits contain a requirement to perform environmental monitoring in the context of submarine tailings disposal, including monitoring of the receiving environment (e.g., of water, sediment, or biota), and monitoring in accordance with the water regulations (ESA 2024). Both, for the environmental management of tailings disposal, and for monitoring under WFD, the concept of mixing zones (see **CHAPTER 6.4.1**) is applied in Norway. For the assessment of the chemical and ecological status of water bodies required under the WFD, national monitoring programmes are conducted. Exempted from status classification of the water body are all local stations for action-oriented monitoring of company discharges (regardless of which matrix they are monitored in) that are located within what is considered to be the **zone of influence** for the discharge (NEA 2018a). The Norwegian Environment Agency has developed a method for calculating the zone of influence surrounding a point source discharge and identifying local stations for monitoring water bodies affected by the discharge (NEA 2019b), in line with EU guidance to establish mixing zones and applicable for permit water monitoring. First, the dilution required to meet national water EQSs is calculated, based on discharge concentrations and reported AA-EQS. Then, the extent of the zone of influence is determined based on pre-defined dilution curves or numerical modelling, and local monitoring stations are identified. The calculation of the area of influence is not supposed to be a tool for assessing whether a discharge can be permitted or not, but only reflects the impact of an already permitted emission (NEA 2019b).

6.3.3.2 Papua New Guinea (PNG)

PNG has three active deep-sea tailings placement operations (Lihir, Simberi, and Ramu Nickel), two permitted one (Woodlark; Wafi Golpu) and one closed operation (Misima). The PNG Government engaged the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) to conduct an independent assessment of DSTP systems in PNG with consideration to international best practice and to prepare draft guidelines and criteria for mining operations in PNG involving DSTP. These guidelines have been published as appendix to the environmental report of the project (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010). The Guidelines include the consideration of feasibility studies and initial mine development (with the establishment of an environmental baseline), mining operations and monitoring (includes the application of a mixing zone), future mine closure plans and post-mining monitoring, and further specify the potential environmental risks to be considered through a site-specific EIA. The current legal status of the draft Guidelines remain a bit vague to the authors: As stated in Ref2014 the Guidelines were presented publically in 2008, published in 2009 and formally adopted by the government of PNG in 2012. Recent environmental impact assessments for the purpose of permit application stated that they are undertaken in accordance with the Draft General Guidelines for DSTP in PNG, to the maximum practicable extent (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018c).

6.3.3.3 Canada

Canada has a long history of submarine tailings disposal. In 1977, a new Canadian law was introduced (Metal Mining Liquid Effluent Regulations) specifying limits for the metal content of mine water (in liquid phase) and for suspended particles that could be disposed of in seawater (NEA 2019b). In 2002, the Metal and Diamond Mining Effluent Regulations came into force under the Fisheries Act, with the requirement of a non-acutely lethal effluent, and TSS limitation of not more than 15 mg/l monthly average, and no dilution (mixing zone) allowed to reach effluent limits, which practically bans all submarine tailings disposal (Kwong et al. 2019). There are several closed large-scale marine mine tailings disposal operations in Canada (Britannia Copper mine, BC; Jordan River Copper Mine, BC; Island Copper Mine, BC, Kitsault Molybdenum Mine, BC, Canada).

6.3.3.4 Operational thresholds

Mine tailings are unique compared to other industrial wastes disposed in offshore settings, with continuous disposal and enormous quantities deposited at the seafloor, sometimes over several decades. At the same time, this offshore activity is the least regulated one. While dredged material for example cannot be disposed in marine waters without passing stringent material testing applying threshold criteria of toxic metals and other compounds and/or toxicity testing, this is not required for marine tailings disposal where regulatory acceptance criteria are missing or are sporadic.

Few thresholds for pressure indicators are operational in the environmental management of marine mine tailings disposal, mostly relying on generic contaminant criteria from existing regulatory frameworks for water and sediment quality. In Norway, thresholds for dissolved contaminant are used to define spatial boundaries of the zone of influence in the water column, which is required both for permit monitoring and to exclude discharge-impacted monitoring stations from the Norwegian chemical and ecological status classification of water bodies within the WFD. Limits for suspended particles in a spatial realm are typically applied in the discharge permits (ESA 2024).

The PNG draft regulation for DSTD requests the monitoring of physical, chemical and biological conditions of sediment and water column to ensure that Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for both water and suspended particulate material are not to be exceeded outside a mixing zone, the size of which is to be agreed upon in the project-specific discharge permit. The PNG Water Quality Criteria, published in 2002 (PNG 2002), are the most obvious source of such criteria, however, especially the thresholds for dissolved metals are relatively high compared to other regulatory frameworks (e.g. Cu being >10 time higher than in ANZG). As can be seen in the two EIA examples provided below, also the ANZG criteria are used as operational thresholds for assessments of proposed projects in PNG. The potential environmental risks to be considered should include the assessment of the potential toxicity of the tailings and the transfer of toxic components to the pelagic food web. In **CHAPTER 6.4.4**, two DSTD operations are described with examples for the application of thresholds during impact assessment and monitoring.

Sedimentation thresholds are not operational for the environmental management of marine tailings disposal, although burial has been shown to directly affect benthic fauna and functional processes. Singaas et al. (2008) determined that instantaneous burial with 0.63 cm of natural sediment would affect 5% of the tested macrofauna species, which is often used as operational threshold for sedimentation in the context of offshore oil and gas operations (see **CHAPTER 6.1.3**). Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2022) conducted an exercise mapping different benthic impact classes for one of the Norwegian deposition sites using modelled sedimentation rates per year and the 0.63 cm sedimentation threshold of Smit et al. (2008a) together with a second burial effects threshold of 2 cm for tailings material based on sedimentation exposure experiments as class boundaries.

The gaps identified with respect to the application of existing sediment and water quality criteria to DSTP management (GESAMP 2016) relate to the limited number of contaminants for which values are available. Furthermore, these criteria were developed using continuous dissolved chronic exposure, and mostly were based on single-species data. Furthermore, existing criteria rely on surrogate species, and the applicability to the deep-sea species remains unclear. Concerns were also expressed about the unknown influence of deep-water environmental conditions on bioavailability, the effects of plumes of fine particulates on filter feeders, and the uncertainties in fluctuating exposure. Whole-sediment toxicity tests were identified as appropriate to for assessing contaminant bioavailability and risks of toxicity, and to derive site-specific guidelines (Simpson and Spadaro 2016).

6.4 Summary of key concepts of environmental management of offshore activities

Approaches for the environmental management of different offshore activities and thresholds operational in these assessments have been reported in the previous sections. Here, we highlight some of the overarching concepts, such as mixing zones in the water column, benthic impact zones, and tiered risk and impact assessment approaches that we think might be informative for the development of environmental regulations of DSM.

Thresholds are operational for different purposes, such as for impact prediction and as part of management and compliance monitoring plans. Different types of thresholds are in use. As summarized in **Table 6.1**, both, thresholds for environmental pressures and for indicators of biological or ecological effects are applied in the management of offshore activities. Most common are pressure thresholds, that are either set for individual substances (generic water and sediment quality criteria such as ANZG DGVs, EU WFD EQS, U.S. EPA WQC; OSPAR PNECs) or for activity-specific stressors such as suspended particles and burial of dredging and drilling waste discharge activities, or they are set as acceptable limits for whole effluent discharges. The derivation of such limits for whole effluents (such as produced water, drilling mud, mine tailings, or dredge spoil) is based on project-specific toxicity testing of the material in different dilutions, resulting in an effects size (e.g., PNEC, NOEC) that is expressed as fraction of undiluted effluent in a receiving environment (seawater). The limits represent effluent concentrations that are safe for the environment and the more toxic an effluent is, the higher is the required dilution to achieve this limit. As illustration example: for drilling mud in the U.S., the minimum fraction at which the effects size (LC_{50}) is fixed at 3% (i.e., the limit is set at a maximum dilution of 33.3%). Operational thresholds are often applied at predicted spatial boundaries of impact in the water column or at the seafloor. In combination with numerical modelling, the spatial extent of impacted water quality can be predicted, and thresholds often have to be met on a spatial boundary or in a temporal realm. Typically, the dimensions of impact zones are constructed by the proponent as part of an EIA, which the regulating authority agrees upon in the discharge permit. Only rarely, the spatial or temporal extents where thresholds must be met are set in a regulation (e.g., at 100 m distance, the PW concentrations will not exceed the chronic NOEC, or: after 4h, the dredge spoil concentrations will not exceed 0.01 of acute LC_{50}). Thresholds are also directly set for biological or ecological effects sizes of e.g., toxicity, bioaccumulation, or biomarkers, which are most commonly applied in tiered assessments of dredged material and in large monitoring programs. Here, a breach of lower tiers primarily addressing pressures to the environment triggers further assessments against higher tier thresholds for biological effects, to provide more confidence in risks and effects. Sometimes, also narrative thresholds are used, such as 'no statistically significant effect on lethal acute endpoints', e.g., to assess sediment quality. How conservatively thresholds are set for the same activities varies significantly between countries and regulations. In addition, the concepts themselves vary, e.g., for the assessment of dredged material and of produced water.

Table 6.1: *Types of assessment criteria (thresholds) operational in the environmental management of offshore activities.*

Type of assessment criteria	Example of application	When is the criteria met? Examples	Example references
Addressing a pressure			
thresholds of metals conc. in water and sediment	STD discharge, oil & gas PW discharge, assessment of dredged material for disposal	when predicted or measured concentrations are below the threshold, at the boundary of an impact zone	ANZG, 2018; OSPAR, 2014; Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture, 2018; NADG, 2009; U.S. EPA, 1991
thresholds of conc. of suspended particulate matter (SPM)	Dredging, STD	when predicted or measured concentration below the threshold for an impact category, or at the boundary of a disposal site	EPA-WA, 2021; ESA, 2024
thresholds for sedimentation depth (burial)	prediction of drilling mud deposition; prediction of dredged material deposition; prediction of tailings material deposition	when predicted thickness is below the threshold	Smit et al., 2008; EPA-WA, 2021; Ramirez-Llodra et al., 2022
Addressing a biological effects size			
99% protection PW chronic WET-PNEC	PW discharge	PEC<PNEC at 50 m distance at boundary of mixing zone	ENI Australia, 2017
chronic WET-PNEC	Prediction of safe PW concentration	At 500 m distance, the predicted PW concentration, expressed as fraction of 100% or dilution, is equal or less than the site-specific whole effluent PNEC (PEC/PNEC<1)	BEIS, 2020
Environmental Impact Factor (EIF)	Prediction of safe PW concentration and monitoring	when EIF<10 at 500 m distance at the boundary of the mixing zone	BEIS, 2020
chronic WET-NOEC	Prediction of safe PW concentration	predicted PW concentration must be equal or lower than chronic NOEC of PW, expressed as fraction of 100% PW, at 100 m distance	U.S. EPA, 2024
acute WET-LC ₅₀ ≥3%	Prediction of safe drilling mud concentration	daily minimum and a monthly average minimum effluent toxicity limitation: acute LC ₅₀ of drilling mud, expressed as fraction of 100% drilling mud, must be 3% or larger	U.S. EPA, 2024
1% of acute WET-LC ₅₀	Prediction of safe dredge spoil concentration	the fraction of the dredge spoil should not exceed 0.01 of LC ₅₀ (expressed as fraction of 100% dredge spoil), to be met everywhere in the water column 4h after disposal	US EPA, 1991; USACE, 2016
chronic WET-EC ₁₀ /2	Monitoring of water quality	dilution of an effluent (as % effluent) at the boundary of a moderate protection zone should be greater than that represented by the lowest chronicEC ₁₀ (i.e. the EC ₁₀ for the most sensitive species) divided by a safety factor of 2.	EPA-WA, 2017
20% of an endpoint relative to control (e.g. chronic toxicity)	Assessment of dredged material for disposal		NADG, 2009
90 th percentile of natural range of a biological or ecological indicator	Monitoring sediment quality		EPA-WA, 2017

Type of assessment criteria	Example of application	When is the criteria met? Examples	Example references
10% mortality	Prediction and monitoring of dredging activities, assessment of dredged material	mean mortality of any one species exposed to proposed dredged sediment does not exceed the mean mortality observed with reference sediments by more than 10%	EPA-WA, 2021; USACE, 2016
Biomarker concentrations (e.g., AChE)	Water quality monitoring		Burgeot et al., 2022
50% mortality	Water quality monitoring		Burgeot et al., 2022
Hazard quotient <60% for benthic communities	Moderate risk sediment class, monitoring MPA		Piccardo et al 2024
Hazard quotient <3 for bioassay battery	Moderate risk sediment class, monitoring MPA		Piccardo et al 2024
Hazard quotient <250 for biomarkers	Moderate risk sediment class, monitoring offshore oil activity		Regoli et al., 2019
Narrative			
No statistically significant effect on lethal acute endpoints	sediment quality		EPA-WA, 2017

6.4.1 MIXING ZONES

A mixing zone is a limited area or volume of water where the initial dilution of a point discharge takes place in the environment and where certain numeric water quality criteria may be exceeded. This implies that not all water quality criteria need to be met at the exact point where pollutants are discharged into a receiving water, but that water quality criteria apply outside and at the edge of the mixing zone (**Figure 6.2**).

Mixing zones allowing for an initial dilution of waste effluents is considered in many regulatory water quality frameworks and guidelines, for example in the US (U.S. EPA 2006a, 2010, 2014), Australia and New Zealand (ANZG 2018h, mixing zone; NT EPA 2013), Papua New Guinea (State of Papua New Guinea 2002) and the EU (ECHA 2016; CIS-WFD 2010a). The concept of mixing zones is typically applied for domestic waste effluents (e.g., WWTP). Legislation for the environmental management of marine offshore activities partly includes this concept, e.g., for the discharge of oil and gas effluents (PW, drilling waste) in the EU (OSPAR Commission 2012b; IOGP 2020; BEIS 2020) and US (U.S. EPA 2024), for the disposal of dredged material in the US (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016 USACE and USEPA 2016), and Australia (Australian Government 2009), or for deep-sea disposal of mine tailings in Papua New Guinea (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010).

The dimensions of the mixing zones (volume, or diameter) are in some cases pre-set by the regulating authority. Alternatively, the contractor proposes a size of the mixing zone based on the required dilution to meet specific water quality or toxicity assessment criteria at the mixing zone boundary and numerical dispersion modeling, considering general narrative limitations by the regulator. In this case, the permitting authority decides case-by-case whether the size is appropriate under the premises to keep the mixing zone as small as practicably possible.

In the US, a National Pollution Discharge Elimination System of permits (NPDES) and concepts of Best Practicable Technology (BPT) and Best Available Technology (BAT) for limiting effluent discharges have been established. General limitations for the definition of mixing zones include that pollutant concentrations within any mixing zone should not be lethal to mobile, migrating, and drifting organisms in the waterbody, do not impair the designated use of the water body as a whole, or do not endanger critical areas such as breeding or spawning grounds or habitats of endangered species (U.S. EPA 2014). In the guidelines for issuance of NPDES permits for the discharge of pollutants from a point source into the territorial seas, the contiguous zone, and the oceans (CWA title 40, chapter I, subchapter D, Part 125, Subpart M), a *mixing zone* is defined as the zone extending from the sea's surface to the seabed and extending laterally to a **distance of 100 meters** in all directions from the discharge point(s) **or to the boundary of the zone of initial dilution** as calculated by a plume model, whichever is greater. Following dilution as measured at the boundary of the mixing zone, discharge of pollutants must not exceed the limiting permissible concentration (LPC) for the liquid, suspended particulate and solid phases of the waste material as described in the Ocean Dumping Criteria (§ 227.27). The LPC is the concentration which, **after allowance for initial mixing**, does not exceed applicable WQC or other assessment criteria for in the liquid, suspended particulate and solid phase. The regulation does not specify whether the applicable WQC is the acute or chronic criteria, but according to the NPDES writer' manual (U.S. EPA 2014), the chronic criteria should apply.

In Australia, mixing zones are regulated at the state or territory level. If mixing zones are to be applied, then they should be as small as practicable (ANZG 2018h). The purpose of a mixing zone is to manage the controlled discharge of soluble, non-bioaccumulatory toxicants whose impacts on local biota are primarily related to their concentration (NT EPA 2013). Mixing zones in Australia are not applicable for managing the discharge of nutrients or particulate substances. In the EU, Article 4 of Directive 2008/105/EC (EQS directive) allows member states to designate mixing zones when the pollutant concentrations exceed the EQS values at effluent discharges. Within the mixing zones the concentration of one or more of the priority substances listed in Part

A of Annex I, may exceed the relevant EQS values. Some guidance on the maximum size of a mixing zone is provided in the Technical Background Document on Identification of Mixing Zones (CIS-WFD 2010a). For coastal waters regulated under the WFD, a maximum radius of 500 m around the discharge point is proposed.

The following paragraph lists some of the specific mixing zone fulfillments required for permitting discharges from offshore industry activities:

US effluent limitations for PW and drilling mud and drill cuttings are defined in CWA title 40, chapter I, subchapter N, Part 435. The General Permit For **Offshore Oil and Gas Activities** in the Eastern Gulf of Mexico (U.S. EPA 2024) specifies that such effluent limitations must be met at 100 m distance from the discharge point. In the case of PW, the limiting concentration, provided as minimum dilution, is based on chronic toxicity testing. The UK national implementation of the OSPAR RBA for PW discharges (BEIS 2020) combines a strict limit of 500 m diameter for accepted exceedance of a water quality criterion around the discharge point with the requirement to subsequently assess compliance with a volume limit based on dispersion modelling in case the strict 500 m limit is breached. The permissible mixing zone for **DSTP** of the Lihir gold mine in PNG extends radially 1.8 km to the north and 2.3 km to the south-east of the outfall, with compliance with the PNG Water Quality Criteria for marine waters required at the mixing zone boundary (SAMS 2007). In the United States, the EPA in conjunction with the Department of the Army has developed guidelines for evaluating discharges of **dredged material** into navigable waters (40 CFR Part 230), which include provisions for determining the acceptability of mixing zones (230.11(f)). Limiting permissible concentrations (LPC) (as defined in Part 227.27) shall not be exceeded **beyond the boundaries of the disposal site** (consists of a bottom surface area and any overlying volume of water) **during initial mixing**, and shall not be exceeded at any point in the marine environment after initial mixing (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016). According to the criteria for ocean dumping (§ 227.29), initial mixing is defined to be the dispersion of liquid, suspended particulate, and solid phases of a waste which occurs within **four hours after dumping (Figure 6.3)**. Locations and boundaries of disposal sites are chosen in a way that temporary perturbations in water quality or other environmental conditions during initial mixing caused by disposal operations anywhere within the site can be expected to be reduced to normal ambient seawater levels or to undetectable contaminant concentrations (§ 228). Whether “applicable WQC” of individual substances are chronic or acute criteria is not specified, neither in the national ocean discharge criteria (Part 227.27, see above) nor in the dredging disposal testing guidelines (U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016). In the provided case studies in U.S. EPA (1991), the use of acute thresholds is documented (which is in contrast to the application of chronic criteria in NPDES writer’ manual (see above; U.S. EPA 2014).

Figure 6.2: *Mixing zone concept. Spatial dimensions (such as 500 m) either set by the regulating authority or identified as small as possible by the operator, using best available techniques and permitted by the permitting authority. Offshore activities applying this concept include the management of produced water discharge and of marine mine tailings discharge. T: threshold defining the boundary.*

Figure 6.3: Concept of initial dilution. Assessed risks for adverse impacts of disposal of dredged material in the water column after initial dilution (4h after stopping of discharge). Breach would initiate a tiered assessment with further LoE. T: threshold defining the boundary.

6.4.2 IMPACT CATEGORIZATION SCHEMES

Some frameworks define spatial impact categories in a zonation scheme, with the individual zones differing in the extent of acceptable damage and hence level of ecological protection (LEP). Criteria as limits of ‘acceptability’ are used to define the boundaries between the zones (**Figure 6.4**), and, in case of point discharges, the level of ecological protection generally increases with distance from the source. Setting the spatial dimension requires predictive numerical modelling. A higher threshold defines the inner (i.e. closest to the source) boundary of the zone where that level of ecological protection is predicted to be achieved. The outer boundary for that zone coincides with the inner boundary of the adjacent zone where a more highly protected (less impacted) category is predicted to be achieved (EPA-WA 2016).

Figure 6.4: Concept of impact classification. Zones with different levels of acceptable harmful impacts to the ecosystem as function of distance, with different associated levels of ecological protection (LEP) for environmental management. The population of classes of impact with respect to acceptable effects requires information on biological and ecological effects, potential for recovery etc., based on monitoring data. Boundaries are either defined by proxy thresholds (e.g., for a dissolved metal, or suspended particles), or combined thresholds for multiple pressures (e.g., $TV_{SPM} + TV_{sed.rate}$), could also be set as Quality Index (QI) integrating several parameters (e.g., SPM, diss. metals, biomarkers, bioassays).

In the technical Guidance for Protecting the Quality of Western Australia’s Marine Environment (EPA-WA 2016) an environmental quality management framework (EQMF) is presented that supports the design of fit-for-purpose modelling and monitoring programs to spatially define, assess and manage potential impacts of proposals on marine environmental quality. The EQMF can be used to address management of entire areas,

or cumulative effects of point and non-point source discharges on marine environmental quality. The framework defines different levels of ecological protection (LEPs) for the environmental quality objective “maintain ecosystem integrity”, that each correspond to a different environmental health condition and can be applied spatially. Environmental quality criteria (EQC) quantitatively specify the environmental quality conditions that are required for the achievement of each zone in the water column or at the seafloor (i.e., they provide limits of acceptable change for the different levels of protection for key elements, such as “ecosystem processes”, “biodiversity”, “abundance and biomass of marine life” and “quality of water, biota, sediment”). EQC have been defined for many contaminants and physico-chemical parameters of ecological concern in the Australia and New Zealand water quality guidelines (recent version is ANZG 2018b), and can be used as benchmarks against which environmental monitoring data are compared in order to determine whether environmental quality objectives have been met. In an example for **wastewater discharge** with Cu as major contaminant, the concept of spatial zones with different levels of protection is applied. Three **different levels of ecological protection** were defined (high, moderate, low), using a set of thresholds for dissolved Cu to define the boundaries between the zones (95% GV and 90% ANZG GV). The spatial extent of these zones is predicted using a numerical modelling approach. To decide whether the anticipated LEP is achieved, the 95th percentile value of the stressor concentration at a monitoring site is compared to the associated EQC. If below, this means that for most of the time the concentration should be below the specified environmental quality criterion for that level of ecological protection.

For dredging projects in Western Australia, a Technical Guidance for environmental impact assessments of marine **dredging** proposals sets out a methodology that proponents can use for impact prediction, assessment and management of dredging proposals on marine biota – particularly benthic communities (EPA-WA 2021). The framework sets out a **zonation scheme approach** that is expected to be used to present impact predictions. This approach distinguishes benthic zones of high impact (ZOHI), zones of moderate impact (ZOMI), and zones of influence (ZOI), that are separated by boundaries defined by tolerance thresholds for pressure indicators. Typically, the thresholds combine numerical values for one or more pressures and a temporal component (duration, frequency). The guideline presents two sets of thresholds for the different zones: named probable (less conservative) and possible (more conservative) effects thresholds that are used as management target and compliance target, respectively, in project-related monitoring programs.

Ramirez-Llodra et al. (2022) exemplified colour-coded **benthic impact categories** for a **marine mine tailing disposal** project in Norway. The class boundaries are defined by two different thresholds for sedimentation (0.63 cm and 2 cm), combined with modeled prediction of annual sedimentation rates at the seafloor.

For **monitoring** purposes of impact zones, an approach integrating the monitoring of pressure and state indicators is recommendable. EPA-WA (2021) recommends that management monitoring should involve monitoring of biological effects besides that of pressure, to increase confidence in validity of predicted zones and to allow for a refinement of tolerance threshold values according to local conditions.

6.4.3 HIERARCHY OF TRIGGERS FOR MANAGEMENT ACTION

For the environmental management of offshore activities and for environmental quality assessments within water body monitoring programs, hierarchical triggers can be used to initiate staged management actions or to come to a management decision, according to increasing levels of risk. The **categorization of risk levels** can be presented in a color-coded traffic-light scheme (**Figure 6.5**).

Figure 6.5: Generalized hierarchy of action triggers (T1 and T2) in a traffic-light scheme, which, when breached, trigger different management actions or decisions. The triggers present the boundaries between different levels of risk/harm.

The hierarchical concepts are either dimension-less or embedded in spatial zones with different management targets/level of protection, as part of environmental management and monitoring plans. There are different ways to set triggers indicating lower and higher levels of risk, respectively. Early-warning triggers can be set for easy to measure pressure indicators and higher-tier triggers set for indicators better constraining the risk for biological effects (i.e., state indicators). Alternatively, the same set of (pressure indicator) triggers can be used, varying in the numerical values (concentration, duration) according to lower or higher level of risk indicated in case the trigger is breached, i.e., how conservatively they are set.

Any tiered assessment in decision-making frameworks involve hierarchical triggers of action or decision, e.g. the **quality assessments of contaminated marine sediments or of dredged sediment proposed for ocean disposal**. The simplest approach involves the application of two chemical action levels (AL) to decide whether dredged material can be disposed in the ocean or not (<AL1: suitable for disposal; AL1>x<AL2: further studies required to proof or disproof biological effects; >AL2: dredge spoil not suitable for disposal). More complex assessments involve several LoE, with lower triggers addressing pressures (e.g., total or bioavailable metal concentrations in bulk sediment or sediment elutriate) and higher level triggers addressing effects (e.g., toxicity, bioaccumulation) to evaluate whether there is indeed an environmental risk associated with exceedance of early-tier thresholds.

Monitoring programs to assess the **quality of marine environments in Western Australia** apply a tiered management system with hierarchical triggers of action (EPA-WA 2016, **Figure 6.6**). Environmental quality indicators are used to assess environmental quality objectives and typically relate to water, sediment or biota quality, environmental/ecological processes, abundance and biomass and/or biodiversity measures. Addressing the level of risk, two sets of **environmental quality criteria** are defined for these indicators: relatively simple and easy to measure environmental quality guidelines (**EQG**) providing early warning of potential environmental effects and more robust environmental quality standards (**EQS**) further along the pressure-response pathway indicating if the level of risk is no longer acceptable and trigger management to prevent environmental harm or pollution (**Figure 6.6** left). EQGs are typically defined as limits for pressure indicators and if the EQG is not met then there is some uncertainty as to whether the associated environmental quality objective has been achieved and a more detailed assessment against an EQS is triggered. EQS are threshold numerical values or narrative statements that indicate a level which if not met indicates there is a

significant risk that the associated environmental quality objective has not been achieved and a management response is required. This response will focus on identifying the cause (or source) of the exceedance and then reducing the load of the contaminant of concern (i.e. source control) and may also require *in situ* remediation work to be undertaken (EPA-WA 2016). EQS are typically defined for state indicators such as toxicity, bioaccumulation, or direct ecological changes, but can also represent limits for refined pressure indicators (such as bioavailable metal concentrations). Increasing confidence can be reached if multiple lines of evidence with several EQS are applied in a tiered management, to give greater certainty that an effect has or has not occurred. Each consecutive EQS would be for an indicator situated further along the pressure/ response pathway and provide greater certainty of environmental effect. Breaching an EQG/EQS initiates further assessment, and a management action is triggered if the highest tier EQS is breached.

Figure 6.6: Left: tiered (hierarchical) environmental quality monitoring concept in Western Australia (modified from EPA-WA 2016). Right: Levels of harm concept of Leduc et al. (2024) for the environmental management of DSM.

The implementation of an environmental quality monitoring program in Western Australia is exemplified for the heavily used Cockburn Sound in Perth's coastal waters (EPA-WA 2017). Here, a range of environmental quality criteria for protecting the marine ecosystem from the effects of toxicants and other stressors in marine waters and marine sediment are presented. The criteria that are available for different LoEs are to be used in a tiered assessment (see **Table 5.6** in **CHAPTER 5.6**). When considering sediment quality, for example, early warning EQG thresholds for metal concentrations in sediments can be applied. If not met, a more detailed assessment of sediment quality is triggered that involves different variables tested against their EQS. This can involve bioavailable metal concentrations in the sediment, metal concentrations in pore water, sediment toxicity, and direct biological or ecological measures in a tiered approach. The overall EQS for management action is triggered if a higher tier biological assessment (toxicity, direct biological/ecological measures) shows a breach of the respective EQS.

An example for the use of hierarchical triggers of action in a **Monitoring and Management Framework for a petroleum activity** project is provided for Goodwyn Alpha in Western Australia (Woodside 2018). Considering the Technical Guidance for Protecting the quality of Western Australia's marine environment (EPA-WA 2016) and consistent with the principles of the Australian National Water Quality Management Strategy, the project framework makes use of low tier triggers and high tier environmental performance standards for

monitoring of Produced Water discharges. To determine if acceptable limits (no impacts from PW beyond the approved mixing zone) have been exceeded routine monitoring of trigger values is undertaken. If a trigger value is met uncertainty whether ecosystem integrity is still being maintained arises and further investigation against the environmental performance standards is required.

Leduc et al. (2024) defined three different **levels of harm for future deep-sea mining activities** according to an increasing intensity or magnitude of expected impact – detectable, significant, and serious - with a lower 'threshold' and a higher 'limit' as boundaries between these levels that would initiate different management actions. Below the threshold, no management action is deemed necessary, while at the level of significant harm (i.e., between threshold and limit), avoidance and minimization management responses should start, and above the limit for the level of serious harm all activities would need to be stopped. Proposed as monitoring concept for an EMMP, this dimensionless traffic-light approach is not yet embedded in a spatial and/or temporal realm. Populating the different levels of harm and setting appropriate thresholds defining the boundaries will only be possible with better ecosystem knowledge and effects monitoring data and requires adaptive management strategies in EMMPs. Based on current knowledge, Leduc et al. (2024) suggest to define the thresholds indicating *significant harm* to key species or to ecosystem function in relation to baseline conditions, such as a statistically significant difference outside the range of natural variability. As limits that if exceeded would indicate that *serious harm* has occurred they suggest indicators of effects that affect a specific proportion of a habitat, or are irreversible, or involve a massive biomass reduction or extinction of a key species.

For the **assessment of hazardous substances and their biological effects** within **OSPAR** regions, an approach has been developed that integrates monitoring data for metal contaminants and biological effects indicators (biomarkers of exposure and effects) with bioassays, to derive an overall assessment criterion for the environmental status (Vethaak et al. 2017; Burgeot et al. 2022). Depending on the assessment outcomes for monitoring sites, visualized in a multistep traffic-light scheme (see **Table 5.6** in **CHAPTER 5.6**), appropriate environmental management actions can be prompted (such as no action, conduct further biological tests, adjust monitoring frequency, verify findings through targeted biological effects or benthic community analysis, consider resource management issues) (Vethaak et al. 2017; Bignert et al. 2004). This monitoring approach also addresses the assessment of Good Environmental Status (GES) in the MSFD as required by descriptor 8 ("Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects"). Such monitoring data can also be used to **populate predicted impact zones** according to the respective management objective/level of protection (e.g., no mortality) of impact in an adaptive management framework. This is of special relevance for offshore projects in areas where only few locally relevant effects data are available, such as for future deep-sea mining activities, and where any predicted impact zonation necessarily comes with high uncertainty and low confidence.

Figure 6.7: Combining traffic-light approach with spatial zonation of impact categories in the context of dredging activities. Combination of spatial zonation and alert traffic light approach at monitoring sites within and at the boundaries of the different management zones (MZ).

Hierarchical triggers of management actions are also applied in the context of **dredging operations in Western Australia** (see Fisher et al. 2019; EPA-WA 2021). As part of an EIA, benthic impact zones for a dredging project are predicted (ZOHI, ZOMI, ZOI), with the individual zones differing in the extent of acceptable damage. The boundaries between the zones are represented by pressure-based tolerance thresholds of acceptability that have been derived for sensitive key communities and are used as management targets. Pressures within ZOI must be lower than the threshold defining the outer boundary of ZOMI, and similarly, pressures within ZOHI must be lower than the threshold defining the outer ZOHI boundary. The monitoring programs for dredging projects are supposed to consider both, monitoring informing (adaptive) management and compliance monitoring (EPA-WA 2021). Monitoring sites should be established in the identified impact zones, focusing on locations within ZOMI and close to the boundary of ZOMI/ZOI, and primarily monitor dredging-related pressures. The thresholds used to categorize the predicted impacts are typically comprised of a numerical value for one or a combination of pressures, such as DLI and turbidity, and a temporal component (as averaging period). For management monitoring in the benthic impact zones, a series of tiered triggers can be used, based on the same pressure variables but set at different concentrations and/or a different duration of averaging (**Figure 6.7**). An early warning alert before a management target at a zone boundary is likely to be breached could for example be set at higher average daily light levels and/or lower turbidity, and/or a shorter averaging period. **Table 6.2** provides an example: if the management threshold is based on a 14-day running mean turbidity and DLI, exceedance of the same trigger over a shorter 7-day running mean would indicate that water quality conditions may be nearing the trigger value, providing an early indicator that management actions may be required. For greater confidence in effects, monitoring of pressure-related tolerance triggers can be coupled with monitoring of biological responses (bioindicators), and the results can be used to adapt management, validate impact predictions made in the EIA and adapt generic tolerance thresholds to local conditions.

Table 6.2: Example of tiered triggers that could be used for corals as part of a tiered management system designed to provide early warning of conditions approaching the management target for the boundary between the ZOMI and ZOI. Considering additive effects of sediment deposition, elevated SSC and reduced light availability; Tier 3 trigger is the probable effects threshold (i.e., the management target) of ZOMI (EPA-WA 2021) that would be triggered if turbidity for a 14-day averaging period exceeds 10 NTU – if not triggered, then monitoring site is located in ZOI.

	Threshold type	Averaging period	MT		
			NTU	SSC	DLI
Tier 1 trigger	Running mean (days)	7d	>6.5	>11.7	<2.3
Tier 2 trigger		7d	>10.0	>18.0	<1.1
Tier 3 trigger		14 d	>10.0	>18.0	<1.1

A tiered assessment with hierarchical triggers could also be applied for monitoring of offshore projects with point discharges, within or at the boundary of a mixing zone in the water column (e.g., STD).

6.4.4 IMPACT PREDICTION: CASE STUDIES

6.4.4.1 Solwara I project

The Solwara I project was expected to become the first commercial operation for exploitation of polymetallic Seafloor Massive Sulphide (SMS) deposits, located at approximately 1,600 m water depth on the seabed of the Bismarck Sea, New Ireland Province, Papua New Guinea (PNG). As part of the initial environmental permit application, the mining company Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited submitted an EIS as the statutory basis for the environmental assessment of the project in 2008 (Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008). Since then, mining and environmental licenses were approved by the permitting authorities, but the project had been stopped in the meantime, and PNG released a moratorium for deep-sea mining. Only recently, Sustainable Mining Solutions (<https://miningdataonline.com/property/3285/Solwara-1-Project.aspx>), who have acquired the assets of Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited, announced the successful completion of a Pilot Test Programme during Q2/Q3 2024, furthering the development of the Solwara 1 Project with a new mining system (<https://miningdataonline.com/property/3285/Solwara-1-Project.aspx>).

As part of the EIS, the potential environmental impacts from dewatering plumes pelagic and benthic organisms were investigated. Such plumes form when after ore dewatering on board the vessel, seawater and remaining sediments are discharged into the ocean. At Solwara I, material was proposed to be discharged into the deep sea at a rate of 1,000 m³/h and an estimated 5,000 mg/L maximum fine sediment of grain sizes <8 µm. The EIS proposed to set a **mixing zone** where dewatering plumes are dispersed and diluted and water quality criteria not necessarily need to be met. To constrain the boundaries of impact to water quality, calculations of required dilution factors to meet the ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) water quality guidelines for dissolved metals and suspended particle concentrations (TSS) were conducted, together with dilution calculation to achieve no toxicity. For monitoring, ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) water quality guidelines are required to be met at and beyond the mixing zone boundary. The research institute CSIRO was contracted by Nautilus to determine physical and chemical properties in sediment samples, to conduct elutriate tests to determine the potential for release of contaminants from particles in ore dewatering plumes, and to conduct elutriate toxicity tests to assess the toxicity to organisms in the water column (Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008, Appendix 7). The elutriate tests involved shaking the crushed sample in representative seawater to investigate metal release processes under various conditions of time, particle size, mineral type (metal concentrations and properties) and total suspended solids (TSS) concentration on metal release from the samples. Charles Darwin University was engaged to conduct further elutriate testing to determine required

dilutions of the discharge plume depending on the effects of time and temperature (Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008, Appendix 9).

The results of elutriate tests carried out with representative ore material and seawater (ratio of 1:10) at representative temperatures and durations of exposure indicated that the metal controlling the number of dilutions required to meet ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) guidelines was zinc, requiring a 600-fold dilution. Hydrodynamic modelling indicates that this dilution will be achieved 85 m from the point of discharge. However, the results of the CSIRO study clearly revealed the strong influence of mineral composition on the mobilized metal content in elutriate tests (i.e., concentrations of individual metals, which can vary by orders of magnitude), which has a direct impact on the calculation of the mixing zone. Plumes of suspended sediment formed from material entrained in the return water discharge are proposed to require a 4,200-fold dilution to meet an ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) guideline value for total suspended solids of 1.2 mg/L (close to the natural background range of 0.1 to 6.6 mg/L with a mean of 1.2 mg/L). For the purposes of this impact assessment, a conservative dilution of 5,000 has been adopted for return water discharge as being necessary to meet the ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) guidelines for all contaminants discharged to the environment. On average (i.e., for 183 days per year), plumes will not extend more than 900 m beyond the point of discharge (and cover an area of 0.81 km²) before meeting the protective target TSS concentration. The maximum distance plumes will travel before meeting the TSS target is 4.2 km, at which point it will cover an area of 11.6 km²; however, this is expected to occur less than 37 days per year. Based on chronic toxicity tests with serially diluted elutriate waters prepared from sediment/chimney mixtures and seawater, dilutions of up to 700 times would be required to result in no toxicity from the elutriate waters to algae and copepods, which is smaller than the dilutions required to meet the TSS threshold (hence, the TSS-based dilution will be protective for algae and copepods). Further LoE addressed bioaccumulation and biomagnification to assess the potential for contaminants to accumulate via the food chain into top-order species such as surface schooling mackerel and tuna, which revealed low risks.

It is noted here, that the cited ANZECC and ARMCANZ (2000) target of 1.2 mg/L for suspended particles (TSS) refers to the Queensland tropical marine region >10 km offshore, see Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality 2000 Volume 2 Aquatic Ecosystems — Rationale and Background Information. The more recent GV for the Queensland wet tropics marine offshore region is 0.7 mg/kg (State of Queensland 2009), derived as the 80th percentile of a reference dataset.

6.4.4.2 Wafi-Golpu Project

The Wafi-Golpu project is a proposed gold and copper mine in PNG. Gold and Cu are predominantly hosted in disseminated and vein-style Cu sulphides in porphyries and in copper mineral and pyrite mineralization in epithermal high-sulphidation overprints in metasedimentary and volcanic host rocks. The potential environmental impacts arising from the planned subsea disposal of tailings from the mine (DSTP) on the offshore marine pelagic and benthic environment have been assessed in an environmental impact statement (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018d). At the time of writing, the project received the environmental permit based on the EIS, but no mining license has been issued yet. The submarine outfall is planned at 200 m water depth, and a majority of the tailings are expected to form a density current that flows down the steep submarine slope below the outfall down to the bottom of the Markham Canyon. Subsurface tailings plumes comprised of highly dilute fine tailings solids (generally with a particle size diameter less than 20µm) and tailings liquor (i.e., process water containing residual trace metals, reagents and chemicals) are predicted to form a dispersing plume shearing off from the tailings density current into the water column. Because these plumes are so dilute they will be neutrally buoyant and initially will neither rise nor fall, but spread out horizontally as they are transported laterally by ocean currents at the depth at which they form (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture

2018c). Prior to entering the DSTP outfall pipelines, the tailings slurry will be diluted with seawater, in a mix/de-aeration tank in a ratio of 1:4 (v/v).

The EIS proposed to set a mixing zone around the discharge point. To define the mixing zone, a priority (proxy) contaminant should be identified based on the maximum dilution required to meet the respective PNG water quality criterion. Using the results of numerical modelling, the spatial dimensions of the mixing should be calculated where PNG water quality criteria (PNG Environment (Water Quality Criteria) Regulation 2002) for the priority contaminant and hence all other contaminants are met at the boundary. Considering these outcomes, the regulatory mixing zone for the DSTP discharge has to be set by the PNG government. The dissolved component of the tailings discharge after dilution within the mixing zone will be required to comply with the PNG water criteria at the boundary of the mixing zone.

The ecotoxicological investigations have been conducted by CSIRO (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018a), who (1) investigated the chemical composition of the two tailings in comparison to Australian WQGVs and SQGVs, and to PNG water quality criteria, (2) determined tailings dilutions required to meet WQGVs and SQGVs and PNG water quality criteria (based on a time series at constant tailings dilution and on tailings dilution series experiments, respectively), and (3) assessed the toxicity of a diluted tailings liquor to marine aquatic organisms and derived a 'safe' dilution of tailings liquor. Toxicity testing was conducted using up to eight different dilutions of filtered tailings liquor, and, applying the SSD approach using EC/IC₁₀ values from chronic toxicity tests, a PC95 value was derived (i.e., a dilution that is protective for 95% of species).

The CSIRO results were used in the EIS to constrain the dimensions of the mixing zone. Based on measured metals concentrations in the tailings-seawater mixture at a constant dilution of 1:10 after 72 hours, the dissolved metal requiring the highest number of dilutions to meet the PNG ambient marine water quality criteria is cobalt, with 1,800-fold dilution of pre-treated tailings slurry (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018a). Lower dilutions are required for copper, nickel, and zinc. In combination with numerical modelling, a 2200 m radial distance has been determined as boundary of the proposed regulatory mixing zone. Compliance with receiving water quality criteria at the mixing zone boundary is to be assessed with quarterly monitoring for the first two years, then annually, to confirm that the tailings behave as predicted and that there is sufficient dilution between the point of discharge and the mixing zone boundary (Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018b). Additional ecotoxicological tests revealed a required dilution lower than the 1,800-fold dilution as determined by comparison of tailings contaminants to PNG ambient marine water quality criteria, indicating that the modelled distance of 2200 m would be protective for 95% of species. To study the potential of dissolved metals to disperse and desorb from the particulate material in addition to metals contained in process water, mixing tests using tailings and seawater at different dilution factors were carried out, and measured concentrations in the filtered fractions were compared to Australian/New Zealand WQGV and PNG water quality criteria. When compared to PNG quality criteria, a 'safe' dilution for Co is only required at a dilution of 1:10,000, while Cu, in comparison with the ANZG guidelines, requires even higher dilutions of up to 50,000-fold. This is at least more than one order of magnitude higher than the dilution factors calculated from measured concentrations in the fixed dilution experiment, but it has not been considered for the mixing zone specifications.

To assess risks for adverse impacts from contaminants at the seafloor, several other LoE were used, such as toxicity testing of sediments and bioaccumulation, sediment quality GV and bioavailability of metals in sediments, and release of metals from sediment into overlying water (i.e., potential toxicity for benthic organisms). The results of sediment toxicity tests showed that tailings may cause adverse effects on amphipod and copepod reproductive output if at concentrations of more than 1-10% mixed with local sediments (depending on tailings composition). Bioaccumulation and biomagnification risks in pelagic organisms are supposed to be low. Studies addressing potential physical impacts of tailings plumes on pelagic organisms concluded that the predicted low average TSS concentrations in the dispersing turbidity plumes is similar to

natural background TSS concentrations and is of insufficient magnitude or exposure duration to cause sub-lethal or lethal physical effects on zooplankton, micronekton organisms, and fish species.

It should be noted, that the PNG water quality criterion for Cu is significantly less conservative compared to the ANZG guideline value (factor 23). The PNG water quality criterion for Co is based on the limit of detection (LOD), which is, in the case of CSIRO laboratory, with 0.01 µg/L ten times lower than the ANZG guideline values (0.1 µg/l).

6.4.4.3 Woodlark Island Gold Project

The Woodlark Island gold project is a planned gold mine in Papua New Guinea (PNG). The mine tailings will be disposed in the ocean, with the outfall planned at 230 m water depth. Ultimately, the tailing solids in the density current will settle out and form tailing deposits on the ocean floor. A main zone of tailing solids deposition is predicted to occur along the density current pathway between of 0.1 and 1.9 m in thickness and cover an area of 61 km² (Woodlark Mining Limited 2013). Deposition is expected to be patchy with the thickest and most extensive deposition below 3,400 m water depth. Tailing solids deposition, up to 0.1 m in thickness, will also occur outside the main zone of tailing solids deposition but cannot be predicted with certainty. To apply for an environmental permit, the contractor prepared an EIS (Woodlark Mining Limited 2018). Cyanide was identified as the dissolved compound of highest concern. Combining the required dilution based on cyanide elutriate concentrations and PNG water quality criterion for cyanide with dispersion modelling, the contractor proposed the extent of the mixing zone around the outfall. The PNG water criteria are expected to be met at around 1000 m distance from the outfall, and a circle with a radius of 1000 m is included as boundary of the mixing zone in the environmental permit. In addition, toxicity testing was used to determine a 'safe' dilution to protect 95% of species with 50% confidence, which revealed that on average this criterion is met at a horizontal distance of 1,205 m from the proposed DSTP outfall (maximum distance 3-4 km).

The allowable mixing zone for the Lihir gold mine in PNG extends radially 1.8 km to the north and 2.3 km to the south-east of the outfall, with compliance with the PNG Environment (PNG 2002) for marine waters required at the mixing zone boundary (Stauber et al. 2022). At Misima, the boundary is set at a radius of 1200 m around the discharge point/deaeration tank (SAMS 2007, Appendix 7). Environmental monitoring has shown that PNG water quality criteria are generally met outside the mixing zones.

7. Challenges for the development of management thresholds addressing metal toxicity for DSM

The environmental pressures of DSM are complex, leading to risks for both pelagic and benthic fauna due to habitat destruction, suspension of surface sediment and dispersal of material plumes, and particle deposition and blanketing of the seafloor. Although key for EIAs, EMMPs, and REMPs, no numerical assessment criteria to distinguish harmful environmental conditions have yet been developed for DSM. To establish thresholds as management tools, metrics for changes of environmental conditions need to be defined in an appropriate framework, consider social and ethical values, and meet legal requirements. Prediction of risks and effective monitoring of DSM activities rely on the establishment of robust environmental indicators, and appropriate thresholds for impact. Considering identified knowledge gaps, the development of suitable assessment criteria, specifically for metals in water and sediment will, however, be challenging. **Major challenges** are:

- Specific environmental objectives and an accepted definition of serious (or unacceptable) harm are missing in the DSM regulatory context (Tunncliffe et al. 2020; Levin et al. 2016; Pickens et al. 2024; Leduc et al. 2024). These targets are required to frame the definition of thresholds;
- Knowledge and data on faunal community structure, ecosystem functions, food web structure and species connectivity in DSM environments are highly fragmented and the lack of identified key species (relating to ecological roles) hampers targeted studies;
- Limited availability of physico-chemical baseline data, including data on spatial and temporal variability, especially for trace metals in seawater that would be required to derive robust baseline datasets;
- Multiple stressors act during DSM activities, and metal toxicity may be integrated with other, particle-induced impacts, such as burial, clogging of filter organs, reduced food intake, mechanical damage, and with biomagnification in the food web; observed biological effects in laboratory or field experiments cannot be easily attributed to a specific stressor;
- Potentially toxic metals occur in chemical mixtures and different physical and chemical forms rendering their availability along different uptake routes; cumulative effects (synergistic, antagonistic, additive) are possible – questioning the appropriateness of thresholds based on single-metal toxicity testing;
- The influence of effects-modifying factors (e.g., pressure, temperature, metal binding, particle grain size and sharpness) that vary between different geological and environmental conditions and the type of activity needs to be considered during threshold development;
- Data from locally-relevant toxicity/effects testing that considers high-pressure and low-temperature conditions typically occurring in DSM settings are still rare, primarily hampered by the costs and technical challenges of *in situ* testing at ambient deep-sea conditions and the current lack of published results on (ecotoxicological) assessments from mining tests (e.g., Patania II, TMC/Allseas);
- The derivation of site-specific biological effects data is technically challenging and costly (testing, sampling, monitoring);
- The lack of a general, integrated methodology to assess the (combined) effects from multiple stressors complicates the assessment of cumulative impacts on marine ecosystems;
- The lack of general methodology and standardization for sediment and water sampling and measurement, as well as the lack of quality standards for generated data; analytical challenges for trace metal assessment in open ocean deep seawater (related to contamination issues, high salt matrix, low concentrations), high costs, and required state-of-the-art methodology.

Addressing these challenges requires integrative approaches with multidisciplinary methodologies to derive thresholds applicable to be implemented into regulatory frameworks for DSM.

8. Conclusions and Recommendations for DSM threshold development

Regulatory thresholds are criteria to assess the environmental risks associated with human activities, to determine the status of the ecosystem change in response to those activities, to guide management decisions, and to trigger management actions to ensure effective protection of the ecosystem from damage according to defined environmental objectives and management goals. Hence, thresholds form an integral part of regulatory environmental management frameworks for offshore activities, from the environmental impact assessment in the permit application phase to the monitoring and management in the operational phase, ensuring compliance with the legal framework. They can be defined for stressors that affect the environment, or for measurable indicators of biological exposure and effects.

Intending to provide a sound basis of available information for the discussion on DSM threshold values, in this report we have reviewed existing national and international regulations for offshore activities of oil & gas production, dredging, and submarine mine tailing disposal that may provide meaningful guidance on approaches and methodologies for the development of a legal framework for thresholds for deep-sea mining activities, because they address similar environmental pressures, i.e. increased suspended particle loads in the water column, smothering of benthic habitat from redeposition of suspended particles, particulate and dissolved toxicants in the sediment and water column. We further reviewed national and international regulatory frameworks for the protection of marine environments that provide threshold values for environmental pressures such as metal contaminants and that are useful resources for threshold derivation, e.g. through mesocosm or laboratory or field studies.

8.1 General considerations

A prerequisite for the development of thresholds is the **definition of goals for environmental protection and management** of operations. These goals should address the spatial and temporal context of the pressures and effects, for example, no increased faunal mortality or loss of species or loss of biodiversity or loss of seafloor integrity in the zone of moderate impact; or no sublethal biological effects or significant change in ecosystem functions (e.g. benthic oxygen respiration, bioturbation) outside the mixing zone. Hence, suitable and reliable indicators for the status of the ecosystem are needed. To derive such thresholds with high confidence ensuring the protection of local deep-sea ecosystems (protection ability), sound environmental baseline datasets, a profound understanding of local biological effects to individual and combined stressors at various ecosystem levels, and a robust ecosystem understanding are required. However, to date, we lack the database and knowledge to develop locally-relevant, effects-based thresholds for pressure indicators with clear dose-response relationships, such as for metal concentrations, suspended particulate material, or sediment deposition thickness/rate. This calls for a **precautionary approach for threshold development**, setting initially conservative thresholds in an **adaptive regulatory and management framework** that is regularly updated while more knowledge becomes available through scientific research, but also the contractors' work, including exploration and monitoring of test mining and commercial mining operations. With increasing availability of site-specific data and ecosystem understanding, the confidence for site-specific validity and predictive ability for ecosystem effects will increase, thereby decreasing the uncertainty of regulatory thresholds. **Adaptive management is a recommended strategy for reducing the environmental risks associated with deep-sea mining.**

As a general guiding principle the precautionary approach also calls for a **tiered monitoring and management concept** consisting of a combination of spatial zones of impact grades and individual thresholds for different levels of risk for serious harm, e.g. a hierarchical or “traffic-light” system providing early-warning indicators for increased risk of ecosystem damage, followed by indicators for moderate-to-high risk – still addressing reversible damage, and finally indicators for unacceptable damage. At each stage, a breach of the thresholds would trigger appropriate management actions consisting of mitigation measures that must be suitable to prevent irreversible damage or serious harm to the environment. As a consequence, the **regulatory framework for thresholds needs to holistically connect EIAs and EMMPs of individual exploitation activities to REMPs** to address the larger-scale risks and impacts arising on regional ecosystem level related to connectivity of species and ecosystem compartments (e.g. benthic to mesopelagic, biological carbon pump to seafloor flux). In their EIS, contractors need to demonstrate that their intended exploitation activity adequately fulfills the protection and management goals, and the administering authority (e.g., ISA) must assess exploitation applications also in the context of the risks for wider regional-scale impacts, thus avoiding long-lasting, severe damage (i.e. serious harm) to the ecosystem (e.g., what scale of exploitation (impact) is acceptable in a contract area, and how many exploitation operations are acceptable on regional scale?).

Figure 8.1: Illustration of a possible combination of Zones of Impact (horizontal and vertical distance may vary) and traffic light systems for different trigger actions (linked to the mitigation hierarchy concept). Monitoring at the indicated spatial distances from the disturbance source (i.e. mining site and/or plume source) checks for compliance with T1, T2, and T3, which consist of a combination of spatial and temporal as well as effects-based and stressor-based thresholds. The Zone of high impact is considered to experience permanent loss of ecosystem functions and biodiversity, which is accounted for in the spatial environmental management plan for the license area preventing harm to the local ecosystem (i.e. by defining a network of appropriate conservation areas and defining ecologically acceptable sizes for the zones of high impact). The environmental management plan is furthermore linked to the REMP.

8.2 Specific considerations

What guidance can environmental impacts and environmental regulations of existing offshore activities provide?

Offshore activities such as oil & gas production, dredging or disposal of mine tailings create similar pressures on the environment as we expect to occur from deep-sea mining, including benthic habitat removal, the

dispersion and settling of particle clouds, and particulate or dissolved metal toxicants in the water column and sediment. The activities are partly ongoing for decades and laboratory and mesocosm tests as well as empirical field studies in the affected marine areas provide insights into (long-term) environmental impacts associated with these pressures and ecosystem recovery. Although environmental conditions, affected ecosystems, frequency/duration of exposure, and properties of suspended/settled material mostly differ from DSM settings, the regulatory frameworks and guidelines in place can provide useful guidance for the development of a legal framework for thresholds for deep-sea mining activities, such as: Which thresholds are used and how are they implemented into concepts for risk assessment and monitoring? How are multiple stressors being dealt with? How are spatial and temporal aspects of the activities regulated? What gaps exist?

What is needed to define thresholds for acceptable disturbance/effect levels in impact zones (e.g., high impact, moderate impact) according to management goals for environmental protection? What are suitable indicators to determine if goals have been achieved or that there is a risk for breaching them?

A good knowledge of the ecosystems to be protected (key species, ecosystem functions, species connectivity, biogeochemical conditions, complete ecosystem understanding, etc.) is required as well as data on ecological responses (biological, functional, biogeochemical) from monitoring in the field or experiments conducted *in situ* or under realistic conditions in the laboratory. This would allow for proxy indicators with proven correlations with ecological effects and thresholds with high confidence in protecting local deep-sea ecosystems according to management objectives – however, we are not yet there. As a consequence, confidence in the protective capacity of any applied threshold is currently low and, therefore, such initial thresholds should be set very conservatively.

Integrated monitoring data for stressors and biological effects at different biological levels are needed to gain information on ecological conditions and environmental pressures during mining activities as underpinning for threshold development. Monitoring data is also needed to test the protectiveness of applied pressure thresholds, i.e., are they overprotective or non-protective, and will inform on the correctness of predicted spatial and temporal dimensions of risk in the water column or at the seabed. Adaptive management allows thresholds and spatial dimensions to be adjusted/refined in order to fulfill management objectives for environmental protection. Adaptive monitoring informs the management during operations and enables mitigation actions (e.g., by adjusting operations) in case environmental conditions deteriorate or become unacceptable. Suitable indicators could include indicators of stress to the environment (e.g., metals, SPM, burial thickness), and/or direct effects measures (e.g., toxicity, biodiversity/biomass, food availability/oxygen consumption) or areal extent of disturbed benthic habitat.

Three general options to implement thresholds for DSM exist: (i) application of existing values from other environmental regulations including those for offshore industries, (ii) the derivation of new, locally-relevant thresholds based on activity-specific effects studies, and (iii) the derivation based on local, natural background datasets. In the following sections we discuss the achievable confidence in protection ability as well as their suitability for DSM.

Which types of thresholds are implemented in environmental regulations for the protection of marine environments?

The most commonly found type are **thresholds for environmental stressors**. These include, for example, a range of metals in water, sediment, and biota (only Hg). Rarely, thresholds for suspended particles are provided. Such thresholds are often generic, i.e. not location-specific. **Thresholds for indicators of effects**

or ecological status are used less frequently. They are, for example, set for various biological effects, such as for biomarkers, toxicity or other biological responses, or the areal extent of disturbed benthic habitat.

Different Lines of Evidence (LoE) are typically used to **assess the environmental quality** of a water body or sediment and **evaluate risks associated with human activities**. This means that both, indicators of stress as well as indicators of actual exposure or direct biological or ecological effects are studied to derive a conclusive picture of the ecological status. The different LoEs are either applied in a hierarchical procedure (e.g., a traffic-light system indicating increased risk levels with corresponding thresholds along the stressor-impact pathways initiating further investigations and mitigation actions) to investigate whether effects are actually occurring and to determine their severity. Alternatively, or as last step in the assessment hierarchy, the different LoEs are evaluated together in a holistic model (e.g., weight-of-evidence).

For which stressors have thresholds been implemented in other offshore industries and what concepts for risk assessment and environmental management are used?

Thresholds have been implemented for the following stress factors:

a) **Metals in water or sediments, total particle concentrations in water, burial thickness, or sedimentation rates:** Thresholds are mostly generically defined, absolute values, and typically originate from environmental regulations (in the case of metals) or were derived from activity-specific experimental exposure experiments.

b) **Total toxicity of industrial wastewater, drilling mud, sediment spoil or mine tailings:** These thresholds are set as effects measures (e.g., 1% of EC₅₀, PNEC) that have to be addressed by the operator on a project-specific basis. Based on toxicological testing, they are, for example, determined as non-toxic fraction of discharged material in the water or the necessary dilution of the discharge, to meet these criteria.

c) Furthermore, **thresholds for the toxicity of sediments** (relative to control groups exposed to uncontaminated sediment), for metal concentrations in biota (from bioaccumulation tests relative to control groups), and for other biological or ecological indicators/endpoints for stress exposure and exposure-induced effects are in use, usually defined as the maximum allowable change relative to control groups.

The applied thresholds are often set in a **spatial (rarely a temporal) context**, i.e. they are not applied directly (e.g., at the source of a discharge), but define the boundary between two zones with different management objectives. For example, mixing zones are defined in water, in which certain adverse environmental effects are accepted and thresholds may be exceeded; however, outside the zone, thresholds must not be exceeded. In the benthic zone at the seafloor, different categories of impact are defined, for example for dredging operations in WA. With increasing distance from the activity, the strength of accepted effects decreases, and different protection goals and management objectives apply. The boundaries between the zones are defined by pressure thresholds. Less frequently, the threshold values are applied directly, e.g. metal thresholds for sediments to decide whether dredged sediment may be discharged back into the sea or not.

The **spatial and temporal extent of impacts** is either specified in the regulation by the authority (e.g., for oil & gas produced water discharge in the United States), or, more commonly, proposed by the contractor in his application based on modelled impact predictions in the water column and at the seafloor (applying ratios of predicted concentrations/discharge dilutions/sediment thicknesses to respective thresholds) and approved case-by-case by the permitting authority. Sometimes also a time limit is defined in the regulation when the threshold must be met: e.g., for the discharge of sediment sludge from dredging this is 4 hours after the end of the activity. Predicting impacts in space and time requires modelling with high confidence in the prediction ability and a sound understanding of pressure-effect relationships. While oceanographic processes and

sedimentation processes can be predicted quite reliably by numerical models, the modelling of chemical processes occurring during the dispersal of discharged material faces several challenges. A conservative mixing of the discharged material with the surrounding seawater is unlikely and processes such as adsorption, desorption, mineral dissolution and mineral precipitation can occur during the dispersal of material plumes.

A distinction is made between **concepts** that are **applied in the application phase** of a project (risk assessment) **and** those that are **applied during an activity**. Before the start of a project, for example, the overall toxicity of dredged sediment or tailings plume material must be determined in case-by case-assessments, modelling of the dispersion of discharged production water or sludge must be conducted to determine the environmental risks in the water body and at the seafloor and to determine the spatial boundaries of impact zones based on the defined management objectives. During activities, thresholds are used for adaptive management of the activities and for ensuring compliance with agreed management objectives. Both, assessment frameworks for risk prediction and for monitoring may apply tiered, hierarchical procedures for decision-making or to trigger management actions, using staggered thresholds of one or different LoEs along the stressor-effect pathway. A weight-of-evidence method can be used as well, examining various LoEs together, and subsequently assess the overall risk.

Instead of using only one criterion as boundary between acceptable and non-acceptable states, some monitoring concepts apply a **traffic light system of tiered thresholds** for stressors and for effects that allows to monitor when environmental conditions evolve towards unacceptable harm. These tiered thresholds define the boundaries between different levels of risks or harm and trigger certain management actions. The monitoring can be conducted close to the predicted impact zone boundaries and additionally within the zones. Thresholds for pressure indicators are used as early warning thresholds, i.e., set at a low level (as boundary between green and orange) as indicators for increasing risk, whereas effect thresholds are used as showstopper criteria, i.e., set at a high level (i.e., boundary between orange and red), e.g. for macrofauna species abundance, or toxicity. However, lower and upper thresholds can also both be set for a stressor, but at different concentrations, durations, or frequencies, if dose-response relationships are well defined.

What are the challenges when setting threshold values in regulations for DSM?

It is challenging to determine suitable thresholds by means of experiments/studies because of the presence of **multiple stressors** with potential interactions, the **temporal-spatial complexity** of the stress fields, the **knowledge gap on key deep-sea species**, as well as the **lack of and difficulty to obtain *in situ* and laboratory experiments with local fauna**.

During deep-sea mining activities, ecosystems are affected by **multiple stressors**. Primarily, this includes the removal of substrate and seafloor, the presence of particle-rich clouds in the near-bottom water layer and the deposition of suspended sediment/ore material layers. Further stress on the environment may arise from metals reaching toxic concentrations both in the suspended plumes and in the deposited sediment, changed food availability as well as altered substrate properties. Dissolved and particulate metals occur as mixtures, naturally as well as in suspended mining plumes and in blanketing layers. These stressors will often act simultaneously (e.g., fauna exposed to plumes may be affected by mechanical injury and clogging of filtration apparatuses, metal toxicity, or starvation), and resulting effects can be additive (stressors act independently and do not influence each other), synergistic (stressors interact, i.e., one stressor influences the biological response to another stressor causing greater effects than the purely additive effect), or antagonistic (i.e., the overall effect is smaller than the purely additive effect). Hence, deriving simple dose-response relationships is difficult. Furthermore, **effects-modifying factors** need to be considered. Environmental conditions, including temperature and pressure regimes, are known to influence biological responses to individual stressors and may also influence recovery rates (e.g., Murray et al. 2024; Brown et al. 2017). Chemical and physical speciation

of metals determines metal toxicity, and effects from burial depend on particle grain size, mineralogy, and availability of potentially toxic metals. Such factors vary strongly between different geological and environmental conditions and the type of activity. The adaptation of fauna to local background conditions likely also plays a role.

One approach to set thresholds for DSM is to use **independent thresholds for individual stressors** and apply them in combination. The threshold values for all criteria would need to be met in order to meet the protection targets, and the overall threshold is exceeded if one of the individual thresholds is exceeded. However, when applying (existing) thresholds for the different stressors (dissolved metals, SPM, burial, metal concentrations in sediments) for risk prediction, **only effect addition can be considered**, but not interactions.

Considering the potentially cumulative impacts of elevated metal concentrations with particle-induced effects or reduced food availability, an integrated assessment of effects seems most promising for the development of appropriate and protective thresholds. **Joint effects/toxicity assessments with mining-relevant plume sediment/ore material** could be suitable, aiming to evaluate the joint effects from all potential stressors that are acting during plume dispersal (whole plume toxicity) or during/after deposition (whole blanketing toxicity) of the material in realistic exposure scenarios, and to identify suitable (proxy) pressure indicators. However, the bulk effects approach faces **complications** because of the potential **decoupling of stressors in the field**. Stressors will have different spatial gradients and act on different time scales, and interactions can vary depending on time and location. Particle properties will change as the plume drifts away from the source, and the colloidal/dissolved plume compounds might decouple from the settling particles in settings that are more distal and with time. Sediment toxicity would persist for a long time, transformation of sulphide minerals after deposition could change/enhance the toxic risk of deposited material with time, and biomagnification in the food web may occur for specific metal contaminants. Such changing conditions are difficult to replicate in laboratory batch experiments and challenges the validity of a derived proxy indicator for a range of stress conditions. Suitable long-term monitoring approaches are required to study the spatiotemporal distribution of stressors during mining activities and derive suitable indicators of (joint) effects, thereby generating information that could also be used for suitable experimental setups. Disentangling the different impact mechanisms to unequivocally reveal the mode of interaction between the different stressors would not be possible though. For an in-depth understanding of impact mechanisms and mode of interaction between different stressors, laboratory studies investigating both, individual and joint effects would be required. As metals naturally occur in mixtures and are unlikely to decouple, it is most appropriate to determine the bulk toxicity of such mixtures instead of testing individual metals that would have to be spiked and then occur in different chemical and physical forms. Conducting tests with sediment/ore material suspended in seawater at different concentrations and separately with elutriates of such suspensions in different dilutions would allow to distinguish between effects of the bulk (particulate + dissolved) fraction and the dissolved multi-metal fraction alone and hence decipher the mode of interaction between particles and dissolved metals in realistic scenarios. The influence of different particle properties can be tested, for example, by using different grain sizes, modifying the pre-treatment of the sediment suspensions (e.g., a suspension is left for some time to let larger and coagulated particles settle - the longer the waiting time, the smaller the particles remaining in the suspension).

Information on integrated effects typically originates from scientific research and monitoring programs, but is seldomly considered in thresholds for offshore industries.

For DSM it is recommended that more consideration should be given to integrated effects and the influence of effects-modifying factors when developing thresholds for metals, particle loads, and sediment deposition.

Can existing thresholds for metals and other stressors in water and sediment be used?

Rather not, as the protection ability for abyssal deep-sea ecosystems, such as in the CCZ, is uncertain. They are not fit-for-purpose.

Metal thresholds for water and sediment are provided e.g., in ANZECC, WFD, US-EPA, CCME, OSPAR, and other regional and national regulations, but they are only available for selected metals and are generic, i.e., they don't consider site-specific abiotic (e.g., pressure, temperature, metal binding) and biotic factors (e.g., local fauna) determining the sensitivity of organisms and modifying toxic effects. Generic **thresholds for metals in water** are derived from single metal exposure tests with shallow water organisms at standard conditions (1 bar, 25°C), typically via a species sensitivity distribution (SSD). To apply such thresholds to the deep sea, one has to assume similar sensitivities of abyssal species compared to the tested shallow water organisms. Furthermore, the datasets used to derive thresholds often include data for algae and photosynthetic plants that are in some cases (e.g., ANZECC Cu) the most sensitive organisms but are absent in the deep sea. Organisms exposed to water-bearing contaminants in DSM settings need to include benthic fauna, while exposure tests are predominantly conducted with planktonic species (or with larvae of sediment-dwelling species). In addition, the number of metals for which thresholds are available is rather limited and the concentration range for individual metals is often quite large (Cd: 0.2-9 µg/L; Pb: 1.3-4.4 µg/L; Cu: 0.4-3.1 µg/L; Ni: 5.8-8.6 µg/L; As: 0.6-36 µg/L; Mn: 0.05-300 µg/L). Compared to natural trace metal concentrations in local CCZ bottom seawater, some of the threshold values for As are below natural conditions, while the new ANZG 95% GV for Cu is close to the background. In contrast, all available threshold values for Pb or Co are found to be several orders of magnitude higher than the CCZ background. All threshold values in existing regulations are derived from single-metal toxicity tests, but in nature, metals occur in mixtures and plume formation during DSM will mobilize several and not only one specific metal. The application of thresholds for individual metals assumes that metals act independently and effects in metal mixtures are purely additive, but completely ignores potential synergistic effects.

Threshold for metals in sediment are mostly based on a dataset that includes ecological field data from North American shelf sediments and laboratory effects data with spiked sediments. Approaches how to address local factors such as the presence of AVS and oxides that significantly influence metal toxicity in sediments exist, and would need to be applied during quality assessments.

Thresholds for suspended particles and sediment deposition thickness that are operational for oil & gas and dredging activities should not be applied in the deep sea. Except for three PNECs for burial, suspended barite and suspended mud that are based on SSDs, thresholds operational for these stressors directly reflect effects sizes. Threshold values are based on tests with shallow water organisms that are normally adapted to higher particle concentrations and sedimentation rates compared to deep-sea settings. Sensitivities of organisms in the deep sea that are adapted to very low SPM and sedimentation rates are likely not the same as in shallow-water environments, and the protection ability of suspended particle thresholds derived for example for corals and sponges in Western Australia is uncertain. Effects-modifying factors such as pressure, grain size, metal content and binding, and physical properties of suspended or settled particles vary in different ecosystems and for different offshore activities, further questioning the validity of existing generic thresholds independent from the environmental setting.

The protection ability of existing thresholds for single metals or suspended particles is highly uncertain for DSM environments, as effects sizes cannot be generalized. Existing thresholds must at least be modified, considering site-specific conditions. For DSM multiple stressors and integrated effects should be considered, demanding multidisciplinary and integrative approaches to identify links between stressors and ecotoxicological/ecological effects, define suitable indicators and derive

site-specific, protective threshold values. The classical distinction between typical ecotoxicological approaches based on standardized laboratory tests with single species and ecological studies on communities in real ecosystems is rendered obsolete (see also Schäfer et al. 2023).

What approaches exist to derive locally relevant thresholds and to what extent are these applicable to the deep sea?

Locally relevant threshold values could be derived either by adapting generic thresholds to local conditions, or by developing new, site-specific values based on laboratory, mesocosm and field studies. A third approach uses background datasets for stressors to derive thresholds in the absence of local effects data. Environmental regulations, such as ANZECC, that propose to develop site-specific thresholds in preference to the application of generic ones, provide guidance on these approaches. They are specifically recommended in case the background (metal) concentrations are higher than the threshold values or, as for turbidity, if the background can be strongly different, or if there are other reasons to have low confidence in using generic thresholds. Approaches for deriving risk assessment criteria in the presence of multiple stressors are specifically addressed in frameworks for offshore activities.

The **recalculation approach to adapt existing thresholds** for metals removes those species that are not occurring in the local environment from the SSD curve that is used to derive threshold values. The key site-adapted toxicity consideration for deep-sea environments is the exclusion of algae and photosynthetic plants. This would be significant for example for ANZG copper where the most sensitive species are algae. On the other hand, available toxicity data for more relevant species could be added to the datasets, including such for cold-water species or species tested in the context of DSM. Screening the available literature, we found an increasing number of published exposure experiments that have been conducted with deep sea (max. 300 m) and shallow water fauna in the context of deep-sea mineral deposits, however, with a focus on SMS settings. Sources of exposure range from single dissolved metals (mainly Cd and Cu) to suspended natural sediment, suspended SMS particles, and sediment elutriates (i.e., exposure to metal mixtures). While this data is not yet sufficient to derive new, DSM-specific threshold values, it can be used to adapt existing thresholds.

As noted by the European Commission (2011) and ANZG (2018), the relationship between metal toxicity and natural background concentrations is unknown, and some populations might in fact live close to their upper tolerance limit, particularly in areas, where ecosystems are already stressed by extreme natural conditions. Fauna used to develop the existing generic thresholds is not locally-relevant for the CCZ and most generic thresholds are usually provided as total risk figures (i.e. they do not distinguish between background concentrations and added concentrations; e.g., Australia, the United States, Canada). Some regulations (OSPAR, Norway), however, suggest the ARA (**added risk approach**) as one approach to modify a generic threshold. It considers the maximum permissible addition of a substance to the background concentration to derive a site-adapted threshold (e.g., for the application of PNECs in OSPAR and EQS in Norway). The approach implies that (i) organisms are adapted to their site-specific background, (ii) only the anthropogenically added metal concentration would be harmful, and (iii) the sensitivity of organisms to such an added concentration is similar across different environmental settings. Applying this approach to protect deep-sea ecosystems would also assume that there are no differences in the sensitivity of fauna, and pressure and temperature do not modify toxic effects – for both currently very little information exists and while effects are known, currently they cannot be quantified.

Adaptable thresholds that consider the influence of local effects-modifying factors on metal toxicity are not available. Only the influence of DOC on Cu toxicity is reflected in some of the regulations. Biotic ligand models could be an option to consider the influence of toxicity-modifying factors such as temperature or DOC on metal bioavailability for biota, but they are rare and for the marine environment only available for copper (as

draft version). Hence, this approach is currently not applicable for DSM. As alternative to modifying the threshold itself according to local conditions, the bioaccessible fractions of metals in water and sediment could be determined (e.g. by DGT passive samplers) and compared to generic threshold values.

More sophisticated approaches to derive site-specific thresholds would involve the **derivation of new effects-based thresholds at locally relevant conditions**, either with local water (or plume material) and shallow-water proxy organisms (as local deep-sea organisms cannot be tested *ex situ*), or *in situ* with local water and local fauna. Tests can have different complexity, from single dissolved substance testing to whole plume testing with a series of different plume dilutions or sediment testing with a series of burial thicknesses. Considering the presence of multiple stressors during DSM activities, where metal toxicity might be integrated with particle-induced effects, burial effects or reduced food availability, **integrated assessments of joint effects are recommended** and common procedure used in other offshore activities (e.g., toxicity testing of dredge spoil or produced water). **Direct toxicity testing** is an approach that considers any change in species or systems, no matter which impact mechanism exactly causes the biological effect. Exposure studies investigating joint effects from relevant operational and dewatering plume material should be conducted along pressure gradients (i.e., either different dilutions of suspended material, or different deposition thicknesses of settled material) to identify suitable (proxy) pressure indicators that are related to the exposure or the effects. **Bulk effects-based thresholds** that ensure protection of site-specific communities can be derived in form of PNECs, accepting that the exact mechanisms leading to observed adverse effects in the presence of multiple stressors may remain unknown. Effects-based thresholds can be defined for individual stressors (or stressor groups such as metal mixtures) or for proxy indicators that are more easily measured during DSM operations, such as the concentration of suspended particles. If tests are carried out with a sufficient number of locally relevant species, more robust thresholds can be derived from a species sensitivity distribution (SSD). While field studies are logistically and methodologically quite challenging, currently there is no evidence that experiments with shallow-water organisms reflect the sensitivity of deep-water species. Assessment factors can be used to acknowledge uncertainty resulting from extrapolation from lab to field, from shallow-water p-T conditions to deep-sea conditions and other sources of uncertainty.

Another option is to **determine thresholds for stressors based on local background values** of the undisturbed natural environment. This reference site approach is recommended if no locally-relevant biological-effects data are available or possible and allows to derive site-specific thresholds (e.g., Canada, ANZECC). However, for metals in the near-bottom seawater of the CCZ currently only very little background data has been published or is publicly accessible. The determination of metal concentrations in the deep sea is not routine, but requires advanced technologies and methods for sampling and analysis. Since the composition of the bottom water in the CCZ appears to be relatively homogeneous, applying recommended approaches to derive background-based threshold values (e.g., 80th or 90th percentile of dataset) would result in quite conservative values.

To derive thresholds for suspended particles for the deep-sea settings in the absence of effects data, van der Grient and Drazen (2022) used an approach studying **responses and sensitivities of fauna to suspended particles normalized to background concentrations** (i.e., to particle concentration increase above background) and found the relative sensitivities being similar across very different shallow-water habitats. They showed that overall, at 4 times background concentrations of suspended sediments 50% of species would be affected (EC₅₀). This factor has been postulated to be transferable also to deep-sea environments and was used to derive new, site-adapted thresholds for the CCZ and Mid-Atlantic Ridge settings, respectively. Their finding, however, needs validation for DSM settings, considering the various modifying factors that may influence the impacts of suspended particles, questioning the generality of such thresholds assuming similar relative sensitivities of shallow water and deep-sea organisms. Suspended particle plumes from SMS mining, for example, will be enriched in potentially toxic metals, and exposure to this type of particles has been shown

to induce biological responses in deep-water corals and sponges that are likely caused by combined and potentially synergistic mechanical and metal toxicological impacts from the plume material (Carreiro-Silva et al. 2022; Wurz et al. 2024). Furthermore, data from shallow-water coral habitats in Western Australia (Fisher et al. 2019) showed lower conversion factors of only 1.5-2.2 between the background mean and observed effects concentrations compared to the factor of 4 derived from van der Grient and Drazen (2022), which could, however, also be related to the different effect sizes considered.

Could it be possible to determine, in a similar approach, **fauna sensitivities to metals in relation to background metal concentrations** in different shallow-water settings, and, if these relative sensitivities are similar between different shallow-water habitats, extrapolate it to the deep sea to calculate a threshold based on local background concentrations and this ratio? As the available database is not sufficient and the approach does not consider the effect-modifying factors temperature and pressure, such an approach is **not feasible**. Regulatory metal threshold values are typically not derived for a specific habitat and related toxicity tests are often conducted in standard test media and with standard organisms and are not related to a local water type. Regulatory thresholds are usually provided as total concentrations, i.e. they do not distinguish between background concentrations and anthropogenically added concentrations when assessing toxic risks. Only the Norwegian guidelines provide background concentrations in their classification scheme and apply thresholds for added concentrations. The ANZECC guidelines do not provide background concentrations, as these are supposed to vary widely across the different environments, and thresholds are also not based on local species, but mostly rely on data from overseas. Furthermore, regulatory threshold values are typically not equal to an effects size for a sensitive organism, but either account for uncertainties due to e.g., interspecies differences in sensitivity, by applying additional application factors to the lowest observed effects size, or use the species sensitivity approach calculating a HC5. Hence, the data from exposure studies themselves, testing the same species but using different ambient water having different background concentrations as test media is needed to determine whether faunal sensitivities for toxic effects are primarily driven by local background metal concentrations. Such datasets are typically very small and restricted to very few elements.

Uncertainties deriving from unknown effects of pressure and temperature or use of non-local fauna with respect to protection ability of existing generic thresholds can be accounted for **by applying additional assessment factors**. Threshold values or effects sizes are divided by this factor, resulting in decreased and hence more conservative threshold values. However, this may result in unrealistically low concentrations below background values. If effects sizes for newly developed thresholds are derived from laboratory experiments using shallow-water surrogate organisms or communities, assessment factors could acknowledge the unknown effect of pressure.

While several approaches to develop site-specific, protective thresholds are available, for DSM laboratory tests with shallow-water surrogate species and the background datasets approach seem appropriate initially. The protection ability of adapted, existing thresholds is uncertain and needs to be proven case-by-case first. *In situ* field studies should be conducted in a subsequent step to derive thresholds with higher confidence, but sufficient data to derive activity-specific thresholds based on monitoring of larger-scale field tests or mining operations (leading to high confidence) will only be available sometime in the future or after industrial DSM has started.

How can DSM-specific thresholds be developed and implemented in the Mining Code?

Laboratory studies or field tests can be used to **derive activity-specific, effects-based thresholds (PNECs)** for pressure indicators such as SPM, metals, or burial thickness. Continued research (by the scientific community and also industry/contractors) with meaningful experimental set-ups in the laboratory and in the field is required to generate sufficient data for this threshold development process. Alternatively or in addition,

effects thresholds for toxicity or other measures of biological response can be implemented (e.g., 1% of EC_{50} , or 10% change in mortality or species abundance relative to control settings). Based on direct exposure experiments with the waste slurry material planned to be discharged, contractors need to provide information on its toxicity/risk for effects and determine project-specific criteria, such as minimum effluent dilutions, or no-effect concentrations of a proxy indicator that have to be met in order to comply with the regulation. As part of the EIA these experiments can be conducted either with plume suspensions or with deposited material. The implementation of indirect effects thresholds addressing local, site specific effects is favourable in the absence of activity-specific effects data necessary to derive regulatory pressure thresholds. They could be implemented as single assessment criteria or as higher tiers of traffic-light risk assessment or monitoring schemes. If implemented as prerequisite for permit application, contractors need to be provided with clear advice on the methodologies. Based on increasing data becoming available from studies and monitoring initial regulatory thresholds for pressure indicators are refined or new, fit-for-purpose thresholds are derived.

Considering that different species have different sensitivities to different toxicants/stressors, a range of organisms having differing exposure pathways (feeding strategies and behaviours) and different test endpoints (for example, survival, development, growth, reproduction) are generally favourable for ecotoxicological assessments. However, because it is currently challenging to test local fauna *in situ* and in the absence of information on key species, laboratory tests might be carried out with surrogate shallow-water organisms of the most vulnerable (likely filter-feeding) type of species. Long-term exposure tests with different life stages (or larval stages if these have been shown to be the most sensitive), measuring sublethal effects, are recommended. If only lethal effects can be observed, thresholds would need to be set more conservatively (e.g., by application of additional assessment factors). When testing deposition material, tests should include meio- and macrofauna.

It should be noted that, while the first PMN mining tests have been conducted, a Best Available Technique (BAT) is still to be determined and today's information on plume formation and plume settling in PMN mining settings is likely to change with technology advancements. Technology for SMS mining has not been demonstrated until now and hence, details on plume formation, particle characteristics, and metal release remain speculative, but are a pre-requisite to develop appropriate toxicity tests.

Testing for plume effects: Effects in fauna exposed to suspended plume material may result from either or a combination of suspended particles, metal toxicity, or reduced food availability. To determine the risk for site-specific taxa, it seems most appropriate to conduct locally-relevant testing with particle suspensions of sediment/ore material over the expected range of concentrations with vulnerable species and apply a conceptual response model to investigate responses as a function of level of exposure. Such studies can be conducted in the laboratory or in the field. **Field studies** should be conducted during test mining or during mining operations, using sessile benthic fauna or caged pelagic fauna along the suspended particle gradient of the produced plume, thereby determining dissolved metals, labile-bound metals, particle concentrations and particulate metal concentrations together with the biological effects to identify pressure-response relationships and derive suitable proxy indicators. Thresholds may be defined for a combination of individual stress indicators, or solely for one proxy indicator. In the **laboratory**, shallow-water surrogate species could be exposed to (i) spiked single dissolved metals in local seawater (not recommended), (ii) suspended whole plume material in a series of different concentrations, or (iii) elutriates of suspended plume material (filtered water of a sediment suspension) in a series of different dilutions. The exposure to combined stressors in bulk toxicity tests allows deriving thresholds for (proxy) indicators, such as concentrations of SPM or DGT-labile metals, while testing with spiked single metals or elutriates of sediment suspensions would allow to address toxicity of dissolved metals. The uncertainty on derived effects data, however, would be relatively high, because such tests can only be conducted with non-local, shallow-water surrogate organisms that are adapted to different natural environmental conditions. The application of additional assessment factors could

acknowledge the unknown effect of pressure. Whether using local deep seawater as test media is a feasible option or not would need to be discussed. Deriving thresholds from bulk experiments is complicated by the potential decoupling of stressors and changing modes of interaction. The protective ability of these indicators in abyssal deep-sea settings would need to be validated with biological field data.

Testing for blanketing effects: Effects in fauna exposed to deposited plume material could result from burial itself, low food availability, altered substrate characteristics or exposure to toxic metals in particulate or dissolved form. While metal toxicity will likely mainly be of concern in blanketing from SMS discharge plumes (sulfides) and possibly also from PMN (oxides) discharge plumes, metals in blanketing from operational PMN plumes are not expected to reach toxic concentrations. Considering integrated impacts from sediment burial itself and from metal exposure that prevent deciphering clear single stressor dose-response relationships, the most meaningful approach would be an integrated assessment of joint effects in the presence of a sediment deposition layer, regardless of whether the effects are caused by the burial or metal toxicity (or particle sharpness, reduced food supply, altered substrate properties, or a combination thereof). In the **field**, monitoring along the blanketing thickness gradient created by mining tests or mining operations is recommended. Biological effects at different levels of biological organization should be studied together with sediment chemistry and other biogeochemical variables, metal bioavailability, and SPM concentrations in the water column, to derive one or more suitable proxy indicators that correlate with any observed effects along the deposition gradient. Burial thickness itself can be determined in sediment cores, though only with limited accuracy in cores with PMN, but sedimentation rates could be measured with small sediment traps at the seafloor. Artificially generated gradients of sediment deposition thickness can also be tested in the **laboratory** in mesocosms to determine joint effects on different meiofauna, macrofauna, megafauna with differing feeding strategies (e.g., deposit feeders, filter feeders, scavengers). Since deposited layers of operational plumes may have a different toxicity than those of waste discharge plumes, and metal toxicity is expected to be of major concern for SMS mining, different tests may be necessary, depending on the type of suspended material that is deposited. Metal thresholds for deposited plume material can only be derived if a clear correlation of metal concentrations and biological effects can be proven, allowing to derive a Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC). Transformation of minerals after deposition may change the toxic risk potential of deposited material over time, which currently is difficult to predict due to lack of data.

8.3 Recommendations for DSM

Considering the limited current knowledge, uncertainties in protective ability of existing thresholds and the challenges in deriving new, effects-based threshold values, **a precautionary approach setting conservative initial thresholds is required**, designed to ensure protection until more knowledge becomes available. Such thresholds can only be used as early warning indicators of potentially increasing risk, triggering further assessment of effects using different LoE. With increasing availability of effects data and ecosystem understanding, the confidence for site-specific validity and predictive ability for biological effects will increase, decreasing the uncertainty of regulatory thresholds. **Future research should focus on improving data availability and understanding the complex interactions within marine ecosystems to refine the early stage thresholds.** For example, monitoring data from mining tests and operations should feed into the development of more fit-for-purpose thresholds in adaptable DSM regulatory regimes.

Operational thresholds for metals from other environmental regulations cannot be applied directly in the deep sea because (i) their derivation is based on organisms that do not occur in the deep sea, (ii) high uncertainties due to exposure tests with single metals at standard conditions, (iii) the thresholds of arsenic and copper are below or very close to natural background. Options to adapt existing thresholds to local

conditions are limited, but should at least involve the removal of algae and photosynthetic plants from the datasets, and the application of additional assessment factors to account for the uncertainties related to non-local relevance, the potential effects of pressure and low temperature on toxicity, and the potential for synergistic effects in metal mixtures and in the presence of other, non-chemical stressors.

Operational thresholds for suspended particles and sedimentation thickness from other offshore industries cannot be applied directly in the deep sea because (i) threshold values are based on tests with shallow-water organisms that are normally adapted to higher natural concentrations, (ii) many of the influencing factors, such as grain size, composition and physical properties of suspended or settled particles, vary in different ecosystems and for different offshore activities.

Effects testing is challenging, inter alia due to high water depth of the ecosystem to be protected and multiple stressors that may act on different spatiotemporal scales. **Field investigations will provide the most conclusive picture on integrated effects of DSM in space and time at different levels of biological organization.** Obtained data can be used to derive proxy indicators, but information on individual effects mechanisms cannot be gained. **Lab experiments are inconclusive** as only non-local shallow-water fauna can be tested, but studies allow faster data generation and the possibility to study modes of stressor interaction.

At early stages, guidelines could provide thresholds for pressure indicators (e.g., derived from background values), while further steps in the assessment of risks and effects would need to be conducted by the contractors.

Management zones with categories of acceptable impacts/biological effects should be defined for the water column and the seabed (Figure 8.1). Mixing zones allow for certain negative environmental effects within the initial zone of mixing between discharged waste material / suspended plume material / released toxicants and the oceanic seawater. Outside the mixing zone, the natural state should be maintained and no ecological effects should occur. The boundary could be defined by threshold values indicative for chronic toxicity as conservative measure. For the benthic environment zones of different impact categories should be defined for key species, vulnerable/sensitive organisms, and ecosystem functions. Impacts decrease with increasing distance from the activity, i.e. different management objectives apply. The spatial boundaries between the impact zones are defined by thresholds. To monitor the activities and ensure that management objectives are met within a zone, tiered thresholds values should be installed (e.g. traffic light system consisting of early warning indicators for an increased risk and high-level knock-out criteria causing operations to stop). The definition of mixing zones and benthic impact zones requires accurate predictions of the spatial and temporal footprint of the environmental impact (e.g., dispersion and deposition of the suspended particle plume, release of toxicants, response of the ecosystem and its functions and processes). Model results need to be validated with monitoring data collected during the activities, and the zone boundaries need to be adjusted.

The implementation of traffic lights (e.g., in EMMPs) enables early management actions in response to an exceedance the early warning threshold (green-orange transition) to prevent unacceptable impacts (orange-red transition). Management actions may involve intensified monitoring and laboratory tests to validate the actual risk for adverse effects, and mitigation measures. If thresholds are used to assess compliance with agreed targets, breaching the upper threshold would be seen as requiring a mining activity to cease. In addition to compliance boundaries, additional management boundaries could be set within a management zone but closer to the source that will inform early on increasing risk, triggering adaptive management of mining operations.

At an early stage of threshold development, suitable early warning thresholds could be defined based on local background metal or particle concentrations (requiring robust background data sets that adequately cover the spatial and temporal variability) and either set as absolute (e.g., Cu = 0.5 µg/L; SPM = 50

µg/L) or relative values (e.g., 99th percentile of site-specific background dataset). The upper threshold could be defined as a multiplier of the first, or an (adapted) version of an existing threshold is used, although this carries a high uncertainty in terms of protection ability. The definition of thresholds for biological effects measures such as mortality, toxicity, or meio- or macrofaunal species abundance as maximum change compared to undisturbed settings seems more suitable as higher tier threshold. The disadvantages of such effects thresholds include the delay until the results are available and that measured responses are serious impacts. **With improving scientific understanding, suitable biological effects indicators** (e.g. eDNA, biomarkers, oxygen consumption) **should be developed** that (i) allow to indicate sub-lethal effects in key or sentinel species, (ii) are easy to measure and (iii) develop rapidly in response to the disturbance and (iv) provide fast feedback. Furthermore, tailored thresholds for fit-for-purpose stress indicators should be developed that can predict accurately when the risk is high. Such effect-based thresholds can be derived from monitoring data of mining tests or full operations, and from laboratory studies. At high confidence in prediction ability and by varying the accepted effects size, such thresholds could be used to define both the green-orange and orange-red boundaries. Ideally, these (proxy) indicators can be measured online using sensor technology, by autonomous vehicles, and/or automated procedures.

Since the determination of dissolved metals and metalloids is technically challenging and bears risks for contamination and producing false data, it is recommended to focus on selected metals and develop more simple methodological procedures for the assessment, e.g., the passive DGT sampling technique. If direct correlation with other stress indicators such as SPM can be proven, these should be used instead.

Standards and guidelines for the environmental management of DSM should provide detailed guidance on procedures and methodologies to assess risks for environmental impacts and prove compliance.

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Appendix 1: Bibliography for further reading

This appendix provides a comprehensive bibliography relevant in the context of developing and implementing regulatory thresholds for DSM, on i) DSM-relevant ecotoxicological exposure experiments using shallow-water and deep-sea fauna, ii) environmental risks and impacts of DSM, iii) environmental risks and impacts of other offshore industries such as submarine tailings disposal, dredging, and oil and gas, focussing on effects from metal toxicity, enhanced suspended particle load and enhanced sedimentation, iv) existing international, national and regional regulatory frameworks for water and sediment quality that provide numerical assessment criteria, including guidance documents for threshold derivation, environmental management, and monitoring, and v) available data sources for natural trace metal concentrations in Pacific seawater and sediment. The appendix lists the key reading material and sources of information for the derivation and implementation of numerical assessment criteria as regulatory management tools for DSM. Bibliographic citations are subject-grouped in individual tables, with full references provided at the end of each table.

A compilation of available numerical assessment criteria (standards, guidelines, criteria, benchmarks) for metals in marine waters, sediment and biota from existing regulatory frameworks, as well as operational thresholds used in active offshore industries is provided in Appendix 2 and the accompanying **Excel file: *Regulatory and operational threshold values***.

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Table 1: Ecotoxicology of deep-sea mining: exposure experiments using deep-sea fauna

Type of organism	Species	depth (m)	Habitat	Location	Source of exposure	Endpoint	Pressure	References	Title
Amphipod	<i>Abyssochomene distinctus</i>	1600	Polymetallic nodules	South China Sea	Cu spiked in food	proteomics, Cu	in situ	Kwan et al. 2019	Comparative Proteomics on Deep-Sea Amphipods after in Situ Copper Exposure
Shrimp	<i>Mirocaris fortunata</i>	1700	Hydrothermal vents	Lucky Strike, MAR	dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cu	0.1 MPa	Mestre et al. 2019	Are shallow-water shrimps proxies for hydrothermal-vent shrimps to assess the impact of deep-sea mining?
Shrimp	<i>Rimicaris exoculata</i>	3620	Hydrothermal vents	TAG, MAR	dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, metals	30 Mpa	Auguste et al. 2016	Development of an ecotoxicological protocol for the deep-sea fauna using the hydrothermal vent shrimp <i>Rimicaris exoculata</i>
Coral	<i>Dentomuricea meteor</i>	~200	Seamount	Condor Seamount, MAR	dissolved Cu	mortality	0.1 MPa	Martins et al. 2018	Assessment of Cu sub-lethal toxicity (LC50) in the cold-water gorgonian <i>Dentomuricea meteor</i> under a deep-sea mining activity scenario
Coral	<i>Primnoa resedaeformis</i>	200	Fjord	Nakken Reef in Langenuen Fjord	crushed granite rock (to simulated inert mine tailings) and warmer temperature	respiration rates; nutrient flux; lysosomal destabilization	0.1 MPa	Scanes et al. 2018	Mine waste and acute warming induce energetic stress in the deep-sea sponge <i>Geodia atlantica</i> and coral <i>Primnoa resedaeformis</i> ; results from a mesocosm study
Coral	<i>Dentomuricea aff. meteor</i>	185-210	Seamount	Condor Seamount	suspended polymetallic sulphide (PMS) particles, suspended quartz particles	tissue condition, survival, Co, Cu, and Mn metabolism, oxidative stress and damage, gene expression	0.1 MPa	Carreiro-Silva et al. 2022	Mechanical and toxicological effects of deep-sea mining sediment plumes on a habitat-forming cold-water octocoral
Holothurian	<i>Amperima sp.</i>	4196	Abyssal plain	CCZ	Cu-spiked artificial sediment	behavior, oxidative stress	in situ	Brown et al. 2017	A comparative experimental approach to ecotoxicology in shallow-water and deep-sea holothurians suggests similar behavioural responses
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiulus azoricus</i>	1700	Hydrothermal vents	Lucky Strike, MAR	dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, gene expression	17.5 Mpa	Martins et al. 2017	Physiological impacts of acute Cu exposure on deep-sea vent mussel <i>Bathymodiulus azoricus</i> under a deep-sea mining activity scenario

Type of organism	Species	depth (m)	Habitat	Location	Source of exposure	Endpoint	Pressure	References	Title
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	850	Hydrothermal vents	Menez Gwen, MAR	dissolved Cd, Cu, Hg	oxidative stress and damage	0.85 MPa	Company et al. 2004	Effect of cadmium, copper and mercury on antioxidant enzyme activities and lipid peroxidation in the gills of the hydrothermal vent mussel <i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	850	Hydrothermal vents	Menez Gwen, MAR	dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cu	0.1 MPa	Company et al. 2008	Antioxidant biochemical responses to long-term copper exposure in <i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i> from Menez-Gwen hydrothermal vent
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	850	Hydrothermal vents	Menez Gwen, MAR	dissolved Cd	oxidative stress and damage, MTs	0.85 MPa	Company et al. 2006	The effect of cadmium on antioxidant responses and the susceptibility to oxidative stress in the hydrothermal vent mussel <i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	850	Hydrothermal vents	Menez Gwen, MAR	dissolved Cd	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cd	0.1 MPa	Company et al. 2010	Sub-lethal effects of cadmium on the antioxidant defence system of the hydrothermal vent mussel <i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>
Mussel	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>	2300	Hydrothermal vents	Rainbow, MAR	transplanted to Lucky Strike	oxidative stress and damage, MTs	in situ	Company et al. 2007	Adaptation of the antioxidant defence system in hydrothermal-vent mussels (<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i>) transplanted between two Mid-Atlantic Ridge sites
Mussel	<i>Gigantidas platifrons</i>	1119	cold seep	South China Sea	dissolved Cd, Cu, Cd+Cu	oxidative stress and damage, immune function, MTs, metabolomics, Cd, Cu	0.1 MPa	Zhou et al. 2021	Biochemical and metabolic responses of the deep-sea mussel <i>Bathymodiolus platifrons</i> to cadmium and copper exposure
Mussel	<i>Gigantidas platifrons</i>	1119	cold seep	South China Sea	dissolved Cd	oxidative stress and damage, immune function, metabolomics, proteomics, Cd	0.1 MPa	Zhou et al. 2023	Toxicological effects of cadmium on deep-sea mussel <i>Gigantidas platifrons</i> revealed by a combined proteomic and metabolomic approach
Mussel	<i>Gigantidas platifrons</i>	1119	cold seep	South China Sea	dissolved Mn, Fe	oxidative stress and damage, immune function, energy	0.1 MPa	Zhou et al. 2024a	Integrated biomarker response to assess toxic impacts of iron and manganese on deep-sea mussel <i>Gigantidas platifrons</i> under a deep-sea mining activity scenario

Type of organism	Species	depth (m)	Habitat	Location	Source of exposure	Endpoint	Pressure	References	Title
						metabolism, Fe, Mn			
Mussel	<i>Gigantidas platifrons</i>	1119	cold seep	South China Sea	dissolved Cu and Cd	oxidative stress and damage, immune response, energy and lipid metabolism, Cu, Cd	in situ and 0.1MPa	Zhou et al. 2024b	Toxicology assessment of deep-sea mining impacts on <i>Gigantidas platifrons</i> : A comparative <i>in situ</i> and laboratory metal exposure study
Mussel	<i>Gigantidas platifrons</i>	1100	cold seep	South China Sea	dissolved Cu	transcriptomic, metabolomic	0.1MPa	He et al. 2024	Integrated transcriptomic and metabolomic approaches reveal molecular response and potential biomarkers of the deep-sea mussel <i>Gigantidas platifrons</i> to copper exposure
Jellyfish	<i>Periphylla periphylla</i>	0-800	fjord	Lurefjord, and Sognefjord	abyssal plain sediment, warmer temperatures	metabolism, health rating, microbiome, transcriptomic	0.1MPa	Stenvers et al. 2023	Experimental mining plumes and ocean warming trigger stress in a deep pelagic jellyfish
Sponge	<i>Geodia barretti</i>	200	Sponge ground????	Langenuen	natural bottom sediment and crushed granite rock (to simulated inert mine tailings)	respiration rate; tissue energy content; ash content	0.1 MPa	Kutti et al. 2015	Metabolic responses of the deep-water sponge <i>Geodia barretti</i> to suspended bottom sediment, simulated mine tailings and drill cuttings
Sponge	<i>Geodia atlantica</i>	190-200	Fjord	Nakken Reef, Langenuen Fjord	crushed granite rock (to simulated inert mine tailings) and warmer temperature	respiration rates; nutrient flux; lysosomal destabilization	0.1 MPa	Scanes et al. 2018	Mine waste and acute warming induce energetic stress in the deep-sea sponge <i>Geodia atlantica</i> and coral <i>Primnoa resedeaformis</i> ; results from a mesocosm study

Type of organism	Species	depth (m)	Habitat	Location	Source of exposure	Endpoint	Pressure	References	Title
Sponge	<i>Vazella pourtalesii</i>	160-217	Sponge ground	Emerald Basin off Nova Scotia	natural bottom sediment	survival; respiration rate; bacterial clearance rate; potential recovery (tissue condition and accumulation of particles)	0.1 MPa	Wurz et al. 2021	The Hexactinellid deep-water sponge <i>Vazella pourtalesii</i> (Schmidt, 1870) (Rossellidae) copes with temporarily elevated concentrations of suspended natural sediment
Sponge	<i>Geodia barretti</i>	330	sponge ground	Tromsøflaket East	crushed seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposit	metabolism, tissue condition, Fe, Cu, S, microbiome	0.1 MPa	Wurz et al. 2024	Adverse effects of crushed seafloor massive sulphide deposits on the boreal deep-sea sponge <i>Geodia barretti</i> Bowerbank, 1858 and its associated fauna

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Table 2: Ecotoxicology of deep-sea mining and other offshore activities: exposure experiments using shallow-water fauna (list is not exhaustive but contains most relevant studies).

Type of organisms	Species	Activity addressed / Source of exposure	Endpoint/ Biomarker	Temperature (°C)	Pressure	References	Title
Bacteria	<i>Vibrio fischeri</i>	Oil & Gas Produced water	microtox test (EC50 or EC20)	15	0.1 MPa	Azetsu-Scott et al. 2007	Precipitation of heavy metals in produced water: Influence on contaminant
Algae	<i>Skeletonema pseudocostatum</i>	Mine Tailings mine tailings with and without flotation and flocculation	growth, yield	22	0.1 MPa	Brooks et al. 2019	An ecotoxicological assessment of mine tailings from three Norwegian mines
Phytoplankton	<i>Skeletonema marinoi-dohrnii</i> complex	DSM leachates of metals and metalloids. Ba-rich ore, Fe-rich ore, and Zn-Pb-rich ore.	growth	20	0.1 MPa	Fuchida et al. 2017	Leaching of Metals and Metalloids from Hydrothermal Ore
Brine shrimp	<i>Artemia</i> sp.	deep sediment elutriate	mortality, behavior	25	0.1 MPa	Gambardella et al. 2022	An integrated approach to characterize deep sediment toxicity in Genoa submarine canyons (NW Mediterranean)
Amphipod	<i>Josephosella plumulosa</i>	DSM and Mine tailing chalcopyrite, chalcocite, chalcopyrite copper concentrate, galena, sphalerite, mixed-metal sulfide, dissolved Cu	mortality, reproduction	21	0.1 MPa	Simpson and Spadaro 2016	Bioavailability and Chronic Toxicity of Metal Sulfide Minerals to Benthic Marine Invertebrates: Implications for Deep Sea Exploration, Mining and Tailings Disposal
Amphipod	<i>Corophium</i> sp.	Mine Tailings mine tailings with and without flotation and flocculation	survival, NOEC, LOEC, EC50	15	0.1 MPa	Brooks et al. 2019	An ecotoxicological assessment of mine tailings from three Norwegian mines
Copepod	<i>Tisbe battagliai</i>	Mine Tailings mine tailings with and without flotation and flocculation	mortality	20	0.1 MPa	Brooks et al. 2019	An ecotoxicological assessment of mine tailings from three Norwegian mines
Shrimp	<i>Palaemon elegans</i>	DSM dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cu	10	0.1 MPa	Mestre et al. 2019	Are shallow-water shrimps proxies for hydrothermal-vent shrimps to assess the impact of deep-sea mining?
Shrimp	<i>Palaemon serratus</i>	DSM dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cu	10	0.1 MPa	Mestre et al. 2019	Are shallow-water shrimps proxies for hydrothermal-vent shrimps to assess the impact of deep-sea mining?
Shrimp	<i>Palaemon varians</i>	DSM dissolved Cu	oxidative stress and damage, MTs, Cu	10	0.1 MPa	Mestre et al. 2019	Are shallow-water shrimps proxies for hydrothermal-vent shrimps to assess the impact of deep-sea mining?

Type of organisms	Species	Activity addressed / Source of exposure	Endpoint/ Biomarker	Temperature (°C)	Pressure	References	Title
Shrimp	<i>Palaemon varians</i>	DSM dissolved Cu	mortality, oxidative stress, metabolism, Cu, Cd	10, 20	0.1, 10 MPa	Brown et al. 2017a	The Effects of Temperature and Hydrostatic Pressure on Metal Toxicity: Insights into Toxicity in the Deep Sea
Shrimp	<i>Palaemon varians</i>	DSM Chalcopyrite	metabolism	10	0.1 MPa	Brown and Hauton 2018	Ecotoxicological responses to chalcopyrite exposure in a proxy for deep-sea hydrothermal vent shrimp: implications for seafloor massive sulphide mining
Barnacle	<i>Amphibalanus amphitrite</i>	deep sediment elutriate	mortality, behavior	20	0.1 MPa	Gambardella et al. 2022	An integrated approach to characterize deep sediment toxicity in Genoa submarine canyons (NW Mediterranean)
Holothurian	<i>Holothuria forskali</i>	DSM Cu-spiked artificial sediment	behavior, oxidative stress	10	0.1 MPa	Brown et al. 2017a; Brown et al. 2017b	A comparative experimental approach to ecotoxicology in shallow-water and deep-sea holothurians suggests similar behavioural responses
Mussel	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	mine tailings	oxidative stress and damage, MTs	local	not relevant	Mestre et al. 2017	Environmental hazard assessment of a marine mine tailings deposit site and potential implications for deep-sea mining
Mussel	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	DSM sediment	oxidative stress and damage, metabolism, gene expression	16	0.1, 0.4, 5 MPa	Pinheiro et al. 2019	Ecotoxicology of deep-sea environments: Functional and biochemical effects of suspended sediments in the model species <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> under hyperbaric conditions
Mussel	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	DSM sediment (different grain sizes)	oxidative stress and damage, metabolism, gene expression	16	4 MPa	Pinheiro et al. 2021	Functional, biochemical and molecular impact of sediment plumes from deep-sea mining on <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> under hyperbaric conditions
Mussel	<i>Mytilus edulis</i>	Mine Tailings mine tailings formed of ~50% limestone (CaCO ₃) + quartz, feldspar, mica and iron sulfides + production chemicals like FLOT2015.	mortality, genotoxicity, oxidative damage, neurotoxicity, metabolism, stress on stress, condition index, Al, Ag, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb, Sn, Zn, methyl triethanol ammonium	10	0.3 MPa	Brooks et al. 2018	An integrative biological effects assessment of a mine discharge into a Norwegian fjord using field transplanted mussels
Mussel	<i>Sinonovacula constricta</i>	Dredging: suspended solids.	survival, oxidative stress, metabolism	~12-14	0.1 MPa	Yang et al. 2017	Effect of the exposure to suspended solids on the enzymatic activity in the bivalve <i>Sinonovacula constricta</i>
Clam	<i>Spisula solida</i>	DSM marine sediments	oxidative stress and damage, metabolism	16	4 MPa	Marassi et al. 2023	Deep-sea mining: using hyperbaric conditions to study the impact of sediment plumes in the subtidal clam <i>Spisula solida</i>

Type of organisms	Species	Activity addressed / Source of exposure	Endpoint/ Biomarker	Temperature (°C)	Pressure	References	Title
Clam	<i>Spisula trigonella</i>	chalcopyrite, chalcocite, chalcopyrite copper concentrate, galena, sphalerite, mixed-metal sulfide, dissolved Cu	mortality	21	0.1 MPa	Simpson and Spadaro 2016	Bioavailability and Chronic Toxicity of Metal Sulfide Minerals to Benthic Marine Invertebrates: Implications for Deep Sea
Oyster	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	Mine Tailings mine tailings with and without flotation and flocculation	reproduction, growth, NOEC, LOEC, EC10, EC50	20	0.1 MPa	Brooks et al. 2019	An ecotoxicological assessment of mine tailings from three Norwegian mines
Coral	<i>Lophelia pertusa</i>	Oil & Gas natural sediment and drill cutting with a water-based mud containing glycol and barite (from oil drilling activities).	behaviour, tissue condition, growth	8	0.1 MPa	Larsson and Purser 2011	Sedimentation on the cold-water coral <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> : Cleaning efficiency from natural sediments and drill cuttings
Coral	<i>Duva florida</i>	Mine Tailings rough mine tailings and spherical glass beads	behavior, food intake, particle absorption	4-6	0.1 MPa	Liefmann et al. 2018	Eco-physiological responses of cold-water soft corals to anthropogenic sedimentation and particle shape
Coral	<i>Primnoa resedaeformis</i>	Mine Tailings rough mine tailings and spherical glass beads	behavior, food intake, particle absorption	4-6	0.1 MPa	Liefmann et al. 2018	
Nematode	<i>Halomonhystera disjuncta</i>	dissolved Cu	mortality, Cu	10, 20	0.1, 10 MPa	Mevenkamp et al. 2017	Hydrostatic pressure and temperature affect the tolerance of the free-living marine nematode Marassi et al. 2023 <i>Halomonhystera disjuncta</i> to acute copper exposure
Brittle star	genus <i>Ophiura</i>	DSM crushed seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposit	crushed seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposit	6.5°C , 10.5°C	0.1 MPa	Wurz et al. 2024	Adverse effects of crushed seafloor massive sulphide deposits on the boreal deep-sea sponge <i>Geodia barretti</i> Bowerbank, 1858 and its associated fauna

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Table 3: Scientific literature on environmental impacts of deep-sea mining (list is not exhaustive but contains most relevant studies for ecotoxicology assessments)

Title	Authors	Habitat	Key points
Stressors of emerging concern in deep-sea environments: microplastics, pharmaceuticals, personal care products and deep-sea mining	Pinheiro et al. 2023		Review recent literature on emerging stressors such as microplastics, pharmaceuticals and personal care products, and DSM and discuss cumulative effects with climate change associated variables. The main knowledge gaps in the field are identified and discussed, and future research priorities are highlighted to improve hazard and risk assessment.
Impacts of the first deep-sea seafloor massive sulfide mining excavation tests on benthic communities	Washburn et al. 2023	SMS	Japan undertook the first ever tests of deep-sea seafloor massive sulfide (SMS) excavation in 2017 in the Okinawa Trough. This study examines infauna (nano, meio, macro) from several nearby stations before and up to 3 yr after disturbance. Distance from excavation, current direction, seafloor topography, and modelled and observed deposition and metal concentrations were analysed.
Identifying Toxic Impacts of Metals Potentially Released during Deep-Sea Mining—A Synthesis of the Challenges to Quantifying Risk	Hauton et al. 2017	PMN	Potentially toxic metal mixtures may be released at sea during different stages of the mining process and in different physical phases (dissolved or particulate), whereas the individual toxicity of some dissolved metals has been established in laboratory studies, the complex and variable mineral composition of seabed resources makes the a priori prediction of the toxic risk of DSM extremely challenging. Synthesis presents a summation of recent advances in our understanding of the potential toxic impacts of metal exposure to deep-sea meio- to megafauna at low temperature and high pressure, and consider the limitation of deriving lethal limits based on the paradigm of exposure to single metals in solution. Authors advocate the adoption of an existing practical framework for characterizing bulk resource toxicity in advance of exploitation (Weight of Evidence approach).
Geological, Mineralogical and Textural Impacts on the Distribution of Environmentally Toxic Trace Elements in Seafloor Massive Sulfide Occurrences	Fallon et al. 2019	PMN	A combination of mineralogy, trace element composition and texture characterisation of SMS from various geotectonic settings, when considered along with our current knowledge of oxidation rates and galvanic coupling, can be used to predict potential toxicity of deposit types and individual samples and highlight which may be of environmental concern. Whilst the geological setting does dictate metal endowment, ultimately mineralogy is the largest control of trace element distribution and subsequent potential toxicity. The authors state that this type of study can be combined with “bulk lethal toxicity” assessments and used throughout the stages of a mining project to help guide prospecting and legislation, focus exploitation, and minimise environmental impact.
Evaluating deep-sea communities' susceptibility to mining plumes using shallow-water data	van der Grient and Drazen 2022	PMN	Increased suspended sediment concentrations (SSC) are a major stressor across aquatic habitats. Here, the literature was synthesized to show that animal responses to increases in relative SSC (test concentration/natural background concentration) were similar in type and negative across different shallow-water (marine, estuarine, freshwater) habitats. Further, animal sensitivities are similar across habitats based on relative SSC and occur starting at low relative SSC increases in all habitats despite differences in natural background SSC. Based upon these similarities in relative SSC sensitivities, deep-sea sensitivity values for acute exposure to increased SSC, where empirical data are almost non-existent, were estimated. How the methods and results can be used to inform regulatory thresholds are discussed. Because of the large variability in shallow water datasets and differences between deep-sea and shallow water habitats, deep-sea specific data are needed to verify the estimates and improve their precision.
Ecological risk assessment for deep-sea mining	Washburn et al. 2019		Ecological risk assessment for deep-sea mining is challenging, given the data-poor state of knowledge of deep-sea ecosystem structure, process, and vulnerability. Polling and a scale-intensity-consequence approach (SICA)

Title	Authors	Habitat	Key points
			were used in an expert elicitation survey to rank risk sources and perceived vulnerabilities of habitats associated with seabed nodule, sulfide, and crust mineral resources.
Metal ecotoxicology: An essential component in environmental impact assessment of deep-sea mining	Kwan et al. 2023		Review on Current advances in metal ecotoxicology studies related to DSM. Authors advocate for standardizing workflows for deep-sea metal ecotoxicology in future baseline surveying
Environmental Protection Requires Accurate Application of Scientific Evidence	Smith et al. 2021		Scientific misconceptions are likely leading to miscalculations of the environmental impacts of deep-seabed mining. These result from underestimating mining footprints relative to habitats targeted and poor understanding of the sensitivity, biodiversity, and dynamics of deep-sea ecosystems. Addressing these misconceptions and knowledge gaps is needed for effective management of deep-seabed mining.
Assessing the impacts of seabed mineral extraction in the deep sea and coastal marine environments: Current methods and recommendations for environmental risk assessment	Kaikkonen et al. 2018	PMN	Synthesis of the empirical evidence from experimental seabed mining and parallel industries to infer the effects of seabed mineral extraction on marine ecosystems, focusing on polymetallic nodules and ferromanganese concretions. Authors use a problem-structuring framework to evaluate causal relationships between pressures caused by nodule extraction and the associated changes in marine ecosystems. Authors propose that future impact assessments use pressure-specific expert elicitation. Authors further discuss integrating ecosystem services in the impact assessments and the implications of current methods for environmental risk assessments.
Threatened by mining, polymetallic nodules are required to preserve abyssal epifauna	Vanreusel et al. 2016	PMN	Insight into the fauna associated with nodules is crucial to support effective environmental management. In this study video surveys were used to compare the epifauna from sites with contrasting nodule coverage in four license areas.
Effects of a deep-sea mining experiment on seafloor microbial communities and functions after 26 years	Vonnahme et al. 2020	PMN	Authors revisited the only midsize deep-sea disturbance and recolonization experiment carried out in 1989 in the Peru Basin nodule field to compare habitat integrity, remineralization rates, and carbon flow with undisturbed sites. By highlighting the importance of nodules for the epifaunal biodiversity of this abyssal area, the authors urge for cautious consideration of the criteria for determining future preservation zones.
Application of scientific criteria for identifying hydrothermal ecosystems in need of protection	Gollner et al. 2021	SMS	Several intergovernmental organizations have developed suites of criteria to identify vulnerable, sensitive, and ecologically or biologically significant ecosystems in need of protection. In this case study, we combine criteria developed by FAO for VMEs (Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems), by CBD for EBSAs (Ecologically or Biologically Significant Areas), and by IMO for PSSAs (Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas) to assess whether the 11 confirmed vent fields on the nMAR may meet these criteria.
Digging deep: lessons learned from meiofaunal responses to a disturbance experiment in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone	Lefaible et al. 2023	PMN	In this paper, findings from a small-scale seabed disturbance experiment in the German contract area (Clarion-Clipperton Zone, CCZ) are described, with a focus on the soft-sediment ecosystem component. Despite the limited spatial scale of the induced disturbance on the seafloor, this experiment allowed us to evaluate how short-term (< 1 month) soft-sediment changes can be assessed based on sediment characteristics (grain size, nutrients and pigments) and metazoan meiofaunal communities (morphological and metabarcoding analyses) show how benthic measurements can be combined with numerical modelling of sediment transport to enhance our understanding of meiofaunal responses to increased sedimentation levels. The lessons learned within this study highlight the major issues of current deep-sea mining-related ecological research such as deficient baseline

Title	Authors	Habitat	Key points
			knowledge, unrepresentative impact intensity of mining simulations and challenges associated with sampling trade-offs (e.g., replication).
Potential impacts of polymetallic nodule removal on deep-sea meiofauna	Pape et al. 2021	PMN	To determine potential impacts of polymetallic nodule removal, we investigated the importance of nodule presence for the abundance, composition and diversity of sediment meiofauna, and evaluated the existence and composition of nodule crevice meiofauna in the Global Sea Mineral Resources (GSR) exploration contract area. The authors formulated environmental management recommendations at the contract area and regional (CCFZ) scale related to sampling effort, set-aside preservation and monitoring areas, and potential rehabilitation measures.
Biological effects 26 years after simulated deep-sea mining	Simon-Lledó et al. 2019	PMN	Using data inferred from seafloor photo-mosaics, authors studied the effects of simulated mining impacts, induced during the “DISturbance and reCOLonization experiment” (DISCOL) conducted in 1989.
	Lefaible et al. 2024	PMN	An industrial polymetallic nodule collector trial was conducted by the company Global Sea Mineral Resources (GSR) in their exploration contract area in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone using the pre-prototype vehicle Patania II (PATII). In this study, meiofaunal (i.e., nematode abundance, ASV diversity and genus composition) and environmental (i.e., grain size, total organic carbon/total nitrogen and pigment) properties are compared between disturbance categories (i.e., Pre-impact, Collector Impact and Plume Impact). Authors conclude that complex benthic pressure-response relationships associated with the PATII trial, combined with the high degree of natural spatial and temporal variability in abyssal meiofaunal communities and sedimentary parameters, complicates the quantitative assessment of deep-sea mining associated disturbances.
Impacts of the first deep-sea seafloor massive sulfide mining excavation tests on benthic communities	Washburn et al. 2023	SMS	Japan undertook the first ever tests of deep-sea seafloor massive sulfide (SMS) excavation in 2017 in the Okinawa Trough. This study examines infauna from several nearby stations before and up to 3 yr after disturbance. The authors state that the small scale of disturbance requires caution when extrapolating to full-scale mining, but the results suggest current direction and topography greatly influence the extent of mining impacts; in addition, several metals may be useful for identifying the mining footprint. Biological results indicate that larger macroinfauna may be less resistant and resilient to mining impacts than smaller meiofauna and impacts from even small-scale mining activities may persist for at least 3 yr.

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Table 4: Scientific literature on environmental management of DSM (list represents a selection of studies)

Title	Authors	Key points
Thresholds in deep-seabed mining: A primer for their development	Hitchin et al. 2023	This paper introduces the use of thresholds in the context of deep-seabed mining and explores the range of ways that thresholds can be derived, set out the challenges in translating ecological and management data into thresholds, highlight factors for acceptance and operationalisation of thresholds in deep-seabed mining, and explain the necessity of refining thresholds as knowledge on impacts to features improves. The authors state, that in order to be acceptable to the wide range of deep-seabed mining stakeholders, thresholds need to strike a balance among levels of harm acceptable by society, levels of environmental precaution justifiable by governments, scientific robustness, and operational practicality.
Strategic environmental planning for deep seabed mining in the area	Jaeckel 2020	Discussions about an environmental management strategy for deep seabed mining in the area have been underway for a number of years. In 2018, the International Seabed Authority has adopted its first 5-year strategic plan, covering all aspects of its mandate. This article examines whether the new strategic plan integrates elements of an environmental management strategy and what might be missing. It demonstrates that while some overlaps exist, there are several key gaps left by the current strategic plan which could be filled by an environmental management strategy. These include the development of environmental goals and objectives, a systematic approach to environmental regulation and management, setting priorities, filling gaps in substantive obligations, and allocating environmental management tasks to specific actors.
Strategic Environmental Goals and Objectives: Setting the basis for environmental regulation of deep seabed mining	Tunncliffe et al. 2020	This paper reviews the concept and process for a holistic approach to planning environmental management in the deep sea based on Strategic Environmental Goals and Objectives. To date (of publication), the ISA has considered marine spatial planning largely around the current exploration contract blocks. Other elements of environmental management, including the requirements for baseline studies, impact assessment, post-impact monitoring and the treatment of harmful effects and serious harm need to be implemented to support well-defined environmental goals and objectives. The authors suggest that this planning be executed for scales larger than individual blocks, through a Strategic Environmental Management Plan, to ensure sustainable use of ocean resources across the Area.
Deep-sea mining: Interdisciplinary research on potential environmental, legal, economic, and societal implications	Koschinsky et al. 2018	In this paper, the authors present a comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge in the economic, environmental, social, and legal implications of potential commercial deep-sea mining operations, as well as a comparison of the impacts associated with conventional terrestrial mining. Furthermore, the authors identify knowledge gaps that should be urgently addressed to ensure that the world at large benefits from safe, efficient, and environmentally sound mining procedures.
Existing environmental management approaches relevant to deep-sea mining	Jones et al. 2019	This paper identifies and details existing environmental management approaches relevant to DSM that can be used to improve performance. Project specific environmental management, through environmental impact assessment, baseline assessment, monitoring, mitigation and environmental management planning, will be critical to identify and reduce potential impact.
The current status of deep-sea mining governance at the International Seabed Authority	Blanchard et al. 2023	This article describes the current state of deep-sea mining governance in areas beyond national jurisdiction, providing an accessible overview of the structure and functioning of the International Seabed Authority (ISA), as well as some background information on the different instruments developed by the ISA for deep-sea mining

Title	Authors	Key points
		regulation, control and management. In particular, the article focuses on the way environmental considerations are currently being discussed and negotiated under the Draft Exploitation Regulations. Given that there are no official records kept of ISA meetings, this article thereby also provides an overview of a body of information that is difficult to access.
Area-based management tools to protect unique hydrothermal vents from harmful effects from deep-sea mining: A review of ongoing developments	Blanchard and Gollner 2022	The authors review the current regulatory and policy framework for deep-sea spatial management for PMS, and set it into the environmental context. The authors conclude that all current management measures of the ISA would not be suited to protect the marine environment from harmful mining impact. The authors recognize that ISA's area-based management tools are under development, and suggest that improvements can be achieved by studying and recognizing the ecological attributes of ecosystems and their connectivity, as well as governance connectivity, taking into account area-based management tools of different users in the same area.
Assessment of scientific gaps related to the effective environmental management of deep-seabed mining	Amon et al. 2022	A synthesis of peer-reviewed literature and consultations with deep-seabed mining stakeholders revealed that, despite an increase in deep-sea research, there are few categories of publicly available scientific knowledge comprehensive enough to enable evidence-based decision-making regarding environmental management, including whether to proceed with mining in regions where exploration contracts have been granted by the International Seabed Authority. Closing the scientific gaps related to deep-seabed mining is a monumental task that is essential to fulfilling the overarching obligation to prevent serious harm and ensure effective protection, and will require clear direction, substantial resources, and robust coordination and collaboration. Based on the information gathered, the authors propose a potential high-level road map of activities that could stimulate a much-needed discussion on the steps that should be taken to close key scientific gaps before any exploitation is considered.
Ecosystem-based Management through the lenses of International Seabed Authority stakeholders: current status, implications, and opportunities for the deep-sea mining regime in the Area	Guilhon et al. 2023	Through an online survey and in-depth interviews, ISA stakeholders have been inquired about their perception of the understanding, current status, implications, and opportunities of EBM for the deep-sea mining regime. The authors state that the clarification on what EBM entails for the seabed mining regime should be a matter of major interest to the ISA and all its stakeholders.
Revisiting procedural requirements for the assessment of environmental impacts arising from the different stages of deep seabed mining: Current practices at the International Seabed Authority and recommendations for improvement	Guilhon et al. 2022	This paper seeks to clarify the ISA's procedural framework for the assessment of environmental impacts arising from the different mining stages and reveals that its current practices do not represent a comprehensive, transparent, or participative EIA process that conforms to EBM. Based on the identified shortcomings, this paper provides some recommendations for improvement of EIA practices at the ISA.
Regulating Deep Sea Mining. A Myriad of Legal Frameworks	Willaert 2021	This book provides a comprehensive analysis and explanation of the legal regime with regard to deep sea mining, and identifies all relevant legal instruments, assesses their role, explains their interactions, and engages with some of the topical issues that surround them.
From what-if to what-now: Status of the deep-sea mining regulations and underlying drivers for outstanding issues	Pickens et al. 2024	This paper identifies major issues that remain outstanding in the draft rules, regulations and procedures (RRPs) relating to exploitation and discusses the underlying drivers for their lack of agreement with the aim of providing an indication of the amount of work ahead for the ISA. The authors find that over 30 major regulatory issues remain

Title	Authors	Key points
		outstanding because of not receiving sufficient time for discussion, divergent views amongst member States, and due to a lack of information and inputs to progress negotiations. These findings suggest that member States and prospective contractors should expect negotiations on the adoption of RRP to continue long into the foreseeable future.
Research is needed to inform environmental management of hydrothermally inactive and extinct polymetallic sulfide (PMS) deposits	van Dover et al. 2020	This paper calls for actions of the scientific community and the emergent seabed mining industry to i) undertake fundamental ecological descriptions and study of ecosystem functions and services associated with hydrothermally inactive PMS deposits, ii) evaluate potential environmental risks to ecosystems of inactive PMS deposits through research, and iii) identify environmental management needs that may enable mining of inactive PMS deposits.
Risk Assessment for Deep-Seabed Mining	van Doorn et al. 2022	This book chapter describes the different risks involved in deep-seabed mining, develops a methodology for risk assessment for the exploitation of marine mineral resources that takes into consideration the state of knowledge and evolving research on deep-sea ecosystems, and informs on possible environmental threshold values in relation to deep-seabed mining operations.
A procedural framework for robust environmental management of deep-sea mining projects using a conceptual model	Durden et al. 2017	Robust environmental management of deep-sea mining projects must be integrated into the planning and execution of mining operations, and developed concurrently. It should follow a framework indicating the environmental management-related activities necessary at each project phase, and their interrelationships. An environmental management framework with this purpose is presented in this paper; it facilitates the development of environmental information and decision-making throughout the phases of a mining project.
Environmental Impact Assessment process for deep-sea mining in 'the Area'	Durden et al. 2018	This article presents an ideal EIA process for DSM, drawing upon the application of EIA from allied industries. It contains screening, scoping and assessment phases, along with the development of an environmental management plan. It also includes external review by experts, stakeholder consultation, and regulatory review. Lessons learned from application of EIA elsewhere are discussed in relation to DSM, including the integration of EIA into UK domestic law, and the reception of EIAs prepared for seabed ore extraction in the Exclusive Economic Zones of New Zealand and Papua New Guinea. Finally, four main challenges of implementing the EIA process to DSM in the Area are presented.
Review of National Legislations Applicable to Seabed Mineral Resources Exploitation	Roux and Horsfield 2020	This chapter seeks to provide a broad overview of seabed mining within the national jurisdictions of sovereign coastal states. Section 2 provides a brief outline of international legal and governance instruments that are intended to provide a framework for national policy and decision-making on seabed mining. Section 3 seeks to provide a comparative analysis of legal and policy approaches adopted by various countries in relation to seabed exploration and exploitation. Section 4 provides a more in-depth case study of South Africa, focusing on marine phosphate prospecting. Section 5 provides a brief synthesis of approaches adopted by other countries and the legal and governance principles that underpinned these approaches. Overall, this seeks to provide a structure for decision-making on seabed mining in the national jurisdictions of coastal States.
Marine Pollution - Monitoring, Management and Mitigation	Reichelt-Brushett 2023	The study of marine environments inevitably involves considering the problem of marine pollution, which includes questions that focus on the essential need to ensure the long-term health of these exceptional ecosystems and

Title	Authors	Key points
		the lives and livelihoods they support. The open access textbook "Marine Pollution: monitoring, management and mitigation" approaches these questions.
Moving towards an operational framework for defining serious harm for management of seabed mining	Leduc et al. 2024	The authors propose a scientifically focused risk framework approach for defining serious harm in the context of polymetallic nodule mining based on ISA documentation, as well as international and national criteria, and approaches developed for managing deep-sea resources. A three-tier "traffic light" scheme is proposed, with a threshold level between detectable (green) and significant harm (orange), and a further limit beyond which significant harm becomes serious harm (red). The authors further provide illustrations of the type of criteria that could be used in defining levels of harmful effects, and further discuss aspects related to ensuring definitions and their application are fit-for-purpose. The work bridges the gap between earlier attempts at defining serious harm in the context of deep-sea mining and the need for a clear and consistent approach to operationalise the concept of serious harm.

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Table 5: Other relevant scientific literature

Title	Authors	Key points
A novel approach for estimating and predicting uncertainty in water quality index model using machine learning approaches	Uddin et al. 2023	This research provides a robust statistically sound methodology for assessment of water quality index (WQI) model uncertainties. Eight WQI models are considered. The Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) technique was applied to estimate model uncertainty, while the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) algorithm was utilised to predict uncertainties in the WQI models at each sampling site.
Best Practices for Derivation and Application of Thresholds for Metals Using Bioavailability-Based Approaches	van Genderen et al. 2020	The primary goal of the present study is to provide a broad view of best practices for evaluating bioavailability models for metals for use in the protection of aquatic life. The authors describe the state of the science regarding 1) the evaluation and selection of ecotoxicity data, 2) the selection of bioavailability models for use in normalization, and 3) subsequent application of bioavailability models.
How Specific Is Site-Specific? A Review and Guidance for Selecting and Evaluating Approaches for Deriving Local Water Quality Benchmarks	van Dam et al. 2019	Guidance on methodologies to derive site-specific thresholds and benchmarks Existing prescriptive guidance on the derivation of local water quality benchmarks (WQBs; e.g., guideline values, criteria, standards) for protecting aquatic ecosystems is limited to only 3 to 4 specific approaches. This review addresses the deficiency in guidance by 1) defining local WQBs and outlining initial considerations for deciding if one is required; 2) summarizing the existing regulatory context; 3) summarizing existing guidance and identifying gaps; 4) describing strengths, weaknesses, and potential applications of a range of derivation approaches based on laboratory and/or field data; and 5) presenting a conceptual framework for appropriately selecting and evaluating a derivation approach to best suit the need. The guidance can be used by industry, regulators, and others for both the a priori selection and the post hoc evaluation of appropriate approaches for deriving local WQBs.

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Table 6: Scientific literature in environmental impacts from offshore industries other than DSM (submarine tailings disposal, dredging and dredging disposal, oil and gas) and general studies in suspended sediment and sedimentation effects

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
Submarine tailings disposal			
	A generic environmental risk assessment framework for deep-sea tailings placement	Stauber et al. 2022	Review, description of major stressors of deep-sea tailings placements, literature references for ecotox testing
	An integrative biological effects assessment of a mine discharge into a Norwegian fjord using field transplanted mussels	Brooks et al. 2018	Study on biological effects of the Hustadmarmor discharge tailings on transplanted mussels living in the water column at known distances from the discharge outlet
	An ecotoxicological assessment of mine tailings from three Norwegian mines	Brooks et al. 2019	Study assessed the environmental toxicity of three Norwegian mine tailings from Omya Hustadmarmor, Sydvaranger, and Sibelco, which are all released into a seawater recipient. Ecotoxicity assessments were performed on the overlying water extracted from the mine tailings, the transformation/dissolution waters obtained from the mine tailings, and whole sediment assessment using a suite of marine organisms including algae, Crustacea, and Mollusca
	Biological effects of long term fine limestone tailings discharge in a fjord ecosystem	Brooks et al. 2015	Benthic infaunal data collected from 1993 to 2010 were analysed to examine the effect of long term discharge of fine limestone tailings on macrofaunal species assemblages in a fjord. Relative distance from the outfall and proportion of fine tailings in the sediment were correlated with benthic community structure
	Epifaunal and infaunal responses to submarine mine tailings in a Norwegian fjord	Trannum et al. 2019	Results from a field study in Frænfjorden, Norway, which is subject to disposal of mine tailings in marine shallow water. Structural and functional responses of benthic infauna and epifauna were investigated along a gradient from heavy tailings deposition to reference conditions; tailings clearly impacted the faunal composition; Sessile and tube-living taxa, and deposit and suspension feeders decreased, probably due to smothering in combination with tailings-associated changes of the substrate. Functional diversity decreased for both infauna and epifauna, but less than the structural diversity
	Effects of submarine mine tailings on macrobenthic community structure and ecosystem processes	Trannum et al. 2018	Dose and response of 3 types of mine tailings studied in a soft-bottom mesocosm, environmental thresholds for sedimentation
	Recolonization and recovery of an Arctic benthic community subject to mine-tailings deposits	Trannum et al. 2023	At a 40 + – year old tailing deposition area for a copper mine in the Arctic fjord Repparfjorden, both short-term colonization of mine tailings contaminated sediments through a field experiment, and the present faunal state in the old deposit area were studied
	Benthic community status and mobilization of Ni, Cu and Co at abandoned sea deposits for mine tailings in SW Norway	Schaanning et al. 2019	Abandoned deposit sites were sampled to assess the state of metal contamination and macrobenthic communities 20–30 years after deposition was ended; investigation of faunal responses by means of field samples and mesocosm set-up

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	Risk Assessment and Ecotoxicology: Limitations and Recommendations for Ocean Disposal of Mine Waste in the Coral Triangle	Reichelt-Brushett 2012	Reviews three factors—tailing characterization, ecotoxicology, and bioaccumulation / biomagnification — in relation to the current application of these methods to risk assessment of submarine tailings disposal (STD), and identifies ways to improve current practices. A decision-tree approach has been developed specific to STD risk assessment for implementation at the pre-proposal stage of a project
	Impacts of gold mine waste disposal on deepwater fish in a pristine tropical marine system	Brewer et al. 2007	Assess the impacts of the Lihir gold mine waste disposal on tropical deep-water fish communities by comparing (i) fish abundances and (ii) concentrations of trace metals in the tissues of fish from regions adjacent to and away from the Lihir gold mine
	New insights into submarine tailing disposal for a reduced environmental footprint: Lessons learnt from Norwegian fjords	Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2022	Synthesis of results of a multidisciplinary programme on environmental impacts of STDs in Norwegian fjords; provides new knowledge that will support guidelines for best available technologies and improved management in Norway and internationally
	Submarine and deep-sea mine tailing placements: A review of current practices, environmental issues, natural analogs and knowledge gaps in Norway and internationally	Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2015	Review on impacts and existing legislation, environmental thresholds for sedimentation
	Leaching of Metals and Metalloids from Hydrothermal Ore Particulates and Their Effects on Marine Phytoplankton	Fuchida et al. 2017	Fresh hydrothermal sulfides were collected from the Izena Hole, Okinawa Trough and immediately subjected to leaching experiments onboard. The data were then used to evaluate the potential for metal leaching from hydrothermal sulfide into seawater
	Scientific Considerations for the Assessment and Management of Mine Tailings Disposal in the Deep Sea.	Vare et al. 2018	Builds on previous reviews and case studies to consider (1) tailings disposal options, (2) impacts and recovery potential from tailings disposal in the deep sea, and (3) the role of scientific information in analysis of case studies. With a focus on DSTD the following aspects are discussed; societal and environmental impacts, approaches to reducing environmental impact, future prospects, legal controls and constraints, science gaps and DSTD relevance to broader environmental management in the deep ocean
	Biogeochemical impact of historical submarine mine tailings on benthic ecosystems in the Repparfjord (Northern Norway)	Hoff et al. 2024	Investigation of historical copper mine tailings deposited in the Repparfjord, Northern Norway The study couples the pore water chemistry and the foraminiferal analysis obtained from selected sediment cores (gravity core, multicore, box cores) to examine metal stability and the past and current status of the foraminifera community. The authors measured down-core sulfate and trace metal concentrations and Eh-Ph and applied the Shannon index, the AZTI's Marine Biotic Index (F-AMBI) index and the foraminiferal abnormality index. This study confirms the ongoing leaching of Cu from the underlying mine tailings and release across the sediment-water interface.
	Ecological impacts of large-scale disposal of mining waste in the deep sea	Hughes et al. 2015	The authors studied the impacts of an active (Lihir) and a closed (Misima) deep-sea tailings disposal site in Papua New Guinea.

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
			Investigations around the Lihir and Misima island mines in Papua New Guinea were conducted to measure the impacts of ongoing DSTP and assess the state of benthic infaunal communities after its conclusion. At Lihir, where DSTP has operated continuously since 1996, abundance of sediment infauna was substantially reduced across the sampled depth range (800–2020m), accompanied by changes in higher-taxon community structure, in comparison with unimpacted reference stations. At Misima, where DSTP took place for 15 years, ending in 2004, effects on community composition persisted 3.5 years after its conclusion. The study is based on the Shimmield et al. (2011) report
	Gold mining and submarine tailings disposal: Review and case study	Edinger 2012	Case study of the Newmont Minahasa Raya gold mine in Indonesia, focussing on toxic impacts
	Threshold response of benthic macrofauna integrity to metal contamination in West Greenland	Josefson et al. 2008	The authors examined effects of submarine tailings deposition (STD) on benthic invertebrate community structure in an Arctic fjord system in Western Greenland, where submarine tailings from a lead–zinc mine, containing high concentrations of metals, mainly lead and zinc and to some extent copper, were deposited. Sediment metal chemistry and benthic infauna surveys have been conducted over 33 years following a BACI protocol. The authors found clear predictable changes of benthic fauna composition in response to STD both temporally and spatially.
	In situ characterisation of complex suspended particulates surrounding an active submarine tailings placement site in a Norwegian fjord	Davies and Nepstad 2017	The authors present detailed in situ measurements of the distribution of suspended mine tailings within Frænfjorden, Norway. Measurements focused on characterisation of spatial variability in particle and floc size, and determination of suspended mine tailing concentrations. Multiple instruments were used to ensure that all relevant particle sizes could be observed. These included a LISST-100x, a LISST-Holo and a bespoke particle imaging system, which were deployed together on a profiling frame at multiple stations transecting the fjord.
	High-resolution numerical modelling of a marine mine tailings discharge in Western Norway	Nepstad et al. 2020	To understanding the environmental impact of releasing large amounts of mine tailings into the marine system, multiple processes must be well characterised, including those relating to the transport and fate of the disposed material. The authors applied a set of high-resolution models for wind, hydrodynamics, and sediment transport to simulate a submarine mine tailings discharge in a Norwegian fjord. The transport model includes processes to account for the effect of flocculation on mine tailings transport and fate.
Dredging			
	Effect of the exposure to suspended solids on the enzymatic activity in the bivalve <i>Sinonovacula constricta</i>	Yang et al. 2017	Study on long-term impact of high levels of suspended solids on the physiology of the adult bivalve mollusc <i>Sinonovacula constricta</i>

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	A review of the potential effects of suspended sediment on fishes: potential dredging-related physiological, behavioral, and transgenerational implications	Kjelland et al. 2015	Review on suspended sediments effects on freshwater and estuarine fish including short-term (i.e., physiology and behavior) and long-term effects (transgenerational)
	Effects of suspended sediments on the sponge holobiont with implications for dredging management	Pineda et al. 2017	Environmental threshold for suspended solids
	A critical analysis of the direct effects of dredging on fish	Wenger et al. 2017	Meta-analysis following a conservative approach is used to understand how dredging-related stressors, including suspended sediment, contaminated sediment, hydraulic entrainment and underwater noise, directly influence the effect size and the response elicited in fish across all aquatic ecosystems and all life history stages. This is followed by an in-depth review summarizing the effects of each dredging-related stressor on fish
	Environmental impacts of dredging and other sediment disturbances on corals: A review	Erftemeijer et al. 2012	A review of published literature on the sensitivity of corals to turbidity and sedimentation is presented, with an emphasis on the effects of dredging. The risks and severity of impact from dredging (and other sediment disturbances) on corals are primarily related to the intensity, duration and frequency of exposure to increased turbidity and sedimentation. The sensitivity of a coral reef to dredging impacts and its ability to recover depend on the antecedent ecological conditions of the reef, its resilience and the ambient conditions normally experienced. Effects of sediment stress have so far been investigated in 89 coral species (~10% of all known reef-building corals). Results of these investigations have provided a generic understanding of tolerance levels, response mechanisms, adaptations and threshold levels of corals to the effects of natural and anthropogenic sediment disturbances.
Oil and Gas			
	Environmental impacts of produced water and drilling waste discharges from the Norwegian offshore petroleum industry	Bakke et al. 2013	Review of papers on effects of discharges of produced water and drilling waste from offshore petroleum operations; Produced water may cause toxic effects on individual organisms in laboratory and close to outlets; effects of oil contaminated drill cuttings deposits on the benthos are confined to within less than 2 km; effects of water based cuttings are reported from laboratory and only close to drill wells; effects of the discharges on populations and communities have not yet been verified and are unlikely.
	Environmental Impacts of the Deep-Water Oil and Gas Industry: A Review to Guide Management Strategies	Cordes et al. 2016	A general review of impacts from oil and gas activities; spatial footprints and recovery, environmental management approaches
	Species sensitivity distributions for suspended clays, sediment burial, and grain size change in the marine environment	Smit et al. 2008	Development of marine species sensitivity distributions (SSDs) for three nontoxic stressors: suspended clays, burial by sediment, and change in sediment grain size; provide management thresholds for suspended particles, grain size changes, sedimentation

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	Whole Effluent Toxicity Data and Discharge Volumes to Assess the Likelihood that Environmental Risks of Offshore Produced Water Discharges Are Adequately Controlled	Karman and Smit 2019	Assessment of the likelihood that the environmental risk of produced water discharges is adequately controlled based on WET data for 19 oil- and gas-producing platforms and their discharge volumes. Our analysis shows that, with the selected risk criterion of predicted exposure concentration (PEC)/predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) should not exceed 1 at 500 m, there is a mean likelihood of 99.5% (or more) that the environmental risk from the produced water discharges is adequately controlled for installations that discharge $30 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$ (or less)
	Effects of suspended drill cuttings on the coral <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> using pulsed and continuous exposure scenarios	Baussant et al. 2018	Cold-water coral <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> was exposed to drill cuttings from offshore exploration in the lab with the goal to assess precautionary thresholds of effects . Overall, a DC concentration of 10 mg/L seems to represent a threshold above which changes in coral conditions were observed however with no apparent physiological consequences for the coral within the experimental time scale
	Effects of drill cuttings on biogeochemical fluxes and macrobenthos of marine sediments	Schaanning et al. 2008	Experimental work was performed on drill cuttings sampled from off-shore drilling operations; benthic mesocosms, investigation of community response; a significant difference in community composition between clean and cuttings treatments, and three taxa showed significantly reduced abundances in the cuttings treatments. Chemical toxicity of mud components is assumed to be small, and the observed effect was more likely a result of physical properties such as the size or shape of cuttings particles
	Environmental effects of offshore produced water discharges: A review focused on the Norwegian continental shelf	Beyer et al. 2020	Review of offshore produced water (PW) ecotoxicity Provides an updated summary of knowledge on the ecotoxicology of offshore PW discharges, primarily addresses research and monitoring reports from Norwegian research groups, and put most emphasis on peer-reviewed publications, looks at the adequacy of the present systems of environmental regulation and management of PW on the Norwegian continental shelf
	Critical review of the OSPAR risk-based approach for offshore-produced water discharges	Nielsen et al. 2023	In 2010, OSPAR introduced the risk-based approach (RBA) for PW management. The RBA includes a hazard assessment estimating PW ecotoxicity using two approaches: whole-effluent toxicity (WET) and substance-based (SB). Set against the framework of the WET and SB approach, a literature review on the magnitude and cause of PW ecotoxicity was conducted, respectively, and on the challenges of estimating these
	Environmental Risk Assessment of Discharges from Onshore Facilities to Coastal Environments	Rye Henrik et al. 2011	Provides an overview of the development of the EIF for coastal discharges; risk approach is based on a comparison of the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC) and the Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC). Toxicity risks as well as risks from temperature increase, oxygen depletion and suspended particles are included in the tool. The EIF is calculated for both that water column and the seafloor representing the volume or area of the recipient where PEC exceeds PNEC.
	Produced Water: Overview of Composition, Fates and Effects	Neff et al. 2011	Reviews scientific knowledge regarding the composition, environmental fate and biological effects of produced water discharges to the ocean

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	An impact-based environmental risk assessment model toolbox for offshore produced water discharges	Nepstad et al. 2023	<p>Approach to environmental risk assessment of produced water discharges based on explicit impact and probability, using a combination of transport, fate and toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic models within a super-individual framework.</p> <p>Approach is based on the well-established fate model DREAM, and accounts for time-variable exposure, considers body burden and effects for specific species and stressors, and assesses the probability of impact.</p>
	Comparison of Substance-Based and Whole-Effluent Toxicity of Produced Water Discharges from Norwegian Offshore Oil and Gas Installations	de Vries et al. 2022	<p>Toxicity assessed based on WET and substance-based was compared for 25 offshore produced water effluents collected for the Norwegian implementation of the Oslo–Paris convention risk-based assessment program. The objectives were, firstly, to examine the concurrence between toxicity estimates derived from these two lines of evidence; and, secondly, to evaluate whether toxicity of produced water discharges predicted from substance-based data is adequately addressed in comparison with ground truth reflected by WET</p>
	Studies on the impact of a water-based drilling mud weighting agent (Barite) on some Benthic invertebrates	Strachan 2010	<p>A comparative study was carried out to observe effects of standard grade and fine grade barite on the filtration rates of four suspension feeding bivalves, <i>Modiolus modiolus</i>, <i>Dosinia exoleta</i>, <i>Venerupis senegalensis</i> and <i>Chlamys varia</i>; Standard grade barite, the most commonly used weighting agent in water-based drilling mud, was responsible for altering the filtration rates of the four bivalve species and damaging the gill structure. The four bivalves were exposed to 0.5mm, 1.0mm and 2.0mm daily depth equivalents of standard grade barite, which permanently remained in suspension. All three barite levels altered the filtration rates leading to 100% mortality.</p>
Others /sediment quality assessments/Effects of suspended particles and sedimentation (including from bottom trawling)			
	Macrobenthic community response to copper in Shelter Island Yacht Basin, San Diego Bay, California	Neira et al. 2011	Macrofaunal response to enhanced Cu
	Sediment toxicity testing	Simpson et al. 2016	<p>Describes sediment toxicity testing methods that primarily assess effects to whole organisms, including survival, reproduction, development, and behaviour; focuses on laboratory-based whole-sediment toxicity tests</p>
	Sediment Toxicity Tests: A Critical Review of Their use in Environmental Regulations	Leppanen et al. 2024	<p>The present review assesses the implementation of sediment toxicity testing in environmental regulations globally. The authors critically survey the use of sediment toxicity testing in international environmental regulations, with the aim to identify where sediment toxicity testing is used effectively and where and how applications could be improved. A distinction is made between sediment toxicity testing aimed to protect sediments facing contamination by newer pollutants (prospective testing, i.e., for chemical or product safety assessments) and testing used to regulate historically contaminated sediments (retrospective assessments). Emphasis is on European, North American, and Australasia regulations; however, the limited relevant regulations from other parts of the world are also discussed</p>

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	Risk assessments of contaminated sediments from the perspective of weight of evidence strategies – a Swedish case study	Bruce et al. 2021	Provides an increased understanding of how ERAs of contaminated sediments are conducted in comparison to established guidelines, Sweden as a case study with seven ERAs compared with four internationally established strategies.
	A review of chemical-based sediment quality assessment methodologies for the marine environment	Birch 2018	This review of 19 chemical approaches used in assessing sediment quality are classified into empirical, mechanistic and sediment quality indices (SQI) groups. The 41 SQGs reviewed show a considerable range in upper and lower guideline values. Grain size and organic content should be included into SQGs, however inclusion of suspended sediment into SQGs raises concerns. SQGs are built into decision-tree schemes with other lines-of-evidence and evaluated in a weight-of-evidence framework.
	Sediment quality guidelines: challenges and opportunities for improving sediment management	Kwok et al. 2014	During the International Conference on Deriving Environmental Quality Standards for the Protection of Aquatic Ecosystems held in Hong Kong in December 2011, an expert group, comprising scientists, government officials, and consultants from four continents, was formed to discuss the important scientific and regulatory challenges with developing sediment quality guidelines (SQGs). This document summarizes the key findings from the expert group.
	Effects of sediment exposure on corals: a systematic review of experimental studies	Tuttle and Donahue 2022	Systematic review and meta-analysis of experimental studies that explore the effects of sediment on corals. exposure levels that adversely affect corals were identified environmental thresholds for suspended solids and sedimentation
	Experimental mining plumes and ocean warming trigger stress in a deep pelagic jellyfish	Stenvers et al. 2023	The authors investigate the effects of simulated ocean warming and sediment plumes on the cosmopolitan deep-sea jellyfish <i>Periphylla periphylla</i> , combining insights gained from physiology, gene expression and changes in associated microbiota.
	Influence of suspended inorganic particles (kaolinite) on eggs and larvae of the pelagic shrimp <i>Lucensosergia lucens</i>	Alam et al. 2022	Experimental study; the authors tested the hypothesis that elevated levels of suspended inorganic (kaolinite) particles in seawater negatively affect the hatching ratio of fertilized eggs, and the survival, growth, and metamorphosis of nauplius and elaphocaris larvae of <i>L. lucens</i>
	Ecophysiological and behavioural response of juveniles of the Chilean cold-water coral <i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) huinayensis</i> to increasing sediment loads	Fähse et al. 2023	The authors investigated the sensitivity of cold-water corals (CWCs) to sediment stress, using juvenile <i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) huinayensis</i> as a model. A 12-week aquarium experiment was conducted with three sediment loads: the average natural sediment concentration in Comau Fjord, 100- and 1000-fold higher sediment levels, expected from gravel road use and coastal erosion. Changes in coral mass and calyx dimensions, polyp expansion, tissue retraction and respiration were measured.
	Vulnerability of six cold-water corals to sediment resuspension from bottom trawling fishing	Bilan et al. 2023	Study on survival, growth, and physiological response of six CWCs from a Mediterranean submarine canyon (<i>Dendrophyllia cornigera</i> , <i>Desmophyllum dianthus</i> , <i>Desmophyllum pertusum</i> , <i>Madrepora oculata</i> , <i>Leiopathes glaberrima</i> and <i>Muriceides lepida</i>), exposed to a long-term, aquarium-based sedimentary disturbance experiment.

Offshore Industry	Title	Authors	Key points
	Rapid respiratory responses of the deep-water sponge <i>Geodia barretti</i> exposed to suspended sediments	Tjensvoll et al. 2013	Study on the effects of suspended sediment exposure related to bottom trawling on deep-water sponges. In a laboratory experiment, <i>Geodia barretti</i> (Bowerbank 1858) (Class: Demospongiae) was exposed to 5 different sediment concentrations (0, 10, 50, 100 and 500 mg l ⁻¹). Respiration rates were measured before, during and after the exposure period.
	Responses of a common New Zealand coastal sponge to elevated suspended sediments: Indications of resilience	Cummings et al. 2020	The study assessed the functioning (survival, respiration, morphology) of a common New Zealand cushion sponge, <i>Crella incrustans</i> (Carter, 1885), during four weeks of exposure to a gradient of suspended sediment concentrations (SSC). Survival was high, and oxygen consumption was not affected. Sponges did, however, develop apical fistules, a phenomenon never-before observed in this species.
	Short-term physiological responses of the New Zealand deep-sea sponge <i>Ecionemia novaezealandiae</i> to elevated concentrations of suspended sediments	Mobilia et al. 2021	Exposed the deep-sea New Zealand sponge <i>Ecionemia novaezealandiae</i> (Dendy, 1924) (Demospongiae: Ancorinidae) to a range of suspended sediment concentrations (SSC) (32, 78 and 475 mg l ⁻¹) and control conditions (no added sediment) continuously for two weeks. Survival was high (97%), with only one death (at the highest SSC). Half of the sponges in the 475 mg l ⁻¹ treatment showed partial necrosis by the end of the two-week exposure. Respiration rates of sponges in the sediment addition treatments decreased relative to control sponges by 27, 37 and 60%, respectively, after day 1; and by 7, 17, and 27%, respectively, after 14 days of suspended sediment exposure.

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Table 7: Reports on environmental impacts from offshore industry activities other than DSM (submarine tailings disposal, dredging and oil and gas).

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
Submarine tailings disposal			
	Mining industry and tailings disposal - status, environmental challenges and gaps of knowledge (M-1335)	NEA NEA 2019	Compilation of existing data and knowledge regarding disposal of waste rock and tailings and environmental assessments relating to the use of chemicals in the mining industry. National and international experience has been applied, with a focus on disposal of tailings in the marine environment. Emphasis on identifying knowledge gaps related to the dispersal of tailings and environmental impact. Overview on relevant legislation
	Proceedings of the GESAMP International Workshop on the Impacts of Mine Tailings in the Marine Environment". (IMO/FAO/UNESCO-IOC/UNIDO/WMO/IAEA/UN/UNEP/UNDP Joint Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection)	GESAMP 2016	Workshop report; concluded that there are major gaps that need to be addressed in the scientific understanding of the behaviour of mine tailings in the sea at depths greater than 20 to 80 m and consequently the short and long term impacts on the marine environment and other potential users of marine resources. Furthermore, scientific gaps in measurement and monitoring techniques in assessing impacts of existing and proposed new deep-sea discharges of mine tailings need to be addressed; efforts should inform the policy discussion on the need to develop international guidelines, including best management practices. Stressors from STD: dispersal of sediment plumes and enhanced sedimentation, contaminants in the tailings, habitat change
	Technical Report on the discharge of mining waste chemicals and materials into Norwegian water bodies	ESA 2024	Technical report describes the results of a review of technical and scientific data concerning the discharge of mining waste chemicals and materials into Norwegian water bodies, including fjords, and their impacts on the ecological and chemical status of those water bodies. This technical report is focused on issues relating to the Water Framework Directive (WFD).
	An Independent Evaluation of Deep-Sea Mine Tailings Placement (DSTP) in PNG	SAMS Report (Shimmiel et al. 2010)	The Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) was contracted through its trading company SAMS Research Services Limited (SRSL) by the Papua New Guinea (PNG) Government to provide research services as a component of the EU funded Mining Sector Support Programme (MSSP). Brief was to improve understanding of the ecological and geochemical processes in deep water that accompany Deep Sea Mine Tailings Placement (DSTP) in Papua New Guinea (PNG). The focus on deep-water processes was appropriate because much less is known about these than processes in shallow water which are focussed in the vicinity of the mines and processing plants

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
			<p>The present report outlines the mining context for each DSTP, the background environmental information gathered by the mining companies during their monitoring programmes and some additional information from the scientific literature, the methods used in the present research, the results and a discussion of these results. The data collected are included in full in appendices. Additionally, guidelines on best practice for DSTP have been developed in consultation with a large group of stakeholders and are included in an appendix.</p>
Dredging			
	<p>The Effects of Turbidity and Suspended Sediments on ESA-Listed Species from Projects Occurring in the Greater Atlantic Region</p>	<p>NOAA Fisheries (Johnson 2018)</p>	<p>Paper reviews recent information about turbidity and suspended sediment, including the potential effects of sedimentation on Greater Atlantic Region marine and anadromous species listed under the ESA, as well as effects to their habitats (including critical habitats, as defined by the ESA, where applicable) and prey species; considers concentration level thresholds for various effects (behavioral, physiological, and lethal) on listed fish; Thresholds provided</p>
	<p>WAMSI Dredging Science Node Theme 6 Synthesis report: Defining thresholds and indicators of filter feeder responses to dredging-related pressures</p>	<p>WAMSI (Wahab et al. 2019)</p>	<p>The WAMSI Dredging Science Node is a strategic research initiative that evolved in response to uncertainties in the environmental impact assessment and management of large-scale dredging operations and coastal infrastructure developments. Its goal is to enhance capacity within government and the private sector to predict and manage the environmental impacts of dredging in Western Australia, delivered through a combination of reviews, field studies, laboratory experimentation, relationship testing and development of standardised protocols and guidance for impact prediction, monitoring and management</p> <p>Biological responses of sponges to dredging-related stressors; assess the effects of dredging related stressors, including SSCs, light attenuation and sediment smothering, in isolation and in combination under conditions simulating realistic dredging scenarios in a series of laboratory experiments, provide ecological (pressure) thresholds</p>
	<p>Effects of dredging and dredging related activities on water quality: Impacts on coral mortality and threshold development</p>	<p>WAMSI (Fisher et al. 2019)</p>	<p>Study uses water quality and coral health datasets from four large scale dredging projects in the Pilbara to develop management threshold values for suspended sediment conc. and sediment deposition, based on combination of ex situ laboratory studies and in situ field based studies; thresholds for boundaries between the management zones of impact defined by EPA-WA for dredging EIAs</p>
	<p>Effects of dredging-related stressors on sponges: laboratory experiments. Report of Theme 6</p>	<p>WAMSI (Pineda et al. 2017)</p>	<p>Detailed summary of how sponges respond to dredging-related stressors, including experimentally derived stress thresholds</p> <p>Light attenuation, SSCs and sediment smothering were tested in isolation and in a combined experiment</p>

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
			Results contributed to the derivation of trigger values that can be used to interrogate models for impact prediction and in water quality monitoring programs
	Effects of dredging-related pressures on critical ecological processes for corals Synthesis Report of Theme 7	WAMSI (Negri et al. 2019)	<p>The main objective of the WAMSI Theme 7 program was to improve understanding of the relative sensitivity of the reproductive and larval settlement stages of corals to the pressures of elevated suspended sediment concentrations (SSC), light attenuation and sedimentation leading to enhanced confidence in the prediction and management of dredging related impacts on corals</p> <p>Theme 7 was divided into two phases, the first involving a review of the available literature and the second based around laboratory experiments that were informed by the reviews</p> <p>Synthesis sets out the key findings of the research program in the context of providing knowledge to better evaluate the level of risk posed to coral reproductive processes from suspended and deposited sediments associated with dredging activities in WA</p>
	Effects of dredging-related pressures on critical ecological processes for finfish: a review and possible management strategies. Report of Theme 8	WAMSI (Harvey et al. 2017)	collated and analysed the available literature on the effect of sediment concentrations on fishes from a variety of aquatic habitats, provide suggestions for trigger values
	Assessment Criteria for Dredged Material with special focus on the North Sea Region	SedNet 2011	The main intention of this paper is to compare applied assessment criteria for assessing chemical contamination of material to be disposed at sea. Different national guidelines are in use for the management of dredged material in the countries of the North Sea region. The implementation and the setting of assessment criteria is within the custody of each country. Hence, there are differences concerning the assessment criteria for the material to be disposed at sea.
	Dredging and Seafloor Integrity Paper	CEDA 2023	Information paper from the Central Dredging Association CEDA on impacts of dredging on D6 descriptor seafloor integrity. This includes a description on how different types of dredging, disposal, and placement of dredged material or marine construction activities may affect Seafloor Integrity and discusses the relevant spatial and time scales in relation to assessing the possible impact of dredging projects under MSFD requirements. It also describes the cumulative effects of dredging projects on benthic ecosystems, as well as the benthic community's potential for recovery.
	Assessment of the environmental impact of dredging for navigational purposes	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2009b)	The assessment is a contribution to the series of assessments of human activities, as listed in the Strategy for a Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP) Appendix 3 and focuses on the impacts on the marine environment of dredging for navigational purposes.

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
			The assessment of the environmental impact of dredging activities is based on the responses received from several Contracting Parties and the non-governmental observer organization CEDA to two questionnaires and on information contained in the background document on environmental impacts on marine species and habitats of dredging for navigational purposes.
	Literature Review on the Impacts of Dredged Sediment Disposal at Sea	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2008)	Report provides an overview of information on the physical, chemical and ecological effects of the disposal of dredged material based on a study of available scientific literature. It summarizes the present knowledge, identifies scientific gaps and suggests directions for further research. It also provides summaries of studies on the effects of dumping of dredged material in the OSPAR Maritime Area
Oil and Gas			
	Threshold levels and risk-functions for non-toxic sediment stressors: burial, grain size changes, and hypoxia – summary report	TNO-Report (Smit et al. 2006)	Threshold values for burial, grain size change and oxygen depletion; provides an overview of the results related to the establishment of threshold values and risk curves for non-toxic sediment stressors to be included in the calculation rules for the Environmental Impact Factor for drilling discharges (EIF DD)
	Assessment of impacts of offshore oil and gas activities in the North-East Atlantic	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2009a)	Synthesis of environmental issues from oil and gas activities arising from major pressures (oil, produced water, chemicals, cutting piles etc); review of management actions in order to reduce impacts in OSPAR regions
	Assessment of the disturbance of drill cuttings during decommissioning	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2019)	The Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP) 2014 – 2021 requires an assessment of the impacts of the offshore oil and gas industry on the marine environment, including possible releases of oil and chemicals from any disturbance of cuttings piles containing non-aqueous drilling fluids; report includes literature review of potential environmental impacts of disturbance of cutting piles
	Report on impacts of discharges of oil and chemicals in produced water on the marine environment	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2021)	Impact of continuous discharges of PW on the offshore ecosystem is assessed in this report as one of several steps in preparation of input to the OSPAR Quality Status Report 2023 for the offshore oil & gas sector Assessment builds on the Intermediate Assessment 2017 for the offshore oil & gas sector, on existing data and information from e.g. Norwegian Water Column Monitoring (WCM) reports as well as other data made available from the Contracting Parties. In addition to this, information from peer-reviewed research articles, publicly available reports Summarizing scientific research as well as reports from surveys of PW impact in the water column has been included. Finally and in addition to WCM, data from seabed monitoring programs around offshore platforms have been included, as interactions between water

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
			column and seabed cannot be dismissed. A summary of available publications from the last decade have been summarized after the main report on produced water
	Handbook. Species and habitats of environmental concern. Mapping, Risk Assessment, Mitigation and Monitoring. - In relation to Oil and Gas activities.	DNV GL AS Oil & Gas (Offshore Norge 2024)	Describes key species and habitats such as corals and sponges and how these can be impacted by drilling, anchoring and pipeline construction. The document gives recommended methods and requirements for visually assessing the habitats, impact assessment, mitigation and documentation/monitoring of effects. A summary of existing knowledge on impact from the various operations is given; Thresholds for sedimentation
	Environmental Fates and Effects of Ocean Discharge of Drill Cuttings and Associated Drilling Fluids From Offshore Oil and Gas Operations	International Association of Oil & Gas Producers 2016	This report reviews scientific literature on the fate and effects of ocean discharge of drill cuttings and associated drilling fluids from offshore oil and gas operations.
	Literature report on burial: Derivation of PNEC as component in the MEMW model tool. Environmental Risk Management System Report	ERMS report (Kjeilen-Eilertsen et al. 2004)	Contribution to the ERMS task addressing burial of organisms as a stressor due to drilling discharges. The report addresses the potential drilling discharge- and burial process, as well as tolerance-, escape- and toxicity aspects of such a process. This forms the background for a discussion of burial in relation to other Environmental Impact Factor (EIF) sediment parameters and how to define a Predicted No Effect Threshold (PNET) for the burial stressor in the EIF
	Impacts of drilling mud discharges on water column organism and filter feeding bivalves	Bechmann et al. 2006	Project report on possible effects of drilling mud discharges on water column organism (plankton and fish), and filter feeding bivalves, and on bioaccumulated metals in fish and bivalves exposed to suspended particles of drilling mud.
	Composition, Environmental Fates, and Biological Effects of Water Based Drilling Muds and Cuttings Discharged to the Marine Environment: a Synthesis and Annotated Bibliography	Neff 2005	Synthesis report on drilling waste discharges in the US
	Environmental effects of offshore produced water discharges evaluated for the Barents Sea	NEA (Beyer et al. 2019)	This report presents (1) an overview of the ecotoxicological knowledge regarding offshore produced water (PW) discharges on the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NCS), (2) an overview of the ecological characteristics and values of the Barents Sea, and (3) an overview of the tools that presently are available for assessing the possible environmental risk associated with offshore PW discharges. The overall objective with this work is to provide a basis for discussing the need for a stricter environmental management of PW discharges in the Barents Sea in comparison to elsewhere at the NCS. Based on information presented herein there appear not to be a clear systematic pattern that organisms/systems in Barents Sea are significantly more sensitive to chemical

Offshore Industry	Title	Issuing organization / authors	Key points and addressed stressors
			contamination and ecotoxicity of PW compared to organisms/systems elsewhere at the NCS. However, there are still many unknowns in this field of study, as only a relatively small number of PW effect studies provide data for sensitivity comparisons of Barents Sea and non-Barents Sea organisms/systems.
	Assessment of impacts of the offshore oil and gas industry on the marine environment.	OSPAR (Marappan et al. 2022)	Offshore oil and gas activities have developed in the OSPAR area over the past 50 years. Environmental impacts can occur throughout the lifecycle of these activities, exploration, production and decommissioning. Impact can arise from discharge of produced water, oil, chemicals, drilling muds and cuttings, physical impact from the placement of installations and pipelines, noise from seismic surveys and drilling, light emitted from the installations and atmospheric emissions.
Other			
	Feeder Report 2021 - Extraction of non-living Resources	OSPAR (OSPAR Commission 2023)	Summarises extraction of non-living resources within the OSPAR Maritime Area and measures taken to manage the environmental impacts sand and gravel, also addresses marine mining
	Ecological Research on Offshore Wind Farms: International Exchange of Experiences PART B: Literature Review of Ecological Impacts	TU Berlin (Bundesamt für Naturschutz 2006)	Literature review addresses ecological impacts from human offshore activities to benthic communities and habitats, to fish fauna, to seabirds, and the marine mammals (addressing suspended sediment, burial

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Table 8: Main regulatory frameworks and other relevant guidelines providing numerical assessment criteria for marine contaminants: main EU legislation, Regional Sea Conventions (RSC) and other relevant national and international regulatory frameworks (an Excel table providing numerical values is provided separately). The 'Objective' column is partly based on Tornero et al., 2022.

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
Water Framework Directive (WFD) (The European Parliament and the Council 2013)	EU-wide, territorial waters (for chemical status)	Adopted in 2000, main law for water protection in Europe. It applies to inland, transitional and coastal surface waters as well as groundwaters. Article 16 of the WFD sets out the strategy against chemical pollution of waterbodies including inland waters (freshwater) and transitional, coastal and territorial waters (marine). Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) have been derived at EU level and apply to all MS for assessing the chemical status of waterbodies. The EQS is the concentration of a particular pollutant or group of pollutants in water, sediment or biota which should not be exceeded in order to protect human health and the environment. The EQS Directive (EQSD, 2008/105/EC) established EQS in surface waters for 33 Priority Substances (PS) and 8 other pollutants which, if met, allow(s) the chemical status of the waterbody to be described as 'good'. This Directive was updated in 2013 (2013/39/EU). Currently, EQS _{water} have been set for 44 PS and EQS _{biota} for 11 of those PS. In addition, the WFD establishes the principles to be applied by MS to develop EQS for River Basin Specific Pollutants (RBSP) that "are discharged in significant quantities" (Annex VIII substances of the WFD) as part of the assessment of the ecological status.	Environmental quality standards (EQS) for water and biota; interim QS for sediment without any legal status derived for Cd and Pb in EQS dossiers; EQS water derived for pelagic community;	Priority Substances (Cd, Hg, Pb, Ni; Ag as candidate PS) River Basin Specific Pollutants: such as As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Zn Sediment: Cd and Pb	Directive of the European Union
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (The European Parliament and the Council 2008)	EU-wide, EEZ	Adopted in 2008, for effective management and protection of the marine environment across Europe. The MSFD applies to all 'marine waters', which are defined in article 3(1) to mean the waters, seabed and subsoil that extend from the baseline of the territorial sea to the 'outermost reach of the area where a Member State has or exercises jurisdiction'. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) aims to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) of the EU's marine waters and to protect the resource base upon which marine-related economic and social activities depend. The definition of GES is based on a list of generic qualitative descriptors contained in Annex I of the MSFD. The Commission has also produced a set of	Descriptor D8 addresses chemical contaminants # Considers threshold and reference values from different EU-wide and other regional or national conventions and regulations (see JRC technical Reports, 2019 and 2022)	As reported from Member States WFD Priority Substances (Cd, Hg, Pb, Ni) WFD River Basin Special Pollutants (other than WFD PS: Al, As, Ba, Cr, Cu, Co, Fe, Mn, Se, Ag, Tl, V, Zn)	Directive of the European Union

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
		<p>detailed criteria and methodological standards to help Member States implement the MSFD</p> <p>Complete assessment framework with comprehensive criteria linked to policy objectives, first EU legislative instrument related to the protection of marine biodiversity</p> <p>The Directive lists four European marine regions – the Baltic Sea, the North-east Atlantic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. These are located mainly within the geographical boundaries of the existing Regional Sea Conventions cooperation between the Member States of one marine region and with neighbouring countries which share the same marine waters.</p> <p>Good Environmental Status (GES) will be assessed on a regional basis and as such the programmes of the various Regional Sea Conventions, including OSPAR, will provide a valuable source of data for the assessments that will be required.</p> <p>The MSFD requires Member States to achieve and maintain GES across their marine waters in relation to the eleven ‘descriptors’ set out in MSFD Annex I. Descriptor 1 (benthic habitats) and Descriptor 6 (sea-floor integrity) are the main descriptors for assessing the state of the seabed, while other descriptors address particular pressures and impacts on the seabed. Descriptor 8 (Concentrations of contaminants are at levels not giving rise to pollution effects) has been interpreted as requiring assessments of contaminant concentrations and their biological effects.</p> <p>The directive is potentially relevant to deep-sea mining in seabed areas subject to Member State jurisdiction to the extent that such activities may hinder the achievement of ‘good environmental status’ (GES).</p>		RSC substances (other than WFD PS: Cr, Co, Cu, Zn, Se)	
HELCOM (Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission)	Baltic Sea	<p>Main goal is to protect the marine environment of the Baltic Sea from all sources of pollution, and to restore and safeguard its ecological balance.</p> <p>A list of priority substances was released in HELCOM Recommendation 31E/1 and adopted in 2010 in the framework of the Baltic Sea Action Plan. HELCOM core indicators for biodiversity and hazardous substances were developed. Regionally agreed threshold values are derived from a number of sources to select values that have been scientifically tested and developed with the purpose of assessing environmental status or</p>	<p>The threshold values for Cd, Hg, Pb are based on WFD Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for PS in water (Cd, Pb), and biota (Hg); secondary QS for metals in sediment according to WFD EQS dossiers (Pb, Cd) or newly derived (Cu) – but no legal status; secondary EQS biota secondary poisoning newly</p>	Cd, Hg, Pb, Cu (with preference of biota standards, if available)	Regional Sea convention (RSC)

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
		ensuring human safety. If several threshold values are available, thresholds based on EQS and the sampling matrix biota are preferred.	derived for Cd and Pb (for Pb in fish liver OSPAC BAC used)		
<p>OSPAR (Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic)</p> <p>https://www.ospar.org/site/assets/files/1169/ospar_convention.pdf</p>	<p>North-eastern Atlantic</p> <p>The OSPAR maritime area encompasses extensive areas in the Wider Atlantic (OSPAR Region V) and the Arctic Waters (OSPAR Region I) that are beyond the limits of national Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). This Area Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) covers approximately 40% of the OSPAR maritime area)</p>	<p>OSPAR is the Regional Seas Convention responsible for protecting and conserving the North-East Atlantic and its resources. It manages human activities impacting the marine environment and provides regular assessments of the state of the North-East Atlantic with a view to securing its vision of a clean, healthy and biologically diverse North-East Atlantic which is productive, used sustainably and resilient to climate change and ocean acidification.</p> <p>It is a legal mechanism through which the contracting parties that make up the OSPAR Commission cooperate to protect the marine environment</p> <p>Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (the “OSPAR Convention”) was opened for signature at the Ministerial Meeting of the former <i>Oslo</i> and <i>Paris</i> Commissions in Paris on 22 September 1992. The Convention entered into force on 25 March 1998. It has been ratified by Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom and approved by the European Community and Spain.</p> <p>5 marine sub-regions defined</p> <p>The OSPAR Convention contains a set of basic rules and principles which are elaborated in its 5 Annexes and 3 accompanying Appendices. The four Annexes that were adopted together with the Convention deal with pollution from land-based sources (Annex I), pollution by dumping or incineration (Annex II), pollution from offshore sources (Annex III) and the assessment of the quality of the marine environment (Annex IV). Annex V on the Protection and Conservation of Ecosystems and Biological Diversity of the Maritime Area was adopted in 1998</p> <p>Contracting Parties to the OSPAR Convention have an obligation to adopt the necessary and possible measures to prevent and combat pollution, protect the marine environment from the impacting effects of human activities, preserve and restore marine ecosystems and safeguard human health.</p>	<p>Effects Range-Low (ERL) values are used for metals in sediment; Further provides a list of the naturally occurring substances usually being analyzed to characterize produced water (PW) samples along with their established PNECs (Agreement 2014–05)</p>	<p>List of OSPAR Chemicals for Priority Action (Cd, Pb, Hg)</p> <p>Biota (as EC-MPC): Pb, Cd, Hg</p> <p>Sediment (as ERL): Pb, Cd, Cu, Cr, Zn, Hg</p> <p>Water (PNECs): As, Pb, Cd, Ni, Zn, Co, Cr, Hg (for Pb, Cd, Ni = WFD EQS)</p>	<p>Regional Sea convention (RSC)</p>

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
		<p>The OSPAR convention, like other regional conventions aimed at protecting the marine environment and its biodiversity, also contributes to the objective of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, which is to achieve good environmental status in EU marine waters</p> <p>OSPAR develops common indicators from which it is possible to infer how much the current situation deviates from good environmental status. OSPAR also ensures that there is a coordinated, coherent, consistent and comparable monitoring programme. Joint monitoring is carried out to assess the environmental status of the OSPAR regions</p> <p>The work of OSPAR in establishing a network of MPAs in the North Atlantic in areas both under the national jurisdiction of coastal States and in areas beyond national jurisdiction is in particular of potential relevance to deep-sea mining</p>			
<p>Norwegian Water Regulations</p> <p>NEA 2016, rev. 2020</p> <p>Direktoratsgruppen for gjennomføringen av vannforskriften 2018, updated 2020</p>	<p>Norway territorial waters</p>	<p>The Regulations on the Framework for Water Management (the Water Regulations) implement the EU Water Framework Directive (the Water Directive) in Norwegian law. The main purpose of the regulation is to provide a framework for setting environmental objectives that ensure the most comprehensive possible protection of the aquatic environment, and sustainable use of water bodies. The regulations lay down specific guidelines on the process and criteria for managing water resources</p> <p>With ratification of EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60/EC 2000) by Norway in 2007 and the subsequent application of the daughter directive on Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) (2013/39/EU 2013) the assessment of the environment using EQS became imperative.</p> <p>The daughter directive outlines 45 priority substances or groups of substances. There is a provision in this daughter directive which allows a country to develop their own EQS for water, sediment and biota provided these offer the same level of protection as the EQS set for water. Norway used this approach and developed their own EQS for biota, water and sediments for “river basin specific pollutants” not otherwise accounted for by the EU directives</p>	<p>Classification scheme for metals and organic contaminants in seawater, sediment, biota: 5 groups (ranging from “Background” to “Very Bad”), boundary between group 2 and 3 represents the Environmental Quality Standard (EQS) for Norway:</p> <p>For the elements Pb, Cd, Ni, the water EQS corresponds to the AA-EQS of the WFD for PS; values for As, Zn, Cr, Hg based on EU-RAR and other documents</p> <p>Sediment: boundaries between classes represented respectively, the upper limit of background concentrations, the PNEC_{chronic}, the PNEC for acute exposure, and 2-10 times the acute PNEC.</p> <p>Where a sediment quality standard has been proposed in the European Union Water</p>	<p>Water: Pb, Cd, Ni, As, Zn, Cr, Hg Biota: Hg Sediment: As, Pb, Cd, Ni, Zn, Cu, Cr, Hg</p>	<p>National regulations</p>

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
		Information related to classification, monitoring and follow-up of environmental status in water bodies in accordance with the provisions of the Water Regulations	Framework Directive, it was used instead of the PNEC _{chronic} .		
Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality (ANZG 2018)	Australia and New Zealand territorial waters	<p>Guidelines are part of the National Water Quality Management Strategy (NWQMS), whose primary objective is 'to achieve sustainable use of the nation's water resources by protecting and enhancing their quality while maintaining economic and social development.</p> <p>Guidelines developed for aquatic ecosystem protection, provide authoritative guidance on the management of water quality in Australia and New Zealand (planning, approvals, licensing, compliance, monitoring and assessment), interactive platform that can be used by water managers, guidance on derivation of quantitative thresholds, framework considers different levels of protection</p> <p>the Water Quality Guidelines' DGVs are not mandatory and have no formal legal status, but that, where appropriate, state, territory or local jurisdictions may incorporate the processes and tools, including the DGVs, provided within the Water Quality Guidelines, into their water quality protection policy and regulatory tools</p> <p>introduce a tiered assessment framework so that exceedance of the quality guideline value leads to additional studies to confirm or deny the possibility of biological impacts</p>	<p>Default Guideline Values (DGV) for water and sediment quality (not mandatory);</p> <p>SSD method to derive thresholds for metals in water at four different protection levels (99%, 95%, 90%, 80%)</p> <p>intended to be applied at specific sites, where possible, using a decision tree. The level of protection depends on the management objective for a water type. A decision scheme gives step by step guidance on how to assess test site data and tailor the guideline values according to site-specific environmental conditions;</p> <p>for sediment, TEL values adopted as default guideline values</p>	<p>Water: Pb, Cd, Co, Ni, Zn, Cu, V, Cr, Zn, Hg, Ag</p> <p>Sediment: same as water (except for Co)</p>	National guidelines
United States Environmental Protection Agency Water Quality Criteria (U.S. EPA 2002) (U.S. EPA 2017; updated 2023)		<p>Under Clean Water Act section 304(a), U.S. EPA is required to develop and publish water quality criteria that reflect the latest scientific knowledge.</p> <p>EPA's recommended water quality criteria don't automatically become part of a state's water quality standards but they must be adopted to protect the designated uses of their water bodies. These can include scientifically defensible site-specific criteria that are different from EPA's national recommended criteria, as long as the site-specific criteria are protective of the designated use. National water quality criteria are derived for freshwater or saltwater or both to protect aquatic organisms and their uses from unacceptable effects due to exposures to high</p>	<p>National recommended water quality criteria;</p> <p>Sediment: based on the large database assembled by Long et al. (1995) in only saltwater, Effects Range-Low (ERL) and Effects Range-Median (ERM) values were calculated as specific chemical concentrations of a toxic substance in marine sediment, provided as benchmark values</p>	<p>Water: As, Cd, Cr (VI), Cu, Pb, Hg, Ni, Se, Ag, Zn;</p> <p>Sediment: As, Pb, Cd, Ni, Zn, Cu, Cr, Ag,</p>	National recommendation

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
		<p>concentrations for short periods of time (Criterion Maximum Concentration or CMC), lower concentrations for longer periods of time (Criterion Continuous Concentration or CCC) and combinations of the two.</p> <p>Through its National Status and Trends (NS&T) Program, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) generates considerable amounts of chemical data on sediments. Sediment quality guidelines (SQGs) were developed as informal, interpretive tools to evaluate whether a concentration of contaminant in sediment might have toxicological effects (NOAA, 1999).</p>			
<p>Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines (CEQGs) and Canadian Federal Environmental Quality Guidelines (FEQGs)</p> <p>(Canadian Environmental Protection Act 1999)</p> <p>(CCME 1999a, 1999b, 2007)</p>		<p>The Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) 1999 provides for the preparation of guidelines, objectives and codes of practice in relation to a wide range of issues. In Part 3 of CEPA 1999, the Minister of the Environment (Section 54) and the Minister of Health (Section 55) are enabled to create a wide range of non-regulatory tools, such as guidelines and codes for environmentally sound practices, and objectives for desirable levels of environmental quality.</p> <p>Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines (CEQGs), developed by the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME), are nationally endorsed, science-based goals for the quality of atmospheric, aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Marine thresholds have been developed to address the protection of marine water quality, marine sediment quality and tissue quality for the protection of wildlife consumers of aquatic life.</p> <p>Under the Chemicals Management Plan, there is an additional need to develop FEQGs to support federal environmental quality monitoring and risk assessment and risk management activities on substances for which CCME guidelines do not yet exist. FEQGs may be used directly as evaluation tools in environmental monitoring to assess whether ambient concentrations of pollutants may pose risks to aquatic life. In addition, they may also be used as risk management tools and performance measures. They also provide a science-based starting point to derive site-specific effluent limits and risk management targets.</p>	<p>Thresholds for water quality, sediment quality, tissue quality for protection of wildlife consumers; for sediment adopted TEL values</p>	<p>Water: As, Cd, Cr(III), Cr(VI), Ag, Hg, V Sediment: As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Hg, Zn</p>	<p>National guidelines</p>

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
London Protocol: Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (IMO)	Global marine	<p>One of the first and most important global instruments available to protect the oceans from pollution by controlling sources of waste and developing preventive measures is the Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Waste and Other Matter, 1972 (London Convention, LC). In 1996, the London Convention was updated by the London Protocol (LP), which entered into force in 2006.</p> <p>protect the oceans from pollution by controlling sources of waste and developing preventive measures</p> <p>Currently, 45 States are Parties to the London Protocol</p> <p>Under the London Protocol, Article 4 – Dumping of Wastes or Other Matter, “Contracting Parties shall prohibit the dumping of any wastes or other matter with the exception of those listed in Annex 1” - eight types of waste that may be considered for dumping at sea, including “inert, inorganic geological material (e.g. mining wastes)”</p> <p>do not cover discharges from land-based sources such as pipes and outfalls, wastes generated incidental to normal operation of vessels, or placement of materials for the purposes other than mere disposal, providing such disposal is not contrary to aims of the Convention</p> <p>London Protocol has developed a series of guidelines that contain step-by-step procedures to evaluate wastes being considered for sea disposal, including a waste prevention audit, consideration for other potential waste management, chemical, physical and biological characterization of the waste, analysis of environmental impact, disposal site selection and monitoring and permitting procedures</p> <p>Article III (c) of the London Convention expressly excludes the dumping of wastes arising from deep-sea mining from its scope. Similarly, Protocol does not apply to waste arising from deep-sea mining either.</p>	Non (narrative)		International Treaty
Draft General Guidelines and Criteria for mining operations in Papua New Guinea (PNG) involving		<p>Not yet implemented in Papua New Guinea national law</p> <p>Drafted as Appendix 10 to science report “Independent Evaluation of Deep-Sea Mine Tailings Placement (DSTP) in PNG - Final Report, SAMS 2011”</p>	no new thresholds, only ensure that EQS for both water and suspended particulate material are not exceeded outside mixing zone (1000-2000 km) agreed in the discharge permit		National Guidelines (draft)

Framework	Region	Objective	Thresholds	Metals	Type
Deep Sea Tailings Placement (DSTP) (SAMS Research Services Limited 2010)					

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Table 9: List of guidance documents, for threshold derivation and other technical aspects of environmental management.

Issuing Organization / Authors	Document Title	Content/Key points
EU		
European Chemical Bureau (De Bruijn et al. 2003)	EU Technical Guidance Document on risk assessment , Part II: Environmental risk assessment	Technical Guidance Document, supports legislation on assessment of risks of chemical substances to human health and the environment. Risk assessment should proceed in the following sequence: hazard identification; dose (concentration) - response (effect) assessment; exposure assessment, risk characterisation. The document is intended to assist the competent authorities to carry out the environmental risk assessment of notified new substances, priority existing substances and active substances and substances of concern in a biocidal product. This guidance document includes advice on the following issues: how to calculate Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PECs) and Predicted No-Effect-Concentrations (PNECs) and, where this is not possible, how to make qualitative estimates of environmental concentrations and effect/no effect concentrations; how to conduct a PBT (persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity) assessment; and how to decide on the testing strategy, if further tests need to be carried out and how the results of such tests can be used to revise the PEC and/or the PNEC.
ECHA (European Chemicals Agency 2014)	Principles for Environmental Risk Assessment of the Sediment Compartment: Proceedings of the Topical Scientific Workshop	Topical Scientific Workshop on Risk Assessment for the Sediment Compartment was held from 7 to 8 May 2013 at ECHA, bringing together experts in the field of sediment risk assessment to brainstorm and develop updated scientific principles and guidelines for assessing ecological risks of chemical substances for freshwater and marine sediments. Recent developments for particular substance types (such as metals) and a broad understanding of risk assessment methodologies in other regulated products and from schemes outside the EU were part of the discussion. The primary objective of this workshop was to review the state of the art and to develop updated scientific principles and guidelines for assessing ecological risks of chemical substances for freshwater and marine sediments.
ECHA (ECHA 2016)	Guidance on information requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment Chapter R.16: Environmental exposure assessment	Guidance describes the information requirements under REACH with regard to substance properties, exposure, use and risk management measures, in the context of the chemical safety assessment for substances manufactured or imported in a quantity of 10 tonnes or more per year. Part R.16 deals with the exposure assessment
ECHA (ECHA 2023)	Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment - Chapter R.7b : endpoint specific guidance	Guidance describes the information requirements under REACH with regard to substance properties, exposure, use and risk management measures, in the

Issuing Organization / Authors	Document Title	Content/Key points
		<p>context of the chemical safety assessment for substances manufactured or imported in a quantity of 10 tonnes or more per year.</p> <p>Part 7b deals with information requirements on properties of a substance under REACH: aquatic pelagic toxicity and toxicity to sediment organisms</p>
ECHA (ECHA 2008)	Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment - Chapter R.10: Characterisation of dose [concentration]-response for environment	Part R10 deals with PNEC derivation
Water Framework Directive		
CIS-WFD 2009	Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) Guidance Document No. 19 - Guidance on surface water chemical monitoring under the water framework directive	<p>This guidance includes the monitoring of the WFD priority substances, other specific pollutants and all other chemical parameters relevant in the assessment of the ecological or chemical status of a water body or in the assessment of programmes of measures. The guidance focuses on monitoring including sampling and laboratory analyses, it covers also in situ field monitoring of physico-chemical quality elements, but not the monitoring of hydromorphological elements. Since there is an overlap between WFD and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC) as regards chemical pollutants in territorial waters a link between monitoring activities for both Directives has to be established. However, this guidance refers to monitoring of inland, transitional and coastal water bodies under the WFD, and includes some areas of territorial waters also covered by the MSFD.</p>
CIS-WFD 2010	Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) Guidance Document No. 25 - Guidance on chemical monitoring of sediment and biota under the Water Framework Directive	<p>This guidance document addresses the different requirements for compliance checking and temporal trend monitoring for biota and sediment, taking into account the obligations of the EQS Directive. The recommendations given in this guidance are addressed to surveillance, operational and investigative monitoring. Since the WFD also covers the protection inland, transitional, coastal marine and territorial waters for chemical status, the guidance includes specific recommendations on the different water categories.</p> <p>Mentions passive sampling as additional method</p> <p>Includes some information of ecotoxicity testing with sediments</p> <p>Case studies</p>
CIS-WFD 2018	Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) revised Guidance Document No. 27 – Technical Guidance for Deriving Environmental Quality Standards	<p>Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs) are tools used for assessing the chemical status of waterbodies. This guidance document addresses the derivation of environmental quality standards for water, sediment and biota. Whilst it does not cover the implementation of an EQS (e.g. design of monitoring programmes, sampling, chemical analysis) the guidance does highlight where the methods used</p>

Issuing Organization / Authors	Document Title	Content/Key points
		<p>to implement an EQS have a direct bearing on the way an EQS is derived and expressed.</p> <p>Accounting for bioavailability, background concentrations</p> <p>Appendix providing toxicity data and bioconcentration and biomagnification data</p>
CIS-WFD 2019	<p>Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) Guidance Document No. 38 - Technical Guidance for implementing Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for metals</p>	<p>The main aim of this guidance is to facilitate the consideration of bioavailability in the status assessment of freshwater bodies in relation to metals, including the application of EQS (EQSbioavailable). It also aims to explain how natural background concentrations (NBCs) may be accounted for, including when no suitable bioavailability model exists.</p> <p>The scope of this guidance covers the practical steps required to implement approaches that account for bioavailability by using a so-called EQS bioavailable. implementation guidance intends to be generic and is thus not specific to any particular metal or region. While emphasising compliance assessment under the WFD, it attempts to show how bioavailability and NBC corrections can be used in different cases for risk assessment, prioritisation of measures or where available monitoring information may not be comprehensive.</p> <p>Case studies</p>
Australia/New Zealand		
Simpson et al. 2013	Revision of the ANZECC/ARMCANZ Sediment Quality Guidelines	<p>This document updates the original SQG documents prepared for the revised Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality released in 2000.</p> <p>The SQG revision builds on the original SQG document with the tiered, decision-tree approach adopted for the interim sediment quality guideline values (SQGVs) maintained, and guidance is provided for use of a weight-of-evidence (WOE) framework to improve the assessment of the potential impacts of contaminated sediments for more complex risk assessments. In addition to chemical measures of potential bioavailability (e.g. acid-volatile sulfides, AVS) and the ecotoxicology LOE that were part of the original framework, the revised framework explicitly allows for the considering of bioaccumulation and ecological health as two additional LOEs.</p>
Simpson and Batley 2015	Sediment Quality Assessment – a practical guide, 2 nd edition	<p>Detailed guidance on how to interpret and apply sediment quality guidelines in regulatory framework of Australia and New Zealand</p> <p>Review on contaminant exposure pathways and the application of several lines of evidence in tiered assessment schemes</p>

Issuing Organization / Authors	Document Title	Content/Key points
Batley et al. 2018	Technical rationale for changes to the method for deriving Australian and New Zealand water quality guideline values for toxicants	Prepared for the revision of the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality Report describes key changes from the 2000 Guidelines relating to methods for the derivation of guideline values for toxicants Discussion on acceptable toxicity test endpoints (traditional and non-traditional), and Use of field, mesocosm and microcosm data to derive thresholds, minimum dataset requirements
Warne et al. 2018	Revised method for deriving Australian and New Zealand water quality guideline values for toxicants – update of 2015 version.	Prepared for the revision of the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality Builds on the technical rationale (Batley et al., 2018) and presents a revised method for deriving water quality guideline values for metal, non-metallic inorganic and organic toxicants in Australia and New Zealand
ANZG 2018	Australian and New Zealand guidelines for fresh and marine water quality, revision 2018, online document	Water Quality Management Framework for Australia and New Zealand Provide toxicant default guideline values for water quality and sediment quality, recommend using multiple lines of evidence as part of the weight-of-evidence process to better assess the risk to a sediment ecosystem if a DGV is exceeded Recommends the derivation and application of site-specific guideline values, provides guidance on available approaches to tailor the default guideline values (including assessment of bioavailability, reference-site approach, toxicity testing, field tests, weight of evidence) and refers additionally to van Dam et al., 2019
Claydon 2023	Analysis of the Australia and New Zealand Water Quality Guidelines Improvement Program Status Report	
Australian Government 2009	National Assessment guidelines for dredging	Australia implements its obligations under the London Protocol through the Commonwealth Environment Protection (Sea Dumping) Act 1981 (the Sea Dumping Act). Through the Sea Dumping Act, the Australian Government assesses proposals to load and dump wastes and other matter at sea, permits acceptable activities, and places conditions of approval, to mitigate and manage environmental impacts. The National Assessment Guidelines for Dredging set out the framework for the environmental impact assessment and permitting of the ocean disposal of dredged material. The framework includes: evaluating alternatives to ocean disposal, assessing loading and disposal sites, assessing potential impacts on the marine environment and other users, and determining management and monitoring requirements. The Guidelines are intended to provide greater certainty about the assessment and permitting process as well as provide some guidance on opportunities for longer-term strategic planning.

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		The document outlines methods for sediment sampling and analysis, sediment quality assessment and biological testing. The Screening Levels used in this document (Table 2) are the same as the ISQG-Low values in ANZECC/ARMCANZ 2000, as updated (in draft) by Simpson et al. (2008).
Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality (ANZG 2023)	Guidance on the use of ecosystem receptor indicators for the assessment of water and sediment quality	Guidance document provides updated information on the measurement of ecosystem receptor indicators required for the ecosystem receptor lines of evidence for the assessment of water and sediment quality in Australia and New Zealand. The guidance provided here is an extension of the ANZG (2018) guidance on indicators and their selection for the assessment of water and sediment quality, and is applicable to all water types. Hyperlinks to the relevant ANZG (2018) guidance are provided throughout this document. This document describes 4 lines of evidence for ecosystem receptors: biodiversity, toxicity (including direct toxicity testing DTA), bioaccumulation and biomarkers.
Batley et al. 2003	A Guide to the Application of the ANZECC/ARMCANZ Water Quality Guidelines in the Minerals Industry	The new ANZECC/ARMCANZ Water Quality Guidelines were introduced in 2000 and represent a major shift in the way surface water quality is managed in Australia. While they represent world's best practice in terms of water quality management, the biggest problem with the new Guidelines is their apparent complexity. The Guideline package consists of several large volumes of information and provides a complete outline of how the Guidelines should be applied, together with lengthy discussion of the underpinning science. For members of specific industries, accessing the relevant information from this comprehensive package is a daunting, yet necessary task. The aim of this handbook is to simplify this task, by encapsulating in a more easily understandable form, all of the necessary information to the new water quality guidelines. The handbook is written specifically for the minerals industry and uses relevant case study examples to demonstrate key points of the implementation process.
Environmental Protection Authority of Western Australia (selection is provided below)	Technical guidance documents	Different guidance documents
Environmental Protection Authority of Western Australia (EPA-WA 2016)	Technical guidance - Protecting the Quality of Western Australia's Marine Environment	environmental quality management framework (EQMF) for protecting and maintaining the quality of the State's marine environment, EQMF is risk-based and flexible, and can be fine-tuned to address specific issues or management of entire areas

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		<p>The EQMF is based on the recommendations and approaches in the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality (ANZECC & ARMCANZ, 2000a)</p> <p>assist proponents to design fit-for-purpose modelling and monitoring programs to spatially define, assess and manage potential impacts of their proposal on marine environmental quality</p> <p>technical advice on the potential effects of toxicants and other contaminants</p> <p>document sets out the context for the guidance, describes the structure of the environmental quality management framework and how it is to be applied through environmental impact assessment to maintain a high level of quality in Western Australia's marine waters</p> <p>defines different levels of ecological protection</p>
EPA-WA 2021	<p>Technical Guidance – Environmental impact assessment of marine dredging proposals</p>	<p>Activity-based guidance that sets out an approach for presenting and managing the predicted impact of suspended sediment from dredging operations on benthic habitats and communities (shading, abrasion, sedimentation, and clogging of feeding mechanisms), and the uncertainty associated with these predicted impacts</p> <p>Only considers impacts over the limited time frames associated with these predicted impacts considers tolerance thresholds of key benthic marine organisms to dredging pressures and on critical life cycle windows where important marine taxa are likely to be particularly sensitive to these pressures</p> <p>effects caused by removal/burial at the sites of dredging and disposal, and the effects of suspended and deposited sediments further afield guidance doesn't address the potential effects of disturbance and release of toxicants and other contaminants associated with dredged sediments that may affect seafood quality, or other environmental issues such as potential effects on coastal processes or marine fauna that may be associated with dredging activities</p> <p>zonation scheme approach for impact predictions present numerical guidelines that signify critical levels of dredging pressure to key species groups, based on biological response thresholds (e.g., corals, sponges, seagrass), considering light, sediment deposition, suspended sediment as combined pressures</p> <p>generic guidance that applies State-wide and as such, it does not differentiate between types of dredging proposals or regional environmental differences, nor does it provide specific technical guidance on impact prediction methodology for developing or using pressure-response thresholds for predicting environmental impacts</p> <p>The underlying WAMSI DSN report undertook research to identify and collate relevant information to better understand and manage the potential impacts of dredging on critical life cycle processes of important marine taxa in Western Australia (WA).</p>

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		Also provides guideline values considering recovery of benthic communities (such as levels or mortality)
<p>NZEPA (New Zealand Environmental Protection Authority 2015)</p>	<p>Applying for a marine consent to dump waste</p>	<p>Document provides guidance to operators who dump waste in New Zealand's Exclusive Economic Zone and Continental Shelf on how to comply with the Exclusive Economic Zone and Continental Shelf (Environmental Effects) Act 2012 (EEZ Act) and the Exclusive Economic Zone and Continental Shelf (Environmental Effects – Discharge and Dumping) Regulations 2015 (D&D Regulations).</p> <p>The EEZ Act has provided a framework for environmental management in New Zealand's EEZ and CS since 28 June 2013. Its purpose is to promote sustainable management of the natural resources and to protect the environment from pollution in this area. This purpose also aligns the EEZ Act with the 1996 London Protocol (the Protocol), which is an international agreement on how waste may be dumped in the marine environment. The key principle of the Protocol is given effect in the decision-making framework for a marine dumping consent and includes consideration of any practical opportunities to reuse, recycle, or treat the waste, or any other alternative methods of disposal.</p>
<p>EPA Victoria (Victoria Environmental Protection Authority 2010)</p>	<p>1344: Guidance for the determination and assessment of mixing zones</p>	<p>The purpose of these guidelines is to assist people from industry who are involved with mixing zones. The aim of these guidelines is to provide a clear and objective approach to the determination and assessment of mixing zones. It explains how mixing zones fit into the current legislative framework and places them in the context of current continuous improvement ideals and provides guidance on the process for determining, assessing, monitoring and reporting mixing zones.</p>
<p>NT EPA (Northern Territory Environmental Protection Authority 2013)</p>	<p>Guidelines mixing zones</p>	<p>The objective of these guidelines is to assist industries proposing a mixing zone as part of a project undergoing environmental impact assessments, or seeking to apply for a mixing zone as part of a waste discharge licence (WDL) under the Water Act, or an environment protection approval (EPA) or licence (EPL) or under the Waste Management and Pollution Control Act.</p> <p>They have been developed with reference to the Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality 2000 (ANZECC 2000).</p> <p>The purpose of a mixing zone, as outlined in ANZECC 2000, is to manage the controlled discharge of soluble non-bioaccumulatory toxicants whose impacts on local biota are primarily related to their concentration. Mixing zones allow for a designated zone of impact, typically between a discharge point and a compliance point, rather than prescribing concentration requirements at the discharge point. Case studies for mixing zones also provided in ANZECC Volume 2 Appendix 1</p>

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Norway		
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (Ramirez-Llodra et al. 2019)	Guidelines and best available techniques for submarine tailings disposal in Norwegian fjords: Recommendations from the NYKOS project	NYKOS project aimed at addressing some of the main knowledge gaps on the environmental impacts of submarine tailing disposal (STD) to facilitate the development of techniques, practices and management measures that will minimize such impact. Addresses how this new knowledge can be used by the authorities to develop guidelines for best available techniques related to STDs in Norwegian fjords
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (Brooks et al. 2023)	The Norwegian Water Column Monitoring programme 2021: Assessing the impacts of Ekofisk and Eldfisk offshore oil and gas installations on the marine environment	The Norwegian offshore Water Column Monitoring (WCM) programme investigated the potential effects of Ekofisk and Eldfisk oil and gas installations on the marine environment. Produced water (PW) impacts were assessed in the water column by deploying monitoring stations containing mussels, passive samplers (PSDs), scallops and scientific equipment downstream of the Ekofisk and Eldfisk installations.
TNO (Smit et al. 2006c)	Framework for the Environmental Impact Factor for drilling discharges	Follow-up on the development of the Environmental Impact Factor for produced water discharges (EIF PW), based on environmental risk and hazard identification, an EIF for drilling discharges (EIF DD) was developed; The EIF PW addresses environmental risk in the water column, based on toxicity as the only stressor. The EIF for drilling discharges also takes into account risk in the sediment compartment; concept for the EIF DD should be based EU-TGD approach (PEC:PNEC) Thresholds provided for toxic stressors and for suspended particles , based on substance-based SSD and assessment factors,
TNO (Smit et al. 2006b)	Threshold levels and risk-functions for non-toxic sediment stressors: burial, grain size changes, and hypoxia – summary report	Threshold values for burial, grain size change and oxygen depletion in relation to drilling discharges; provides an overview of the results related to the establishment of threshold values and risk curves for non-toxic sediment stressors to be included in the calculation rules for the Environmental Impact Factor for drilling discharges (EIF DD)
TNO (Smit et al. 2006a)	The derivation of a PNEC-water for weighting agents in drilling mud	In order to assess the relevance and the potential impact of increased SPM concentrations due to the presence of weighting agents in Water Based Muds (WBM) discharges, a literature review is performed; PNEC threshold values for barite, bentonite, attapulgitite and WBM were derived
SINTEF (Singsaas et al. 2007)	Environmental Risk Management System (ERMS) A summary report	Development of an Environmental Impact Factor (EIF) for drilling discharges – as environmental risk-based decision support tool, to assist the oil industry in establishing cost-effective mitigation measures for reducing potential harmful

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		discharges to the marine environment; The concept of the EIF DD is based on the PEC/PNEC ratio approach, calculation is implemented in the DREAM model
Offshore Norge 2024	Handbook Species and Habitats of Environmental Concern: Mapping, Risk Assessment, Mitigation and Monitoring. - In Relation to Oil and Gas Activities	<p>The aim of the document is summarising relevant legislations, conservation status of species and habitats of concern and recommended best practices for mapping, impact assessment and mitigation of environmental impact where species or habitats of environmental concern (SHEC) can occur.</p> <p>Describes key species and habitats such as corals and sponges on Norwegian continental shelf and how these can be impacted by drilling, anchoring and pipeline construction. Literature summary on biological effects, The document gives recommended methods and requirements for visually assessing the habitats, impact assessment, mitigation and documentation/monitoring of effects. A summary of existing knowledge on impact from the various operations is given, provides summary of findings of monitoring campaigns regarding spatial footprints at the seafloor and in the water column also in comparison with model simulations (such as DREAM) – depositions up to 10 mm usually restricted to <250 m from discharge</p> <p>detailed literature review with summary tables on experimental conditions and observed damages</p> <p>Proposes management threshold criteria for risk assessments</p>
Norwegian Environment Agency and contributors 2020	Guidelines for environmental monitoring of petroleum activities on the Norwegian continental shelf: M408	<p>The Norwegian Pollution Control Authority (SFT, now the Environment Agency) demanded in 1973 that operators prepare annual environmental reports, and environmental monitoring on the Norwegian continental shelf has therefore been ongoing for almost 50 years. Today, monitoring is carried out in accordance with the Environment Agency's guide M-300 (M-408 English version).</p> <p>Companies operating on the Norwegian continental shelf are required to carry out environmental monitoring in order to obtain information on the actual and potential environmental impacts of their activities and to provide authorities with a better basis for regulation.</p> <p>Guidelines contain detailed requirements on how to carry out and report from the monitoring activities. They cover the expected scope of monitoring activities, which parameters must be analyzed, and which methods must be used, as well as provide requirements on necessary accreditation and templates for reporting</p>
NEA 2018	Risk assessment of contaminated sediment – guidelines: M-1132 Translation of the original Norwegian publication, M-409	The Norwegian environment agency guidelines for environmental risk assessment of contaminated sediments focus on the risk of release of hazardous substances from contaminated sediments, the impact on human health and the impact on the ecosystem. The assessment is carried out in a tiered approach at three levels, with increasing complexity and demand for local data. The greater the amount of local

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		data, the less conservative the risk assessment. The guidelines are harmonised with the system for classification of contaminated sediments.
		Guidelines apply to the disposal of contaminated sediments in condition class III or more in the Norwegian Environment Agency's current system for classification of water, sediment and biota; relate to pollution control act;
Norwegian Environment Agency 2021	Contaminants in coastal waters of Norway 2020: M-2124	The monitoring programme "Contaminants in coastal waters of Norway" (Miljøgifter i norske kystområder - MILKYS) examines levels, trends and effects of contaminants in biota. The 2020-investigation included analyses of more than 176 different contaminants or biological effect parameters in six species (blue mussel, cod, dogwhelk, common periwinkle, flounder and common eider). The contaminants measured includes metals (Hg, Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn, Ag, As, Ni, Cr and Co), and organic compounds
NEA 2016, rev. 2020	Grenseverdier for klassifisering av vann, sediment og biota –revidert 30.10.2020 (Quality standards for water, sediment and biota – revised 2020): M608	<p>Provides a classification scheme, the class limits represent an expected increasing degree of damage to the organism community in the water column and sediments. The limits are based on available information from laboratory tests, risk assessments and dossiers on acute and chronic toxicity to organisms</p> <p>In connection with the revision of the guide 02/2018 Classification of environmental status in water, limit values (status class I-V) for priority pollutants that include metals and organic pollutants in water, sediment and biota are published. The guideline is based on basic data from reports TA-3001/2012 and M-241/2014 and is a compilation of limit values for use in the classification of environmental status in water, sediment and biota. The guideline was revised in 2020</p>
NEA 2014	Kvalitetssikring av miljøkvalitetsstandarder (Quality assurance of environmental quality standards), 2014: M241	In 2012, the Norwegian Environment Agency (then the Norwegian Climate and Pollution Agency) prepared environmental quality standards and classification limits in water, sediment and biota for a number of pollutants. These are presented in the report "Background document for the preparation of environmental quality standards and classification of pollutants in water, sediment and biota" (TA3001/2012). Both priority substances under the Water Framework Directive and substances that are relevant as river basin specific pollutants were included in the assignment. In August 2013, the daughter directive on priority substances (Directive 2013/39 EU) was finally adopted. As a result, the Norwegian Environment Agency needed to correct some of the environmental quality standards and class boundaries. There was also a need for a thorough quality

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		<p>assurance of the environmental quality standards. This quality assurance is covered by the present report.</p> <p>Detailed methodology provided on the derivation of class boundaries</p>
Olsen et al. 2019	<p>Contaminated Sediments: Review of solutions for protecting aquatic environments</p>	<p>Report give a status of regulatory framework and sediment management within selected Nordic countries (Norway, Sweden, Finland and Denmark). In addition, the report gives a short overview of international knowledge on remediation approaches, techniques and materials</p>
Offshore Norge 2022	<p>084 – Recommended Guideline for standard EIF calculations for Produced Water Discharges</p>	<p>OSPAR 12/05 Recommendation includes requirements to perform risk assessments on discharge of PW, and that best available measures shall be selected in order to reduce risk. Risk assessments should be performed with methods based on comparison of predicted environmental concentrations (PEC) and predicted no effect concentrations (PNEC) on substance level and EIF is suggested used for this guideline to provide a standardized method for modelling and determination of the EIF as a basis for environmental risk management and reporting for offshore discharges of PW in the Norwegian sector of the North Sea, the Norwegian Sea and the Barents Sea</p> <p>Guideline shall form the basis for all EIF determinations related to required annual reporting from the oil and gas operators in the Norwegian sector to the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA). The objective is to secure uniform and standardized EIF determination by all operators, thus facilitating comparison of EIF across years and independent of the party performing the calculations</p>
Offshore Norge 2023	<p>Environmental Report 2023</p>	<p>Each year, Offshore Norge publishes an environmental report containing a detailed overview of last year’s emissions and discharges from the petroleum industry. Environmental report is based upon the annual emission and discharge reports which all field operators are required to submit to the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA), conforming to the regulatory requirements as detailed in the NEA’s guideline M-107. This applies to all planned and officially approved operational emissions and discharges, as well as to those occurring accidentally</p>
United States		
U.S. EPA 2006	<p>Framework for Developing Suspended and Bedded Sediments (SABS) Water Quality Criteria</p>	<p>Document describes an integrative assessment process for developing water quality criteria for suspended and bedded sediments in aquatic systems.</p> <p>The purpose of this document is to provide a technical resource for states, tribes, and regions that wish to develop suspended or bedded sediment criteria, restoration targets, or use the analyses to develop stressor-response associations for causal analysis.</p>

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Adams and Garman 2024	Recommended updates to the USEPA Framework for Metals Risk Assessment: Aquatic ecosystems	In 2007, the USEPA issued its “Framework for Metals Risk Assessment.” The framework provides technical guidance to risk assessors and regulators when performing human health and environmental risk assessments of metals. The goal of this article is to review the recent scientific findings related to metals risk assessment and suggest areas where the USEPA Metals Framework could be updated to reflect the latest science. The authors focus on four areas that are primarily associated with freshwater ecosystems: (1) bioavailability of metals in aquatic systems; (2) biodynamic models for assessing bioaccumulation; (3) fate of metals in aquatic ecosystems; and (4) evaluation of metal toxicity in sediments.
U.S. EPA 1985; rev. 2010	Guidelines for Deriving Numerical National Water Quality Criteria for the Protection Of Aquatic Organisms and Their Uses	EPA uses a series of guidelines established in 1985 to derive ambient water quality criteria (AWQC) for aquatic life. The guidelines address acute risk (short-term effects such as survival and growth) and chronic risk (longer term effects such as reproduction) for traditional pollutants. The guidelines describe an objective, internally consistent, appropriate, and feasible way of deriving national criteria for the protection of aquatic ecosystems. The derivation of numerical national water quality criteria for the protection of aquatic organism and their uses is a complex process that uses information from many areas of aquatic toxicology. In 2013, EPA published a revision to one of its recommended procedures for deriving site-specific water quality criteria for the protection of aquatic life. The Revised Deletion Process for the Site-Specific Recalculation Procedure for Aquatic Life Criteria is intended to provide flexibility to States to tailor criteria development to reflect the aquatic community at a given site.
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency 2005	Procedures for the Derivation of Equilibrium Partitioning Sediment Benchmarks (ESBs) for the Protection of Benthic Organisms: Metal Mixtures (Cadmium, Copper, Lead, Nickel, Silver and Zinc)	This equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmark (ESB) document describes procedures to derive concentrations of metal mixtures in sediment which are protective of the presence of benthic organisms. The equilibrium partitioning (EqP) approach was chosen because it accounts for the varying biological availability of chemicals in different sediments and allows for the incorporation of the appropriate biological effects concentration. This provides for the derivation of benchmarks that are causally linked to the specific chemical, applicable across sediments, and appropriately protective of benthic organisms. The ESBs do not consider the antagonistic, additive or synergistic effects of other sediment contaminants in combination with metal mixtures or the potential for bioaccumulation and trophic transfer of metal mixtures to aquatic life, wildlife or humans.
Burgess et al. 2013	Mechanistic sediment quality guidelines based on contaminant bioavailability: equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmarks	The study summarizes a mechanistic SQG based on equilibrium partitioning (EqP), which uses the dissolved concentrations of contaminants in sediment interstitial

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		waters as a surrogate for bioavailable contaminant concentrations. The EqP-based mechanistic SQGs are called equilibrium partitioning sediment benchmarks (ESBs) and are presented for seven metals. Also included is an overview of EqP theory, ESB derivation, examples of applying ESB values, and considerations when using ESBs. The ESBs are intended as a complement to existing sediment-assessment tools, to assist in determining the extent of sediment contamination, to help identify chemicals causing toxicity, and to serve as targets for pollutant loading control measures.
U.S. EPA 1991	Evaluation of Dredged Material Proposed for Ocean Disposal	
U.S. EPA 1995	QA/QC Guidance for Sampling and Analysis of Sediments, Water, and Tissues for Dredged Material Evaluation: Chemical Evaluations (1995)	
U.S. EPA 1998	Guidelines for Ecological Risk Assessment	
USACE and USEPA 2016	Guidance for Performing Tests on Dredged Material Proposed for Ocean Disposal	This guidance document presents the sediment testing guidelines and requirements to be used by applicants who wish to obtain a Department of the Army (DA) permit from the New York District (NYD) of the United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) for dredging and placement of dredged material at the Historic Area Remediation Site (HARS) in the Atlantic Ocean. The USACE and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) are responsible for reviewing test results for compliance with the Ocean Dumping Criteria as described below.
Canada		
CCME 2003 CCME 1999	Canadian water quality guidelines for the protection of aquatic life: Guidance on the site-specific application of water quality guidelines in Canada: Procedures for deriving numerical water quality objectives.	This report was prepared to provide scientific and technical guidance on the development of site-specific water quality objectives (WQOs). More specifically, this report was prepared to describe the role of WQGs in the management of Canada's water resources (Chapter 2), to present a framework for developing numerical WQOs (Chapter 3), to identify the factors that could influence the derivation of WQOs (Chapter 4 and Appendix 1), and to describe the recommended methods for deriving such WQOs (Chapter 5). The role of site-specific WQOs in the management of point source effluent discharges is also discussed (Chapter 5). Further provides a brief history on the Canadian Water Quality Guidelines
OSPAR		

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OSPAR Commission 2014	Establishment of a list of Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNECs) for naturally occurring substances in produced water (OSPAR Agreement 2014-05)	<p>In support of Recommendation 2012/15 for a Risk Based Approach to the Management of Produced Water Discharges from Offshore Installations (OSPAR Agreement: 2012-7)</p> <p>Background document on derivation of PNEC values for naturally occurring substances typically found in produced water, derived following a substance-based approach, set of PNECs is presented and the way these PNEC-values have been determined is described</p> <p>Highest priority was given to the most recent reviewed PNEC or EQS available from reliable sources. For that reason, EQS values established under the EU- WFD, latest reviewed and published in 2013, were preferred before PNECs derived from EU-RARs. Under the EU-WFD, EQS are listed for a number of priority substances (EC, 2013a). The AA-EQS-values for other surface waters are selected as PNECs (Cd, Ni, Pb). In the case where there was no EQS established under the EU-WFD, PNECs established in EU-RARs were preferred (Cu). Priority was given to final EU-RARs, otherwise draft RARs were used. In case there was no EU-WFD or EU-RAR PNECs available, other international or national PNEC s may be applied (As, Cr, Zn). Where multiple PNEC exist, the PNEC derived from the most recent data, with background information publicly available was used. In these cases the most recent PNEC was chosen, derived according to the Technical Guidance for deriving Environmental Quality Standards (EC, 2011).</p>
OSPAR Commission 2017	Agreement 2017-02: Guidelines for monitoring the environmental impact of offshore oil and gas activities	<p>Document is designed to provide guidance on the design and conduct of monitoring programmes under the range of differences that exist between different production areas. Consistency in monitoring guidelines is emphasised, both with respect to the selection of parameters and the approach to sampling and analysis. The application of quality assurance protocols (where they exist) will enable the results of the investigations to be compared from year to year and evaluated holistically across the entire area</p> <p>The aim of these OSPAR guidelines is to harmonize monitoring of environmental impacts of discharges from offshore installations, and to harmonise reporting and assessment of the data</p>
OSPAR Commission 2012a	JAMP Guidelines for the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment of Contaminants and their effects (Commission Agreement 2012-09)	<p>Purpose of this document is to provide guidance on integrated chemical and biological effects monitoring within the OSPAR area, in the context of the Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP) issues and the list of OSPAR priority chemicals. In addition, it provides the context for the associated Technical Annexes describing biological effects techniques include a list of the supporting parameters which are required in an integrated programme, as well as the chemical determinands relevant to the effects being studied.</p>

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		<p>The JAMP Guideline is supported by associated Background Documents which provide information on the scientific background to the contaminants and biological effects measurements included in the Programme, and on the derivations and values of assessment criteria (Background Concentrations, Background Assessment Concentrations, and Environmental Assessment Criteria for chemical contaminants, and analogous assessment criteria for biological effects measurements)</p> <p>It is recognized that assessment for MSFD Descriptor 8 will require both chemical and biological effects measurements. It is likely that a robust and holistic approach will seek to integrate the assessment chemical and biological effects data into a single process.</p>
OSPAR Commission 1999, rev. in 2018	CEMP Guidelines for Monitoring Contaminants in Biota (Agreement 1999-02). Revision 2018	<p>Monitoring of contaminants in marine biota in the North-east Atlantic Ocean is performed within the framework of OSPAR as the regional convention for the protection of the marine environment of this area. The objectives of monitoring and assessment are described in the Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP) under the Hazardous Substances Strategy, providing the basis for the monitoring programme of chemicals for priority action, and hazardous substances in general</p> <p>Guidelines concern the sampling and analysis of contaminants in fish, shellfish and seabird eggs. They are suitable for hazardous substances</p>
OSPAR Commission 2002, rev. in 2018	CEMP Guidelines for Monitoring Contaminants in Sediments (Agreement 2002-16). Revised in 2018	<p>Guidelines, including the technical annexes, provide advice on the use of marine, estuarine and coastal sediments in environmental monitoring, with the aim of ensuring comparable results between monitoring programmes. They also give general guidance on the sampling and analysis of sediments and the interpretation of data</p> <p>The purpose of sediment monitoring is described fully in the Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (Oslo and Paris Commissions, 1995, 2010, 2014). The monitoring should meet the requirements of the Marine Strategy Directive Framework taking into consideration the OSPAR strategy objectives</p>
OSPAR Commission 2016, rev. in 2021	OSPAR Agreement 16-04: CEMP guidelines for coordinated monitoring for hazardous substances , revised in 2021	<p>In 2019 the OSPAR Commission adopted a revised OSPAR Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP) 2014–20232 (http://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/jamp) focusing on the development of assessments of the quality status of the marine environment for the QSR 2023.</p> <p>OSPAR coordinates repeated measurement and assessment of the marine environment over a 10–20 year time frame. strategic objective with regard to hazardous substances is to prevent pollution of the OSPAR maritime area by continuously reducing discharges, emissions and losses of hazardous substances,</p>

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		with the ultimate aim to achieve concentrations in the marine environment near background values for naturally occurring substances and close to zero for man-made synthetic substances. Programmes for monitoring the state of and pressures caused by hazardous substances to the marine environment have been implemented, comprising monitoring different compartments of the sea and inputs from rivers and atmosphere. This document provides links to the monitoring guidelines, data sources, processing procedures and assessment products
OSPAR/ICES (Bignert et al. 2004)	OSPAR/ICES Workshop on the evaluation and update of Background Reference Concentrations (BRCs) and Ecotoxicological Assessment Criteria (EACs) and how these assessment tools should be used in assessing contaminants in water, sediment, and biota. Report of the joint OSPAR/ICES Workshop	Workshop report
OSPAR Commission 2009	Background Document on CEMP assessment criteria for the QSR 2010	Background document has been developed to support the assessment of OSPAR CEMP data underpinning the OSPAR Quality Status Report 2010. It provides the background for the agreement on CEMP Assessment Criteria for the QSR 2010 (Agreement number: 2009-2) adopted by the OSPAR Environmental Assessment and Monitoring Committee in 2009 and provides a background on their application. Three colour traffic light system has been used for assessing hazardous substances data for marine sediments and biota for the purposes of the QSR 2010.
ICES 2021	Working Group on Biological Effects of Contaminants (WGBEC). ICES Scientific Reports. 3	The Working Group on Biological Effects of Contaminants (WGBEC) investigates the biological effects of contaminants in the marine environment. The group provides research and increases the understanding of contaminant interactions and effects, including the development of integrated biological effects monitoring strategies, which are used to support international research and monitoring. The WGBEC has contributed significantly to the implementation and harmonization of techniques that can be used to evaluate the biological effects of pollutants in national monitoring programmes. An overview of national effect-based monitoring programmes of Member States is provided with the aim to support European countries and Regional Seas Conventions on their implementation
(ICES 2024)	Working Group on Biological Effects of Contaminants (WGBEC) ICES Scientific Reports. 6	In this period, the group has contributed to the OSPAR Quality Status Report 2023, with the report "Integrated biological effects and chemical contaminants approach - a case study". The group has also contributed to novel scientific issues such as the effects of contaminants of emerging concern, reviewed methods to assess the bioavailability and effects of contaminants on sediment-dwelling organisms,

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		evaluated species differences in biological effects monitoring, and addressing the effects of mixtures of chemicals on marine organisms.
OSPAR Commission 2023b https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/ospar-common-indicators	OSPAR Common Indicators	The common indicators have been adopted by the OSPAR Commission. These indicators are the basis for regular OSPAR assessments of the changing status of the marine environment and the intensity of pressures from human activities. Common indicators are adopted for specific OSPAR Regions and ensure consistency and comparability of updated assessments over time. e.g, Benthic Habitat common indicator, hazardous substances common indicators (such as metals in sediment)
OSPAR Commission 2021	Strategy of the OSPAR Commission for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic 2030 (Agreement 2021-01: North-East Atlantic Environment Strategy (replacing Agreement 2010-03))	Updates OSPAR strategy paper for the period 2020-2030; continue work to monitor and assess the status of the marine environment of the OSPAR maritime area through OSPAR's Joint Assessment & Monitoring Programme. The key deliverable is the publication of the Quality Status Report (QSR) guided by 12 strategic objectives to lead us towards achieving good environmental status in the marine environment. The strategic objectives are grouped under four themes: achieve clean seas; achieve productive and sustainably used seas; achieve biologically diverse and healthy seas; achieve seas resilient to the impacts of climate change and ocean acidification;
OSPAR Quality Status Report 2023 (Marappan et al. 2022)	Assessment of impacts of the offshore oil and gas industry on the marine environment	The OSPAR Commission has put in place a significant number of measures aimed at reducing discharges from the oil and gas industry in the OSPAR Maritime Area. The vast majority of these have been made since 2000 and aim to reduce the environmental impacts of the industry on the marine environment. Measures introduced by OSPAR have reduced oil in produced water discharges and the discharge of hazardous chemicals and drilling fluids. OSPAR has with a few exceptions, effectively prohibited the disposal of disused offshore installations at sea Studies have been undertaken by OSPAR Contracting Parties looking at a wide range of potential impacts including historical cuttings piles, discharges of produced water, drilling fluids and chemicals. There has been a measurable decrease in emissions and discharges.
OSPAR Quality Status Report 2023 (Larsen and Hjermann 2022)	Status and Trend for heavy metals (Mercury, Cadmium, and Lead) in Fish, Shellfish and Sediment - Common Indicator Assessment	Assessment of status and environmental trends for metals in fish, shellfish and sediment, sampled between 1979 and 2020. Identification of knowledge gaps (such as lack of ecotoxicological data for developing new assessment criteria based on the European Union Water Framework Directive or OSPAR Environmental Assessment Criteria (EAC) principles, to replace the current ERL criteria).

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OSPAR Commission 2023a	Levels and trends in marine contaminants and their biological effects – CEMP Assessment report 2023	This report summarises the 2023 annual CEMP assessment of levels and trends of contaminants and their biological effects. It assessed 14950 time series (of three years or more) in biota, of which 9687 were assessed for trends and 9738 for environmental status and 2788 for human health status; 7635 time series in sediment, of which 3777 were assessed for trends and 5729 for status; and 1443 time series in water, of which 1082 were assessed for trends and 515 for status. Regional trends and environmental status were assessed for metals in biota and sediment.
OSPAR Commission 2019	The OSPAR list of chemicals for priority Action - Suggestions for future actions	Within the Hazardous Substances Strategy, the OSPAR Commission has prioritized substances (including the metals Hg, Pb, and Cd) for which measures, actions and background documents were adopted in order to reach the stated vision. This report analyzed and evaluated if and which of the OSPAR background documents needed updating, in addition to giving suggestions on potential further actions OSPAR could take in order to protect the marine environment against hazardous substances.
OSPAR Commission 2009, update 2024	OSPAR Guidelines for the Management of Dredged Material at Sea	Developed in order to reduce the adverse effects of dredging and dumping operations on the marine ecosystem; specifically address the disposal of dredged material by dumping in the maritime area; Contracting Parties are encouraged to exercise control over dredging operations, including sidecast and agitation dredging practices, in order to minimise the quantity of the material that has to be dredged and the impact of the dredging activities. The technical Annex III to the guidelines contains Best Environmental Practices (BEPs) for minimizing the effects of dredging operations on the environment
OSPAR Commission 2008	Overview of Contracting Parties' National Action Levels for Dredged Material (2008 Update)	Document compiles Contracting Parties' national action levels , and includes a survey of the approaches used by Contracting Parties in order to help understand how action levels for dredged material have been derived by different Contracting Parties. Action levels represent sediment quality criteria for the management of dredged material. Most countries use a "3 category action level" approach which means that 2 concentrations are provided. Concentrations of contaminants in the material falling below the lower limit represent those of little concern. Those failing between the lower limit and the upper limit may trigger further investigation of the material proposed for dumping. Those concentrations above the upper value generally mean that dumping of the material at sea is not permitted. Where action levels have not been developed, a "case-by-case" approach is taken for each application considered individually Also provides an overview of how action levels are used in the licensing procedures of Contracting Parties.

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Mason et al. 2022	Reviewing the UK's Action Levels for the Management of Dredged Material	Action Levels (ALs) are thresholds which are used to determine whether dredged material is suitable for disposal at sea by providing a proxy risk assessment for potential impacts to biological features such as fish and benthos. This project tested proposed scenarios for changes to the UK Action Levels to determine the likely implications for navigational dredge licensing in England and Wales. Approximately 3000 sample data records from 2009 to 2018 were collated with varying numbers of concentrations for contaminant parameters including trace metals, organotins, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs).
OSPAR Commission 2012c	Recommendation 2012/5 for a Risk-Based Approach to the Management of Produced Water Discharges from Offshore Installations	Recommendation aims to achieve a reduction of oil in produced water discharged into the sea to a level which will adequately ensure that each of those discharges will present no harm to the marine environment, and a reduction in discharges of hazardous substances via produced water with the ultimate aim of achieving concentrations in the marine environment that are near background values for naturally occurring substances and close to zero for man-made synthetic substances. The method used to undertake the risk-based approach should be based on the determination of PEC:PNEC ratios or the fraction of species potentially affected
MMO 2015	High Level Review of Current UK Action Level Guidance	The purpose of this project was to: 1. Undertake an independent high level review of the current action level guidance for the UK. This includes the application of action levels and a high level comparison of the UK process with those of other EU states. 2. Provide recommendations with regards whether existing guidance and action levels are appropriate and fit for purpose given current requirements and policy or whether a further, more detailed, review of action levels is required.
OSPAR Commission 2012b	OSPAR Guidelines in support of Recommendation 2012/5 for a Risk-based Approach to the Management of Produced Water Discharges from Offshore Installations, OSPAR Agreement: 2012-7, updated by OIC 2014 and OIC 2021	The purpose of this Recommendation is to: guide Contracting Parties in the application of a risk-based approach to assess the environmental risk posed by produced water discharges; describe methods to characterise the risks and; guide Contracting Parties in reducing those risks which are not adequately controlled through the application of BAT and BEP This framework follows principles of environmental risk assessment already in use in, e.g. the European Union (ECHA - Technical Guidance documents) and United States (US-EPA Guidance on risk assessment); risk characterisation following a WET based approach or risk characterisation following a substance based approach; Results from both the WET and substance based approach are considered different

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		lines of evidence, both containing complementary pieces of information. Both sets of data can be used to inform the risk assessment
OSPAR Commission 2006	OSPAR Recommendation 2006/5 on a management scheme for offshore cuttings piles	This recommendation sets out measures to reduce pollution from oil or other chemicals from cuttings piles.
HELCOM		
HELCOM 2020	HELCOM Guidelines for Management of Dredged Material at Sea and HELCOM Reporting Format for Management of Dredged Material at Sea	Amount and frequency of sampling, management options
HELCOM 2018	HELCOM core indicator report: metals	Core indicator evaluates the status of the marine environment based on concentrations of the heavy metals in the Baltic Sea. Lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd) and mercury (Hg) are measured in water, biota (fish and mussels) and sediments. The indicator presents a status evaluation using all available data in the HELCOM region during the assessment period 2011 - 2016.
HELCOM 2023	Copper as a HELCOM core indicator	This core indicator evaluates the status of the marine environment based on concentrations of copper (Cu) in Baltic Sea sediments. The indicator presents a status evaluation using available data in the HELCOM region during the assessment period 2016 – 2021.
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)		
JRC Technical Report (Tornero and Hanke 2016)	Identification of marine chemical contaminants released from sea-based sources	A review focusing on regulatory aspects The MSFD provisions foresee the consideration of contaminants that are not covered by the WFD, but entail a significant risk to, or via, the marine environment. A close collaboration with Regional Sea Conventions is crucial, as contaminants cross national and EU borders. Chemical substances occurring in the marine environment might derive from specific sea-based sources, such as shipping, mariculture, offshore oil and gas production, marine renewable energy devices, seabed mining, dredging of sediments, dumping of dredged material and historical dumping. This report consists of a scientific review of the literature to compile a list of marine specific contaminants potentially entering the marine environment from these sea-based sources. It also provides an overview of the environmental policy instruments and frameworks in place to oversee and regulate these substances within the EU.

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JRC technical Report (Tornero et al. 2022)	Development and Implementation of Marine Contaminant Threshold Values	Compiles available threshold values (TV) for marine chemical contaminants at EU, regional and beyond EU level in different compartments; details on threshold settings for WFD, OSPAR, US-EPA etc, provides a review on marine threshold values, describes details on threshold derivation, problems, discrepancies, confidence etc. for the different guidelines
JRC Technical Report (Tornero et al. 2019)	Marine chemical contaminants – support to the harmonization of MSFD D8 methodological standards	Highlights large differences in threshold values used by different countries reporting to MSFD – provides tables which country reports which metal (WFD PS, RSC metals, other contaminants) and which thresholds are used
European Commission	Descriptors under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Descriptors of MSFD, with development of thresholds for the derived indicators, such as for seafloor integrity, ensures functioning of the ecosystem
JRC Technical Report (Vasilakopoulos et al. 2022)	Marine Strategy Framework Directive Thresholds for MSFD Criteria: state of play and next steps	Describes current status of used thresholds by member states and newly developed standards such as for D6
E.C. 2022	Article 8 MSFD Assessment Guidance MSFD - Guidance document 19	Purpose of this Document is to guide Member States in the review and update of the assessment of their marine waters in respect of each marine region or subregion; aim is that Member States' assessments under Article 8 MSFD are comparable at EU-level, coherent within marine regions, consistent with Union legislation and with agreements in marine regions (e.g. Regional Sea Conventions), transparent and repeatable. Guidance on thresholds for all MSFD descriptors
ICES (Davies and Vethaak 2012)	Integrated marine environmental monitoring of chemicals and their effects	It is now generally agreed that the assessment of environmental quality, and the design and monitoring of measures to improve environmental quality, are best undertaken on the basis of combinations of appropriate sets of chemical and biological measurements. There have been many apparent barriers to following this strategy; for example, there has been a lack of coherent frameworks to guide the selection of organisms, substances, and biological effects measurements for monitoring and assessment programmes; and a lack of guidance on methodology, particularly guidance on the interpretation of data in terms of biological (environmental) significance and on how suites of chemical and biological measurements can be integrated to give the added power and scope of assessment promised by such a multifactorial approach.
ICES (Desprez et al. 2022)	Marine aggregate extraction and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive: A review of existing research. ICES Cooperative Research Reports	Environmental impact of marine aggregate extraction in the context of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the overarching objective of achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) across a number of relevant descriptors. The review identifies gaps in current knowledge, and highlights the need for expert judgement where understanding is limited. In particular, this report calls attention

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		to the need to account for seabed recovery and recolonization when seeking to understand the footprint of effects from aggregate dredging. Information from this study should be used to optimize the management of marine aggregate extraction and its sustainable development, thus addressing policy and management needs
European Commission 2020	Background document for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive on the determination of good environmental status and its links to assessments and the setting of environmental targets	Also links to quality standards of other policies
European Commission 2017	Commission Decision 2017/848 of 17 May 2017	This Decision lays down: (a) criteria and methodological standards to be used by Member States when determining a set of characteristics for good environmental status in accordance with Article 9(1) of Directive 2008/56/EC, on the basis of Annexes I and III and by reference to the initial assessment made pursuant to Article 8(1) of that Directive, to assess the extent to which good environmental status is being achieved, in accordance with Article 9(3) of that Directive; (b) specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment, to be used by Member States when establishing coordinated monitoring programmes under Article 11 of Directive 2008/56/EC, in accordance with Article 11(4) of that Directive; (c) a timeline for the establishment of threshold values, lists of criteria elements and methodological standards through Union, regional or subregional cooperation; (d) a notification requirement for criteria elements, threshold values and methodological standards.
ICES 2022	Workshop to scope assessment methods to set thresholds (WKBENTH2).	The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) requires Member States to achieve good environmental status (GES) across their marine waters. The EU have requested ICES to advise on methods for assessing adverse effects on seabed habitats, including from bottom-trawl fisheries, through selection of relevant indicators for the assessment of benthic habitats and seafloor integrity and associated threshold values for GES in relation to Descriptor 6 – Seabed integrity under the MFSD. The MFSD Descriptor 6 determination of GES needs both a quality threshold (when are seabed habitats in a good state in a specific location) and an extent threshold (proportion of the assessment area that needs to have seabed habitats in good state). Eleven different methods for setting thresholds were identified, of which more are suitable for setting quality than for extent thresholds. Preferred methods identified an ecologically-motivated difference between a good and degraded state, rather than another transition. Quality thresholds based on

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		the lower boundary of the range of natural variation were considered most promising. This approach can be used for most, but not all, indicators.
European Commission 2024	Commission notice of 11 March 2024 on the threshold values set under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC and Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 (document 2024_1268)	Summarizes current state of established threshold values for good environmental status set under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC and Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848
Hiddink et al. 2023	Setting thresholds for good ecosystem state in marine seabed systems and beyond	The authors provide an overview of methods that have been used for setting environmental management thresholds , the level of change in state that is deemed acceptable using each method, and the strengths and weaknesses of these approaches. The authors use examples from seabed ecosystems affected by bottom trawling activities. The overview is followed by a case study on setting good-state thresholds for the seabed impacted by mobile bottom-contacting fishing gears based on the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive requirements.
Others		
OECD 2019	Guiding Principles and Key Elements for Establishing a Weight of Evidence for Chemical Assessment	This document is intended to provide universal Guiding Principles that should be considered when developing or augmenting systematic approaches to Weight of Evidence (WoE) for chemical evaluation and key elements to formulating a systematic approach to WoE.
HPA/DGE (Roeper and Netzband 2011)	Assessment Criteria for Dredged Material with special focus on the North Sea Region	Different national guidelines are in use for the management of dredged material in the countries of the North Sea region. The framework for these guidelines is given by international conventions, like the London Convention (LC) 1972, and the Oslo-Paris Convention (OSPAR). The implementation and the setting of assessment criteria is within the custody of each country. Hence, there are differences concerning the assessment criteria for the material to be disposed at sea. The main intention of this paper is to compare the applied criteria for assessing chemical contamination of sediments. In the first part of the document datasheets give a detailed overview about criteria in Germany, The Netherlands, Belgium, France, UK, Ireland, Norway, Denmark, and – in addition – Ireland and Spain. All countries make use of guidance levels and/or threshold levels for the characterisation of dredged material .
UK Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy (BEIS 2020)	The United Kingdom Risk-Based Approach Programme	The Oslo and Paris Commission (OSPAR) Recommendation 2012/5 required Contracting Parties to implement a risk-based approach (RBA) for the management of produced water discharges from offshore installations. Guidance related to the Recommendation can be found in OSPAR Agreement

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		<p>2012/7. It was up to individual Contracting Parties to develop an implementation programme within the framework described in the Recommendation and Agreement</p> <p>Guidance provides an update to the UK RBA implementation programme approach, which is summarised in Figure 1-1. The programme still involves six steps, covering four assessment tiers. The update to the guidance now means that an installation with a permit to discharge produce water will not need to complete all four assessment tiers, if certain criteria are met, which could allow a permit holder to screen out an installation from further assessment tiers</p>
IOGP 2020	Risk Based Assessment of Offshore Produced Water Discharges	<p>This Report offers guidance on the assessment and management of potential toxic risk to the marine environment caused by the offshore discharge of produced water. This document presents industry good practice and aims to broaden the understanding and acceptance of RBA techniques internationally. This guidance aims to improve consistency in the application of assumptions, levels of conservatism, and selection of risk endpoints. A tiered approach to RBA is recommended by this guidance. If first tier assessment identifies a risk greater than acceptable thresholds, additional (higher tier) investigation is conducted. Higher tier assessment involves more data collection and analysis in order to reduce uncertainty in the assessment.</p>
IMARES (de Vries and Tamis 2014)	Manual to proposed Dutch implementation of OSPAR’s risk-based approach to the management of produced water discharges	<p>This manual is intended to assist operators on the Dutch Continental Shelf in the application of the Dutch implementation of the risk-based approach (RBA). In essence all oil and gas platforms on the Dutch Continental Shelf (DCS) have to go through the risk management cycle at least once, where the pre-screening determines in which order the platforms enter the cycle.</p>
Commercial projects		
Ramboll 2019	Baltic Pipe Offshore Pipeline – Permitting and Design Environmental Impact Assessment – Baltic Sea - Denmark	EIA gas pipeline
Coffey natural systems, 2008 (Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008)	Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited – Solwara 1 Project Environmental Impact Statement Executive Summary	EIS DSM
Coffey natural systems, 2013 (Woodlark Mining Limited 2013)	Environmental Impact Statement Woodlark Island Gold Project Volume A: Executive Summary	EIS DSTD

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Table 10: Scientific literature and data sources for trace metals in Pacific seawater

Location	Author	Title	Year	Content
North Pacific	Zheng et al. 2019	Distinct basin-scale-distributions of aluminum, manganese, cobalt, and lead in the North Pacific Ocean	2019	Basin-scale and full-depth sectional distributions of Al, Mn, Co, and Pb observed during three GEOTRACES Japan cruises in the North Pacific
North Pacific	Zheng et al. 2021	Sectional Distribution Patterns of Cd, Ni, Zn, and Cu in the North Pacific Ocean: Relationships to Nutrients and Importance of Scavenging	2021	Basin-scale full-depth sectional distributions of the total dissolvable, dissolved, and labile particulate Cd, Ni, Zn, and Cu along the 160°W, 165°E, and 47°N GEOTRACES transects
Central North Pacific	Baar et al. 2018	Low cerium among the dissolved rare earth elements in the central North Pacific Ocean	2018	Full water column REY profiles at the Vertex IV site at 28°N, 155°W in the central North Pacific Ocean
North Pacific	Cutter and Cutter 2006	Biogeochemistry of arsenic and antimony in the North Pacific Ocean	2006	As and Sb determined at 9 vertical profile stations in the western North Pacific Ocean
North Pacific	Collier 1984	Particulate and dissolved vanadium in the North Pacific Ocean	1984	Full water column depth profiles of dissolved and particulate V
Equatorial and North Pacific	Moriyasu et al. 2023	Cu Exists Predominantly as Kinetically Inert Complexes Throughout the Interior of the Equatorial and North Pacific Ocean	2023	Full water column profiles GP15, determination of labile and inert organically complexed Cu, and total Cu
Equatorial and North Pacific	Sieber et al. 2023a	The Importance of Reversible Scavenging for the Marine Zn Cycle Evidenced by the Distribution of Zinc and Its Isotopes in the Pacific Ocean	2023	Full water column profiles GP15, Zn and Zn isotopes
Equatorial and North Pacific	Sieber et al. 2023b	Biological, Physical, and Atmospheric Controls on the Distribution of Cadmium and Its Isotopes in the Pacific Ocean	2023	Full water column profiles GP15, Cd and Cd isotopes
Equatorial and North Pacific	Chmiel et al. 2022	Major processes of the dissolved cobalt cycle in the North and equatorial Pacific Ocean	2022	Full water column profiles GP15, Co
Equatorial and North Pacific	Lawrence et al. 2022	Water mass analysis of the 2018 US GEOTRACES Pacific Meridional Transect (GP15)	2022	Study is not peer-reviewed Nutrients and hydrography of GP15
Western South Pacific	Zheng et al. 2022	Distributions of aluminum, manganese, cobalt, and lead in the western South Pacific: Interplay between the South and North Pacific	2022	Full-depth distributions of these elements in the western South Pacific, which include meridional sections along 170°W (GEOTRACES GP19).

Location	Author	Title	Year	Content
Equatorial and western North Pacific	Fuhr et al. 2021	Tracing Water Mass Mixing From the Equatorial to the North Pacific Ocean With Dissolved Neodymium Isotopes and Concentrations	2021	dissolved neodymium (Nd) isotope compositions (ϵ Nd) and concentrations ([Nd]) obtained along a longitudinal transect at $\sim 180^\circ$ E from $\sim 7^\circ$ S to $\sim 50^\circ$ N
Equatorial Pacific	Haley et al. 2021	Rare earth element and neodymium isotopes of the eastern US GEOTRACES Equatorial Pacific Zonal Transect (GP16)	2021	Full water column profiles along GP16
Equatorial Pacific	Ho et al. 2019	Processes controlling the distribution of dissolved Al and Ga along the U.S. GEOTRACES East Pacific Zonal Transect (GP16)	2019	GP16, dissolved Al and Ga full water column profiles
North Pacific	Sim and Orians 2019	Annual variability of dissolved manganese in Northeast Pacific along Line-P: 2010-2013	2019	E-W offshore Vancouver Island, annual variability, full water column profiles of dissolved Mn
Equatorial Pacific	Lam et al. 2018	Size-fractionated distributions of suspended particle concentration and major phase composition from the U.S. GEOTRACES Eastern Pacific Zonal Transect (GP16)	2018	full water column sections of size-fractionated ($1-51 \mu\text{m}$; $> 51 \mu\text{m}$) concentrations of suspended particulate matter (SPM) and major particle phase composition, including particulate organic matter (POM), calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), opal, lithogenic particles, and iron and manganese (oxyhydr)oxides, as well as the Redfield (C:N:P) stoichiometry of particles, from the U.S. GEOTRACES GP16 Eastern Pacific Zonal Transect (EPZT).
Equatorial Pacific	Lam et al. 2018	Size distribution of particulate trace elements in the U.S. GEOTRACES Eastern Pacific Zonal Transect (GP16)	2018	size-distribution of ten particulate trace elements (pTEs; Al, Cd, Co, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, P, Ti, and V) from the Eastern Tropical South Pacific collected during the U.S. GEOTRACES GP16 cruise
North Pacific	Whitby et al. 2018	Copper-binding ligands in the NE Pacific	2018	E-W offshore Vancouver Island along line-P, Cu full water column profiles at two stations, 10-1400 m
North Pacific	Posacka et al. 2017	Dissolved copper (dCu) biogeochemical cycling in the subarctic Northeast Pacific and a call for improving methodologies		E-W offshore Vancouver Island, full water column profiles, Cu, analytical challenges discussed (UV)
North East Pacific	Conway and John 2015	The cycling of iron, zinc and cadmium in the North East Pacific Ocean - Insights from stable isotopes	2015	SAFe station, Cd, Zn, Fe full water column profiles
World oceans	Bruland and Lohan 2003; Bruland et al. 2014	Controls of Trace Metals in Seawater	2014	Controls on trace metals in seawater,

Location	Author	Title	Year	Content
CCZ, BGR contract area	Schmidt et al. 2022	Assessing the availability of trace metals including rare earth elements in deep ocean waters of the Clarion Clipperton Zone, NE Pacific: Application of an in situ DGT passive sampling method	2022	Baseline trace metals in bottom seawater, labile particulate, dissolved and DGT-labile concentrations of Mn, Cu, Co, Ni, Cd, Y, REE, As, V, , references to published TM data in the wider East Pacific
World oceans		Database of GEOTRACES Publications – GEOTRACES		Overview on publications related to GEOTRACES cruises, filter function for keywords such as “Pacific”
World oceans		GEOTRACES Interactive map		Interactive map with overview of conducted and planned GEOTRACES cruises, allows to search selected cruises for available TM data and further variables
World oceans	GEOTRACES Intermediate Data Product Group 2023	The GEOTRACES Intermediate Data Product	2023	Database for TM data obtained at GEOTRACES stations

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Table 11: Compilation of available trace metal baseline datasets for the water column above CCZ contract areas (until December 2023): example for BGR (and GSR) contract area.

Contract area	Contractor	Type of obtained data	Elements	Year(s)	Source	Remarks
BGR area E	BGR	CTD, BWS, DGT, bottom seawater, few full water column profiles from 2019 Labile particulate, dissolved, DGT-labile concentrations	As, Cd, Co, Cu, Mn, Ni, Y, REE, V	2018, 2019, 2021, 2022, 2023	BGR Exploration cruises, MiningImpact research cruises	TM water samplers (GoFlo), no TM CTD, measurements with TQ-ICPMS (with and without SeaFAST)
BGR area W	BGR	DGT		2023		
GSR B6	BGR	CTD, BWS, DGT, bottom seawater, few full water column profiles from 2019 Labile particulate, dissolved, DGT-labile concentrations	As, Cd, Co, Cu, Mn, Ni, Y, REE, V	2019, 2021, 2022	MiningImpact research cruises	TM water samplers (GoFlo), no TM CTD, measurements with TQ-ICPMS (with and without SeaFAST)
Data by other contractors or research projects?						

Appendix 2: Summary of threshold values

Table 1: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in water

Table 2: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in sediment

Table 3: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in biota

Table 4: Examples of thresholds for metal contaminants and other stressors operational in offshore industries

Full information on resources and other relevant information is provided in the accompanying **Excel file:** *Regulatory and operational threshold values*.

Table 1 cont.: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in water.

	Australian and New Zealand Water Quality Guideline values (7)			Draft Australian and New Zealand Water Quality Guideline values (7)				UK (8)	ECHA (9)	Germany (10)	WHO (11)	typical CCZ background seawater
	>99% protected	>95% protected (DGV)	>80% protected	>99% protected	>95% protected	>90% protected	>80% protected	EQS	PNEC	EQS		Av BGR (2022)
<i>µg/l</i>												
Arsenic				4.8	12	22	48	25	4.7	1.3		1.85
Lead	2.2	4.4	12						3.3	EU WFD		0.001
Cadmium	0.7	5.5	36						1.14	EU WFD		0.1
Cobalt	0.005	1	150						2.36			0.0008
Nickel	7	70	560	1.8	5.8	11	23			EU WFD		0.56
Zinc	3.3	8	21					6.8 (+cb)	7.2	3		0.98
Copper	0.3	1.3	8	0.12	0.4	0.72	1.4	3.76 ⁵	5.2	0.7		0.3
Vanadium	50	100	280									1.78
Chromium										0.6		
Manganese		80		190	300	390	570	0.05	3		300	0.013
Chromium (III)		10 ^x										
Chromium (VI)	0.14	4.4	85					0.6				
Mercury	0.1	0.4	1.4						0.067			
Silver	0.8	1.4	2.6						0.86			
Iron								1				0.068

DGV: Default Guideline Value; CEQG: Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines; FEQG: Federal Environmental Quality Guidelines; BC: British Columbia Water Quality Guidelines; EQS: Environmental Quality Standard; MAC: Maximum allowed concentration; AA: Annual Average Concentration; QS: Quality Standard; UBA: Umweltbundesamt; TV: Threshold Value; EU WFD: European Union Water Framework Directive; WQC: Water Quality Criteria; WQG: Water Quality Guidelines; PNEC: Predicted No Effect Concentration; US-EPA: United States-Environmental Protection Agency; DOC: Dissolved Organic Carbon; cb: background concentration.

Data sources:

(1) EU WFD (surface water other than inland water)

Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/105/2013-09-13>

^{§8}Silver (draft): https://health.ec.europa.eu/document/download/b0b6c394-c77f-48cd-ab64-cd5e764de340_en?filename=scheer_o_022.pdf

(a) depending on water hardness class: ≤ 0.45 (Class 1); 0.45 (Class 2); 0.6 (Class 3); 0.9 (Class 4); 1.5 (Class 5)

(2) Norway (marine)

NEA (2016, rev. 2020): Grenseverdier for klassifisering av vann, sediment og biota – revidert 30.10.2020 - Quality standards for water, sediment and biota – revised 2020.10.30. M-608/2016. Norwegian Environment Agency. <https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/globalassets/publikasjoner/m608/m608.pdf>

** the upper limit is the freshwater PNEC

b) Class III Cd depending on water hardness: ≤ 0.45 (< 40 mg CaCO₃/L); 0.45 (40 - <50 mg CaCO₃/L); 0.60 (50 - <100 mg CaCO₃/L); 0.9 (100 - <200 mg CaCO₃/L); 1.5 (≥200 mg CaCO₃/L).

(c) Class IV Cd depending on water hardness: ≤ 4,5 (< 40 mg CaCO₃/L); 4,5 (40 - <50 mg CaCO₃/L); 6,0 (50 - <100 mg CaCO₃/L); 9 (100 - <200 mg CaCO₃/L); 15 (≥200 mg CaCO₃/L). Higher values: Class V.

(3) OSPAR (marine)

OSPAR Commission (2014): Background Document: Establishment of a list of Predicted No Effect Concentrations (PNECs) for naturally occurring substances in produced water. OSPAR Agreement 2014-05.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7e4b5a40f0b62305b8211b/OSPAR_RBA_Predicted_No_Effect_Concentrations_PNECs_Background_Document.pdf

(4) HELCOM (marine)

see HELCOM indicators (<https://indicators.helcom.fi/>) with resources for threshold development; Pb and Cd: Primary threshold, EQS from WFD EQS dossier

(5) US-EPA (saltwater)

[National Recommended Water Quality Criteria - Aquatic Life Criteria Table | US EPA](#)

(6) Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines and Federal Environmental Quality Guidelines (saltwater)

Canada CEQG: https://rais.ornl.gov/documents/Canadian_water_quality_aquatic_life.pdf

Canada FEQG: <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/evaluating-existing-substances/federal-environmental-quality-guidelines-summary-table.html>

Canadian Environmental Quality Guidelines: Canadian Water Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Aquatic Life - Silver, Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, 2015

(7) Australia and New Zealand Water Quality Guidelines (marine)

Toxicant default guideline values technical briefs (<https://www.waterquality.gov.au>)

Draft Arsenic GV: Golding, L.A.; Valdivia, M.V.; van Dam, J.W.; Batley, G.E.; Apte, S.C. (2022): Toxicity of arsenic (V) to temperate and tropical marine biota and the derivation of chronic marine water quality guideline values. In Environ. Chem. 19 (4), pp. 116–131.

Draft manganese GV: Golding, L.A.; Binet, M.T.; Adams, M.S.; Hochen, J.; Humphrey, C.A.; Price, G.A.V. et al. (2023): Acute and chronic toxicity of manganese to tropical adult coral (*Acropora millepora*) to support the derivation of marine manganese water quality guideline values. In Marine pollution bulletin 194 (Pt B), p. 115242.

x ANZG (2000) DGV: 27 µg/L

(8) UK (marine)

PNEC (long-term) as EQS for WFD River Basin Specific pollutants

UK 2015: The Water Framework Directive (Standards and Classification) Directions (England and Wales) 2015

UK TAG 2010: Proposed EQS for Water Framework Directive Annex VIII substances: manganese (bioavailable) (For consultation) by Water Framework Directive - United Kingdom Technical Advisory Group (WFD-UKTAG)

§ (DOC < 1 mg/l); where DOC > 1 mg/l: $3.76 + (2.677 \times ((\text{DOC}/2) - 0.5))$ µg/l dissolved

(9) European Chemical Agency ECHA (marine)

[ECHA CHEM](#): search for substance, choose substance, go to dossiers - REACH registrations-choose first one - view dossier - see ecotoxicological information

(10) Germany (marine)

[ETOX: Informationssystem Ökotoxikologie und Umweltqualitätsziele](#)- link for EQS datasheets on UBA webETOX website for As, Zn, Co and Cr

(11) WHO

WHO, 2004. Manganese and its compounds: environmental aspects. In: Concise International Chemical Assessment Document 63. International Program on Chemical Safety, World Health Organization, Geneva

Table 2: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in sediment.

	OSPAR (1)			Norway classification (2)					HELCOM (3)	United States benchmarks (NOAA) (4)		Canadian Sediment quality guidelines (5)		Australian and New Zealand Sediment Quality Guidelines (6)	
	BAC*	BAC**	ERL	I Background	II Good (upper boundary = national EQS)	III Moderate	IV Bad	V Very Bad	QS	ERL	ERM	ISQG	PEL	DGV	GV-high
Antimony														2.0	25
Arsenic	25		8.2	0-15	15- <u>18</u>	18-71	71-580	>580		8.2	70	7.24	41.6	20	70
Lead	38	22.4	47	0-25	25- <u>150</u>	150-1480	1480-2000	2000-2500	120	46.7	218	30.2	112	50	220
Cadmium	0.31	0.129	1.2	0-0.2	0.2- <u>2.5</u>	2.5-16	16-157	>157	2,3	1.2	9.6	0.7	4.2	1.5	10
Nickel	36		21	0-30	30- <u>42</u>	42-271	271-533	>533		20.9	51.6			21	52
Zinc	122		150	0-90	90- <u>139</u>	139-750	750-6690	>6690		150	410	124	271	200	410
Copper	27		34	0-20	20- <u>84</u>	20-84	84-147	>147	30	34	270	18.7	108	65	270
Chromium	81		81	0-60	60- <u>620</u>	620-6000	6000-15500	15500-25000		81	370	52.3	160	80	370
Mercury	0.07	0.091	0.15	0-0.05	0.05- <u>0.52</u>	0.52-0.75	0.75-1.45	>1.45		0.15	0.71			0.15	1.0
Silver										1	3.7			1.0	4.0

dw: dry weight; BAC: Background Assessment Concentration; ERL: Effects Range-Low; ERM: Effects Range-Median; ISQG: Interim sediment quality guidelines; PEL: Probable effect levels; DGV: Default Guideline Value; GV: Guidelines Value; TOC: Total Organic Carbon; QS: Quality Standard.

All units are mg kg⁻¹ dw

* All subregions except Iberian Sea and Gulf of Cadiz

** Iberian Sea and Gulf of Cadiz

Data Sources:

(1) OSPAR

https://dome.ices.dk/ohat/trDocuments/2022/help_ac_sediment_contaminants.html. BACs are normalised to 5% aluminium in all subregions except the Iberian Sea and Gulf of Cadiz, where BACs are not normalised; the ERLs are not normalised, but are assumed to be appropriate for concentrations normalised to 5% aluminium in all subregions apart from the Iberian Sea and Gulf of Cadiz, and for non-normalised concentrations in the Iberian Sea and Gulf of Cadiz; the ERLs for arsenic and nickel are below their respective OSPAR Background Concentrations of 15 and 30 mg kg⁻¹ dw; arsenic and nickel concentrations are only assessed against the BAC; the ERL for chromium equals the BAC; chromium concentrations are only assessed against the ERL

(2) NEA

NEA (2014): Kvalitetssikring av miljøkvalitetsstandarder: Quality assurance of environmental quality standards. M-241. Norwegian Environment Agency. Available online at <https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/globalassets/publikasjoner/m241/m241.pdf>.

(3) HELCOM

see HELCOM indicators (<https://indicators.helcom.fi/>) with resources for threshold development; Pb and Cd: Secondary threshold, QS from WFD EQS dossier; (normalized to 5% aluminium); Cu: normalized to 5% TOC

(4) United States (NOAA)

https://rais.ornl.gov/documents/ECO_BENCH_NOAA.pdf

(5) CCME

Canadian Sediment Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Aquatic Life — Summary Tables, Update 2002, Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, Winnipeg, Canada. <https://ccme.ca/en/summary-table>

(6) ANZG

ANZG (2018): Australian and New Zealand Guidelines for Fresh and Marine Water Quality. Edited by Australian and New Zealand Governments and Australian state and territory governments. Cranberra ACT, Australia. Available online at www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines; see also <https://www.waterquality.gov.au/anz-guidelines/guideline-values/default/sediment-quality-toxicants>; Primarily adapted from the effects range low (ERL) and effects range median (ERM) values of Long et al. (1995).

Table 3: Environmental quality threshold values in different regulatory frameworks: metals in biota. For references, see Tornero et al. (2022).

	EU WFD	OSPAR		UNEP MAP		HELCOM	Canada ¹
	EQS	BAC	EC MPC (2)	MED BAC	EAC	TV	TRQG
	µg/kg ww	µg/kg dw or ww	µg/kg ww	µg/kg dw or ww	µg/kg dw or ww	µg/kg ww	µg/kg ww
Lead		Mussels and oysters = 1300 µg/kg dw Fish = 26 µg/kg ww fish liver	bivalves and fish liver = 1500 ² fish and fish muscle = 300 ²	Mussel = 1650 µg/kg dw Fish = 36.6 µg/kg ww	Mussel = 7500 µg/kg dw Fish = 300 µg/kg ww	Fish liver= 26 Mussels= 110	
Cadmium		Mussels = 960 µg/kg dw Oysters = 3000 µg/kg dw Fish = 26 µg/kg ww	bivalves and fish liver = 1000 ² fish and fish muscle = 50 ²	Mussel = 1065 µg/kg dw Fish = 7.8 µg/kg ww	Mussel = 1000 µg/kg ww Fish = 50 µg/kg ww	Mussels and fish= 160	
Mercury	20 [#]	Mussels = 90 µg/kg dw Oysters = 180 µg/kg dw (not used as above the EQS) Fish = 35 µg/kg ww (not used as above the EQS)	bivalves and fish muscle = 500 ²	Mussel = 117 µg/kg dw Fish = 81.2 µg/kg ww	Mussel = 2500 µg/kg dw Fish = 1000 µg/kg ww	20	33 [#]

EU WFD: EQS: Environmental Quality Standard; dw: dry weight; ww: wet weight; BAC: Background Assessment Concentration; EC: maximum levels in food stuff EC Reg. 1881/2006; MPC: Maximum Permissible Concentrations; ME: Mediterranean Sea; EAC: Environmental Assessment criteria; TROG: Tissue residue quality guidelines; MAP: Mediterranean Action Plan; TV: Threshold Value. MPC: Maximum Permissible Concentration.

[#] The toxicity assessment was based on methyl mercury

¹ Canadian or Federal Environmental Quality Guidelines

² Human health threshold (Origin: EC Reg. 1881/2006).

Tornero, V.; Deviller, G.; Hanke, G.; Coatu, V.; do Carmo Alves Martins, I.; Fryer, R. et al. (2022): Development and Implementation of Marine Contaminant Threshold Values. Edited by European Commission, Joint Research Centre. Luxembourg (Publications Office of the European Union, JRC131257). Available online at <https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu>.

Table 4: Examples of thresholds for metal contaminants and other stressors operational in offshore industries. STD: Submarine Tailings Disposal. DSTD: Deep-Sea Tailings Disposal.

Offshore activity	Addressed stressor or effect	operational management threshold/effects size	Reference	Spatial context?	Context
oil & gas	burial (natural sediment)	PNEC (0.65 cm)	Smit et al. 2006b	yes	PEC/PNEC as risk indicator for drilling mud discharges; for calculation of combined Environmental Impact Factor for Drilling Discharges (EIF _{DD}), mPAF for required annual reporting from the oil and gas operators in the Norwegian sector to the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA), and for EIAs
oil & gas	sedimentation	e.g., 1-3 mm, 3-10 mm, >10 mm	Offshore Norge 2024	yes	effects thresholds for different impact categories (low, significant, considerable) in coral and sponge habitats, can be applied in spatial impact areas (decreasing threshold with increasing distance)
oil & gas	suspended solids (barite)	PNEC (0.2 mg/l)	Smit et al. 2006a	yes	PEC/PNEC as risk indicator for drilling mud discharges; for calculation of combined Environmental Impact Factor for Drilling Discharges (EIF _{DD}), mPAF for required annual reporting from the oil and gas operators in the Norwegian sector to the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA), and for EIAs
oil & gas	suspended solids (WBM)	PNEC (0.8 mg/l)	Smit et al. 2006a	yes	PEC/PNEC as risk indicator for drilling mud discharges; for calculation of combined Environmental Impact Factor for Drilling Discharges (EIF _{DD}), mPAF for required annual reporting from the oil and gas operators in the Norwegian sector to the Norwegian Environment Agency (NEA), and for EIAs
oil & gas	suspended solids (drill cuttings)	10 mg/l	Baussant et al 2018	No	effects threshold for corals
oil & gas	suspended solids (WBM)	e.g., 10 mg/l for >60 hours	Offshore Norge, 2024	no	long-term effect threshold for coral and sponge habitats
oil & gas	PW toxicity	whole effluent PNEC (project-specific)	OSPAR Commission 2012	yes	PEC/PNEC as risk indicator in the water column, to be met outside a specific distance or volume of water (specified by the individual member state)
oil & gas	PW toxicity	whole effluent PNEC (project-specific)	BEIS 2020	yes	PEC/PNEC<1 to be met outside 500 m distance
oil & gas	PW toxicity	whole effluent PNEC (project-specific)	de Vries and Tamis 2014	yes	PEC/PNEC<1 to be met outside 500 m distance
oil & gas	PW toxicity	whole effluent PNEC (99% protection level)	ENI Australia 2017	yes	PEC/PNEC<1 to be met outside mixing zone
oil & gas	PW toxicity	whole effluent NOEC (project-specific)	U.S. EPA 2024	yes	PEC/NOEC<1 to be met outside 100 m-mixing zone
oil & gas	Drilling mud toxicity	drilling mud LC50>3% by volume	U.S. EPA 2024	no	Discharged cuttings shall meet both a daily minimum and a monthly average minimum effluent toxicity limitation of at least 3.0 percent by volume
oil & gas	dissolved metals	single substance PNECs	OSPAR Commission 2014	yes	PEC/PNEC as risk indicator in the water column, PEC/PNEC<1 to be met outside mixing zone
oil & gas	metals in sediment	ERL for metals in sediment	OSPAR Commission 2017	no	monitoring composition of cutting piles
oil & gas	Hg in barite	1 mg/kg	U.S. EPA 2024	no	criterion must be met for discharge permit
oil & gas	Cd in barite	3 mg/kg	U.S. EPA 2024	no	criterion must be met for discharge permit

Offshore activity	Addressed stressor or effect	operational management threshold/effects size	Reference	Spatial context?	Context
dredging	combined SSC, burial	10 mg/l, 3 mg/cm ² pulsed deposition, 28d	EPA-WA 2021	yes	boundary criterion of ZOH/ZOMI for sponge habitats
dredging	combined SSC and light	e.g., 9 mg/l and <1.8 DLI, 28d	EPA-WA 2021	yes	boundary criterion of ZOMI/ZOI for coral habitats
dredging	joint effect	10% mortality	EPA-WA 2021	yes	boundary criterion of ZOH/ZOMI for coral habitats, low-reliability guideline
dredging	suspended solids (fine-grained)	10 mg/l	Harvey et al. 2017	no	90% of fin fish species would be protected, for suspension of fine-grained particles <4 µm using species sensitivity distributions (SSD)
dredging	suspended solids	2.4 mg/l	Harvey et al. 2017	no	99% of fin fish species would be protected, low reliability due to variability of endpoints, for suspension of fine-grained particles <4 µm using species sensitivity distributions (SSD)
dredging	metals in sediment	ANZECC ISQGs	Australian Government 2009	no	first tier in tiered approach to assess toxic risk of marine disposal of dredged material
dredging	metals in sediment	ALs Norway (sediment class boundary II/III)	SedNet 2011	no	to prospectively assess toxic risk marine disposal of dredged material
dredging	metals in sediment	ALs	OSPAR Commission 2008	No	to prospectively assess toxic risk marine disposal of dredged material
dredging	metals in sediment	e.g., HELCOM EQS for Cd; Danish NEQS for Cu	Ramboll 2019	yes	assess toxic risk of dredging plume from Baltic Sea Pipeline construction
dredging	turbidity	10 NTU>background for>20 min	Norway counties (pers. comm. Jens Laugesen)	no	typical threshold in permits for dredging in Norway, case-by-case decisions
dredging	dredge spoil toxicity	PEC<1% of LC50	U.S. EPA 1991; USACE and USEPA 2016	yes	to be met 4 hours after dumping
dredging	suspended solids	50 mg/l, or <10% change from background	Esso Highlands Limited 2010	yes	compliance criteria to be met outside mixing zone of LNG project in PNG
dredging	dissolved metal conc.	PNG criteria (EQS) for metals in seawater	Esso Highlands Limited 2010	yes	compliance criteria to be met outside mixing zone of LNG project in PNG
STD	suspended solids	15 mg/l (monthly mean)	Metal and Diamond Mining Effluent Regulations Canada	no	
STD	total metal conc.	e.g., As=0.3 mg/L	Metal and Diamond Mining Effluent Regulations Canada	no	
DSTD	dissolved metals and cyanide	PNG EQS	Woodlark Mining Limited 2013	yes	compliance criteria to be met outside mixing zone (1000 m radius) of proposed DSTD project in PNG, PNG cyanide EQS used to model the extent of the mixing zone
DSTD	dissolved metal conc.	PNG EQS	Wafi-Golpu Joint Venture 2018	yes	compliance criteria to be met outside mixing zone (2200 m radius) of proposed DSTD project in PNG, PNG cobalt EQS used to model the extent of the mixing zone

Offshore activity	Addressed stressor or effect	operational management threshold/effects size	Reference	Spatial context?	Context
DSM	dissolved metals	ANZECC water quality Guideline Values	Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008	Yes	compliance criteria to be met outside mixing zone of proposed DSM project (SOLWARA 1) in PNG
DSM	plume elutriate toxicity	elutriate chronic toxicity	Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008	No	calculate required dilution of plume to be non-toxic, met within mixing zone?
DSM	suspended solids	1.2 mg/l	Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited 2008	Yes	criterion used to calculate extent of the mixing zone (900 m) of proposed DSM project (SOLWARA 1) in PNG; Queensland offshore tropical marine region criterion for suspended particles

PW: Produced Water; PEC: Predicted Effects Concentration; PNEC: Predicted No Effects Concentration; NOEC: No Effects Concentration; WBM Water-Based Mud; EQS: Environmental Quality Standard; DLI: Daily Light Integral.; AL: Action Level; ISQG: Interim Sediment Quality Guidelines

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Australian Government (2009): National Assessment Guidelines for Dredging. Commonwealth of Australia. Canberra. Available online at <https://www.dccew.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/guidelines09.pdf>.

BEIS (2020): The United Kingdom Risk-Based Approach Programme: A risk-based approach to the management of produced water discharges from offshore installations. Version 3.1. Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy. Available online at https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/941162/RBA_Guidance_December_2020_v3.1.pdf.

de Vries, P.; Tamis, J. E. (2014): Manual to proposed Dutch implementation of OSPAR's risk-based approach to the management of produced water discharges. Edited by IMARES - Institute for Marine Resources & Ecosystem Studies. Den Helder (Report / IMARES Wageningen UR, C057.14 A).

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EPA-WA (2021): Technical Guidance - Environmental impact assessment of marine dredging proposals. Edited by EPA. Environmental Protection of Authority Western Australia. Western Australia. Available online at <https://www.epa.wa.gov.au/policies-guidance/technical-guidance-environmental-impact-assessment-marine-dredging-proposals>.

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Harvey, Euan; Wenger, Amelia; Saunders, Benjamin; Newman, Stephen; Wilson, Shaun; Travers, Mike et al. (2017): Effects of dredging-related activities on finfish: a review and management strategies. Western Australian Marine Science Institution (WAMSI Dredging Science Node, Theme 8 Report).

Nautilus Minerals Niugini Limited (2008): Environmental Impact Statement - Solwara 1 Project. Executive Summary.

Offshore Norge (2024): Handbook. Species and Habitats of Environmental Concern: Mapping, Risk Assessment, Mitigation and Monitoring. - In Relation to Offshore Activities (DNV – Report No. 2019-007, Rev. 1). Available online at <https://www.offshorenorge.no/contentassets/13d5d06ec9464156b2272551f0740db0/handbook-species-and-habitats-of-environmental-concern-2024-rev1.pdf>.

OSPAR Commission (2008): Overview of Contracting Parties' National Action Levels for Dredged Material (2008 Update). Available online at <https://www.ospar.org/documents?v=7113>.

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OSPAR Commission (2017): OSPAR Guidelines for Monitoring the Environmental Impact of Offshore Oil and Gas Activities. OSPAR Agreement 2017-02. Available online at <https://www.ospar.org/convention/agreements>.

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